

#	Platform Name	Country	Provider	Platform Name	Latitude	Longitude	EMODnet Plat ID	PSMSL ID	UHSCL ID	IOC ID	GLOSS ID		EMODnet PlatformPage	PSMSL RLR	IOC Link	UHSCL Daily Link	UHSCL Houtrly Link
											GLOSS ID PSMSL	UHSCL					
1	61284	France	IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	61284	43,3189	4,8662	7274						2014 - 2019				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=7274
2	62309	France	EPOC - Environnements Et Paléoenvironnements Océaniques IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	62309	44,8633	0,5461	7377						2005 - 2015				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=7377
3	6900642	France	IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	6900642	57,2010	25,1560	7670						2008 - 2013				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=7670
4	20180920	France	Shom - France	20180920	48,0216	4,5376	369245						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369245
5	20180923	France	Shom - France	20180923	22,2421	166,4162	368874						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368874
6	20180924	France	Shom - France IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	20180924	48,0216	4,5376	368875						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368875
7	20180925	France	Shom - France IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	20180925	48,0216	4,5376	368876						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368876
8	20180926	France	Shom - France IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	20180926	48,0216	4,5376	368877						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368877
9	20180927	France	Shom - France IFREMER - Institut Français de Recherche pour l'Exploitation de la Mer - France	20180927	48,0216	4,5376	368878						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368878
10	20180928	France	Shom - France	20180928	48,0216	4,5376	368879						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368879
11	20180929	France	Shom - France	20180929	48,0216	4,5376	368916						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368916
12	20180930	France	Shom - France	20180930	48,0216	4,5376	368928						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368928
13	20181001	France	Shom - France	20181001	48,0216	4,5376	368943						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368943
14	20181002	France	Shom - France	20181002	48,0216	4,5376	368991						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368991
15	20181003	France	Shom - France	20181003	48,0216	4,5376	369014						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369014
16	20181004	France	Shom - France	20181004	48,0216	4,5376	369061						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369061
17	20181005	France	Shom - France	20181005	48,0216	4,5376	369088						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369088
18	20181006	France	Shom - France	20181006	48,0216	4,5376	369102						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369102
19	20181007	France	Shom - France	20181007	48,0216	4,5376	369119						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369119
20	20181008	France	Shom - France	20181008	48,0216	4,5376	369161						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369161
21	20181009	France	Shom - France	20181009	48,0216	4,5376	369193						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369193
22	20181010	France	Shom - France	20181010	48,0216	4,5376	369222						2020 - 2020				https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369222

23	20181011	France	Shom - France	20181011	48,0216	-	4,5376	369264	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369264	
24	20181012	France	Shom - France	20181012	43,5203		4,1264	369295	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369295	
25	20181013	France	Shom - France	20181013	-	17,8059	-	149,2950	369311	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369311
26	20181014	France	Shom - France	20181014	43,5203		4,1264	369335	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369335	
27	20181015	France	Shom - France	20181015	-	66,6617	140,0100	369336	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369336	
28	20181016	France	Shom - France	20181016	42,6396		8,9352	369366	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369366	
29	10min	France	Shom - France	10min	14,6010	-	61,0630	369138	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369138	
30	1min	France	Shom - France	1min	50,7275		1,5774	369140	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369140	
31	20min	France	Shom - France	20min	-	66,6617	140,0100	369141	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369141	
32	2min	France	Shom - France	2min	-	16,6270	-	143,5692	369146	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369146
33	5min	France	Shom - France	5min	44,8600	-	0,5528	369148	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369148	
34	60min	France	Shom - France	60min	41,9227		8,7629	369149	2017 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369149	
35	A121TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	A121TG	55,4000		3,8100	11617	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=11617	
36	Aalesund	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Aalesund	62,4667		6,1500	8389	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8389	
37	AalesundTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	AalesundTG	62,4694		6,1520	8390	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8390	
38	Aarhus	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Aarhus	56,1500		10,2167	8391	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8391	
39	AarhusTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	AarhusTG	56,1500		10,2167	363738	2015 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=363738	
40	Aberdeen	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Aberdeen	57,1500	-	2,0833	17	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=17	
41	AberdeenTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	AberdeenTG	57,1441	-	2,0801	8392	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8392	
42	Ahus	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Ahus	55,9284		14,3286	25794	2010 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=25794	
43	AiguillonSurMerTG	France	Shom - France	AiguillonSurMerTG	46,3350	-	1,3164	369076	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369076	
44	AiguillonSurMerTG-10min	France	Shom - France	AiguillonSurMerTG- 10min	46,3350	-	1,3164	369405	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369405	
45	AiguillonSurMerTG-5min	France	Shom - France	AiguillonSurMerTG-5min	46,3350	-	1,3164	370003	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370003	

46	AiguillonSurMerTG-60min	France	Shom - France	AiguillonSurMerTG-60min	46,3350	-	1,3164	370004	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370004
47	AjaccioTG	France	Shom - France	AjaccioTG	41,9227		8,7629	8397	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8397
48	AjaccioTG-10min	France	Shom - France	AjaccioTG-10min	41,9227		8,7629	370005	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370005
49	AjaccioTG-1min	France	Shom - France	AjaccioTG-1min	41,9227		8,7629	369407	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369407
50	AjaccioTG-60min	France	Shom - France	AjaccioTG-60min	41,9227		8,7629	370006	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370006
51	AlcudiaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	AlcudiaTG	39,8347		3,1392	8399	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8399
52	AlgecirasTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	AlgecirasTG	36,1769	-	5,3983	8400	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8400
53	Almeria2TG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	Almeria2TG	36,8319	-	2,4809	26120	2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26120
54	AlmeriaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	AlmeriaTG	36,8300	-	2,4780	8402	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8402
55	AlteWeser	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	AlteWeser	53,8633		8,1283	8403	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8403
56	AlteWeserTG	Germany	WSOB - Waterways and Shipping Office Bremerhaven - Germany	AlteWeserTG	53,8633		8,1275	8404	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8404
57	Althagen	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Althagen	54,3769		12,4194	8405	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8405
58	Andenes	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Andenes	69,3167		16,1500	8421	1991 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8421
59	AndenesTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	AndenesTG	69,3261		16,1348	8422	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8422
60	ANDRATX	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	ANDRATX	39,5442		2,3785	13864	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13864
61	Angelholm	Sweden		Angelholm	56,2980		12,7865	25795	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25795
62	AngletConvergentTG	France	Shom - France	AngletConvergentTG	43,5270	-	1,5136	368618	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368618
63	AngletConvergentTG-5min	France	Shom - France	AngletConvergentTG-5min	43,5270	-	1,5136	369414	2007 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369414
64	Aranmore	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Aranmore	54,9896	-	8,4956	543	2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=543
65	AranmoreTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	AranmoreTG	54,9905	-	8,4955	8424	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8424
66	ArcachonEyractTG	France	Shom - France	ArcachonEyractTG	44,6650	-	1,1635	8425	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8425
67	ArcachonEyractTG-10min	France	Shom - France	ArcachonEyractTG-10min	44,6650	-	1,1635	370007	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370007
68	ArcachonEyractTG-1min	France	Shom - France	ArcachonEyractTG-1min	44,6650	-	1,1635	369416	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369416

69	ArcachonEyractG-60min	France	Shom - France	ArcachonEyractG-60min	44,6650	-	1,1635	370008	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370008
70	ArcachonTG	France	Shom - France SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	ArcachonTG	44,6650	-	1,1636	8426	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8426
71	Arko	Sweden		Arko	58,4843	16,9607		15363	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=15363
72	ArrecifeTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ArrecifeTG	28,9670	-	13,5300	8430	2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8430
73	Assens	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Assens	55,2667	9,8833		8432	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8432
74	AudierneTG	France	Shom - France	AudierneTG	48,0216	-	4,5376	371096	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371096
75	AudierneTG-1min	France	Shom - France	AudierneTG-1min	48,0216	-	4,5376	369418	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369418
76	Avonmouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Avonmouth	51,5071	-	2,7114	13	1990 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13
77	AvonmouthPortburyTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	AvonmouthPortburyTG	51,5109	-	2,7150	8433	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8433
78	AWGTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	AWGTG	53,4920	5,9400		11618	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11618
79	Bagenkop	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	Bagenkop	54,7528	10,6778		8435	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8435
80	Balchik	Bulgaria		Balchik	43,4040	28,1650		11257	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11257
81	BaliseARouenTG	France	Shom - France	BaliseARouenTG	49,4318	0,1107		638729	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=638729
82	Ballen	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Ballen	55,8167	10,6444		8436	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8436
83	Ballum	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	Ballum	55,1308	8,6859		8437	2005 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8437
84	BallumTG	Denmark		BallumTG	55,1308	8,6859		9273	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9273
85	Ballycotton	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Ballycotton	51,8278	-	8,0007	544	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=544
86	BallycottonTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	BallycottonTG	51,8278	-	8,0007	8438	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8438
87	Ballyglass	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Ballyglass	54,2530	-	9,8900	545	2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=545
88	BallyglassTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	BallyglassTG	54,2536	-	9,8928	8439	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8439
89	Bandholm	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Bandholm	54,8333	11,4833		8441	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8441
90	Bangor	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Bangor	54,6650	-	5,6692	75	1994 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=75
91	BangorTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	BangorTG	54,6648	-	5,6695	8442	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8442

92	BarcelonaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BarcelonaTG	41,3420	2,1630	8443	1993 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8443
93	Barhoeft	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Barhoeft	54,4397	13,0328	8444	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8444
94	Barmouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Barmouth	52,7167	4,0333	36	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=36
95	BarmouthTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	BarmouthTG	52,7191	4,0452	8445	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8445
96	Barseback	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Barseback	55,7564	12,9033	429	1982 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=429
97	BarsebackTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	BarsebackTG	55,7565	12,9034	8446	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8446
98	BayonneBoucauTG	France	Shom - France	BayonneBoucauTG	43,5273	1,5154	8447	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8447
99	BayonneBoucauTG-10min	France	Shom - France	BayonneBoucauTG-10min	43,5273	1,5154	370009	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370009
100	BayonneBoucauTG-1min	France	Shom - France	BayonneBoucauTG-1min	43,5273	1,5154	369421	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369421
101	BayonneBoucauTG-60min	France	Shom - France	BayonneBoucauTG-60min	43,5273	1,5154	370010	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370010
102	BayonnePontBlancTG	France	Shom - France	BayonnePontBlancTG	43,4818	1,4732	368621	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368621
103	BayonnePontBlancTG-5min	France	Shom - France	BayonnePontBlancTG-5min	43,4818	1,4732	369422	2009 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369422
104	BayonneQuaiDeLessepsTG	France	Shom - France	BayonneQuaiDeLessepsTG	43,4976	1,4794	368622	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368622
105	BayonneQuaiDeLessepsTG-5min	France	Shom - France	BayonneQuaiDeLessepsTG-5min	43,4976	1,4794	369423	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369423
106	Bergen	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Bergen	60,4000	5,3000	8448	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8448
107	BergenTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	BergenTG	60,3981	5,3205	8449	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8449
108	BilbaoTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BilbaoTG	43,3570	3,0500	8450	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8450
109	Bodoe	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Bodoe	67,2833	14,3833	8451	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8451
110	BodoeTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	BodoeTG	67,2883	14,3908	8452	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8452
111	Bogense	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Bogense	55,5667	10,0833	8453	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8453
112	BoVanHeist	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	BoVanHeist	51,3900	3,1990	35397	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=35397
113	Bonan	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Bonan	60,7315	17,3258	967446	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967446
114	BonanzaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BonanzaTG	36,8000	6,3400	8454	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8454

115	BordeauxTG	France	Shom - France	BordeauxTG	44,8600	-	0,5528	368624	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368624
116	BordeauxTG-10min	France	Shom - France	BordeauxTG-10min	44,8600	-	0,5528	370011	2006 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370011
117	BordeauxTG-5min	France	Shom - France	BordeauxTG-5min	44,8600	-	0,5528	369428	2006 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369428
118	Borkum	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Borkum	53,5700		6,7500	8456	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8456
119	BorkumTG	Germany	WSOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany	BorkumTG	53,5570		6,7480	8457	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8457
120	BoucauBayonneTG	France	Shom - France	BoucauBayonneTG	43,5273	-	1,5148	8458	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8458
121	BoulogneSurMerTG	France	Shom - France	BoulogneSurMerTG	50,7275		1,5774	8459	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8459
122	BoulogneSurMerTG-10min	France	Shom - France	BoulogneSurMerTG-10min	50,7275		1,5774	370012	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370012
123	BoulogneSurMerTG-1min	France	Shom - France	BoulogneSurMerTG-1min	50,7275		1,5774	370013	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370013
124	BoulogneSurMerTG-60min	France	Shom - France	BoulogneSurMerTG-60min	50,7275		1,5774	370014	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370014
125	BourcefrancLeChapusTG	France	Shom - France	BourcefrancLeChapusTG	45,8534	-	1,1778	369077	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369077
126	BourcefrancLeChapusTG-10min	France	Shom - France	BourcefrancLeChapusTG-10min	45,8534	-	1,1778	369429	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369429
127	BourcefrancLeChapusTG-5min	France	Shom - France	BourcefrancLeChapusTG-5min	45,8534	-	1,1778	370015	2014 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370015
128	Bournemouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Bournemouth	50,7136	-	1,8747	76	1996 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=76
129	BournemouthTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	BournemouthTG	50,7143	-	1,8749	8460	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8460
130	Bremen	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Bremen	53,1200		8,7133	8461	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8461
131	BremenTG	Germany	WSOBR - Waterways and Shipping Office Bremen - Germany	BremenTG	53,1200		8,7120	8462	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8462
132	Bremerhaven	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Bremerhaven	53,5450		8,5681	8463	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8463
133	BremerhavenTG	Germany	WSOB - Waterways and Shipping Office Bremerhaven - Germany	BremerhavenTG	53,5450		8,5680	8464	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8464
134	BrestNus30TG	France	Shom - France	BrestNus30TG	48,3800	-	4,5000	8465	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8465
135	BrestOptiwaveTG	France	Shom - France	BrestOptiwaveTG	48,3800	-	4,5000	8466	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8466
136	BrestTG	France	Shom - France	BrestTG	48,3829	-	4,4951	8467	1997 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8467
137	BrestTG-10min	France	Shom - France	BrestTG-10min	48,3829	-	4,4951	369944	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369944

138	BrestTG-1min	France	Shom - France	BrestTG-1min	48,3829	-	4,4951	369430	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369430
139	BrestTG-60min	France	Shom - France SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	BrestTG-60min	48,3829	-	4,4951	370016	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370016
140	Brofjorden	Sweden	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	Brofjorden	58,3360	11,4046		967447	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967447
141	Brons	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	Brons	55,1833	8,6833		8469	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8469
142	BronsTG	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	BronsTG	55,1833	8,6833		9274	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9274
143	Brouwershavensegat8TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	Brouwershavensegat8TG	51,7686	3,6173		8471	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8471
144	Buesum	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Buesum	54,1222	8,8592		8472	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8472
145	BuesumTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	BuesumTG	54,1222	8,8592		8473	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8473
146	Burgas	Bulgaria	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	Burgas	42,4800	27,4800		10802	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10802
147	BurgasSouth	Bulgaria	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	BurgasSouth	42,4540	27,5350		11375	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11375
148	CadzandTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	CadzandTG	51,3800	3,3760		8478	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8478
149	CalaisTG	France	Shom - France	CalaisTG	50,9695	1,8677		8480	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8480
150	CalaisTG-10min	France	Shom - France	CalaisTG-10min	50,9695	1,8677		370018	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370018
151	CalaisTG-1min	France	Shom - France	CalaisTG-1min	50,9695	1,8677		369436	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369436
152	CalaisTG-60min	France	Shom - France	CalaisTG-60min	50,9695	1,8677		370019	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370019
153	CarbonerasTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	CarbonerasTG	36,9743	-	1,8996	26121	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26121
154	CascaisTG	Portugal	DGDT - Direção-Geral do Território - Portugal	CascaisTG	38,6833	-	9,4167	28132	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28132
155	Castletownbere	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Castletownbere	51,6496	-	9,9034	546	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=546
156	CastletownbereTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	CastletownbereTG	51,6496	-	9,9034	8481	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8481
157	Cazino-Mamaia	Romania	NIMRD - National Institute for Marine Research and Development - Romania	Cazino-Mamaia	44,2330	28,6320		8483	2013 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8483
158	CenturiTG	France	Shom - France	CenturiTG	42,9658	9,3498		8484	2010 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8484
159	CenturiTG-10min	France	Shom - France	CenturiTG-10min	42,9658	9,3498		370020	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370020
160	CenturiTG-1min	France	Shom - France	CenturiTG-1min	42,9658	9,3498		369437	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369437

161	CenturiTG-2min	France	Shom - France	CenturiTG-2min	42,9658	9,3498	369863	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369863
162	CenturiTG-60min	France	Shom - France	CenturiTG-60min	42,9658	9,3498	370021	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370021
163	CherbourgTG	France	Shom - France	CherbourgTG	49,6513	- 1,6355	8488	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8488
164	CherbourgTG-10min	France	Shom - France	CherbourgTG-10min	49,6513	- 1,6355	370022	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370022
165	CherbourgTG-1min	France	Shom - France	CherbourgTG-1min	49,6513	- 1,6355	369439	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369439
166	CherbourgTG-60min	France	Shom - France	CherbourgTG-60min	49,6513	- 1,6355	370023	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370023
167	CiboureTG	France	Shom - France	CiboureTG	43,3892	- 1,6627	368628	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=368628
168	CiboureTG-5min	France	Shom - France	CiboureTG-5min	43,3892	- 1,6627	369440	2007 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369440
169	CiboureTG-60min	France	Shom - France	CiboureTG-60min	43,3892	- 1,6627	370024	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370024
170	COLONIA-SANT-PERE	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System	COLONIA-SANT-PERE	39,7373	3,2734	15101	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=15101
171	ConcarneauTG	France	Shom - France	ConcarneauTG	47,8738	- 3,9076	8494	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8494
172	ConcarneauTG-10min	France	Shom - France	ConcarneauTG-10min	47,8738	- 3,9076	370025	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370025
173	ConcarneauTG-1min	France	Shom - France	ConcarneauTG-1min	47,8738	- 3,9076	369443	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369443
174	ConcarneauTG-60min	France	Shom - France	ConcarneauTG-60min	47,8738	- 3,9076	370026	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370026
175	Constanta	Romania	NIMRD - National Institute for Marine Research and Development - Romania	Constanta	44,1475	28,6720	11483	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=11483
176	Constanta2	Romania	INFP - National Institute for Earth Physics - Romania	Constanta2	44,1475	28,6720	14218	2015 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=14218
177	CordemaisTG	France	Shom - France	CordemaisTG	47,2772	- 1,8898	368629	1986 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=368629
178	CordemaisTG-5min	France	Shom - France	CordemaisTG-5min	47,2772	- 1,8898	369449	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369449
179	CordemaisTG-60min	France	Shom - France	CordemaisTG-60min	47,2772	- 1,8898	370027	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370027
180	CorunaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	CorunaTG	43,3570	- 8,3890	8495	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8495
181	Cromer	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Cromer	52,9333	1,3000	23	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=23
182	CromerTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	CromerTG	52,9344	1,3016	8496	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8496
183	Cuxhaven	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Cuxhaven	53,8678	8,7175	8498	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8498

184	CuxhavenTG	Germany	WSOC - Waterways and Shipping Office Cuxhaven - Germany	CuxhavenTG	53,8678	8,7175	8499	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8499
185	D151TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	D151TG	54,3167	2,9334	8501	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8501
186	Dagebuell	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Dagebuell	54,7311	8,6883	8502	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8502
187	DagebuellTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	DagebuellTG	54,7310	8,6870	8503	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8503
188	Daugavgriva	Latvia	LEGMA - Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Agency - Latvia	Daugavgriva	57,0500	24,0167	8508	2005 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8508
189	Degerby	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Degerby	60,0319	20,3848	8509	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8509
190	DegradDesCannesTG	France	Shom - France	DeardDesCannesTG	4,8529	52,2722	371429	2008 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371429
191	DegradDesCannesTG-10min	France	Shom - France	DegradDesCannesTG-10min	4,8529	52,2722	370028	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370028
192	DegradDesCannesTG-60min	France	Shom - France	DegradDesCannesTG-60min	4,8529	52,2722	370029	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370029
193	Delfzijl	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands	Delfzijl	53,3300	6,9300	11107	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11107
194	DelfzijlTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DelfzijlTG	53,3270	6,9340	8510	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8510
195	DenHelderTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DenHelderTG	52,9700	4,7500	8512	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8512
196	DenOeverBinnenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DenOeverBinnenTG	52,9313	5,0479	8513	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8513
197	DenOeverBuitenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DenOeverBuitenTG	52,9326	5,0460	8514	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8514
198	DenOeverTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DenOeverTG	52,9326	5,0460	8515	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8515
199	DeshalesTG	France	Shom - France	DeshalesTG	16,3053	61,7959	372084	2015 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372084
200	DieletteTG	France	Shom - France	DieletteTG	49,5525	1,8608	26684	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26684
201	DieletteTG-10min	France	Shom - France	DieletteTG-10min	49,5525	1,8608	370030	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370030
202	DieletteTG-1min	France	Shom - France	DieletteTG-1min	49,5525	1,8608	369460	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369460
203	DieletteTG-5min	France	Shom - France	DieletteTG-5min	49,5525	1,8608	370863	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370863
204	DieletteTG-60min	France	Shom - France	DieletteTG-60min	49,5525	1,8608	370031	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370031
205	DieppeTG	France	Shom - France	DieppeTG	49,9300	1,0850	8517	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8517
206	DieppeTG-10min	France	Shom - France	DieppeTG-10min	49,9300	1,0850	370032	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370032

207	DieppeTG-1min	France	Shom - France	DieppeTG-1min	49,9300	1,0850	369462	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369462
208	DieppeTG-60min	France	Shom - France	DieppeTG-60min	49,9300	1,0850	370033	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370033
209	Dingle	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Dingle	52,1392	10,2773	989003	2017 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=989003
210	DordrechtTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DordrechtTG	51,8200	4,6710	11619	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11619
211	Dover	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Dover	51,1167	1,3167	18	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=18
212	DoverTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	DoverTG	51,1144	1,3227	8519	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8519
213	Dragor	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Dragor	55,6000	12,6833	8520	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8520
214	Drogden	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Drogden	55,5358	12,7117	8521	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8521
215	DublinPort	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	DublinPort	53,3457	6,2217	8522	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8522
216	DublinPortTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	DublinPortTG	53,3460	6,2220	8523	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8523
217	DumontDürvilleTG	France	Shom - France	DumontDürvilleTG	66,6617	140,0100	368637	1996 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368637
218	DumontDürvilleTG-20min	France	Shom - France	DumontDürvilleTG-20min	66,6617	140,0100	369466	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369466
219	DumontDürvilleTG-60min	France	Shom - France	DumontDürvilleTG-60min	66,6617	140,0100	370034	2014 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370034
220	DunkerqueTG	France	Shom - France	DunkerqueTG	51,0482	2,3665	8524	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8524
221	DunkerqueTG-10min	France	Shom - France	DunkerqueTG-10min	51,0482	2,3665	370035	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370035
222	DunkerqueTG-1min	France	Shom - France	DunkerqueTG-1min	51,0482	2,3665	369467	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369467
223	DunkerqueTG-60min	France	Shom - France	DunkerqueTG-60min	51,0482	2,3665	370036	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370036
224	Dunmore	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Dunmore	52,1477	6,9919	25805	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25805
225	E4BronSodertalje	Sweden	E4BronSodertalje	E4BronSodertalje	59,1848	17,6428	967457	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967457
226	Eckernfoerde	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Eckernfoerde	54,4747	9,8361	8525	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8525
227	EckernfoerdeTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toennning - Germany	EckernfoerdeTG	54,4750	9,8370	8526	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8526
228	EdamTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	EdamTG	52,5170	5,0700	8527	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8527
229	EdenTG	Germany	WSOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany	EdenTG	53,3367	7,1864	27256	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=27256

<https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/.php>

230	EemshavenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	EemshavenTG	53,4632	6,8390	8528	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8528	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
231	EiderSP	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	EiderSP	54,2667	8,8433	8530	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8530	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
232	EiderSPTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	EiderSPTG	54,2660	8,8420	8531	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8531	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
233	Eisma	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Eisma	59,5680	26,3050	637399	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=637399	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
234	ElHierroTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ElHierroTG	27,7800	- 17,9000	8533	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8533	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
235	Emden	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Emden	53,3367	7,1864	8534	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8534	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
236	EmdenTG	Germany	WSOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany	EmdenTG	53,3367	7,1864	8535	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8535	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
237	Esbjerg	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Esbjerg	55,4667	8,4333	8536	1993 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8536	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
238	EsbjergTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	EsbjergTG	55,4667	8,4333	8537	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8537	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
239	EuroplatformTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	EuroplatformTG	52,0000	3,2800	8544	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8544	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
240	EXSH0001	France	Shom - France	EXSH0001	48,3600	- 4,7800	368086	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368086	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
241	EXSH0002	France	Shom - France	EXSH0002	48,3800	- 4,5000	368313	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368313	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
242	EXSH0003	France	Shom - France	EXSH0003	47,2600	- 2,2000	368089	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368089	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
243	EXSH0004	France	Shom - France	EXSH0004	49,6500	- 1,6300	368075	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368075	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
244	EXSH0005	France	Shom - France	EXSH0005	- 20,9200	55,2800	368076	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368076	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
245	EXSH0006	France	Shom - France	EXSH0006	49,4819	0,1063	368077	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368077	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
246	EXSH0007	France	Shom - France	EXSH0007	43,6955	7,2853	368078	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368078	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
247	EXSH0008	France	Shom - France	EXSH0008	- 12,7833	45,2583	368079	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368079	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
248	EXSH0009	France	Shom - France	EXSH0009	49,9300	1,0850	368081	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368081	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
249	EXSH0010	France	Shom - France	EXSH0010	41,9200	8,7600	368083	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368083	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
250	EXSH0011	France	Shom - France	EXSH0011	43,2911	5,3558	368314	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368314	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
251	EXSH0012	France	Shom - France	EXSH0012	48,7160	- 3,9660	368315	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368315	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
252	EXSH0013	France	Shom - France	EXSH0013	50,9694	1,8677	368085	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368085	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php

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253	EXSH0014	France	Shom - France	EXSH0014	48,6416	-	2,0280	368088	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368088	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
254	EXSH0015	France	Shom - France	EXSH0015	50,7275	-	1,5775	368091	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368091	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
255	EXSH0016	France	Shom - France	EXSH0016	44,6650	-	1,1636	368093	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368093	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
256	EXSH0017	France	Shom - France	EXSH0017	47,8737	-	3,9074	368095	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368095	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
257	EXSH0018	France	Shom - France	EXSH0018	47,5427	-	2,8952	368316	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368316	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
258	EXSH0019	France	Shom - France	EXSH0019	43,1172	-	5,9131	368096	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368096	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
259	EXSH0020	France	Shom - France	EXSH0020	46,4975	-	1,7937	368099	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368099	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
260	EXSH0021	France	Shom - France	EXSH0021	46,1585	-	1,2207	368100	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368100	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
261	EXSH0022	France	Shom - France	EXSH0022	43,4049	-	4,8929	368103	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368103	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
262	EXSH0023	France	Shom - France	EXSH0023	-	22,2466	166,4116	368080	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368080	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
263	EXSH0024	France	Shom - France	EXSH0024	45,5685	-	1,0616	368082	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368082	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
264	EXSH0025	France	Shom - France	EXSH0025	41,8570	-	9,4040	368084	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368084	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
265	EXSH0026	France	Shom - France	EXSH0026	42,9669	-	9,3502	368087	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368087	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
266	EXSH0027	France	Shom - France	EXSH0027	43,7329	-	7,4237	368090	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368090	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
267	EXSH0028	France	Shom - France	EXSH0028	42,5201	-	3,1073	368092	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368092	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
268	EXSH0029	France	Shom - France	EXSH0029	47,6439	-	3,4471	368317	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368317	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
269	EXSH0030	France	Shom - France	EXSH0030	43,5273	-	1,5148	368094	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368094	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
270	EXSH0031	France	Shom - France	EXSH0031	43,3952	-	1,6816	368097	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368097	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
271	EXSH0032	France	Shom - France	EXSH0032	43,4835	-	6,9338	368098	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368098	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
272	EXSH0033	France	Shom - France	EXSH0033	43,3976	-	3,6991	368101	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368101	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
273	EXSH0035	France	Shom - France	EXSH0035	51,0481	-	2,3667	25807	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25807	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
274	EXSH0036	France	Shom - France	EXSH0036	14,6019	-	61,0636	368318	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368318	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
275	EXSH0037	France	Shom - France	EXSH0037	43,2156	-	6,4307	368102	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368102	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php

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276	EXSH0038	France	Shom - France	EXSH0038	16,2244	-	61,5315	368104	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368104	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
277	EXSH0039	France	Shom - France	EXSH0039	47,2866	-	2,0004	366205	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366205	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
278	EXSH0040	France	Shom - France	EXSH0040	47,3056	-	2,1084	366208	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366208	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
279	EXSH0042	France	Shom - France	EXSH0042	43,5270	-	1,5136	366233	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366233	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
280	EXSH0043	France	Shom - France	EXSH0043	-	13,2847	-	176,1685	366209	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366209	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
281	EXSH0044	France	Shom - France	EXSH0044	-	9,8048	-	139,0341	366257	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366257	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
282	EXSH0045	France	Shom - France	EXSH0045	-	14,9458	-	147,7060	366260	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366260	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
283	EXSH0046	France	Shom - France	EXSH0046	18,0833	-	63,0854	366254	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366254	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
284	EXSH0047	France	Shom - France	EXSH0047	43,3591	-	6,7176	366236	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366236	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
285	EXSH0050	France	Shom - France	EXSH0050	49,2794	-	0,2490	366239	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366239	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
286	EXSH0051	France	Shom - France	EXSH0051	47,2042	-	1,5743	366242	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366242	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
287	EXSH0052	France	Shom - France	EXSH0052	-	17,5331	-	149,5727	366255	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366255	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
288	EXSH0054	France	Shom - France	EXSH0054	47,2772	-	1,8898	366229	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366229	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
289	EXSH0055	France	Shom - France	EXSH0055	43,4818	-	1,4732	366202	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366202	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
290	EXSH0056	France	Shom - France	EXSH0056	43,0147	-	3,0641	366203	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366203	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
291	EXSH0057	France	Shom - France	EXSH0057	-	20,6920	-	164,9431	366207	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366207	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou
292	EXSH0058	France	Shom - France	EXSH0058	-	17,8059	-	149,2950	366259	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366259	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
293	EXSH0059	France	Shom - France	EXSH0059	44,8600	-	0,5528	366230	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366230	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/		
294	EXSH0060	France	Shom - France	EXSH0060	-	16,6270	-	143,5692	366261	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366261	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	
295	EXSH0061	France	Shom - France	EXSH0061	-	14,2960	-	178,1602	366210	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366210	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou
296	EXSH0062	France	Shom - France	EXSH0062	43,5203	-	4,1264	366263	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366263	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
297	EXSH0063	France	Shom - France	EXSH0063	43,3892	-	1,6627	366232	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366232	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	
298	EXSH0066	France	Shom - France	EXSH0066	46,3350	-	1,3164	366265	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366265	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou	

299	EXSH0067	France	Shom - France	EXSH0067	47,2054	-	1,7651	366234	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366234	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
300	EXSH0068	France	Shom - France	EXSH0068	-	20,9185	167,2787	366237	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366237	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
301	EXSH0069	France	Shom - France	EXSH0069	-	21,6138	166,2415	366241	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366241	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
302	EXSH0071	France	Shom - France	EXSH0071	45,9136	-	1,3278	366243	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366243	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
303	EXSH0074	France	Shom - France	EXSH0074	45,9463	-	0,9535	366245	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366245	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
304	EXSH0076	France	Shom - France	EXSH0076	-	8,9149	140,0960	366256	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366256	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
305	EXSH0077	France	Shom - France	EXSH0077	47,1935	-	1,6337	366246	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366246	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
306	EXSH0078	France	Shom - France	EXSH0078	45,6206	-	1,0278	366247	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366247	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
307	EXSH0079	France	Shom - France	EXSH0079	43,4380	-	1,4602	366248	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366248	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
308	EXSH0081	France	Shom - France	EXSH0081	-	49,3521	70,2191	366258	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366258	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
309	EXSH0082	France	Shom - France	EXSH0082	46,3168	-	1,0826	366249	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366249	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
310	EXSH0083	France	Shom - France	EXSH0083	-	21,9829	166,6833	366231	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366231	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
311	EXSH0084	France	Shom - France	EXSH0084	43,4976	-	1,4794	366204	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366204	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
312	EXSH0085	France	Shom - France	EXSH0085	-	66,6617	140,0100	368270	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368270	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
313	EXSH0086	France	Shom - France	EXSH0086	45,8534	-	1,1778	366206	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366206	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
314	EXSH0087	France	Shom - France	EXSH0087	-	23,1178	134,9690	366264	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366264	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
315	EXSH0088	France	Shom - France	EXSH0088	-	21,5478	167,8771	366235	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366235	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
316	EXSH0089	France	Shom - France	EXSH0089	46,7788	-	56,1683	366238	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366238	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
317	EXSH0090	France	Shom - France	EXSH0090	16,3029	-	61,0725	366262	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366262	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
318	EXSH0091	France	Shom - France	EXSH0091	-	20,5498	166,5619	366240	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366240	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
319	EXSH0092	France	Shom - France	EXSH0092	43,5025	-	1,2995	366244	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366244	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
320	EXSH0094	France	Shom - France	EXSH0094	16,3053	-	61,7959	369947	2015 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369947	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	
321	EXSH0094-1min	France	Shom - France	EXSH0094-1min	16,3053	-	61,7959	369676	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369676	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/	

322	EXSH0095	France	Shom - France	EXSH0095	48,6475	-	2,8181	371267	2018 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371267	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
323	EXSH0095-1min	France	Shom - France	EXSH0095-1min	48,6475	-	2,8181	369658	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369658	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
324	F161	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	F161	54,1167		4,0166	8548	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8548	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
325	F3platformTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	F3platformTG	54,8500		4,7200	8550	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8550	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
326	Faaborg	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Faaborg	55,1000		10,2500	8551	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8551	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
327	Falkenberg	Sweden	Falkenberg	Falkenberg	56,8920		12,4895	967474	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967474	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
328	FatouvilleTG	France	Shom - France	FatouvilleTG	49,4318		0,3160	638732	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=638732	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
329	Felixstowe	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Felixstowe	51,9667		1,3500	25810	1990 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25810	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
330	Ferring	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Ferring	56,5246		8,1152	8552	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8552	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
331	FerringHavn	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	FerringHavn	56,5246		8,1152	25811	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25811	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
332	FerringTG	Denmark	FerringTG	FerringTG	56,5246		8,1152	9275	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9275	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
333	Ferrol2TG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	Ferrol2TG	43,4762	-	8,2485	28135	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28135	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
334	FerrolTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	FerrolTG	43,4630	-	8,3260	8553	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8553	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
335	Fishguard	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Fishguard	52,0167	-	4,9833	19	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=19	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
336	FishguardTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	FishguardTG	52,0138	-	4,9833	8560	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8560	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
337	Flensburg	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Flensburg	54,7950		9,4331	8561	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8561	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
338	FlensburgTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	FlensburgTG	54,7960		9,4340	8562	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8562	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
339	FormenteraTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	FormenteraTG	38,7347		1,4189	8565	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8565	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
340	Forsmark	Sweden	Forsmark	Forsmark	60,4086		18,2108	431	1975 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=431	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
341	FortDeFranceTG	France	Shom - France	FortDeFranceTG	14,6010	-	61,0630	8566	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8566	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
342	FortDeFranceTG-10min	France	Shom - France	FortDeFranceTG-10min	14,6010	-	61,0630	370037	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370037	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
343	FortDeFranceTG-1min	France	Shom - France	FortDeFranceTG-1min	14,6010	-	61,0630	369470	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369470	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
344	FortDeFranceTG-60min	France	Shom - France	FortDeFranceTG-60min	14,6010	-	61,0630	370038	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370038	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php

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345	FosSurMerTG	France	Shom - France	FosSurMerTG	43,4049	4,8929	8567	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8567		
346	FosSurMerTG-10min	France	Shom - France	FosSurMerTG-10min	43,4049	4,8929	370039	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370039		
347	FosSurMerTG-1min	France	Shom - France	FosSurMerTG-1min	43,4049	4,8929	369472	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369472		
348	FosSurMerTG-60min	France	Shom - France	FosSurMerTG-60min	43,4049	4,8929	370040	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370040		
349	Fredericia	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Fredericia	55,5667	9,7500	8568	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8568	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
350	Frederikshavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Frederikshavn	57,4333	10,5667	8569	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8569	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
351	FrederikshavnTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	FrederikshavnTG	57,4333	10,5667	363740	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363740	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
352	FuerteventuraTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	FuerteventuraTG	28,5000	13,8500	8570	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8570	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
353	Furuogrund	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Furuogrund	64,9158	21,2306	432	1916 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=432	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
354	Fynshav	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Fynshav	55,0000	9,9833	8572	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8572	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
355	GaletsTG	France	Shom - France	GaletsTG	20,9200	55,3000	8573	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8573	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
356	GaletsTG-10min	France	Shom - France	GaletsTG-10min	20,9200	55,3000	370041	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370041	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
357	GaletsTG-1min	France	Shom - France	GaletsTG-1min	20,9200	55,3000	369473	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369473	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
358	GaletsTG-60min	France	Shom - France	GaletsTG-60min	20,9200	55,3000	370042	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370042	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
359	GalwayPort	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	GalwayPort	53,2690	9,0480	550	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=550	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
360	GalwayPortTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	GalwayPortTG	53,2690	9,0480	8574	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8574	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
361	GandiaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	GandiaTG	38,9950	0,1520	8575	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8575	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
362	Gdansk	Poland	IMWMMB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland	Gdansk	54,3997	18,6981	967435	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967435	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
363	Gedser	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Gedser	54,5667	11,9333	8576	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8576	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
364	Gibraltar	United Kingdom	POL - Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory - United Kingdom	Gibraltar	36,1300	5,3500	25813	2012 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25813	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
365	GijonTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	GijonTG	43,5580	5,6980	8578	1995 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8578	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
366	GoмераTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	GoмераTG	28,0000	17,0000	8579	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8579	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	
367	GoteborgAgnesberg	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgAgnesberg	57,7897	12,0100	26824	2012 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26824	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php	

368	GoteborgEriksberg	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgEriksberg	57,6967	11,9089	26825	2012 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26825	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
369	GoteborgGotaalvbron	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgGotaalvbron	57,7147	11,9669	27261	2010 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=27261	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
370	GoteborgLarjeholm	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgLarjeholm	57,7658	12,0056	26826	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26826	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
371	GoteborgTingstadstunneln	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgTingstadstunneln	57,7231	11,9869	26827	2012 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26827	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
372	GoteborgTorshammen	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GoteborgTorshammen	57,6847	11,7906	433	1967 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=433	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
373	Goteborg-TorshammenTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Goteborg-TorshammenTG	57,6846	11,7907	8580	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8580	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
374	Greifswald	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Greifswald	54,0928	13,4461	8581	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8581	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
375	GreifswaldTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	GreifswaldTG	54,0930	13,4470	8582	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8582	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
376	Grena	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Grena	56,4111	10,9306	8583	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8583	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
377	Haderslev	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Haderslev	55,2500	9,5167	8585	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8585	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
378	Halden	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Halden	59,1247	11,3875	8587	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8587	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
379	Halmstad	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Halmstad	56,6488	12,8358	967437	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967437	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
380	Hamina	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Hamina	60,5628	27,1792	13386	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13386	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
381	Hammerfest	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Hammerfest	70,6667	23,6833	8588	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8588	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
382	HammerfestTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HammerfestTG	70,6646	23,6832	8589	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8589	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
383	Hanko	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Hanko	59,8229	22,9766	13387	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13387	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
384	Hanstholm	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hanstholm	57,1167	8,6000	8590	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8590	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
385	HanstholmTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	HanstholmTG	57,1166	8,6000	9276	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9276	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
386	Haparanda	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Haparanda	65,7717	23,9029	15364	2014 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=15364	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
387	Haringvliet10TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	Haringvliet10TG	51,8641	3,8600	8592	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8592	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
388	Harlingen	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands	Harlingen	53,1800	5,4100	11108	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11108	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
389	HarlingenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	HarlingenTG	53,1770	5,4100	8593	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8593	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
390	Harstad	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Harstad	68,8000	16,5500	8594	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8594	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php

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<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

391	HarstadTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HarstadTG	68,8013	16,5482	8595	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8595	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
392	Harwich	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Harwich	51,9480	1,2920	25	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
393	HarwichTG	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	HarwichTG	51,9480	1,2921	8596	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8596	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
394	Havneby	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Havneby	55,0870	8,5654	8597	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8597	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
395	HavnebyRomo	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	HavnebyRomo	55,0870	8,5654	25817	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25817	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
396	HavnebyTG	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark	HavnebyTG	55,0870	8,5654	9277	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9277	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
397	HavreGPMRouenTG	France	Shom - France	HavreGPMRouenTG	49,4838	0,1146	638733	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=638733	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
398	Heiligenhafen	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Heiligenhafen	54,3731	11,0056	8599	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8599	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
399	HeiligenhafenTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	HeiligenhafenTG	54,3740	11,0070	8600	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8600	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
400	Heimsjoe	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Heimsjoe	63,4333	9,1167	8602	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8602	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
401	HeimsjoeTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HeimsjoeTG	63,4252	9,1015	8603	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8603	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
402	Helgeroa	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Helgeroa	59,0000	9,8667	8604	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8604	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
403	HelgeroaTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HelgeroaTG	58,9952	9,8564	8605	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8605	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
404	Helgoland	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Helgoland	54,1789	7,8900	8606	2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8606	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
405	HelgolandTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	HelgolandTG	54,1789	7,8900	8608	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8608	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
406	Helsingborg	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Helsingborg	56,0412	12,6845	967442	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967442	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
407	Helsinki	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Helsinki	60,1536	24,9562	8610	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8610	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
408	Heltermaa	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Heltermaa	58,8664	23,0466	8611	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8611	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
409	HerbaudiereTG	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTG	47,0249	2,2983	11354	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11354	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
410	HerbaudiereTG-10min	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTG-10min	47,0249	2,2983	370043	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370043	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
411	HerbaudiereTG-1min	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTG-1min	47,0249	2,2983	369476	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369476	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
412	HerbaudiereTG-5min	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTG-5min	47,0249	2,2983	370044	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370044	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
413	HerbaudiereTG-60min	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTG-60min	47,0249	2,2983	370045	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370045	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php

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414	HerbaudiereTGG	France	Shom - France	HerbaudiereTGG	47,0260	2,2990	11345	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11345	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
415	Hesnaes	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hesnaes	54,8167	12,1333	8612	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8612	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
416	Heysham	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Heysham	54,0333	2,29167	8	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
417	HeyshamTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	HeyshamTG	54,0317	2,29204	8613	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8613	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
418	HiengheneTG	France	Shom - France	HiengheneTG	20,6920	164,9431	368640	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368640	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
419	HiengheneTG-1min	France	Shom - France	HiengheneTG-1min	20,6920	164,9431	369479	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369479	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
420	HiengheneTG-60min	France	Shom - France	HiengheneTG-60min	20,6920	164,9431	370046	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370046	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
421	Hinkley	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Hinkley	51,2167	3,1333	8614	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8614	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
422	HinkleyPointTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	HinkleyPointTG	51,2100	3,1300	8615	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8615	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
423	Hirtshals	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hirtshals	57,6000	9,9667	8616	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8616	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
424	HirtshalsTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	HirtshalsTG	57,6000	9,9667	9278	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9278	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
425	HivaOaTG	France	Shom - France	HivaOaTG	9,8048	139,0341	368972	2012 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368972	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
426	HivaOaTG-1min	France	Shom - France	HivaOaTG-1min	9,8048	139,0341	369660	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369660	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
427	HivaOaTG-5min	France	Shom - France	HivaOaTG-5min	9,8048	139,0341	370864	2003 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370864	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
428	HivaOaTG-60min	France	Shom - France	HivaOaTG-60min	9,8048	139,0341	370047	1978 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370047	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
429	Hobro	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hobro	56,6333	9,8000	8617	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8617	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
430	HoekVanHollandTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	HoekVanHollandTG	51,9800	4,1200	8620	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8620	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
431	Hoernum	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Hoernum	54,7500	8,3000	8621	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8621	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
432	HoernumTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	HoernumTG	54,7580	8,2960	8622	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8622	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
433	Hogland	Other	Not Defined	Hogland	60,0167	27,0000	8623	2010 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8623	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
434	Holbaek	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Holbaek	55,7167	11,7167	8625	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8625	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
435	HollandseBrugTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands SMHJ - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	HollandseBrugTG	52,3267	5,1400	8626	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8626	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
436	Holmsund	Sweden	Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Holmsund	63,6555	20,3410	967444	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967444	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php

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437	Holyhead	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Holyhead	53,3167	-	4,6167	11	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
438	HolyheadTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	HolyheadTG	53,3139	-	4,6204	8627	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8627	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
439	HonfleurTG	France	Shom - France	HonfleurTG	49,4283	-	0,2329	638734	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=638734	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
440	HonningsvaagTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HonningsvaagTG	70,9803	-	25,9727	8628	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8628	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
441	Honningsvag	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Honningsvag	70,9833	-	25,9833	8629	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8629	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
442	Hooge	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Hooge	54,5786	-	8,5564	8631	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8631	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
443	Hornbaek	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hornbaek	56,1000	-	12,4667	8632	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8632	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
444	HoutribsluizenNoordTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	HoutribsluizenNoordTG	52,5296	-	5,4347	8633	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8633	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
445	HoutribsluizenZuidTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	HoutribsluizenZuidTG	52,5274	-	5,4344	8634	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8634	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
446	Hov	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Hov	55,9167	-	10,2667	8635	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8635	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
447	Howth	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Howth	53,3915	-	6,0683	8636	2006 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8636	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
448	HowthTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	HowthTG	53,3915	-	6,0683	8637	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8637	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
449	HuahineTG	France	Shom - France	HuahineTG	-	16,7216	-	151,0325	372769	2019 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372769	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
450	HuahineTG-10min	France	Shom - France	HuahineTG-10min	-	16,7216	-	151,0325	370865	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370865	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
451	HuahineTG-60min	France	Shom - France	HuahineTG-60min	-	16,7216	-	151,0325	371430	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371430	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php
452	HuelvaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	HuelvaTG	37,1320	-	6,8340	8638	1996 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8638	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
453	HuibertgatTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	HuibertgatTG	53,5700	-	6,4000	8639	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8639	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
454	Husum	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Husum	54,4722	-	9,0247	8640	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8640	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
455	HusumTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	HusumTG	54,4720	-	9,0250	8641	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8641	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
456	HvideSandeHavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	HvideSandeHavn	56,0008	-	8,1292	25819	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25819	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
457	HvideSandeKyst	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	HvideSandeKyst	55,9988	-	8,1146	8642	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8642	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
458	HvideSandeKystTG	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	HvideSandeKystTG	55,9988	-	8,1146	9279	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9279	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
459	HvideSandeYdermole	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark	HvideSandeYdermole	55,9988	-	8,1146	25820	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25820	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	

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460	IbizaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IbizaTG	38,9111	1,4497	8643	2003 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8643	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
461	IF000374	France	Shom - France	IF000374	48,6411	2,0276	25828	2011 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25828	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
462	IJgeulstroompaa1TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	IJgeulstroompaa1TG	52,4661	4,5189	8649	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8649	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
463	Ilmondstroompaa1TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	Ilmondstroompaa1TG	52,4650	4,5179	8652	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8652	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
464	IjmuidenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	IjmuidenTG	52,4630	4,5550	8653	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8653	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
465	IleDAixTG	France	Shom - France	IleDAixTG	46,0074	1,1743	8654	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8654	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
466	IleDAixTG-10min	France	Shom - France	IleDAixTG-10min	46,0074	1,1743	370048	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370048	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
467	IleDAixTG-1min	France	Shom - France	IleDAixTG-1min	46,0074	1,1743	369401	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369401	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
468	IleDAixTG-60min	France	Shom - France	IleDAixTG-60min	46,0074	1,1743	370049	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370049	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
469	IleRousseTG	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG	42,6396	8,9352	8655	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8655	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
470	IleRousseTG-10min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-10min	42,6396	8,9352	370050	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370050	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
471	IleRousseTG-1min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-1min	42,6396	8,9352	369402	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369402	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
472	IleRousseTG-20min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-20min	42,6396	8,9352	370719	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370719	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
473	IleRousseTG-2min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-2min	42,6396	8,9352	369499	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369499	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
474	IleRousseTG-5min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-5min	42,6396	8,9352	369762	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369762	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
475	IleRousseTG-60min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-60min	42,6396	8,9352	370051	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370051	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
476	IleRousseTG-6min	France	Shom - France	IleRousseTG-6min	42,6396	8,9352	369852	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369852	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
477	IlesDuSalutTG	France	Shom - France	IlesDuSalutTG	5,2500	52,6200	8656	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8656	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
478	IlesDuSalutTG-10min	France	Shom - France	IlesDuSalutTG-10min	5,2500	52,6200	370052	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370052	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
479	IlesDuSalutTG-1min	France	Shom - France	IlesDuSalutTG-1min	5,2500	52,6200	369403	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369403	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
480	IlesDuSalutTG-60min	France	Shom - France	IlesDuSalutTG-60min	5,2500	52,6200	370053	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370053	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
481	IletLaMereTG	France	Shom - France	IletLaMereTG	4,8938	52,1905	370866	2004 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370866	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php
482	IletLaMereTG-10min	France	Shom - France	IletLaMereTG-10min	4,8938	52,1905	370867	1989 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370867	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainimg/stations/.php

483	IleLaMereTG-5min	France	Shom - France	IleLaMereTG-5min	4,8938	-	52,1905	370868			1992 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370868	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
484	IleLaMereTG-60min	France	Shom - France	IleLaMereTG-60min	4,8938	-	52,1905	370054			1978 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370054	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
485	Ilfracombe	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Ilfracombe	51,2167	-	4,1167	9			1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/		
486	IlfracombeTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	IlfracombeTG	51,2110	-	4,1109	8657			2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8657	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/		
487	Immingham	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Immingham	53,6333	-	0,1833	26			1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/		
488	ImminghamTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	ImminghamTG	53,6310	-	0,1860	8658			2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8658	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/		
489	Inishmore	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Inishmore	53,1260	-	9,6600	10686			2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10686	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
490	IOC_abas	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_abas	44,0200	-	144,2900	366609	abas		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366609	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=abas	
491	IOC_abed			IOC_abed	57,1400	-	2,0800	366610	abed		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366610	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=abed	
492	IOC_abur	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_abur	31,5800	-	131,4100	366611	abur		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366611	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=abur	
493	IOC_acaj	El Salvador	other - El Salvador	IOC_acaj	13,5738	-	89,8381	366612	acaj		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366612	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=acaj	
494	IOC_acap2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_acap2	16,8383	-	99,9033	366613	cap2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366613	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=cap2	
495	IOC_acnj	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_acnj	39,3550	-	74,4183	366615	acnj		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366615	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=acnj	
496	IOC_acni2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_acni2	39,3550	-	74,4183	366616	cnj2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366616	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=cnj2	
497	IOC_acor1			IOC_acor1	43,3644	-	8,3989	969395	cor1		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=969395	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=cor1	
498	IOC_acya	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_acya	16,8380	-	99,9030	366614	acya		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366614	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=acya	
499	IOC_adak	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_adak	51,8630	-	176,6320	366617	adak		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366617	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=adak	
500	IOC_adak2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_adak2	51,8630	-	176,6320	368511	dak2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368511	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=dak2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
501	IOC_aden			IOC_aden	12,7883	-	44,9742	366618	aden		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366618	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=aden	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
502	IOC_agal	Mauritius	other - Mauritius	IOC_agal	10,3456	-	56,5856	363948	agal		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363948	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=agal	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
503	IOC_agua			IOC_agua	18,4583	-	67,1650	963329	agua		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=963329	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=agua	
504	IOC_ajac	France	Shom - France	IOC_ajac	41,9200	-	8,7600	366619	ajac		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366619	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=ajac	
505	IOC_ajac2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ajac2	41,9200	-	8,7600	366620	jac2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366620	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=ajac2	

506	IOC_alac1		IOC_alac1	38,3383	-	0,4778	969391	lac1	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=969391	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alac1
507	IOC_alac2		IOC_alac2	38,3389	-	0,4814	969392	lac2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=969392	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alac2
508	IOC_alak	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_alak	56,8975	-	154,2481	363949	alak	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363949	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alak
509	IOC_alam	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_alam	37,7720	-	122,2980	366621	alam	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366621	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alam
510	IOC_albo		IOC_albo	35,9389	-	3,0337	968415	albo	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=968415	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=albo
511	IOC_albu	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy IOC_albu	37,0825	-	8,2604	363950	albu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363950	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=albu
512	IOC_alcu	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain IOC_alcu	39,8346		3,1390	366622	alcu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366622	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alcu
513	IOC_aler	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada IOC_aler	82,4900	-	62,3200	965560	aler	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=965560	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=aler
514	IOC_alex1	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy IOC_alex1	31,2124		29,8849	368299	lex1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=368299	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lex1
515	IOC_alge	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain IOC_alge	36,1770	-	5,3984	363951	alge	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363951	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alge
516	IOC_alme	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain IOC_alme	36,8300	-	2,4784	366623	alme	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366623	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alme
517	IOC_alme2		IOC_alme2	36,8322	-	2,4847	969393	lme2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=969393	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lme2
518	IOC_alofi	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia IOC_alofi	-	19,0527	-	169,9209	lofi	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=638014	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lofi
519	IOC_alva	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico IOC_alva	18,7667	-	95,7667	366624	alva	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366624	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=alva
520	IOC_amal	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_amal	18,3350	-	64,9200	366625	amal	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366625	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=amal
521	IOC_amal2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_amal2	18,3350	-	64,9200	367488	mal2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367488	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mal2
522	IOC_ambon	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia IOC_ambon	-	3,6833	128,1833	366626	mbon	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366626	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mbon
523	IOC_AN15		IOC_AN15	43,6248		13,5065	366627	AN15	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366627	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=AN15
524	IOC_anch	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_anch	61,2380	-	149,8880	366628	anch	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366628	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=anch
525	IOC_anch2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_anch2	61,2380	-	149,8880	975732	nch2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=975732	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=nch2
526	IOC_ancu	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile IOC_ancu	-	41,8674	-	73,8331	ancu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363952	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ancu
527	IOC_ancu2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile IOC_ancu2	-	41,8674	-	73,8331	ncu2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363953	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ncu2
528	IOC_ande		IOC_ande	69,3167		16,1500	366629	ande	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366629	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ande

529	IOC_anta		HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_anta	36,8355	30,6126	968155	anta	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968155	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=anta
530	IOC_anto	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_anto	-	23,6531	70,4044	366630	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366630	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=anto
531	IOC_anto2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_anto2	-	23,6531	70,4044	366631	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366631	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=anto2
532	IOC_apfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_apfl	29,7270	-	84,9820	366632	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366632	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=apfl
533	IOC_apfl2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_apfl2	29,7270	-	84,9820	370223	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370223	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=apfl2
534	IOC_apla	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_apla	29,4496	-	91,3381	363954	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363954	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=apla
535	IOC_arac			IOC_arac	18,4805	-	66,7024	366633	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366633	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arac
536	IOC_arac5			IOC_arac5	18,4805	-	66,7024	979026	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=979026	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arac5
537	IOC_arca	France	Shom - France	IOC_arca	44,6650	-	1,1636	366634	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366634	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arca
538	IOC_aren	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_aren	38,9130	-	123,7050	366635	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366635	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=aren
539	IOC_aric	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_aric	-	18,4758	70,3232	366636	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366636	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=aric
540	IOC_aric2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_aric2	-	18,4758	70,3232	366637	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366637	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=aric2
541	IOC_arrc	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_arrc	-	22,9726	42,0138	363955	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363955	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arrc
542	IOC_arre	Spain	PIE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_arre	28,9719	-	13,5301	366638	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366638	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arre
543	IOC_ascen			IOC_ascen	-	7,9167	14,4167	369016	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369016	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ascen
544	IOC_ashk	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_ashk	21,8500	-	59,5700	363956	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363956	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ashk
545	IOC_asro			IOC_asro	12,6260	-	87,3420	961066	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=961066	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=asro
546	IOC_asto	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_asto	46,2080	-	123,7670	366639	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366639	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=asto
547	IOC_asto2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_asto2	46,2080	-	123,7670	367701	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367701	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=asto2
548	IOC_atka	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_atka	52,2317	-	174,1730	363957	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363957	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=atka
549	IOC_auct	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_auct	-	36,8314	174,7865	366640	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366640	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=auct
550	IOC_audi	France	Shom - France	IOC_audi	48,0216	-	4,5372	366580	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366580	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=audi
551	IOC_audi2	France	Shom - France	IOC_audi2	48,0216	-	4,5372	366581	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366581	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=audi2

552	IOC_avon		IOC_avon	51,5000	-	2,7300	366641	avon	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366641	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=avon	
553	IOC_AZ42		IOC_AZ42	41,4469	-	12,6348	454517	AZ42	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=454517	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=AZ42	
554	IOC_BA05		IOC_BA05	41,1402	-	16,8660	374203	BA05	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=374203	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=BA05	
555	IOC_ball	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	IOC_ball	54,2530	-	9,8900	363958	ball	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363958	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ball
556	IOC_balt			IOC_balt	-	0,4330	-	90,2830	366642	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366642	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=balt
557	IOC_bamd	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bamd	39,2670	-	76,5780	366643	bamd	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366643	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bamd
558	IOC_bamd2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bamd2	39,2670	-	76,5780	367990	amd2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367990	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=amd2
559	IOC_bame	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bame	44,3916	-	68,2050	366644	bame	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366644	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bame
560	IOC_bame2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bame2	44,3916	-	68,2050	367859	ame2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367859	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ame2
561	IOC_bamf	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_bamf	48,8400	-	125,1400	366645	bamf	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366645	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bamf
562	IOC_bamf2	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_bamf2	48,8333	-	125,1333	369735	amf2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369735	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=amf2
563	IOC_bang			IOC_bang	54,6600	-	5,6700	366646	bang	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366646	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bang
564	IOC_bara	Dominican Republic	other - Dominican Republic	IOC_bara	18,2081	-	71,0922	366647	bara	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366647	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bara
565	IOC_barb	Antigua and Barbuda	other - Antigua and Barbuda	IOC_barb	17,5907	-	61,8206	363959	barb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363959	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=barb
566	IOC_barb2	Antigua and Barbuda	other - Antigua and Barbuda	IOC_barb2	17,5907	-	61,8206	992295	arb2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=992295	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arb2
567	IOC_barc	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_barc	41,3418	-	2,1657	366648	barc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366648	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=barc
568	IOC_barm			IOC_barm	52,7200	-	4,0500	366649	barm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366649	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=barm
569	IOC_barn	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_barn	-	41,0501	145,9150	366650	barn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366650	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=barn
570	IOC_bass			IOC_bass	17,2900	-	62,7097	368387	bass	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368387	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bass
571	IOC_bbbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_bbbc	52,1600	-	128,1400	363960	bbbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363960	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bbbc
572	IOC_bdto	United States	other - US	IOC_bdto	9,3509	-	82,2577	363961	bdto	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363961	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bdto
573	IOC_BELE	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_BELE	-	1,4422	48,4963	967585	BELE	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967585	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=BELE
574	IOC_benc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_benc	34,7200	-	76,6700	366651	benc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366651	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=benc

575	IOC_benc2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_benc2	34,7200	-	76,6700	370678	enc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370678	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=enc2
576	IOC_beno	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_beno	-	8,7666	115,2166	366652	beno	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366652	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=beno
577	IOC_bgct	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bgct	41,1733	-	73,1816	366653	bgct	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366653	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bgct
578	IOC_bil3	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_bil3	43,3515	-	3,0451	366654	bil3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366654	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bil3
579	IOC_bitu	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_bitu	1,4389	125,1904		366655	bitu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366655	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bitu
580	IOC_blow			IOC_blow	18,1711	-	63,0926	370790	blow	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370790	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=blow
581	IOC_blr1	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_blr1	41,6000	-	71,3000	363962	blr1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363962	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=blr1
582	IOC_blueb	Mauritius	other - Mauritius	IOC_blueb	-	20,4441	57,7110	366656	lueb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366656	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lueb
583	IOC_bmda	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bmda	32,3667	-	64,7000	366657	bmda	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366657	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bmda
584	IOC_bmda2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_bmda2	32,3667	-	64,7000	366658	mda2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366658	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mda2
585	IOC_bmsa	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_bmsa	-	40,5811	73,7370	363963	bmsa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363963	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bmsa
586	IOC_bmsa2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_bmsa2	-	40,5811	73,7370	363964	msa2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363964	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=msa2
587	IOC_bodr			IOC_bodr	37,0322	27,4235		967478	bodr	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967478	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bodr
588	IOC_bodri	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_bodri	37,0311	27,4248		968156	odri	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968156	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=odri
589	IOC_boma	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_boma	42,3550	-	71,0516	366659	boma	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366659	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=boma
590	IOC_boma2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_boma2	42,3550	-	71,0516	366660	oma2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366660	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oma2
591	IOC_bon2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_bon2	36,8022	-	6,3381	366661	bon2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366661	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bon2
592	IOC_bork	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_bork	53,5575	6,7494		366662	bork	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366662	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bork
593	IOC_bouc	France	Shom - France	IOC_bouc	43,5273	-	1,5148	366663	bouc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366663	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bouc
594	IOC_bouc2	France	Shom - France	IOC_bouc2	43,5273	-	1,5148	366664	ouc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366664	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ouc2
595	IOC_boul	France	Shom - France	IOC_boul	50,7275	1,5775		366665	boul	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366665	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=boul
596	IOC_boul2	France	Shom - France	IOC_boul2	50,7275	1,5775		366666	oul2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366666	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oul2
597	IOC_bour			IOC_bour	50,7100	-	1,8700	366667	bour	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366667	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bour

598	IOC_bozc	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_bozc	39,8357	26,0759	970905	bozc	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=970905	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=bozc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
599	IOC_bres	France	Shom - France	IOC_bres	48,3800	4,5000	366668	bres	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366668	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=bres	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
600	IOC_brid			IOC_brid	13,1080	59,6290	979215	brid	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=979215	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=brid	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
601	IOC_brom	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_brom	-	18,0008	122,2186	brom	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366669	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=brom	
602	IOC_brpt	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_brpt	21,3218	158,1193	363965	brpt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363965	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=brpt	
603	IOC_btny	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_btny	40,7000	74,0200	366670	btny	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366670	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=btny	
604	IOC_btny2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_btny2	40,7000	74,0200	368613	tny2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368613	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tny2	
605	IOC_buca	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_buca	-	34,6394	72,0462	buca	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363966	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=buca	
606	IOC_buca3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_buca3	-	34,6394	72,0462	uca3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363967	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=uca3	
607	IOC_bull	Curaçao	other - Curaçao	IOC_bull	12,1873	69,0196	363968	bull	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363968	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=bull	
608	IOC_busa			IOC_busa	35,0931	129,0375	366671	busa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366671	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=busa	
609	IOC_buve	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_buve	3,8906	77,0808	366672	buve	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366672	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=buve	
610	IOC_buve2	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_buve2	3,8906	77,0808	366673	uve2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366673	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=uve2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
611	IOC_CA02			IOC_CA02	39,2101	9,1142	366675	CA02	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366675	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=CA02	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
612	IOC_cabc	United States	other - US	IOC_cabc	16,8028	88,0820	363970	cabc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363970	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cabc	
613	IOC_cadi	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_cadi	36,5421	6,2806	366674	cadi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366674	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cadi	
614	IOC_cala	France	Shom - France	IOC_cala	50,9694	1,8677	366676	cala	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366676	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cala	
615	IOC_cala2	France	Shom - France	IOC_cala2	50,9694	1,8677	366677	ala2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366677	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ala2	
616	IOC_cald	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cald	-	27,0646	70,8247	cald	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366678	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cald	
617	IOC_cald2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cald2	-	27,0646	70,8247	ald2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366679	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ald2	
618	IOC_call			IOC_call	-	12,0690	77,1668	call	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366680	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=call	
619	IOC_calq			IOC_calq	13,1299	61,1955	369523	calq	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369523	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=calq	
620	IOC_camt	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_camt	19,8120	90,5949	363971	camt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363971	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=camt	

621	IOC_caph	Haiti	other - Haiti	IOC_caph	19,7593	-	72,1934	363972	caph	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363972	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=caph		
622	IOC_cara	Senegal	other - Senegal	IOC_cara	12,5610	-	16,6985	363973	cara	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363973	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cara		
623	IOC_carb	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_carb	36,9743	-	1,8996	363974	carb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363974	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=carb	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
624	IOC_carg	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_carg	37,5700	-	0,9800	366682	carg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366682	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=carg	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
625	IOC_casc			IOC_casc	38,6932	-	9,4154	374102	casc	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=374102	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=casc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
626	IOC_cast			IOC_cast	51,6496	-	9,9034	366683	cast	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366683	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cast		
627	IOC_cbmd	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cbmd	38,5733	-	76,0683	366685	cbmd	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366685	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cbmd	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
628	IOC_cbmd2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cbmd2	38,5733	-	76,0683	790342	bmd2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=790342	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=bmd2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
629	IOC_cbva	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cbva	36,9670	-	76,1130	366686	cbva	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366686	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cbva		
630	IOC_ccar	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_ccar	18,6167	-	91,8167	366687	ccar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366687	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ccar	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
631	IOC_cctx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cctx	27,5800	-	97,2167	366688	cctx	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366688	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cctx	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
632	IOC_cctx2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cctx2	27,5800	-	97,2167	366689	ctx2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366689	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ctx2		
633	IOC_ceib	Honduras	other - Honduras	IOC_ceib	15,7900	-	86,7600	363975	ceib	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363975	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ceib		
634	IOC_cent	France	Shom - France	IOC_cent	42,9669	-	9,3501	366690	cent	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366690	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cent		
635	IOC_cent2	France	Shom - France	IOC_cent2	42,9669	-	9,3501	366691	ent2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366691	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ent2		
636	IOC_ceut			IOC_ceut	35,9000	-	5,3166	366692	ceut	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366692	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ceut	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
637	IOC_CF06			IOC_CF06	39,1436	-	8,3081	366693	CF06	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366693	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=CF06	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
638	IOC_chab			IOC_chab	25,2958	-	60,6030	366694	chab	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366694	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=chab	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
639	IOC_char	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_char	43,3450	-	124,3217	366695	char	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366695	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=char	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
640	IOC_char2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_char2	43,3450	-	124,3217	978395	har2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=978395	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=har2		
641	IOC_chenn			IOC_chenn	13,1000	-	80,3000	366696	henn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366696	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=henn	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
642	IOC_cher	France	Shom - France	IOC_cher	49,6500	-	1,6300	366697	cher	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366697	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=cher	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
643	IOC_cher2	France	Shom - France	IOC_cher2	49,6500	-	1,6300	366698	her2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366698	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=her2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	

644	IOC_chia	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_chia	14,6970	-	92,4110	366699	chia	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366699	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chia	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
645	IOC_chij	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_chij	27,0900	-	142,1900	366701	chij	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366701	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chij	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
646	IOC_chit	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_chit	-	44,0247	-	176,3688	chit	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363976	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chit	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
647	IOC_chnr	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_chnr	-	26,3518	-	70,6338	chnr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363977	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chnr	
648	IOC_chnr2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_chnr2	-	26,3518	-	70,6338	chnr2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363978	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hnr2	
649	IOC_chrp	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_chrp	48,8630	-	122,7580	366702	chrp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366702	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chrp	
650	IOC_chrs	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_chrs	-	10,4294	-	105,6693	chrs	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366703	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chrs	
651	IOC_chst	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_chst	-	41,9032	-	171,4338	chst	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=374572	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chst	
652	IOC_chtt			IOC_chtt	22,3333	-	91,8250	366704	chtt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366704	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=chtt	
653	IOC_CI20			IOC_CI20	42,0940	-	11,7896	366707	CI20	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366707	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=CI20	
654	IOC_cila	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_cila	-	7,7500	-	109,0000	cila	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366705	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cila	
655	IOC_cili	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_cili	-	7,7500	-	109,0000	cili	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366706	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cili	
656	IOC_clst	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_clst	20,8645	-	90,4051	366708	clst	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366708	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=clst	
657	IOC_cmet	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cmet	-	52,9600	-	74,0660	cmet	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363979	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cmet	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
658	IOC_cmet3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cmet3	-	52,9600	-	74,0660	met3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363980	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=met3	
659	IOC_cmnj	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cmnj	38,9683	-	74,9600	366709	cmnj	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366709	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cmnj	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
660	IOC_cmnj2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cmnj2	38,9683	-	74,9600	640307	mnj2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=640307	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mnj2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
661	IOC_cocb	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_cocb	-	12,1167	-	96,8919	cocb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366710	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cocb	
662	IOC_coch			IOC_coch	9,9600	-	76,2600	366711	coch	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366711	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=coch	
663	IOC_cocos	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_cocos	5,5561	-	87,0478	363981	occos	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363981	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=occos	
664	IOC_cois	Nicaragua	other - Nicaragua	IOC_cois	12,3272	-	83,0678	365153	cois	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=365153	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cois	
665	IOC_colo	Sri Lanka	other - Sri Lanka	IOC_colo	6,9406	-	79,8504	366712	colo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366712	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=colo	
666	IOC_como			IOC_como	-	11,7035	-	43,2481	como	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=363982	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=como	

667	IOC_conc	France	Shom - France	IOC_conc	47,8737	-	3,9074	366713	conc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366713	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=conc
668	IOC_conc2	France	Shom - France	IOC_conc2	47,8737	-	3,9074	366714	onc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366714	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=onc2
669	IOC_cons2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cons2	-	35,3561	-	72,4580	ons2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363983	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ons2
670	IOC_const	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_const	-	35,3561	-	72,4580	onst	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363984	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=onst
671	IOC_coqu	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_coqu	-	29,9501	-	71,3353	coqu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366715	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=coqu
672	IOC_coqu2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_coqu2	-	29,9501	-	71,3353	oqu2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366716	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oqu2
673	IOC_cor2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_cor2	43,3573	-	8,3894	366721	cor2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366721	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cor2
674	IOC_cord	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cord	60,5580	-	145,7530	366717	cord	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366717	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cord
675	IOC_cord2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cord2	60,5580	-	145,7530	366718	ord2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366718	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ord2
676	IOC_corf			IOC_corf	39,7900	-	19,9100	369739	corf	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369739	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=corf
677	IOC_cori	Nicaragua	other - Nicaragua	IOC_cori	12,4833	-	87,1675	363985	cori	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363985	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cori
678	IOC_corn	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_corn	37,9452	-	22,9365	363986	corn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363986	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=corn
679	IOC_corr	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_corr	-	39,8866	-	73,4275	corr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366719	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=corr
680	IOC_corr2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_corr2	-	39,8866	-	73,4275	orr2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366720	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=orr2
681	IOC_coru			IOC_coru	43,3666	-	8,4000	366722	coru	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366722	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=coru
682	IOC_cove	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_cove	9,4092	-	76,2053	608174	cove	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=608174	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cove
683	IOC_cpit	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_cpit	-	40,8993	-	176,2317	cpit	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363987	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cpit
684	IOC_cpla	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cpla	29,7682	-	93,3429	363988	cpla	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363988	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cpla
685	IOC_cpla2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cpla2	29,7682	-	93,3429	364470	pla2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364470	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pla2
686	IOC_CR08			IOC_CR08	39,0836	-	17,1371	366725	CR08	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366725	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=CR08
687	IOC_crbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_crbc	50,0400	-	125,2500	366681	crbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366681	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=crbc
688	IOC_cres	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cres	41,7450	-	124,1830	366723	cres	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366723	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cres
689	IOC_cres2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cres2	41,7450	-	124,1830	370667	res2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370667	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=res2

690	IOC_crnl	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_crnl	-	37,0286	-	73,1517	363989	crnl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363989	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=crnl
691	IOC_crnl2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_crnl2	-	37,0286	-	73,1517	363990	rn12	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363990	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=crnl2
692	IOC_crom			IOC_crom		52,9300		1,3000	366724	crom	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366724	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=crom
693	IOC_csta			IOC_csta		44,1600		28,6000	366726	csta	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366726	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=csta
694	IOC_csta2	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_csta2		44,1475		28,6720	367489	sta2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367489	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sta2
695	IOC_cstr	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cstr	-	42,4809	-	73,7582	363991	cstr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363991	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cstr
696	IOC_cstr2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_cstr2	-	42,4809	-	73,7582	363992	str2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363992	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=str2
697	IOC_CT03			IOC_CT03		37,4980		15,0938	366684	CT03	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366684	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=CT03
698	IOC_cule	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cule		18,3008	-	65,3028	366727	cule	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366727	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cule
699	IOC_curri	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_curri		18,0167		120,4833	366728	urri	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366728	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=urri
700	IOC_cuvie	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_cuvie	-	24,2206		113,3969	363993	uvie	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363993	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=uvie
701	IOC_cuxh	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_cuxh		53,8678		8,7175	366729	cuxh	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366729	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cuxh
702	IOC_cwfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cwfl		27,9780	-	82,8320	366730	cwfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366730	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cwfl
703	IOC_cwfl2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cwfl2		27,9780	-	82,8320	373797	wfl2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=373797	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wfl2
704	IOC_cwme	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cwme		44,6567	-	67,2100	366731	cwme	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366731	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=cwme
705	IOC_cwme2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_cwme2		44,6567	-	67,2100	367889	wme2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367889	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wme2
706	IOC_dakar			IOC_dakar		14,6760	-	17,4200	366732	akar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366732	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=akar
707	IOC_darw	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_darw	-	12,4719		130,8458	366733	darw	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366733	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=darw
708	IOC_davo	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_davo		7,1537		125,6629	366734	davo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366734	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=davo
709	IOC_deke			IOC_deke		6,9806		158,2001	366735	deke	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366735	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=deke
710	IOC_delf			IOC_delf		53,3266		6,9330	367634	delf	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367634	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=delf
711	IOC_denh			IOC_denh		52,9637		4,7434	367635	denh	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367635	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=denh
712	IOC_dese			IOC_dese	-	47,7536	-	65,9147	366736	dese	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366736	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dese

713	IOC_desh	France	CNRS - Paris Institute of Earth Physics, Marine Geoscience Laboratory - France	IOC_desh	16,3053	-	61,7959	363994	desh	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363994	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=desh
714	IOC_desi	France	CNRS - Paris Institute of Earth Physics, Marine Geoscience Laboratory - France	IOC_desi	16,3029	-	61,0725	363995	desi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363995	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=desi
715	IOC_dial	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_dial	30,2000	-	88,1000	366737	dial	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366737	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dial
716	IOC_dial2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_dial2	30,2000	-	88,1000	366738	ial2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366738	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ial2
717	IOC_diba	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_diba	25,6490	-	56,2690	363996	diba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363996	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=diba
718	IOC_diel	France	Shom - France	IOC_diel	49,5500	-	1,8600	363997	diel	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363997	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=diel
719	IOC_diel2	France	Shom - France	IOC_diel2	49,5500	-	1,8600	363998	iel2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363998	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=iel2
720	IOC_diep	France	Shom - France	IOC_diep	49,9300	-	1,0850	366739	diep	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366739	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=diep
721	IOC_diep2	France	Shom - France	IOC_diep2	49,9300	-	1,0850	366740	iep2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366740	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=iep2
722	IOC_dlpr	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_dlpr	51,2238	-	1,4093	363999	dlpr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363999	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dlpr
723	IOC_dove			IOC_dove	51,1100	-	1,3200	366741	dove	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366741	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dove
724	IOC_dpnc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_dpnc	36,1833	-	75,7466	366742	dpnc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366742	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dpnc
725	IOC_dpnc2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_dpnc2	36,1833	-	75,7466	366743	pnc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366743	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pnc2
726	IOC_dumo			IOC_dumo	-	66,6519	140,0017	366744	dumo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366744	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dumo
727	IOC_dunk	France	Shom - France	IOC_dunk	51,0481	-	2,3667	366745	dunk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366745	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dunk
728	IOC_dunk2	France	Shom - France	IOC_dunk2	51,0481	-	2,3667	366746	unk2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366746	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=unk2
729	IOC_duqm	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_duqm	19,6600	-	57,7200	364000	duqm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364000	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=duqm
730	IOC_dutc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_dutc	53,8833	-	166,5333	366747	dutc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366747	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dutc
731	IOC_dtzo	France	Shom - France	IOC_dtzo	-	12,7833	45,2583	366748	dtzo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366748	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=dtzo
732	IOC_dtzo2	France	Shom - France	IOC_dtzo2	-	12,7830	45,2583	366749	zo2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366749	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=zo2
733	IOC_east	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_east	-	27,1549	-	109,4394	east	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366750	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=east
734	IOC_east2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_east2	-	27,1549	-	109,4394	ast2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366751	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ast2
735	IOC_ebla2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ebla2	30,0500	-	90,3680	364001	bla2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364001	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=bla2

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

736	IOC_eila	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_eila	29,3700	-	91,3900	366752	eila	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366752	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=eila
737	IOC_elak	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_elak	58,1933	-	136,3433	364002	elak	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364002	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=elak
738	IOC_ellb	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ellb	47,6020	-	122,3350	366753	ellb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366753	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ellb
739	IOC_elpo	Panama	other - Panama	IOC_elpo	9,5583	-	78,9492	364003	elpo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364003	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=elpo
740	IOC_epme	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_epme	44,9033	-	66,9850	366754	epme	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366754	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=epme
741	IOC_epme2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_epme2	44,9033	-	66,9850	367935	epme2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367935	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=epme2
742	IOC_erdem			IOC_erdem	36,6111	-	34,3279	366755	rdem	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366755	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=erdem
743	IOC_espe	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_espe	-	33,8709	121,8954	366756	espe	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366756	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=espe
744	IOC_espr			IOC_espr	-	63,3300	56,9166	366757	espr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366757	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=espr
745	IOC_fbfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fbfl	30,6720	-	81,4650	366758	fbfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366758	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fbfl
746	IOC_fbfl2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fbfl2	30,6720	-	81,4650	975787	fbfl2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=975787	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fbfl2
747	IOC_fer1	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_fer1	43,4629	-	8,3258	366760	fer1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366760	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fer1
748	IOC_fer2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_fer2	43,4762	-	8,2485	366761	fer2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366761	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fer2
749	IOC_ferg	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_ferg	-	19,2773	147,0584	366759	ferg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366759	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ferg
750	IOC_feth	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_feth	36,6207	-	29,0922	364004	feth	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364004	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=feth
751	IOC_figu	France	Shom - France	IOC_figu	43,4835	-	6,9338	366762	figu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366762	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=figu
752	IOC_figu2	France	Shom - France	IOC_figu2	43,4835	-	6,9338	366763	igu2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366763	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=igu2
753	IOC_fish			IOC_fish	52,0100	-	4,9800	366764	fish	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366764	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fish
754	IOC_fima	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fima	41,7000	-	71,2000	364005	fima	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364005	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fima
755	IOC_fmfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fmfl	26,6500	-	81,8700	366765	fmfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366765	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fmfl
756	IOC_fmfl2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fmfl2	26,6500	-	81,8700	978540	mf12	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=978540	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=mf12
757	IOC_fong			IOC_fong	-	8,5025	179,1952	366766	fong	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366766	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=fong
758	IOC_form	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_form	38,7347	-	1,4190	366767	form	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366767	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=form

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/>

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/>

759	IOC_fort	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_fort	-	3,7167	-	38,4667	366768	fort	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366768	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fort	
760	IOC_fosm	France	Shom - France	IOC_fosm	43,4049	-	4,8929	366769	fosm	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366769	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fosm	
761	IOC_fpga	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fpga	32,0330	-	80,9020	366770	fpga	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366770	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fpga	
762	IOC_fpea2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fpea2	32,0330	-	80,9020	370760	pea2	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370760	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pea2	
763	IOC_fpnt	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fpnt	37,8070	-	122,4650	366771	fpnt	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366771	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fpnt	
764	IOC_fptx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_fptx	28,9500	-	95,3100	366772	fptx	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366772	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fptx	
765	IOC_fren	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_fren	23,8670	-	166,2830	366773	fren	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366773	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fren	
766	IOC_frih	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_frih	48,5467	-	123,0100	366774	frih	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366774	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=frih	
767	IOC_frtr	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_frtr	18,1500	-	94,2700	364006	frtr	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364006	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=frtr	
768	IOC_tffr	France	Shom - France	IOC_tffr	14,6017	-	61,0633	366775	tffr	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366775	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tffr	
769	IOC_tfr2	France	Shom - France	IOC_tfr2	14,6017	-	61,0633	368597	tfr2	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368597	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tfr2	
770	IOC_fue2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_fue2	28,4925	-	13,8582	366776	fue2	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366776	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fue2	
771	IOC_fuer2			IOC_fuer2	28,4981	-	13,8564	969396	uer2	2019 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=969396	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=uer2	
772	IOC_fuka	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_fuka	40,6500	-	139,9300	366777	fuka	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366777	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=fuka	
773	IOC_futu	France	Shom - France	IOC_futu	-	14,2960	-	178,1602	366778	futu	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366778	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=futu
774	IOC_GA37			IOC_GA37	41,2100	-	13,5897	607867	GA37	2019 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=607867	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=GA37	
775	IOC_gamb	France	Shom - France	IOC_gamb	-	23,1178	-	134,9689	367051	gamb	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367051	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gamb
776	IOC_gand	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_gand	38,9952	-	0,1514	366779	gand	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366779	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gand	
777	IOC_ganm			IOC_ganm	-	0,6867	-	73,1517	366780	ganm	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366780	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ganm
778	IOC_gaor	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_gaor	45,5550	-	123,9117	366781	gaor	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366781	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gaor	
779	IOC_garc	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_garc	-	7,2333	-	72,4333	366782	garc	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366782	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=garc
780	IOC_gbit	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_gbit	-	36,1890	-	175,4889	364007	gbit	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364007	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gbit
781	IOC_GE25			IOC_GE25	44,4101	-	8,9255	366783	GE25	2018 - 2020		https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366783	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=GE25	

782	IOC_geor			IOC_geor	19,2951	-	81,3835	366784		geor	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366784	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=geor
783	IOC_GI20			IOC_GI20	38,7840	-	15,1933	366789		GI20	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366789	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=GI20
784	IOC_gibr2			IOC_gibr2	36,1300	-	5,3500	366785		ibr2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366785	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ibr2
785	IOC_gij2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_gij2	43,5580	-	5,6984	366786		ij2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366786	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gij2
786	IOC_gila	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_gila	29,2633	-	89,9567	366787		gila	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366787	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gila
787	IOC_gila2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_gila2	29,2633	-	89,9567	366788		ila2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366788	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ila2
788	IOC_gist	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_gist	-	38,6754	178,0229	366790		gist	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366790	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gist
789	IOC_gokc			IOC_gokc	40,2314	-	25,8936	366792		gokc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366792	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gokc
790	IOC_goto			IOC_goto	57,6800	-	11,7800	366793		goto	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366793	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=goto
791	IOC_goug	South Africa	other - South Africa	IOC_goug	-	40,3494	-	9,8803	364008	goug	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364008	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=goug
792	IOC_gptx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_gptx	29,3100	-	94,7930	366794		gptx	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366794	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gptx
793	IOC_gptx2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_gptx2	29,3100	-	94,7930	366795		ptx2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366795	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptx2
794	IOC_greg	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_greg	-	52,6482	-	70,2092	364009	greg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364009	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=greg
795	IOC_greg2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_greg2	-	52,6482	-	70,2092	364010	reg2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364010	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=reg2
796	IOC_groo	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_groo	-	13,8600	136,4158	366796		groo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366796	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=groo
797	IOC_guam	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_guam	13,4380	-	144,6520	366797		guam	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366797	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=guam
798	IOC_guam2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_guam2	13,4380	-	144,6520	366798		uam2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366798	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=uam2
799	IOC_gwda			IOC_gwda	25,1122	-	62,3394	366799		gwda	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366799	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=gwda
800	IOC_hade			IOC_hade	32,4705	-	34,8631	366800		hade	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366800	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hade
801	IOC_hain			IOC_hain	16,0004	-	94,3176	365252		hain	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=365252	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hain
802	IOC_hako	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_hako	41,7800	-	140,7200	366801		hako	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366801	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hako
803	IOC_hana	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_hana	43,2800	-	145,5700	366802		hana	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366802	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hana
804	IOC_hani			IOC_hani	6,7667	-	73,1667	366803		hani	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366803	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=hani

805	IOC_harl		IOC_harl	53,1756	5,4110	367636	harl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367636	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=harl
806	IOC_harv	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	34,4667	120,6667	366804	harv	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366804	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=harv
807	IOC_harw		IOC_harw	51,9500	1,2900	366805	harw	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366805	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=harw
808	IOC_hbay	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	51,3821	1,1152	364011	hbay	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364011	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hbay
809	IOC_helg	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	54,1758	7,8914	366806	helg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366806	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=helg
810	IOC_hens	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	54,1833	133,0000	369869	hens	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369869	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hens
811	IOC_herb	France	Shom - France	47,0260	2,2990	364012	herb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364012	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=herb
812	IOC_herb2	France	Shom - France	47,0250	2,2989	364013	erb2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364013	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=erb2
813	IOC_heys		IOC_heys	54,0300	2,9200	366808	heys	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366808	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=heys
814	IOC_hie2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	27,7841	17,9016	366810	hie2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366810	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hie2
815	IOC_hien	France	Shom - France	20,6928	164,9422	366809	hien	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366809	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hien
816	IOC_hill	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	31,8255	115,7386	366811	hill	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366811	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hill
817	IOC_hilo	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	19,7330	155,0580	366812	hilo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366812	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hilo
818	IOC_hink		IOC_hink	51,2100	3,1300	366813	hink	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366813	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hink
819	IOC_hirt		IOC_hirt	57,6000	9,9700	366814	hirt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366814	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hirt
820	IOC_hiva		IOC_hiva	9,8049	139,0345	366815	hiva	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366815	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hiva
821	IOC_hmda	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	34,9000	132,0700	366816	hmda	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366816	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hmda
822	IOC_hoek		IOC_hoek	51,9775	4,1195	367637	hoek	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367637	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hoek
823	IOC_holy		IOC_holy	53,3105	4,6338	366817	holy	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366817	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=holy
824	IOC_holy2		IOC_holy2	53,3100	4,6200	366818	oly2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366818	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oly2
825	IOC_holyt		IOC_holyt	53,3105	4,6338	366819	olyt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366819	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=olyt
826	IOC_honn		IOC_honn	70,9833	25,9833	366820	honn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366820	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=honn
827	IOC_hono	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	21,3070	157,8670	366821	hono	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366821	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=hono

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

828	IOC_horn	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_horn	54,7581	8,2975	364014	horn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364014	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=horn	
829	IOC_huahi	France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD	IOC_huahi	-	16,7216	151,0324	364015	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364015	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=huahi	
830	IOC_huas2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_huas2	-	28,4608	71,2238	364016	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364016	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=huas2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
831	IOC_huas3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_huas3	-	28,4608	71,2238	364017	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364017	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=huas3	
832	IOC_huat	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_huat	15,7501	-	96,1169	366159	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366159	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=huat	
833	IOC_huat2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_huat2	15,7501	-	96,1169	364018	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364018	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=uat2	
834	IOC_huel	Spain	PDÉ - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_huel	37,1320	-	6,8337	366822	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366822	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=huel	
835	IOC_laix	France	Shom - France	IOC_laix	46,0074	-	1,1742	366823	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366823	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=laix	
836	IOC_ibiz	Spain	PDÉ - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_ibiz	38,9112	-	1,4498	366824	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366824	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ibiz	
837	IOC_iclr	United States	other - US	IOC_iclr	18,5338	-	114,7227	364019	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364019	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iclr	
838	IOC_iler	France	Shom - France	IOC_iler	5,2844	-	52,5869	364020	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364020	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iler	
839	IOC_iler2	France	Shom - France	IOC_iler2	5,2844	-	52,5869	364021	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364021	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iler2	
840	IOC_iffa			IOC_iffa	51,2100	-	4,1100	366825	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366825	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iffa	
841	IOC_IM01			IOC_IM01	43,8769	-	8,0188	366827	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366827	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=IM01	
842	IOC_im02	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_im02	43,8783	-	8,0188	366828	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366828	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=im02	
843	IOC_imbi			IOC_imbi	-	28,2308	48,6508	833488	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=833488	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=imbi	
844	IOC_imbt	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_imbt	-	28,2314	48,6505	969158	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=969158	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=imbt	
845	IOC_immi			IOC_immi	53,6300	-	0,1900	366826	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366826	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=immi	
846	IOC_imuj	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_imuj	21,2167	-	86,7167	366829	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366829	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=imuj	
847	IOC_inav	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_inav	10,1806	-	75,7503	364022	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364022	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=inav	
848	IOC_inav2	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_inav2	10,1806	-	75,7503	364023	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364023	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=inav2	
849	IOC_lqui	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_lqui	-	20,2046	70,1478	366830	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366830	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=lqui	
850	IOC_lqui2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_lqui2	-	20,2046	70,1478	366831	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366831	https://www.psms.l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=lqui2	

851	IOC_ishig	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_ishig	24,3300	124,1600	366832	shig	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366832	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=shig			
852	IOC_iske			IOC_iske	36,5942	36,1768	366833	iske	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366833	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iske			
853	IOC_IT45			IOC_IT45	42,1189	15,5016	639531	IT45	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=639531	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=IT45	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc		
854	IOC_jack	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_jack	-	43,9733	168,6161	366834	jack	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366834	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=jack		
855	IOC_jask			IOC_jask	25,6300	57,7700	366835	jask	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366835	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=jask			
856	IOC_jask2			IOC_jask2	25,6300	57,7700	366836	ask2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366836	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ask2			
857	IOC_iers			IOC_iers	49,1800	-	2,1200	366837	iers	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366837	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=iers	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
858	IOC_john	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_john	16,7390	-	169,5233	366838	john	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366838	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=john	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
859	IOC_juan	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_juan	-	33,6360	-	78,8299	366839	juan	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366839	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=juan	
860	IOC_juan2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_juan2	-	33,6360	-	78,8299	366840	uan2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366840	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=uan2	
861	IOC_june	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_june	58,2983	-	134,4117	366841	june	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366841	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=june	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
862	IOC_kahu	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kahu	20,8980	-	156,4720	366842	kahu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366842	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kahu	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
863	IOC_kahu2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kahu2	20,8980	-	156,4720	975851	ahu2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=975851	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ahu2		
864	IOC_kait	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_kait	-	42,4129	173,7028	364024	kait	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364024	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kait		
865	IOC_kala			IOC_kala	37,0215	22,1098	366843	kala	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366843	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kala	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc		
866	IOC_kant			IOC_kant	-	2,8010	-	171,7180	366844	kant	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366844	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kant	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
867	IOC_kapi			IOC_kapi	1,0780	154,8067	366845	kapi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366845	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kapi			
868	IOC_kara			IOC_kara	24,8117	66,9750	366846	kara	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366846	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kara			
869	IOC_kast			IOC_kast	35,5140	23,6370	965670	kast	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=965670	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kast			
870	IOC_kata			IOC_kata	37,6405	21,3192	366847	kata	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366847	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kata			
871	IOC_kaum	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_kaum	20,7800	-	156,9000	364025	kaum	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364025	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kaum		
872	IOC_kawa	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kawa	20,0360	-	155,8320	366848	kawa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366848	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=kawa		
873	IOC_kawa2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kawa2	20,0360	-	155,8320	608327	awa2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=608327	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=awa2		

874	IOC_keba		IOC_keba	24,1300	67,4300	364026	keba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364026	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=keba	
875	IOC_kepo		IOC_kepo	54,2800	36,5000	366849	kepo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366849	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kepo	
876	IOC_kerg2		IOC_kerg2	49,3525	70,0218	366850	erg2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366850	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=erg2	
877	IOC_ketc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ketc	55,3333	131,6250	366851	ketc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366851	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ketc
878	IOC_kgak	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kgak	55,0594	162,3236	364027	kgak	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364027	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kgak
879	IOC_kiel	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_kiel	54,4997	10,2747	364028	kiel	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364028	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kiel
880	IOC_kinl			IOC_kinl	58,4600	5,0500	366852	kinl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366852	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kinl
881	IOC_kodi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kodi	57,7317	152,5120	366853	kodi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366853	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kodi
882	IOC_kodi2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kodi2	57,7317	152,5120	374111	odi2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=374111	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=odi2
883	IOC_koli	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_koli	6,1067	106,8908	367819	koli	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367819	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=koli
884	IOC_koli2			IOC_koli2	6,1067	106,8908	366854	oli2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366854	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=oli2
885	IOC_koro	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_koro	36,8000	21,9600	364029	koro	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364029	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=koro
886	IOC_kors	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_kors	46,6333	142,7667	364030	kors	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364030	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kors
887	IOC_kpva	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kpva	37,1700	75,9900	366855	kpva	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366855	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kpva
888	IOC_kush	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_kush	42,9800	144,3700	366857	kush	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366857	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kush
889	IOC_kusm	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_kusm	33,4800	135,7700	366858	kusm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366858	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kusm
890	IOC_kwaj	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kwaj	8,7367	167,7383	366859	kwaj	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366859	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kwaj
891	IOC_kwai2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kwai2	8,7367	167,7383	963330	wai2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=963330	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=wai2
892	IOC_kwfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_kwfl	24,5530	81,8080	366860	kwfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366860	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=kwfl
893	IOC_LA23			IOC_LA23	35,4998	12,6044	366892	LA23	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366892	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=LA23
894	IOC_LA38			IOC_LA38	44,0966	9,8576	373555	LA38	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=373555	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=LA38
895	IOC_lago	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_lago	28,0878	17,1083	366861	lago	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366861	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lago
896	IOC_lajo	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lajo	32,8670	117,2580	366862	lajo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366862	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lajo

897	IOC_lajo2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lajo2	32,8670	-	117,2580	367537				ajoj2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367537	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ajoj2
898	IOC_lalb	El Salvador	other - El Salvador	IOC_lalb	13,4851	-	89,3190	364031				lalb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364031	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lalb
899	IOC_lali			IOC_lali	-	2,2177	-	80,9064	366863			lali	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366863	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lali
900	IOC_lame	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lame	18,3182	-	64,7242	366864				lame	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366864	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lame
901	IOC_lame2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lame2	18,3182	-	64,7242	374204				ame2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=374204	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ame2
902	IOC_lamu			IOC_lamu	-	2,2667	-	40,9000	366865			lamu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366865	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lamu
903	IOC_lang	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_lang	43,3465	-	8,5301	364032				lang	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364032	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lang
904	IOC_lank			IOC_lank	6,4160	-	99,7667	366866				lank	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366866	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lank
905	IOC_lapa	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_lapa	28,6778	-	17,7680	366868				lapa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366868	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lapa
906	IOC_lapu	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lapu	47,9133	-	124,6367	364033				lapu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364033	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lapu
907	IOC_larp	France	Shom - France	IOC_larp	46,1585	-	1,2207	366869				larp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366869	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=larp
908	IOC_larp2	France	Shom - France	IOC_larp2	46,1585	-	1,2207	366870				arp2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366870	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arp2
909	IOC_laru2			IOC_laru2	-	4,5000	-	55,5000	366871			aru2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366871	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=aru2
910	IOC_lasp	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_lasp	28,1406	-	15,4118	366990				lasp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366990	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lasp
911	IOC_lata			IOC_lata	-	10,7208	-	165,8019	364034			lata	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364034	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lata
912	IOC_laun	El Salvador	other - El Salvador	IOC_laun	13,3093	-	87,8181	366872				laun	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366872	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=laun
913	IOC_laza	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_laza	17,9399	-	102,1781	364035				laza	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364035	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=laza
914	IOC_lcla	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lcla	30,2016	-	93,2806	372073				lcla	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372073	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lcla
915	IOC_lebu	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_lebu	-	37,5941	-	73,6641	366873			lebu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366873	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lebu
916	IOC_lebu2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_lebu2	-	37,5941	-	73,6641	366874			ebu2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366874	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ebu2
917	IOC_leco	France	Shom - France	IOC_leco	48,3600	-	4,7800	366875				leco	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366875	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=leco
918	IOC_leco2	France	Shom - France	IOC_leco2	48,3600	-	4,7800	366876				eco2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366876	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=eco2
919	IOC_lecy	France	Shom - France	IOC_lecy	47,5427	-	2,8952	366877				lecy	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366877	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lecy

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

920	IOC_lede	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lede	38,7186	-	75,1200	366878	lede	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366878	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lede	http://uhslc.soest-hawaii.edu/data/ netcdf/fast/daily/
921	IOC_lega	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_lega	13,1462	123,7581	366879	lega	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366879	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lega	http://uhslc.soest-hawaii.edu/data/ netcdf/fast/daily/	
922	IOC_leha	France	Shom - France	IOC_leha	49,4819	0,1060	366880	leha	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366880	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=leha		
923	IOC_leha2	France	Shom - France	IOC_leha2	49,4819	0,1060	366881	eha2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366881	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=eha2		
924	IOC_leit			IOC_leit	55,9900	-	3,1800	366882	leit	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366882	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=leit	
925	IOC_lemba	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_lemba	-	8,7309	116,0723	364036	emba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364036	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=emba	
926	IOC_lena	Vanuatu	other - Vanuatu	IOC_lena	-	19,5326	169,2660	364037	lena	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364037	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lena	
927	IOC_lero	France	other - France	IOC_lero	14,6769	-	60,9379	364038	lero	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364038	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lero	
928	IOC_lerw2			IOC_lerw2	60,1553	-	1,1452	366883	erw2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366883	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=erw2	
929	IOC_leso	France	Shom - France	IOC_leso	46,4975	-	1,7937	366884	leso	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366884	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=leso	
930	IOC_leso2	France	Shom - France	IOC_leso2	46,4975	-	1,7937	366885	eso2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366885	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=eso2	
931	IOC_leva	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_leva	37,9950	-	76,4653	364039	leva	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364039	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=leva	
932	IOC_levu			IOC_levu	-	17,6049	177,4383	366886	levu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366886	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=levu	
933	IOC_lcos			IOC_lcos	37,0988	-	8,6668	366887	lcos	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366887	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lcos	
934	IOC_L111			IOC_L111	43,5463	10,2993	366889	L111	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366889	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=L111		
935	IOC_lifo	France	Shom - France	IOC_lifo	-	20,9185	167,2787	364040	lifo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364040	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lifo	
936	IOC_lime	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_lime	17,6947	-	64,7538	364041	lime	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364041	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lime	
937	IOC_limon			IOC_limon	9,9886	-	83,0203	366888	imon	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366888	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=imon	
938	IOC_litz			IOC_litz	-	16,1128	167,4440	364042	litz	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364042	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=litz	
939	IOC_live			IOC_live	53,4500	-	3,0200	366890	live	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366890	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=live	
940	IOC_llan			IOC_llan	53,3300	-	3,8300	366891	llan	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366891	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=llan	
941	IOC_lomb			IOC_lomb	-	2,0421	147,3737	366893	lomb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366893	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lomb	
942	IOC_losa	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_losa	33,7190	-	118,2720	366894	losa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366894	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=losa	

943	IOC_losa2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_losa2	33,7190	-	118,2720	370761	osa2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=370761	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=osa2	
944	IOC_lott	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_lott	-	37,5503	178,1590	364043	lott	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364043	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lott	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
945	IOC_lowe			IOC_lowe	52,4700	-	1,7500	366895	lowe	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366895	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lowe	
946	IOC_lbbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_lbbc	54,2000	-	133,1000	366807	lbbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366807	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lbbc	
947	IOC_luba	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_luba	13,8184	-	120,2022	364044	luba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364044	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=luba	
948	IOC_luga	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_luga	-	15,5156	167,1886	364045	luga	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364045	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=luga	
949	IOC_lymg	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_lymg	50,7403	-	1,5071	364046	lymg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364046	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lymg	
950	IOC_made	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_made	14,7124	-	92,4012	366700	made	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366700	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=made	
951	IOC_madry			IOC_madry	-	42,7627	-	65,0307	adry	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366896	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=adry	
952	IOC_maer			IOC_maer	40,7667	-	27,9667	366897	maer	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366897	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=maer	
953	IOC_magi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_magi	17,9701	-	67,0464	366898	magi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366898	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=magi	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
954	IOC_magi2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_magi2	17,9701	-	67,0464	637234	agi2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=637234	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=agi2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
955	IOC_maho	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_maho	39,8930	-	4,2706	366899	maho	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366899	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=maho	
956	IOC_mais	South Africa	other - South Africa	IOC_mais	-	46,8667	37,8667	364047	mais	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364047	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mais	
957	IOC_mais2	South Africa	other - South Africa	IOC_mais2	-	46,8667	37,8667	364048	ais2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364048	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ais2	
958	IOC_maji	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_maji	24,5180	-	56,6060	364049	maji	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364049	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=maji	
959	IOC_maju	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_maju	-	6,1893	105,8411	372979	maju	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=372979	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=maju	
960	IOC_maka	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_maka	21,3200	-	157,6690	370791	maka	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=370791	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=maka	
961	IOC_make	France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD	IOC_make	-	16,6269	-	143,5691	make	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364050	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=make	
962	IOC_mai3	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_mai3	36,7118	-	4,4171	366923	mai3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366923	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mai3	
963	IOC_mala			IOC_mala	7,3282	-	134,4502	366901	mala	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366901	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mala	
964	IOC_male			IOC_male	4,1900	-	73,5267	366902	male	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366902	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=male	
965	IOC_mali	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	IOC_mali	55,3717	-	7,3343	366903	mali	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366903	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mali	

966	IOC_malk	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_malk	43,8700	146,8200	366199	malk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366199	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=malk
967	IOC_malo			IOC_malo	61,9333	5,1167	366904	malo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366904	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=malo
968	IOC_malp	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_malp	4,0024	81,6042	364740	malp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364740	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=malp
969	IOC_malp2	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_malp2	4,0024	81,6042	364708	alp2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364708	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=alp2
970	IOC_mani	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_mani	14,5822	120,9716	366905	mani	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366905	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mani
971	IOC_mare	France	Shom - France	IOC_mare	21,5478	167,8771	366906	mare	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366906	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mare
972	IOC_mari	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_mari	42,4061	8,6911	366907	mari	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366907	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mari
973	IOC_marm			IOC_marm	15,4100	73,8000	366908	marm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366908	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=marm
974	IOC_mars	France	Shom - France	IOC_mars	43,2911	5,3558	366909	mars	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366909	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mars
975	IOC_marsh	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_marsh	7,1061	171,3725	366910	arsh	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366910	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=arsh
976	IOC_masi			IOC_masi	20,6833	58,8667	366911	masi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366911	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=masi
977	IOC_mata	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_mata	17,0009	72,1088	366912	mata	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366912	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mata
978	IOC_maya	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_maya	18,2176	67,1588	368470	maya	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368470	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=maya
979	IOC_maza	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_maza	23,1814	106,4239	366913	maza	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366913	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=maza
980	IOC_MC41			IOC_MC41	42,7426	10,2383	366914	MC41	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366914	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=MC41
981	IOC_ME13			IOC_ME13	38,1963	15,5635	366917	ME13	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366917	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ME13
982	IOC_meji	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_meji	23,0977	70,4507	364051	meji	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364051	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=meji
983	IOC_meji2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_meji2	23,0977	70,4507	364052	ei2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364052	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ei2
984	IOC_meli	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_meli	35,2906	2,9285	366915	meli	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366915	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=meli
985	IOC_mera	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_mera	34,9200	139,8300	366916	mera	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366916	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mera
986	IOC_mhav			IOC_mhav	51,7100	5,0500	366918	mhav	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366918	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mhav
987	IOC_mhpa			IOC_mhpa	39,8100	75,4100	364053	mhpa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364053	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mhpa
988	IOC_midx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_midx	28,2070	177,3560	366919	midx	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366919	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=midx

989	IOC_midx2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_midx2	28,2070	-	177,3560	369920	idx2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369920	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=idx2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
990	IOC_mill			IOC_mill	55,7500	-	4,9100	366920	mill	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366920	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mill	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
991	IOC_mimz	France	Shom - France	IOC_mimz	44,2107	-	1,2951	364054	mimz	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364054	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mimz	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
992	IOC_mimz2	France	Shom - France	IOC_mimz2	44,2107	-	1,2951	364055	imz2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364055	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=imz2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
993	IOC_mini			IOC_mini	8,2800		73,0500	366921	mini	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366921	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mini	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
994	IOC_mins	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_mins	24,2900		153,9800	366922	mins	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366922	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mins	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
995	IOC_mnkt	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_mnkt	-	37,0466	174,5117	364056	mnkt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364056	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mnkt	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
996	IOC_moal	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_moal	30,7083	-	88,0433	364057	moal	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364057	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=moal	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
997	IOC_moku	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_moku	21,4370	-	157,7930	366924	moku	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366924	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=moku	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
998	IOC_momb			IOC_momb	-	4,0670	39,6500	366925	momb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366925	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=momb	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
999	IOC_mona	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_mona	18,0900	-	67,9383	366926	mona	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366926	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mona	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1000	IOC_monc			IOC_monc	43,7287		7,4216	366927	monc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366927	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=monc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1001	IOC_monc2			IOC_monc2	43,7287		7,4216	366928	onc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366928	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=onc2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1002	IOC_mont	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_mont	36,6050	-	121,8867	366929	mont	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366929	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mont	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1003	IOC_mont2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_mont2	36,6050	-	121,8867	373018	ont2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=373018	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ont2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1004	IOC_mony	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_mony	41,0483	-	71,9600	366930	mony	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366930	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mony	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1005	IOC_mony2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_mony2	41,0483	-	71,9600	368522	ony2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368522	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ony2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1006	IOC_motr	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_motr	36,7202	-	3,5236	366931	motr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366931	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=motr	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1007	IOC_moul			IOC_moul	16,4833		97,6166	366932	moul	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366932	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=moul	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1008	IOC_mrig	Dominica	other - Dominica	IOC_mrig	15,5479	-	61,2831	364058	mrig	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364058	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mrig	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1009	IOC_mrms			IOC_mrms	36,5017		28,2306	968157	mrms	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968157	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mrms	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1010	IOC_ms001	Malaysia	other - Malaysia	IOC_ms001	6,2571		99,7344	366867	s001	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366867	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=s001	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1011	IOC_ms002	Malaysia	other - Malaysia	IOC_ms002	5,4510		100,1822	364186	s002	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364186	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=s002	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/

1012	IOC_ms004	Malaysia	other - Malaysia	IOC_ms004	5,9326	102,7667	364091	s004	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364091	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=s004	
1013	IOC_ms005	Malaysia	other - Malaysia	IOC_ms005	6,8779	116,8460	366856	s005	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366856	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=s005	
1014	IOC_ms006	Malaysia	other - Malaysia	IOC_ms006	5,7556	119,0775	364133	s006	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364133	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=s006	
1015	IOC_mtw			IOC_mtw	-	10,2670	40,2000	368194	mtwa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368194	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mtwa
1016	IOC_mumb			IOC_mumb	51,5700	-	3,9800	366933	mumb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366933	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mumb
1017	IOC_murc2			IOC_murc2	37,5964	-	0,9736	969397	urc2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=969397	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=urc2
1018	IOC_mus2	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_mus2	23,6276	58,5653	366934	mus2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366934	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mus2	
1019	IOC_musc	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_musc	23,6333	58,5667	366935	musc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366935	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=musc	
1020	IOC_NA23			IOC_NA23	40,8397	14,2692	961332	NA23	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=961332	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=NA23	
1021	IOC_nafi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_nafi	26,1300	-	81,8070	366936	nafi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366936	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nafi
1022	IOC_naga	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_naga	32,7400	129,8700	366937	naga	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366937	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=naga	
1023	IOC_naha	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_naha	26,2100	127,6700	366938	naha	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366938	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=naha	
1024	IOC_naho	Russian Federation		IOC_naho	42,7800	132,8600	364059	naho	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364059	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=naho	
1025	IOC_nain	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_nain	56,5500	-	61,6800	366939	nain	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366939	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nain
1026	IOC_nain2	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_nain2	56,5333	-	61,6833	369736	ain2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369736	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ain2
1027	IOC_nanc			IOC_nanc	8,0500	93,5500	366940	nanc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366940	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nanc	
1028	IOC_nans	China	FIOSEA - First Institute of Oceanography, State Oceanic Administration - China	IOC_nans	9,5000	112,5000	364060	nans	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364060	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nans	
1029	IOC_napt	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_napt	-	39,4757	176,9201	366941	napt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366941	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=napt
1030	IOC_naur			IOC_naur	-	0,5200	166,9100	366942	naur	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366942	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=naur
1031	IOC_nauu	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_nauu	-	0,5319	166,9092	366943	nauu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366943	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nauu
1032	IOC_nawi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_nawi	21,9570	-	159,3600	366944	nawi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366944	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nawi
1033	IOC_nbpa			IOC_nbpa	40,1400	-	74,1500	364061	nbpa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364061	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nbpa
1034	IOC_ncla	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ncla	30,0266	-	90,1133	364062	ncla	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364062	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ncla

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/rly/d.nc>
<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

1035	IOC_ncpt	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_ncpt	-	34,4100	173,0500	364063	ncpt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364063	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ncpt
1036	IOC_neah	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_neah	48,3680	-	124,6170	366945	neah	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366945	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=neah
1037	IOC_newl			IOC_newl	50,1030	-	5,5428	366946	newl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366946	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=newl
1038	IOC_newl2			IOC_newl2	50,1030	-	5,5428	366947	ewl2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366947	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ewl2
1039	IOC_nhav			IOC_nhav	50,7800	0,0600		366948	nhav	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366948	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nhav
1040	IOC_nice	France	Shom - France	IOC_nice	43,6950	7,2850		366949	nice	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366949	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nice
1041	IOC_nice2	France	Shom - France	IOC_nice2	43,6950	7,2850		366950	ice2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366950	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ice2
1042	IOC_niki	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_niki	60,6866	-	151,3966	366951	niki	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366951	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=niki
1043	IOC_niko	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_niko	52,9417	-	168,8716	364066	niko	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364066	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=niko
1044	IOC_nkfa			IOC_nkfa	-	21,1368	-	175,1807	nkfa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366952	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nkfa
1045	IOC_nnsk	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_nnsk	55,2000	166,0200		369216	nnsk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369216	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nnsk
1046	IOC_noct			IOC_noct	18,1000	-	15,9500	366953	noct	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366953	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=noct
1047	IOC_nome	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_nome	64,5000	-	165,4300	366954	nome	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366954	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nome
1048	IOC_noto	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_noto	37,5000	137,1600		364067	noto	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364067	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=noto
1049	IOC_noua	Mauritania	other - Mauritania	IOC_noua	20,8135	-	17,0362	364068	noua	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364068	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=noua
1050	IOC_npor			IOC_npor	51,5500	-	2,9900	366955	npor	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366955	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=npor
1051	IOC_nshi			IOC_nshi	55,0100	-	1,4400	366956	nshi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366956	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nshi
1052	IOC_nspi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_nspi	40,7670	-	124,2170	366957	nspi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366957	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nspi
1053	IOC_nspi2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_nspi2	40,7670	-	124,2170	370550	spi2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370550	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=spi2
1054	IOC_ntue	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_ntue	-	38,7423	-	73,4310	ntue	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364064	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ntue
1055	IOC_ntue2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_ntue2	-	38,7423	-	73,4310	tue2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364065	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tue2
1056	IOC_nuku			IOC_nuku	-	8,9148	-	140,0847	nuku	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366958	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=nuku
1057	IOC_numbo	France	Shom - France	IOC_numbo	-	22,2466	166,4116	366959	umbo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366959	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=umbo

1058	IOC_nuuk		IOC_nuuk	64,1713	-	51,7198	366791		nuuk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366791	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=nuuk
1059	IOC_ryal		IOC_ryal	78,9333		11,9500	366960		ryal	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366960	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ryal
1060	IOC_ocmd	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_ocmd	38,3280	-	75,0920	364069		ocmd	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364069	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ocmd
1061	IOC_ofun	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan IOC_ofun	39,0200		141,7500	366961		ofun	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366961	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ofun
1062	IOC_oinc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_oinc	35,8000	-	75,5500	364070		oinc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364070	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oinc
1063	IOC_omae	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan IOC_omae	34,6100		138,2200	366962		omae	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366962	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=omae
1064	IOC_OR24		IOC_OR24	42,3559		14,4149	373015		OR24	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=373015	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=OR24
1065	IOC_oran	Aruba	other - Aruba IOC_oran	12,5167	-	70,0333	364071		oran	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364071	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oran
1066	IOC_orma	Pakistan	other - Pakistan IOC_orma	25,2037		64,6764	364072		orma	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364072	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=orma
1067	IOC_oste		IOC_oste	51,2331		2,9206	368388		oste	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368388	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=oste
1068	IOC_OT15		IOC_OT15	40,1464		18,4969	366964		OT15	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366964	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=OT15
1069	IOC_otat	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand IOC_otat	-	45,8143	170,6294	366963		otat	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366963	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=otat
1070	IOC_ouin	France	Shom - France IOC_ouin	-	21,9829	166,6833	366965		ouin	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366965	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ouin
1071	IOC_PA07		IOC_PA07	38,1214		13,3713	374160		PA07	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=374160	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=PA07
1072	IOC_paak	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_paak	56,2467	-	134,6467	364073		paak	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364073	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=paak
1073	IOC_pada	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia IOC_pada	-	0,9500	100,3667	366966		pada	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366966	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pada
1074	IOC_pagb	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_pagb	13,4283		144,7970	366967		pagb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366967	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pagb
1075	IOC_pago	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_pago	-	14,2766	170,6907	366968		pago	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366968	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pago
1076	IOC_pago2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_pago2	-	14,2766	170,6907	366969		ago2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366969	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ago2
1077	IOC_pagx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US IOC_pagx	-	14,2766	170,6907	962763		pagx	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=962763	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pagx
1078	IOC_paib	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada IOC_paib	49,2256	-	124,8137	366970		paib	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366970	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=paib
1079	IOC_palm	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain IOC_palm	39,5602		2,6375	366971		palm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366971	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=palm
1080	IOC_palm1		IOC_palm1	16,7550	-	22,9833	366987		alm1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366987	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=alm1

1081	IOC_pana	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_pana	-	7,7484	108,5013	364074	pana	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364074	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pana	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
1082	IOC_pang	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pang	-	48,1250	123,4400	366972	pang	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366972	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pang	
1083	IOC_pant	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_pant	-	36,8348	11,9366	364075	pant	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364075	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pant	
1084	IOC_pape			IOC_pape	-	17,5331	149,5727	366973	pape	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366973	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pape	
1085	IOC_papo	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_papo	-	25,0090	70,4687	364076	papo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364076	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=papo	
1086	IOC_papo2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_papo2	-	25,0090	70,4687	364077	apo2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364077	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=apo2	
1087	IOC_parh	Antigua and Barbuda	other - Antigua and Barbuda	IOC_parh	-	17,1500	61,7833	371917	parh	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=371917	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=parh	
1088	IOC_pata	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pata	-	20,8032	70,1980	364078	pata	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364078	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pata	
1089	IOC_pata2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pata2	-	20,8032	70,1980	364079	ata2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364079	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ata2	
1090	IOC_pbbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_pbbc	-	48,4000	123,4000	366974	pbbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366974	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pbbc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
1091	IOC_pbfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pbfl	-	30,2130	85,8780	366975	pbfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366975	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pbfl	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
1092	IOC_pbil			IOC_pbil	-	14,0190	83,3830	961113	pbil	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961113	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pbil	
1093	IOC_pblu			IOC_pblu	-	11,9980	83,6920	961114	pblu	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961114	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pblu	
1094	IOC_pcas	Honduras	other - Honduras	IOC_pcas	-	15,9231	85,9508	366976	pcas	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366976	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcas	
1095	IOC_pcfi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pcfi	-	30,1520	85,6670	364080	pcfi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364080	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcfi	
1096	IOC_pcha	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pcha	-	45,4671	72,8200	364081	pcha	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364081	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcha	
1097	IOC_pcha2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pcha2	-	45,4671	72,8200	364082	cha2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364082	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=cha2	
1098	IOC_pchi	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pchi	-	38,0567	122,0383	364083	pchi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364083	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pchi	
1099	IOC_pcoi			IOC_pcoi	-	12,3270	83,0680	961115	pcoi	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961115	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcoi	
1100	IOC_pcor	Honduras	other - Honduras	IOC_pcor	-	15,8433	87,9587	367025	pcor	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367025	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcor	
1101	IOC_pcert			IOC_pcert	-	12,4830	87,1670	961116	pcert	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961116	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pcert	
1102	IOC_pdas			IOC_pdas	-	37,7300	25,6800	366977	pdas	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366977	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pdas	
1103	IOC_PE09			IOC_PE09	-	37,2858	13,5268	366979	PE09	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=366979	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=PE09	

1104			IOC_PE21		37,2857	13,5268	366980	PE21		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366980	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=PE21
1105	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pedn	-	49,1299	74,4090	364084	pedn		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364084	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pedn
1106	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pedn2	-	49,1299	74,4090	364085	edn2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364085	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=edn2
1107			IOC_peir		37,9347	23,6212	366978	peir		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366978	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=peir
1108			IOC_penr	-	9,0010	158,0510	366981	penr		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366981	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=penr
1109			IOC_penu		17,9725	66,7618	979027	penu		2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=979027	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=penu
1110	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_petr		53,0167	158,6500	366982	petr		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366982	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=petr
1111	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pflla		29,1200	90,2000	364086	pflla		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364086	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pflla
1112	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_phbc		50,7167	127,4833	367004	phbc		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367004	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=phbc
1113	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_phpa		39,9333	75,1416	366983	phpa		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366983	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=phpa
1114	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pich2	-	32,1356	71,5293	364087	ich2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364087	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ich2
1115	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pich3	-	32,1356	71,5293	364088	ich3		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364088	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ich3
1116	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pisa	-	19,5969	70,2156	364089	pisa		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364089	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pisa
1117	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pisa2	-	19,5969	70,2156	364090	isa2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364090	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=isa2
1118	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pitx		26,0600	97,2150	366984	pitx		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366984	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pitx
1119	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_pkem	-	34,4738	150,9119	366985	pkem		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366985	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pkem
1120			IOC_PL14		40,0299	15,2753	366989	PL14		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366989	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=PL14
1121			IOC_plat2	-	38,0002	57,5385	366986	lat2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366986	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=lat2
1122	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_plmy		5,8900	162,0900	366988	plmy		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366988	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=plmy
1123			IOC_pluz		28,1300	15,4100	366991	pluz		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366991	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pluz
1124			IOC_plvm		50,3700	4,1900	366992	plvm		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366992	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=plvm
1125	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pmel	-	43,8985	73,7482	364092	pmel		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364092	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pmel
1126	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pmel2	-	43,8985	73,7482	364093	mel2		2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364093	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=mel2

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

1127	IOC_pmon	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pmon	-	41,4847	-	72,9612	366993	pmon	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366993	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pmon	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1128	IOC_pmon2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pmon2	-	41,4847	-	72,9612	366994	mon2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366994	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mon2	
1129	IOC_pmur	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_pmur	-	21,8167	-	114,1910	364094	pmur	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364094	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pmur	
1130	IOC_pnfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pnfl	-	30,4030	-	87,2120	366997	pnfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366997	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pnfl	
1131	IOC_pnfl2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pnfl2	-	30,4030	-	87,2120	366998	pnfl2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366998	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pnfl2	
1132	IOC_pnfo			IOC_pnfo	-	10,1833	-	61,4200	366999	pnfo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366999	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pnfo	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1133	IOC_pntn			IOC_pntn	-	4,7833	-	11,8333	369017	pntn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369017	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pntn	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1134	IOC_PO40			IOC_PO40	-	40,8952	-	12,9656	400208	PO40	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=400208	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=PO40	
1135	IOC_porf	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_porf	-	42,7370	-	124,4970	367000	porf	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367000	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=porf	
1136	IOC_porl	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_porl	-	38,3434	-	141,6132	367001	porl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367001	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=porl	
1137	IOC_porp			IOC_porp	-	54,8400	-	5,1200	367002	porp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367002	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=porp	
1138	IOC_port	France	Shom - France ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_port	-	45,5685	-	1,0616	367003	port	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367003	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=port	
1139	IOC_posi	Russian Federation		IOC_posi	-	42,6500	-	130,8000	367005	posi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367005	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=posi	
1140	IOC_pots			IOC_pots	-	13,0104	-	87,5040	961083	pots	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=961083	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pots	
1141	IOC_ppcp	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_ppcp	-	36,6691	-	15,1228	364095	ppcp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364095	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ppcp	
1142	IOC_prai			IOC_prai	-	14,9123	-	23,5021	367006	prai	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367006	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=prai	
1143	IOC_prat	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_prat	-	62,4793	-	59,6629	367007	prat	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367007	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=prat	
1144	IOC_prat3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_prat3	-	62,4793	-	59,6629	367008	rat3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367008	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=rat3	
1145	IOC_prba			IOC_prba	-	15,6946	-	88,6220	367009	prba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367009	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=prba	
1146	IOC_prec	France	other - France ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_prec	-	14,8076	-	61,2266	364096	prec	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364096	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=prec	
1147	IOC_preo	Russian Federation		IOC_preo	-	42,9092	-	133,9225	367010	preo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367010	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=preo	
1148	IOC_pric	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_pric	-	12,0054	-	61,7648	364097	pric	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364097	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtain/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=pric	

1149	IOC_prig	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_prig	8,2833	111,7333	367011	prig	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367011	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prig	
1150	IOC_prin	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_prin	54,3200	130,3200	367012	prin	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367012	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prin	
1151	IOC_prin2	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_prin2	54,3167	130,3167	369737	rin2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=369737	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rin2	
1152	IOC_prog	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_prog	21,3033	89,6667	367013	prog	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367013	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prog	
1153	IOC_prog2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_prog2	21,3033	89,6667	367014	rog2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367014	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rog2	
1154	IOC_prsc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_prsc	33,6550	78,9180	367015	prsc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367015	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prsc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1155	IOC_prud	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_prud	70,3880	148,5100	367016	prud	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367016	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prud	
1156	IOC_prud2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_prud2	70,3880	148,5100	367017	rud2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367017	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rud2	
1157	IOC_prus			IOC_prus	55,2100	6,6600	367018	prus	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367018	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=prus	
1158	IOC_psan			IOC_psan	12,2010	86,7650	961084	psan	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961084	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=psan	
1159	IOC_psdn	Nicaragua	other - Nicaragua	IOC_psdn	12,2011	86,7644	364098	psdn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364098	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=psdn	
1160	IOC_psjj			IOC_psjj	11,2510	85,8750	961134	psjj	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=961134	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=psjj	
1161	IOC_psla	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_psla	28,9317	89,4067	364099	psla	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364099	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=psla	
1162	IOC_pslu	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pslu	35,1680	120,7530	367019	pslu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367019	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=pslu	
1163	IOC_pslu2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_pslu2	35,1680	120,7530	989745	slu2	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=989745	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=slu2	
1164	IOC_PT17			IOC_PT17	40,8422	8,4039	367039	PT17	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367039	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=PT17	
1165	IOC_ptan	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_ptan	15,6667	96,4917	367020	ptan	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367020	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptan	
1166	IOC_ptan2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_ptan2	15,6667	96,4917	367021	tan2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367021	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tan2	
1167	IOC_ptar	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_ptar	53,1237	70,8620	367022	ptar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367022	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptar	
1168	IOC_ptar2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_ptar2	53,1237	70,8620	367023	tar2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367023	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tar2	
1169	IOC_ptbl			IOC_ptbl	11,6800	92,7600	367024	ptbl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367024	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptbl	
1170	IOC_ptca	Dominican Republic	other - Dominican Republic	IOC_ptca	18,5046	68,3755	364100	ptca	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364100	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptca	
1171	IOC_ptfe	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptfe	43,3592	6,7175	367026	ptfe	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367026	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ptfe	

1172	IOC_ptfe2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptfe2	43,3592	6,7175	367027	tfe2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367027	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptfe2	
1173	IOC_ptis	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_ptis	50,5942	- 4,8344	364101	ptis	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364101	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptis	
1174	IOC_ptln	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptln	43,0092	3,0372	364102	ptln	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364102	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptln	
1175	IOC_ptlu	Mauritius	other - Mauritius	IOC_ptlu	- 20,1572	57,5043	367028	ptlu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367028	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptlu	
1176	IOC_ptma			IOC_ptma	35,9211	14,4942	366496	ptma	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366496	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptma	
1177	IOC_ptmd2	Dominica	other - Dominica	IOC_ptmd2	15,5768	- 61,4582	364103	tmd2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364103	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tmd2	
1178	IOC_ptme	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ptme	43,6566	- 70,2466	367029	ptme	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367029	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptme	
1179	IOC_ptmt			IOC_ptmt	50,8000	- 1,1100	367030	ptmt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367030	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptmt	
1180	IOC_ptos	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_ptos	- 0,0614	- 51,1679	367032	ptos	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367032	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptos	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1181	IOC_ptow	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ptow	48,1010	- 122,7580	367033	ptow	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367033	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptow	
1182	IOC_ptpl	Dominican Republic	other - Dominican Republic	IOC_ptpl	19,7988	- 70,7020	367034	ptpl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367034	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptpl	
1183	IOC_ptpr	Haiti	other - Haiti	IOC_ptpr	18,5345	- 72,3800	639068	ptpr	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=639068	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptpr	
1184	IOC_ptpt	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptpt	16,2244	- 61,5315	366995	ptpt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366995	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptpt	
1185	IOC_ptpt2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptpt2	16,2244	- 61,5315	366996	ptpt2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366996	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptpt2	
1186	IOC_ptre	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_ptre	37,9970	- 122,9750	367035	ptre	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367035	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptre	
1187	IOC_ptro			IOC_ptro	17,9346	- 76,8456	367036	ptro	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367036	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptro	
1188	IOC_ptsc			IOC_ptsc	13,2630	- 59,6449	367037	ptsc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367037	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptsc	
1189	IOC_ptsp			IOC_ptsp	10,6500	- 61,5167	367038	ptsp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367038	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptsp	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1190	IOC_ptve	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptve	42,5201	3,1073	367040	ptve	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367040	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ptve	
1191	IOC_ptve2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ptve2	42,5201	3,1073	367041	tve2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367041	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tve2	
1192	IOC_puert	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_puert	20,6585	- 105,2437	367042	uert	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367042	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=uert	
1193	IOC_pumo	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_pumo	20,8681	- 86,8668	364104	pumo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364104	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=pumo	
1194	IOC_pumo2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_pumo2	20,8681	- 86,8668	364105	umo2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364105	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=umo2	

1195	IOC_puyt	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_puyt	-	46,0848	166,5894	364106	puyt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364106	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=puyt	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1196	IOC_pwil	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pwil	-	54,9332	-	67,6106	pwil	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367043	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=pwil	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1197	IOC_pwil2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_pwil2	-	54,9332	-	67,6106	wil2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367044	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=wil2		
1198	IOC_qaao			IOC_qaao	-	60,7176	-	46,0350	qaao	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367575	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=qaao		
1199	IOC_qcbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_qcbc	-	53,2500	-	132,0667	qcbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367046	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=qcbc		
1200	IOC_qing	China	FIOQA - First Institute of Oceanography, State Oceanic Administration - China	IOC_qing	-	19,5700	-	110,8200	qing	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364107	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=qing		
1201	IOC_qtro	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_qtro	-	32,7755	-	71,5254	qtro	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364108	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=qtro		
1202	IOC_qtro2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_qtro2	-	32,7755	-	71,5254	tro2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364109	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=tro2		
1203	IOC_quar			IOC_quar	-	22,2911	-	114,2133	quar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367045	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=quar		
1204	IOC_quel	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_quel	-	39,3976	-	73,2151	quel	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364110	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=quel		
1205	IOC_quel2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_quel2	-	39,3976	-	73,2151	uel2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364111	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=uel2		
1206	IOC_quepo			IOC_quepo	-	9,4255	-	84,1702	uepo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367047	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=uepo		
1207	IOC_quin			IOC_quin	-	13,7751	-	109,2543	quin	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367048	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=quin		
1208	IOC_quir	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_quir	-	36,6361	-	73,0573	quir	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364112	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=quir	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1209	IOC_quir2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_quir2	-	36,6361	-	73,0573	uir2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364113	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=uir2		
1210	IOC_qura	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_qura	-	23,2600	-	58,9250	qura	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364114	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=qura		
1211	IOC_RA10			IOC_RA10	-	44,4921	-	12,2829	RA10	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372861	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=RA10		
1212	IOC_raba			IOC_raba	-	4,2000	-	152,1750	raba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367049	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=raba		
1213	IOC_rangi	France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD	IOC_rangi	-	14,9458	-	147,7060	angi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367050	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=angi		
1214	IOC_raro	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_raro	-	21,2000	-	159,7830	raro	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367198	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=raro	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1215	IOC_rbct	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_rbct	-	29,2800	-	177,8944	rbct	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364115	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=rbct		
1216	IOC_RC09			IOC_RC09	-	38,1217	-	15,6489	RC09	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367199	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=RC09		
1217	IOC_redg	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_redg	-	67,0650	-	164,0650	redg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364116	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=redg		

1218	IOC_redw	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_redw	37,5067	-	122,2100	364117	redw	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364117	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=redw	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1219	IOC_reun	France	Shom - France	IOC_reun	-	20,9200	55,2800	367200	reun	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367200	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=reun		
1220	IOC_reun2	France	Shom - France	IOC_reun2	-	20,9200	55,2800	367201	eun2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367201	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=reun2		
1221	IOC_reyk			IOC_reyk	64,1500	-	21,9333	367202	reyk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367202	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=reyk		
1222	IOC_rrft	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_rrft	-	29,2511	-	177,9038	rrft	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364118	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rrft		
1223	IOC_riki			IOC_riki	-	23,1222	-	134,9666	riki	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367052	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=riki		
1224	IOC_rodr	Mauritius	other - Mauritius	IOC_rodr	-	19,6802	63,4212	367053	rodr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367053	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rodr		
1225	IOC_rorv			IOC_rorv	64,8667	-	11,2500	367054	rorv	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367054	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rrov		
1226	IOC_ross	France	Shom - France	IOC_ross	48,7160	-	3,9660	367055	ross	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367055	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ross		
1227	IOC_ross2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ross2	48,7160	-	3,9660	367056	osc2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367056	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=osc2		
1228	IOC_rose	United States	University of Hawaii	IOC_rose	15,3139	-	61,3892	367504	rose	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367504	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rose		
1229	IOC_ross	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_ross	-	23,1610	150,7902	367057	ross	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367057	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ross		
1230	IOC_rothe			IOC_rothe	-	67,5667	-	68,1333	othe	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367058	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=othe	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1231	IOC_rous	France	Shom - France	IOC_rous	42,6356	-	8,9381	364119	rous	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364119	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rous		
1232	IOC_rous2	France	Shom - France	IOC_rous2	42,6356	-	8,9381	364120	ous2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364120	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ous2		
1233	IOC_rptx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_rptx	28,0216	-	97,0466	367059	rptx	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367059	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rptx		
1234	IOC_rtas	Honduras	other - Honduras ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring -	IOC_rtas	16,3455	-	86,5404	364121	rtas	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364121	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rtas		
1235	IOC_rudn	Russian Federation	Russia	IOC_rudn	44,3500	-	135,8000	367060	rudn	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367060	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=rudn		
1236	IOC_SA16			IOC_SA16	40,6766	-	14,7508	367068	SA16	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367068	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=SA16		
1237	IOC_saba	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_saba	5,8333	-	95,3333	367061	saba	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367061	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=saba		
1238	IOC_sado	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_sado	38,3200	-	138,5200	364122	sado	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364122	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=sado		
1239	IOC_sagr	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_sagr	37,0104	-	8,9282	364123	sagr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364123	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=sagr		
1240	IOC_sagu	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_sagu	39,6339	-	0,2062	367062	sagu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367062	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=sagu		

1241	IOC_said	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_said	35,1119	-	2,2929	364124	said	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364124	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=said
1242	IOC_saig	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_saig	36,2000	133,3300	367063	saig	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367063	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=saig	
1243	IOC_sain	France	Shom - France	IOC_sain	47,2600	-	2,2000	367064	sain	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367064	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sain
1244	IOC_saip			IOC_saip	15,2266	145,7416	367065	saip	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367065	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=saip	
1245	IOC_sala	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_sala	16,9350	54,0067	791862	sala	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=791862	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sala	
1246	IOC_sali	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_sali	16,1684	-	95,1968	367066	sali	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367066	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sali
1247	IOC_sali2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_sali2	16,1684	-	95,1968	367067	ali2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367067	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ali2
1248	IOC_salv	Brazil	other - Brasil	IOC_salv	-	12,9673	-	38,5167	367069	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367069	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=salv
1249	IOC_sama	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_sama	11,2352	-	74,2216	364125	sama	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364125	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sama
1250	IOC_sams	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_sams	41,2949	36,3375	968171	sams	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968171	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sams	
1251	IOC_san2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_san2	43,4613	-	3,7908	367108	san2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367108	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=san2
1252	IOC_sana	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_sana	12,5695	-	81,7015	367070	sana	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367070	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sana
1253	IOC_sanb	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sanb	34,4080	-	119,6850	367071	sanb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367071	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sanb
1254	IOC_sand	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sand	32,7130	-	117,1730	367072	sand	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367072	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sand
1255	IOC_sanf	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sanf	-	26,2922	-	80,1085	367073	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367073	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sanf
1256	IOC_sanf3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sanf3	-	26,2922	-	80,1085	367074	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367074	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=anf3
1257	IOC_sanj	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sanj	18,4617	-	66,1167	367075	sanj	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367075	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sanj
1258	IOC_sani2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sani2	18,4617	-	66,1167	367863	ani2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367863	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ani2
1259	IOC_sanm	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sanm	34,0080	-	118,5000	367076	sanm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367076	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sanm
1260	IOC_sano	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sano	-	33,5816	-	71,6182	364126	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364126	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sano
1261	IOC_sano2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sano2	-	33,5816	-	71,6182	364127	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364127	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ano2
1262	IOC_sanp	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sanp	-	47,7038	-	74,8661	364142	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364142	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sanp
1263	IOC_sant			IOC_sant	-	0,7520	-	90,3070	367077	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367077	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sant

1264	IOC_sapz	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_sapz	8,6603	-	77,3653	364128	sapz	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364128	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sapz	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1265	IOC_sapz2	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_sapz2	8,6603	-	77,3653	364129	apz2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364129	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=apz2	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
1266	IOC_sass	Germany	FWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_sass	54,5108	-	13,6431	367078	sass	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367078	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sass	
1267	IOC_saum	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_saum	-	7,9827	131,2906	364130	saum	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364130	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=saum	
1268	IOC_S836			IOC_S836	42,9551	-	13,8898	367079	S836	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367079	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=S836	
1269	IOC_sbea	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sbea	44,6250	-	124,0430	367080	sbea	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367080	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sbea	
1270	IOC_sbea2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sbea2	44,6250	-	124,0430	369772	bea2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369772	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=bea2	
1271	IOC_SC43			IOC_SC43	37,5045	-	13,0765	367082	SC43	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367082	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=SC43	
1272	IOC_scar			IOC_scar	11,1667	-	60,7333	367081	scar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367081	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=scar	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
1273	IOC_scoa	France	Shom - France	IOC_scoa	43,3952	-	1,6816	367083	scoa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367083	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=scoa	
1274	IOC_scoa2	France	Shom - France	IOC_scoa2	43,3952	-	1,6816	367084	coa2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367084	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=coa2	
1275	IOC_scor			IOC_scor	70,4838	-	21,9620	367085	scor	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367085	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=scor	
1276	IOC_sdrp	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_sdrp	50,6511	-	1,1532	364131	sdrp	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364131	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sdrp	
1277	IOC_sdp1	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sdp1	55,3367	-	160,5017	367086	sdp1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367086	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sdp1	
1278	IOC_sdp12	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sdp12	55,3367	-	160,5017	637172	dpt2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=637172	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=dpt2	
1279	IOC_sebe	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_sebe	-	5,9360	105,5121	372980	sebe	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372980	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sebe	
1280	IOC_seld	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_seld	59,4370	-	151,7170	367087	seld	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367087	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=seld	
1281	IOC_sema	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_sema	-	6,9479	110,4201	367088	sema	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367088	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sema	
1282	IOC_sete	France	Shom - France	IOC_sete	43,3976	-	3,6991	367089	sete	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367089	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sete	
1283	IOC_sete2	France	Shom - France	IOC_sete2	43,3976	-	3,6991	367090	ete2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367090	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=ete2	
1284	IOC_setp1			IOC_setp1	26,6833	-	78,9833	367117	etp1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367117	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=etp1	
1285	IOC_setu	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy	IOC_setu	38,4900	-	8,9300	367714	setu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367714	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=setu	
1286	IOC_sev2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_sev2	37,3185	-	6,0077	364132	sev2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364132	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/tation.php?code=sev2	

1287	IOC_sewa	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sewa	60,1190	-	149,4270	367091	sewa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367091	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sewa
1288	IOC_shee			IOC_shee	51,4500	-	0,7400	367092	shee	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367092	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=shee
1289	IOC_shek			IOC_shek	22,2203	-	113,8944	372472	shek	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372472	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=shek
1290	IOC_shen	China	FIOSEA - First Institute of Oceanography, State Oceanic Administration - China	IOC_shen	22,4700	-	113,8800	364134	shen	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364134	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=shen
1291	IOC_shnj	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_shnj	40,4700	-	74,0100	367093	shnj	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367093	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=shnj
1292	IOC_sian	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_sian	19,3127	-	87,4463	364135	sian	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364135	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sian
1293	IOC_sibo	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_sibo	1,7333	-	98,8000	367094	sibo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367094	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sibo
1294	IOC_siga	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_siga	31,1300	-	81,4000	364136	siga	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364136	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=siga
1295	IOC_simd	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_simd	38,3166	-	76,4516	367095	simd	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367095	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=simd
1296	IOC_sino			IOC_sino	42,0167	-	35,1500	367096	sino	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367096	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sino
1297	IOC_sisa	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_sisa	21,1617	-	90,0483	364137	sisa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364137	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sisa
1298	IOC_sitk	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sitk	57,0517	-	135,3417	367097	sitk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367097	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sitk
1299	IOC_sitk2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sitk2	57,0517	-	135,3417	929849	itk2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=929849	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=itk2
1300	IOC_sitt			IOC_sitt	20,1500	-	92,9000	367098	sitt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367098	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sitt
1301	IOC_skag	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_skag	59,4500	-	135,3267	367099	skag	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367099	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=skag
1302	IOC_smag	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_smag	18,2968	-	93,8545	364138	smag	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364138	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=smag
1303	IOC_smar	France	Shom - France	IOC_smar	-	20,8928	55,5369	364139	smar	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364139	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=smar
1304	IOC_smar2	France	Shom - France	IOC_smar2	-	20,8928	55,5369	364140	mar2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364140	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=mar2
1305	IOC_smog			IOC_smog	58,3500	-	11,2200	367100	smog	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367100	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=smog
1306	IOC_sole	France	Shom - France	IOC_sole	41,8358	-	9,3738	367101	sole	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367101	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sole
1307	IOC_ole2	France	Shom - France	IOC_ole2	41,8358	-	9,3738	367102	ole2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367102	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ole2
1308	IOC_solo	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_solo	-	9,4289	159,9555	367103	solo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367103	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=solo
1309	IOC_sosu	Russian Federation	Russia	IOC_sosu	46,5300	-	138,3300	364141	sosu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364141	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sosu

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/>

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

1310	IOC	sove	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_sove	48,9700	140,2900	367104	sove	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367104	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sove
1311	IOC	sped	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_sped	47,1167	74,8833	364143	sped	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364143	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sped
1312	IOC	spfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_spfl	27,7600	82,6270	367105	spfl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367105	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=spfl
1313	IOC	spmi	France	Shom - France	IOC_spmi	46,4713	56,1005	364144	spmi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364144	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=spmi
1314	IOC	sprg	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_sprg	42,5459	147,9327	367106	sprg	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367106	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sprg
1315	IOC	sptx	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_sptx	29,7300	93,8700	367107	sptx	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367107	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sptx
1316	IOC	sscr	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_sscr	51,5701	2,7000	364145	sscr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364145	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sscr
1317	IOC	stan			IOC_stan	51,7500	57,9333	373905	stan	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=373905	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stan
1318	IOC	stcr	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_stcr	17,7467	64,6983	364146	stcr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364146	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stcr
1319	IOC	stcr2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_stcr2	17,7467	64,6983	364147	stcr2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364147	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stcr2
1320	IOC	sthl			IOC_sthl	15,9167	5,7167	367109	sthl	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367109	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sthl
1321	IOC	sthm			IOC_sthm	59,3300	18,0700	367110	sthm	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367110	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=sthm
1322	IOC	stjo	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_stjo	47,5700	52,7200	367111	stjo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367111	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stjo
1323	IOC	stjo2	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_stjo2	47,5667	52,7000	369738	tjo2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369738	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tjo2
1324	IOC	stlo	Senegal	other - Senegal	IOC_stlo	15,9913	16,5078	364148	stlo	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364148	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stlo
1325	IOC	stlo2	Senegal	other - Senegal	IOC_stlo2	15,9913	16,5078	364149	tlo2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364149	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tlo2
1326	IOC	stlu	Saint Lucia	other - Saint Lucia	IOC_stlu	14,0164	60,9974	364150	stlu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364150	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stlu
1327	IOC	stma	France	Shom - France	IOC_stma	48,6416	2,0280	367112	stma	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367112	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stma
1328	IOC	stma2	France	Shom - France	IOC_stma2	48,6416	2,0280	367113	tma2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367113	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tma2
1329	IOC	stmr			IOC_stmr	49,9179	6,3172	367114	stmr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367114	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stmr
1330	IOC	stmt			IOC_stmt	18,0833	63,0854	364151	stmt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364151	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stmt
1331	IOC	stor			IOC_stor	58,2100	6,3900	367115	stor	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367115	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=stor
1332	IOC	stor2			IOC_stor2	58,2100	6,3900	367116	tor2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367116	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tor2

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

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1333	IOC_subi	Philippines	other - Philippines	IOC_subi	14,8167	120,2833	367118	subi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367118	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=subi
1334	IOC_sumt			IOC_sumt	-	43,5696	172,7732	968280	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968280	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sumt
1335	IOC_sura	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_sura	-	7,2000	112,7406	367119	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367119	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=sura
1336	IOC_suro	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_suro	-	22,5700	59,5200	364152	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364152	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=suro
1337	IOC_swpr	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_swpr	50,6093	-	1,9492	364153	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364153	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=swpr
1338	IOC_syow			IOC_syow	-	69,0078	39,5703	367120	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367120	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=syow
1339	IOC_svro			IOC_svro	37,4380	24,9411	367121	svro	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367121	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=svro
1340	IOC_TA18			IOC_TA18	40,4756	17,2238	608052	TA18	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=608052	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=TA18
1341	IOC_tala			IOC_tala	-	4,5778	-	81,2799	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367122	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tala
1342	IOC_talc	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_talc	-	36,7008	-	73,1063	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367123	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=talc
1343	IOC_talc2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_talc2	-	36,7008	-	73,1063	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367124	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=alc2
1344	IOC_talt2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_talt2	-	25,4081	-	70,4917	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364154	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=alt2
1345	IOC_tara			IOC_tara	1,3625	172,9300	367125	tara	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367125	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tara
1346	IOC_tare			IOC_tare	-	6,6928	156,4086	364155	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364155	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tare
1347	IOC_tari	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_tari	36,0065	-	5,6035	367126	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367126	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tari
1348	IOC_tarr	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_tarr	41,0790	1,2133	367127	tarr	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367127	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tarr
1349	IOC_tasu			IOC_tasu	36,2815	33,8362	968172	tasu	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=968172	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tasu
1350	IOC_taut	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_taut	-	37,6411	176,1812	367128	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367128	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=taut
1351	IOC_tdcu			IOC_tdcu	-	37,0500	-	12,3000	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367129	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tdcu
1352	IOC_telc	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_telc	21,3400	-	89,3083	367130	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367130	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=telc
1353	IOC_tema			IOC_tema	5,6353	0,0118	790580	tema	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=790580	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tema
1354	IOC_tene	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_tene	28,4772	-	16,2411	367131	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367131	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=tene
1355	IOC_ters			IOC_ters	53,4278	5,3328	367639	ters	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367639	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ters

1356	IOC_tfbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_tfbc	49,1500	-	125,9100	367136	tfbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367136	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tfbc	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/hourly/d.nc
1357	IOC_thes			IOC_thes	40,6300	-	22,9100	369740	thes	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=369740	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=thes	
1358	IOC_thev	Australia	NTC - National Tidal Centre - Australia	IOC_thev	-	32,1489	133,6413	367132	thev	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367132	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=thev	
1359	IOC_thio	France	Shom - France	IOC_thio	-	21,6138	166,2415	367133	thio	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367133	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=thio	
1360	IOC_thul			IOC_thul	76,5434	-	68,8626	367134	thul	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367134	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=thul	
1361	IOC_tjls	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_tjls	-	6,4829	105,6634	364156	tjls	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364156	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tjls	
1362	IOC_tkdi			IOC_tkdi	4,8821	-	1,7450	790614	tkdi	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=790614	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tkdi	
1363	IOC_tm031			IOC_tm031	28,0469	-	16,7181	969394	tm031	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=969394	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tm031	
1364	IOC_toama	Madagascar	IRD/DCM - Institut de recherche pour le développement - Madagascar	IOC_toama	-	18,1536	49,4281	364157	oama	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364157	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=oama	
1365	IOC_tobe			IOC_tobe	56,6200	-	6,0600	367135	tobe	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367135	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tobe	
1366	IOC_toco2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_toco2	-	22,0937	70,2115	364158	oco2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364158	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=oco2	
1367	IOC_toco3	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_toco3	-	22,0937	70,2115	364159	oco3	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364159	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=oco3	
1368	IOC_tort			IOC_tort	18,4248	-	64,6081	365467	tort	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=365467	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tort	
1369	IOC_tosa	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_tosa	32,7800	-	132,9600	367137	tosa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367137	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tosa	
1370	IOC_toul	France	Shom - France	IOC_toul	43,1172	-	5,9131	367138	toul	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367138	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=toul	
1371	IOC_toul2	France	Shom - France	IOC_toul2	43,1172	-	5,9131	367139	oul2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367139	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=oul2	
1372	IOC_toya	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_toya	36,7600	-	137,2200	367140	toya	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367140	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=toya	
1373	IOC_tpf1	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_tpf1	28,4200	-	80,5900	367141	tpf1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367141	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tpf1	
1374	IOC_TR22			IOC_TR22	45,6544	-	13,7561	367143	TR22	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367143	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=TR22	
1375	IOC_trab			IOC_trab	41,0019	-	39,7445	968173	trab	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=968173	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=trab	
1376	IOC_tret			IOC_tret	58,0000	-	7,5667	367142	tret	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=367142	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=tret	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/edu/data/netcdf/hourly/d.nc
1377	IOC_trin	Sri Lanka	other - Sri Lanka	IOC_trin	8,5637	-	81,1996	364160	trin	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=364160	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=trin	
1378	IOC_tubua	France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD	IOC_tubua	-	23,3418	149,4755	373285	ubua	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as/px?id=373285	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaini ng/stations/ php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/s tation.php?code=ubua	

1379	IOC_tuca		IOC_tuca	21,4336	-	71,1497	370833	tuca	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370833	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tuca	
1380	IOC_tudy	France	Shom - France	IOC_tudy	47,6439	-	3,4471	367144	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367144	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tudy	
1381	IOC_tumc	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_tumc	1,8200	-	78,7287	367145	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367145	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tumc	
1382	IOC_tumc2	Colombia	other - Colombia	IOC_tumc2	1,8200	-	78,7287	367146	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367146	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=umc2	
1383	IOC_tuxp	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_tuxp	20,9700	-	97,4000	367147	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367147	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=tuxp	
1384	IOC_ulla			IOC_ulla	57,9000	-	5,1600	367148	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367148	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ulla	
1385	IOC_upol			IOC_upol	-	13,8268	-	171,7613	367149	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367149	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=upol
1386	IOC_ushu			IOC_ushu	-	54,8170	-	68,2170	367150	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367150	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ushu
1387	IOC_ustk			IOC_ustk	56,0000	163,0000	364161	ustk	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364161	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ustk	
1388	IOC_vair	France	Universite de Polynesie Francaise / Géosciences du Pacifique Sud GEPASUD	IOC_vair	-	17,8059	-	149,2953	367151	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367151	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vair
1389	IOC_vald	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_vald	61,1250	-	146,3620	367152	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367152	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vald	
1390	IOC_vale	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_vale	39,4420	-	0,3113	367153	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367153	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vale	
1391	IOC_valp	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_valp	-	33,0273	-	71,6259	367154	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367154	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=valp
1392	IOC_valp2	Chile	HOS - Hydrographic and Oceanographic Service - Chile	IOC_valp2	-	33,0273	-	71,6259	367155	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367155	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=alp2
1393	IOC_vanu			IOC_vanu	-	17,7553	168,3077	367157	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367157	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vanu	
1394	IOC_vard			IOC_vard	70,3333	31,1000	367158	vard	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367158	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vard	
1395	IOC_vati			IOC_vati	-	17,3978	177,7612	364162	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364162	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vati	
1396	IOC_VE19			IOC_VE19	45,4182	12,4265	367159	VE19	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367159	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=VE19	
1397	IOC_ver1			IOC_ver1	-	65,2500	-	64,2700	367163	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367163	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=ver1
1398	IOC_vera	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_vera	19,1921	-	96,1236	367160	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367160	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vera	
1399	IOC_vera2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico	IOC_vera2	19,1921	-	96,1236	367161	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367161	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=era2	
1400	IOC_verav			IOC_verav	20,9000	70,3600	367162	erav	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367162	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=erav	
1401	IOC_vern			IOC_vern	-	65,2500	-	64,2700	367164	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367164	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/sation.php?code=vern

1402	IOC_vhbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_vhbc	49,2833	-	123,1167	367156				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367156	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vhbc
1403	IOC_VI12			IOC_VI12	41,8881	-	16,1770	374594				2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=374594	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=VI12
1404	IOC_vibc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_vibc	48,4200	-	123,3700	364163				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364163	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vibc
1405	IOC_vieq	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_vieq	18,0939	-	65,4714	369710				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369710	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vieq
1406	IOC_vieq2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_vieq2	18,0939	-	65,4714	366406				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=366406	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ieq2
1407	IOC_vig2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_vig2	42,2431	-	8,7260	367165				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367165	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vig2
1408	IOC_vil2	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IOC_vil2	42,6007	-	8,7700	367166				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367166	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vil2
1409	IOC_vish			IOC_vish	17,6800	-	83,2800	367167				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367167	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vish
1410	IOC_viti			IOC_viti	-	18,1342	178,4236	367168				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367168	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=viti
1411	IOC_vkfl	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_vkfl	24,7170	-	81,1050	367169				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367169	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vkfl
1412	IOC_vlad	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_vlad	43,1300	-	131,9200	367170				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367170	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vlad
1413	IOC_vlis			IOC_vlis	51,4429	-	3,5970	367638				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367638	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vlis
1414	IOC_vodo	Russian Federation	ROSHYDROMET - Federal Service for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	IOC_vodo	51,7268	-	157,9889	963950				2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=963950	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vodo
1415	IOC_vung			IOC_vung	10,3400	-	107,0710	367171				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367171	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vung
1416	IOC_waik	Indonesia	IPB - Institut Pertanian Bogor - Indonesia	IOC_waik	-	9,3898	119,2188	364164				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364164	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=waik
1417	IOC_waka	Japan	JAMSTEC - Japan Marine Science and Technology Center - Japan	IOC_waka	45,4100	-	141,6900	367172				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367172	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=waka
1418	IOC_wake	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wake	19,2900	-	166,6180	367173				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367173	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wake
1419	IOC_wake2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wake2	19,2900	-	166,6180	368161				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368161	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ake2
1420	IOC_wall	France	Shom - France	IOC_wall	-	13,1705	-	176,1007	367174			2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367174	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wall
1421	IOC_warn	Germany	FIWERI - Federal Waterways Engineering and Research Institute - Germany	IOC_warn	54,1697	-	12,1033	367175				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367175	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=warn
1422	IOC_wava	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wava	37,6000	-	75,6000	364165				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364165	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wava
1423	IOC_wbbh	United Kingdom	Channel Coastal Observatory	IOC_wbbh	50,7102	-	2,7640	364166				2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364166	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wbbh

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/r/v/d.nc>

1424	IOC_wbnc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wbnc	34,2100	-	77,7950	364167	wbnc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364167	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wbnc
1425	IOC_weym			IOC_weym	50,6100	-	2,4500	367176	weym	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367176	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=weym
1426	IOC_whbc	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	IOC_whbc	50,7000	-	128,3000	367181	whbc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367181	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=whbc
1427	IOC_whit			IOC_whit	54,4900	-	0,6100	367177	whit	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367177	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=whit
1428	IOC_wick			IOC_wick	58,4400	-	3,0900	367178	wick	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367178	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wick
1429	IOC_wilb	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wilb	46,7050	-	123,9590	367179	wilb	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367179	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/_php	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wilb
1430	IOC_will	Curacao	other - Curacao	IOC_will	12,1043	-	68,9416	363969	will	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=363969		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=will
1431	IOC_winc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_winc	34,2270	-	77,9530	367180	winc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367180		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=winc
1432	IOC_wlgt	New Zealand	LINZ - Land Information New Zealand - New Zealand	IOC_wlgt	41,2846	-	174,7791	367182	wlgt	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367182		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wlgt
1433	IOC_wlms	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wlms	30,3264	-	89,3258	367183	wlms	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367183		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wlms
1434	IOC_wlms2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wlms2	30,3264	-	89,3258	368006	lms2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368006		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=lms2
1435	IOC_wood	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wood	41,5233	-	70,6717	367184	wood	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367184		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wood
1436	IOC_wood2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wood2	41,5233	-	70,6717	368073	ood2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368073		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ood2
1437	IOC_work			IOC_work	54,6500	-	3,5700	367185	work	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367185		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=work
1438	IOC_wpwa	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wpwa	46,9083	-	124,1100	364168	wpwa	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364168		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wpwa
1439	IOC_wsdc	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_wsdc	38,8700	-	77,0200	367186	wsdc	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367186		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wsdc
1440	IOC_wuda	Oman	other - Oman	IOC_wuda	23,8200	-	57,5200	364169	wuda	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364169		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=wuda
1441	IOC_xish	China	FIOSDA - First Institute of Oceanography, State Oceanic Administration - China	IOC_xish	16,8300	-	112,3300	367187	xish	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367187		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=xish
1442	IOC_xmas			IOC_xmas	1,9840	-	157,4730	367188	xmas	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367188		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=xmas
1443	IOC_yabu			IOC_yabu	18,0551	-	65,8330	367626	yabu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367626		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=yabu
1444	IOC_vaku	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_vaku	59,5480	-	139,7350	367190	vaku	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367190		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=vaku
1445	IOC_yaku2	United States	NOAA - National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration - US	IOC_yaku2	59,5480	-	139,7350	637361	aku2	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=637361		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=aku2
1446	IOC_yapi			IOC_yapi	9,5142	-	138,1246	367191	yapi	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367191		http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=yapi

1447	IOC_yobu		IOC_yobu	18,0501	-	65,8330	367189	yobu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367189	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=yobu
1448	IOC_zanz		IOC_zanz	6,1500	-	39,1833	367192	zanz	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367192	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=zanz
1449	IOC_zhap	China	FIOSEA - First Institute of Oceanography, State Oceanic Administration - China IOC_zhap	21,5800	-	111,8200	367193	zhap	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367193	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=zhap
1450	IOC_zihu	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico IOC_zihu	17,6367	-	101,5583	369694	zihu	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369694	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=zihu
1451	IOC_zihu2	Mexico	NUMG - National University Of Mexico (Unam) / Instituto De Geofisica - Mexico IOC_zihu2	17,6367	-	101,5583	367194	ihu2	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367194	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=ihu2
1452	IOC_zygl1	Italy	JRC - Joint Research Centre - Italy IOC_zygl1	34,7263	-	33,3402	367195	zygl1	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367195	http://www.ioc-sealevelmonitoring.org/station.php?code=zygl1
1453	J61TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands J61TG	53,4920	-	5,9400	11620		2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11620	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1454	JerseyTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom JerseyTG	49,1800	-	2,1200	8663		2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8663	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1455	Juelsminde	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden Juelsminde	55,7167	-	10,0167	8664		1996 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8664	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1456	Juten	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden Juten	58,6342	-	16,3248	967451		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967451	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1457	K13Alpha	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands K13Alpha	53,2200	-	3,2200	8667		2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8667	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1458	K13aTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands K13aTG	53,2180	-	3,2190	11621		2015 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11621	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1459	K141TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands K141TG	53,2690	-	3,6262	11622		2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11622	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainings/stations/.php
1460	KabelvaaTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway KabelvaaTG	68,2126	-	14,4822	8669		2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8669	
1461	Kabelvag	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway Kabelvag	68,2167	-	14,5000	8670		1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8670	
1462	KadoelenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden KadoelenTG	52,6593	-	5,9822	8671		2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8671	
1463	Kalix	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden Kalix	65,6970	-	23,0962	435		1974 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=435	
1464	KalixKarlsborg	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden KalixKarlsborg	65,7888	-	23,3033	967452		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967452	
1465	KalixStoron	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden KalixStoron	65,6969	-	23,0961	867346		1974 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=867346	
1466	Kalkgrund	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden Kalkgrund	54,8247	-	9,8881	8672		2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8672	
1467	Kalmar	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden Kalmar	56,6713	-	16,3888	967454		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967454	
1468	Kalvehave	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark Kalvehave	55,0000	-	12,1667	8673		2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8673	
1469	KampenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands KampenTG	52,5525	-	5,9240	11623		2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11623	

1470	KamperhoekTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KamperhoekTG	52,6100	5,6425	8674	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8674	
1471	Kappeln	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Kappeln	54,6644	9,9381	8675	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8675	
1472	Karlskhamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Karlskhamn	56,1542	14,8212	967455	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967455	
1473	Karrebaeksminde	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Karrebaeksminde	55,1833	11,6500	8676	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8676	
1474	Kaskinen	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Kaskinen	62,3440	21,2148	8677	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8677	
1475	KaterveerTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KaterveerTG	52,5000	6,0600	11624	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11624	
1476	KeizersveerTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KeizersveerTG	51,7200	4,8950	11625	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11625	
1477	Kelnase	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Kelnase	59,6380	25,0150	637388	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=637388	
1478	Kemi	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Kemi	65,6729	24,5153	8678	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8678	
1479	KerguelenTG	France	Shom - France	KerguelenTG	-	49,3521	70,2191	368973	2017 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368973
1480	KerguelenTG-1min	France	Shom - France	KerguelenTG-1min	-	49,3521	70,2191	369621	2017 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369621
1481	KeteldiepTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KeteldiepTG	52,5820	5,8450	11626	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11626	
1482	KetelhavenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KetelhavenTG	52,5850	5,7830	11627	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11627	
1483	KielHoltenu	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	KielHoltenu	54,3722	10,1569	8679	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8679	
1484	KielHoltenuTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	KielHoltenuTG	54,3830	10,2040	8680	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8680	
1485	KIELT	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	KIELT	54,4997	10,2733	8681	2011 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8681	
1486	KielTG	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	KielTG	54,5003	10,2750	8682	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8682	
1487	Killybegs	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Killybegs	54,6364	-	8,3949	553	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=553
1488	KillybegsTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	KillybegsTG	54,6364	-	8,3949	8683	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8683
1489	KilrushLough	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	KilrushLough	52,6319	-	9,5021	988853	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=988853
1490	Kinlochbervie	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Kinlochbervie	58,4572	-	5,0496	40	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=40
1491	KinlochbervieTG	United Kingdom	Met Office - United Kingdom SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KinlochbervieTG	58,4566	-	5,0504	8684	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8684
1492	Klagshamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Klagshamn	55,5222	12,8936	436	1929 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=436	

1493	KlagshamnTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KlagshamnTG	55,5223	12,8936	8685	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8685
1494	Klaipeda	Norway	CMR - Christian Michelsen Research - Norway	Klaipeda	55,7333	21,0833	8686	2006 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8686
1495	Kobenhavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Kobenhavn	55,7000	12,6000	8687	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8687
1496	Koeze	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Koeze	55,4500	12,2000	8688	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8688
1497	Kolka	Latvia	LEGMA - Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Agency - Latvia	Kolka	57,7333	22,5833	8689	2005 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8689
1498	KOPER	Slovenia	ARSO - Slovenian Environment Agency - Slovenia	KOPER	45,5482	13,7245	13969	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13969
1499	KornwerderzandBinnenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KornwerderzandBinnenTG	53,0700	5,3380	607948	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=607948
1500	KornwerderzandBuitenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KornwerderzandBuitenTG	53,0710	5,3370	11628	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11628
1501	KornwerderzandTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KornwerderzandTG	53,0710	5,3371	8691	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8691
1502	Korsor	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Korsor	55,3333	11,1333	8692	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8692
1503	Koserow	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Koserow	54,0603	14,0008	8693	2005 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8693
1504	KoserowTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	KoserowTG	54,0600	13,9997	8694	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8694
1505	KrabbersgatluizenNoordTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KrabbersgatluizenNoordTG	52,6944	5,2842	8696	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8696
1506	KrabbersgatluizenZuidTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KrabbersgatluizenZuidTG	52,6923	5,2800	8697	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8697
1507	KrimpenAdLekTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	KrimpenAdLekTG	51,8920	4,6290	11629	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11629
1508	Kristiansund	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Kristiansund	63,1167	7,7500	8698	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8698
1509	KristiansundTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	KristiansundTG	63,1139	7,7344	8699	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8699
1510	Kristineberg1	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Kristineberg1	58,2500	11,4500	18876	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=18876
1511	Kronstadt	Russian Federation	NWAHEM - North-West Regional Administration for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	Kronstadt	59,9667	29,7500	8701	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8701
1512	Kuivastu	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Kuivastu	58,5742	23,3935	8702	2010 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8702
1513	Kungsholmsfort	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Kungsholmsfort	56,1053	15,5894	437	1886 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=437
1514	Kungsvik	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Kungsvik	58,9967	11,1272	438	1973 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=438
1515	KungsvikTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KungsvikTG	58,9966	11,1274	8703	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8703

1516	L91TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	L91TG	53,5660	4,8700	11630	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11630
1517	LaCotiniereTG	France	Shom - France	LaCotiniereTG	45,9136	1,3278	369075	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369075
1518	LaCotiniereTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LaCotiniereTG-10min	45,9136	1,3278	369404	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369404
1519	LaCotiniereTG-5min	France	Shom - France	LaCotiniereTG-5min	45,9136	1,3278	370869	2006 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370869
1520	LaDesiradeTG	France	Shom - France	LaDesiradeTG	16,3029	61,0725	368976	2010 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368976
1521	LaDesiradeTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LaDesiradeTG-1min	16,3029	61,0725	369624	2016 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369624
1522	LaFigueiretteTG	France	Shom - France	LaFigueiretteTG	43,4835	6,9338	8706	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8706
1523	LaFigueiretteTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LaFigueiretteTG-10min	43,4835	6,9338	370055	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370055
1524	LaFigueiretteTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LaFigueiretteTG-1min	43,4835	6,9338	369406	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369406
1525	LaFigueiretteTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LaFigueiretteTG-60min	43,4835	6,9338	370056	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370056
1526	LagosTG	Portugal	DGDT - Direção-Geral do Território - Portugal	LagosTG	37,1000	8,6667	28138	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28138
1527	LandsortNorra	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LandsortNorra	58,7689	17,8589	439	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=439
1528	Langballigau	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Langballigau	54,8233	9,6542	8707	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8707
1529	LangballigauTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	LangballigauTG	54,8233	9,6550	8708	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8708
1530	LangosteiraTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LangosteiraTG	43,3465	8,5301	28140	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28140
1531	LaPalmaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LaPalmaTG	28,6780	17,7680	8709	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8709
1532	Iarn	Cyprus	UNY CYPRUS - Cyprus Oceanography Center - Cyprus	Iarn	34,9162	33,6408	25856	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25856
1533	LaRochelleTG	France	Shom - France	LaRochelleTG	46,1487	1,2259	8710	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8710
1534	LaRochelleTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LaRochelleTG-10min	46,1487	1,2259	370057	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370057
1535	LaRochelleTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LaRochelleTG-1min	46,1487	1,2259	369408	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369408
1536	LaRochelleTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LaRochelleTG-60min	46,1487	1,2259	370058	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370058
1537	LasPalmasTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LasPalmasTG	28,1410	15,4120	8711	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8711
1538	LauwersoogTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	LauwersoogTG	53,4100	6,2000	11631	2015 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11631

1539	LeavaTG	France	Shom - France	LeavaTG	-	14,2960	-	178,1602	368616	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368616
1540	LeavaTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LeavaTG-1min	-	14,2960	-	178,1602	369410	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369410
1541	LeavaTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LeavaTG-60min	-	14,2960	-	178,1602	370059	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370059
1542	LeConquetTG	France	Shom - France	LeConquetTG	48,3593	-	4,7809		8713	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8713
1543	LeConquetTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LeConquetTG-10min	48,3593	-	4,7809		370060	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370060
1544	LeConquetTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LeConquetTG-1min	48,3593	-	4,7809		369411	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369411
1545	LeConquetTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LeConquetTG-60min	48,3593	-	4,7809		370061	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370061
1546	LeCrouestyTG	France	Shom - France	LeCrouestyTG	47,5429	-	2,8954		8714	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8714
1547	LeCrouestyTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LeCrouestyTG-10min	47,5429	-	2,8954		370062	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370062
1548	LeCrouestyTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LeCrouestyTG-1min	47,5429	-	2,8954		369412	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369412
1549	LeCrouestyTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LeCrouestyTG-60min	47,5429	-	2,8954		370063	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370063
1550	LeHavreTG	France	Shom - France	LeHavreTG	49,4816	0,1056			8715	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8715
1551	LeHavreTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LeHavreTG-10min	49,4816	0,1056			370064	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370064
1552	LeHavreTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LeHavreTG-1min	49,4816	0,1056			369413	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369413
1553	LeHavreTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LeHavreTG-60min	49,4816	0,1056			370065	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370065
1554	Lehtma	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Lehtma	59,0690	22,6969			8716	2006 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8716
1555	Leith	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Leith	55,9898	-	3,1804		31	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31
1556	LeithTG	United Kingdom	Met Office - United Kingdom	LeithTG	55,9900	-	3,1800		8717	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8717
1557	LeixoesTG	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	LeixoesTG	41,1867	-	8,7045		8718	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8718
1558	LemmerTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	LemmerTG	52,8390	5,7140			11632	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11632
1559	LePellerinTG	France	Shom - France	LePellerinTG	47,2054	-	1,7651		368617	1986 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368617
1560	LePellerinTG-5min	France	Shom - France	LePellerinTG-5min	47,2054	-	1,7651		369415	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369415
1561	LePellerinTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LePellerinTG-60min	47,2054	-	1,7651		370066	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370066

1562	Leppneeme	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Leppneeme	59,5531	24,8662	637390	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=637390	
1563	LePrecheurTG	France	Shom - France	LePrecheurTG	14,8076	-	61,2266	372351	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=372351
1564	LePrecheurTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LePrecheurTG-1min	14,8076	-	61,2266	370870	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=370870
1565	Lerwick	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Lerwick	60,1546	-	1,1384	20	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=20
1566	LerwickTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	LerwickTG	60,1540	-	1,1403	8719	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8719
1567	LesSablesDOlonneTG	France	Shom - France	LesSablesDOlonneTG	46,4975	-	1,7938	8721	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8721
1568	LesSablesDOlonneTG-10min	France	Shom - France	LesSablesDOlonneTG-10min	46,4975	-	1,7938	370067	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=370067
1569	LesSablesDOlonneTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LesSablesDOlonneTG-1min	46,4975	-	1,7938	369417	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=369417
1570	LesSablesDOlonneTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LesSablesDOlonneTG-60min	46,4975	-	1,7938	370068	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=370068
1571	LesSablesTG	France	Shom - France	LesSablesTG	46,4975	-	1,7937	8722	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8722
1572	LichteilandGoeree1TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	LichteilandGoeree1TG	51,9176	3,6670		8723	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8723
1573	LifouTG	France	Shom - France	LifouTG	-	20,9185	167,2787	368619	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=368619
1574	LifouTG-1min	France	Shom - France	LifouTG-1min	-	20,9185	167,2787	369419	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=369419
1575	LifouTG-60min	France	Shom - France	LifouTG-60min	-	20,9185	167,2787	370069	2013 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=370069
1576	ListTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	ListTG	55,0170	8,4410		8725	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8725
1577	Liverpool	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Liverpool	53,4500	-	3,0167	41	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=41
1578	LiverpoolTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LiverpoolTG	53,4500	-	3,0200	8726	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8726
1579	LjusneOrnskarskajen	Sweden	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	LjusneOrnskarskajen	61,2067	17,1452		967462	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=967462
1580	LladudnoTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	LladudnoTG	53,3300	-	3,8300	8727	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8727
1581	Llandudno	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Llandudno	53,3148	-	3,8237	77	1994 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=77
1582	LlandudnoTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	LlandudnoTG	53,3317	-	3,8252	8728	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8728
1583	LobithTG	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LobithTG	51,8513	6,1041		8730	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=8730
1584	Loudden	Sweden	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	Loudden	59,3425	18,1413		967463	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?x?id=967463

1585	Lowestoft	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Lowestoft	52,4667	1,7500	27	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=27
1586	LowestoftTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	LowestoftTG	52,4730	1,7508	8731	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8731
1587	Luebeck	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Luebeck	53,8931	10,7031	8735	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8735
1588	LuebeckTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LuebeckTG	53,9025	10,7745	8736	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8736
1589	Lunde	Sweden	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Lunde	62,8806	17,8764	967467	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967467
1590	MaaloeyTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	MaaloeyTG	61,9338	5,1133	8738	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8738
1591	MahonTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MahonTG	39,8930	4,2706	8739	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8739
1592	MakemoTG	France	Shom - France	MakemoTG	- 16,6270	- 143,5692	368978	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368978
1593	MakemoTG-2min	France	Shom - France	MakemoTG-2min	- 16,6270	- 143,5692	369630	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369630
1594	MakemoTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MakemoTG-60min	- 16,6270	- 143,5692	370070	2015 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370070
1595	MalagaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MalagaTG	36,7120	- 4,4170	8740	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8740
1596	MalinHead	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	MalinHead	55,3717	- 7,3343	8741	2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8741
1597	MalinHeadTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	MalinHeadTG	55,3717	- 7,3343	8742	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8742
1598	MalmoHamn	Sweden	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	MalmoHamn	55,6257	12,9845	967468	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967468
1599	Maloy	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Maloy	61,9333	5,1167	8743	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8743
1600	MaloyTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	MaloyTG	61,9338	5,1133	11112	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11112
1601	Mando	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	Mando	55,2833	8,5833	8744	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8744
1602	MandoTG	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	MandoTG	55,2833	8,5833	9280	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9280
1603	Mangalia	Romania	INFP - National Institute for Earth Physics - Romania	Mangalia	43,8010	28,5950	14219	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=14219
1604	MareTG	France	Shom - France	MareTG	- 21,5478	167,8771	368620	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368620
1605	MareTG-1min	France	Shom - France	MareTG-1min	- 21,5478	167,8771	369424	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369424
1606	MareTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MareTG-60min	- 21,5478	167,8771	370071	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370071
1607	MarinTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MarinTG	42,4061	- 8,6911	28143	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28143

1608	MarseilleTG	France	Shom - France	MarseilleTG	43,2785	5,3537	8745	2009 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8745	
1609	MarseilleTG-10min	France	Shom - France	MarseilleTG-10min	43,2785	5,3537	370072	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370072	
1610	MarseilleTG-1min	France	Shom - France	MarseilleTG-1min	43,2785	5,3537	369425	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369425	
1611	MarseilleTG-60min	France	Shom - France SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute -	MarseilleTG-60min	43,2785	5,3537	370073	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370073	
1612	Marstrand	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute -	Marstrand	57,8880	11,5732	967469	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967469	
1613	Marviken	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Marviken	58,5537	16,8371	441	1964 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=441	
1614	MataUtutG	France	Shom - France	MataUtutG	-	13,2847 - 176,1685	368623	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368623	
1615	MataUtutG-1min	France	Shom - France	MataUtutG-1min	-	13,2847 - 176,1685	369426	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369426	
1616	MataUtutG-5min	France	Shom - France	MataUtutG-5min	-	13,2847 - 176,1685	370074	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370074	
1617	MataUtutG-60min	France	Shom - France	MataUtutG-60min	-	13,2847 - 176,1685	370075	2013 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370075	
1618	MausundTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	MausundTG	63,8693	8,6652	8747	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8747	
1619	MayotteTG	France	Shom - France	MayotteTG	-	12,7833 - 45,2583	8748	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8748	
1620	MayotteTG-10min	France	Shom - France	MayotteTG-10min	-	12,7833 - 45,2583	370076	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370076	
1621	MayotteTG-1min	France	Shom - France	MayotteTG-1min	-	12,7833 - 45,2583	369427	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369427	
1622	MayotteTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MayotteTG-60min	-	12,7833 - 45,2583	370077	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370077	
1623	MelillaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MelillaTG	35,2910	-	2,9180	8755	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8755
1624	Milford	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Milford	51,7167	-	5,0500	8757	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8757
1625	MilfordHavenTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	MilfordHavenTG	51,7064	-	5,0515	8758	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8758
1626	Millport	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Millport	55,7497	-	4,9047	14	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=14
1627	MillportTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	MillportTG	55,7496	-	4,9058	8759	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8759
1628	MimizanTG	France	Shom - France	MimizanTG	44,2107	-	1,2951	11346	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11346
1629	MimizanTG-10min	France	Shom - France	MimizanTG-10min	44,2107	-	1,2951	370078	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370078
1630	MimizanTG-1min	France	Shom - France	MimizanTG-1min	44,2107	-	1,2951	369431	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369431

1631	MimizanTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MimizanTG-60min	44,2107	-	1,2951	370079	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370079
1632	MO	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	MO	54,1167		4,0166	8760	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8760
1633	Molo-Sartorio	Italy	CNR ISMAR - CNR Isttute of Marine Science - Italy	Molo-Sartorio	45,6436		13,7539	8762	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8762
1634	MonacoPortHerculeTG	France	Shom - France	MonacoPortHerculeTG	43,7329		7,4240	25860	1999 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25860
1635	MonacoTG	France	Shom - France	MonacoTG	43,7330		7,4237	8763	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8763
1636	MonacoTG-10min	France	Shom - France	MonacoTG-10min	43,7330		7,4237	370080	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370080
1637	MonacoTG-1min	France	Shom - France	MonacoTG-1min	43,7330		7,4237	369432	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369432
1638	MonacoTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MonacoTG-60min	43,7330		7,4237	370081	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370081
1639	MondDerVechtTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	MondDerVechtTG	52,5650		6,1020	11633	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11633
1640	MontoirDeBretagneTG	France	Shom - France	MontoirDeBretagneTG	47,3056	-	2,1084	368625	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368625
1641	MontoirDeBretagneTG-5min	France	Shom - France	MontoirDeBretagneTG-5min	47,3056	-	2,1084	369433	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369433
1642	MontoirDeBretagneTG-60min	France	Shom - France	MontoirDeBretagneTG-60min	47,3056	-	2,1084	370082	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370082
1643	MotrilTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MotrilTG	36,7200	-	3,5240	8767	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8767
1644	Mumbles	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Mumbles	51,5697	-	3,9737	11109	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11109
1645	MumblesTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	MumblesTG	51,5700	-	3,9754	8769	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8769
1646	Munalaïd	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Munalaïd	58,2280		24,1185	14101	2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=14101
1647	NantesSalorgesTG	France	Shom - France	NantesSalorgesTG	47,2042	-	1,5743	368626	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368626
1648	NantesSalorgesTG-10min	France	Shom - France	NantesSalorgesTG-10min	47,2042	-	1,5743	369862	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369862
1649	NantesSalorgesTG-5min	France	Shom - France	NantesSalorgesTG-5min	47,2042	-	1,5743	369434	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369434
1650	NantesSalorgesTG-60min	France	Shom - France	NantesSalorgesTG-60min	47,2042	-	1,5743	370083	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370083
1651	NantesUsineBruleeTG	France	Shom - France	NantesUsineBruleeTG	47,1935	-	1,6337	368627	1987 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368627
1652	NantesUsineBruleeTG-5min	France	Shom - France	NantesUsineBruleeTG-5min	47,1935	-	1,6337	369435	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369435
1653	NantesUsineBruleeTG-60min	France	Shom - France	NantesUsineBruleeTG-60min	47,1935	-	1,6337	370084	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370084

1654	Narvik	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Narvik	68,4333	17,4167	8775	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8775
1655	NarvikTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	NarvikTG	68,4283	17,4258	8776	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8776
1656	NazareTG	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	NazareTG	39,5860	9,0740	8777	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8777
1657	NesTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	NesTG	53,4311	5,7610	8778	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8778
1658	Neustadt	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Neustadt	54,0967	10,8128	8780	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8780
1659	NeustadtTG	Germany	WSL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	NeustadtTG	54,0870	10,8130	8781	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8781
1660	Newhaven	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Newhaven	50,7833	0,0667	10	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=10
1661	NewhavenTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	NewhavenTG	50,7818	0,0570	8782	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8782
1662	Newlyn	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Newlyn	50,1000	5,5333	28	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=28
1663	NewlynTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	NewlynTG	50,1030	5,5428	8783	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8783
1664	Newport	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Newport	51,5496	2,9860	79	1993 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=79
1665	NewportTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	NewportTG	51,5500	2,9874	8784	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8784
1666	NiceTG	France	Shom - France	NiceTG	43,6956	7,2855	8785	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8785
1667	NiceTG-10min	France	Shom - France	NiceTG-10min	43,6956	7,2855	370085	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=370085
1668	NiceTG-1min	France	Shom - France	NiceTG-1min	43,6956	7,2855	369438	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=369438
1669	NiceTG-60min	France	Shom - France	NiceTG-60min	43,6956	7,2855	370086	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=370086
1670	NieuweStatenzijTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	NieuweStatenzijTG	53,2327	7,2080	8786	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8786
1671	NieuwpoortTG	Belgium	MDR - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	NieuwpoortTG	51,1510	2,7280	8787	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8787
1672	Norderney	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Norderney	53,6967	7,1583	8788	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8788
1673	NorderneyTG	Germany	WSOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany	NorderneyTG	53,7000	7,1600	8789	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8789
1674	NordreRose	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	NordreRose	55,6361	12,6867	8790	1992 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8790
1675	NorthCormorantTG	Other	Oil Platform - Private Industry	NorthCormorantTG	61,3400	1,1600	8792	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8792
1676	NorthShields	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NorthShields	55,0000	1,4333	8794	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8794

1677	NorthShieldsTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	NorthShieldsTG	55,0100	-	1,4400	8795	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8795	
1678	NoumeaNumboTG	France	Shom - France	NoumeaNumboTG	-	22,2421	166,4162	8796	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8796	
1679	NoumeaNumboTG-10min	France	Shom - France	NoumeaNumboTG-10min	-	22,2421	166,4162	369637	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369637	
1680	NoumeaNumboTG-1min	France	Shom - France	NoumeaNumboTG-1min	-	22,2421	166,4162	369441	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369441	
1681	NoumeaNumboTG-60min	France	Shom - France	NoumeaNumboTG-60min	-	22,2421	166,4162	370087	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370087	
1682	NukuHivaTG	France	Shom - France	NukuHivaTG	-	8,9149	-	140,0960	368979	2007 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368979
1683	NukuHivaTG-1min	France	Shom - France	NukuHivaTG-1min	-	8,9149	-	140,0960	369639	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369639
1684	NyAalesund	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	NyAalesund	78,9333	11,9500		8803	1992 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8803	
1685	NyAalesundTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	NyAalesundTG	78,9285	11,9380		8804	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8804	
1686	Ny-AlesundTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Ny-AlesundTG	78,9286	11,9380		8802	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8802	
1687	NynasFiskehamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	NynasFiskehamn	58,9006	17,9536		967476	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967476	
1688	OlandsNorraUdde	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	OlandsNorraUdde	57,3661	17,0972		442	1961 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=442	
1689	Onsala	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Onsala	57,3920	11,9190		15365	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=15365	
1690	Oostende	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	Oostende	51,2300	2,9200		8811	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8811	
1691	OostendeTG	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	OostendeTG	51,2340	2,9270		8812	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8812	
1692	Oosterschelde11TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	Oosterschelde11TG	51,6400	3,4800		8814	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8814	
1693	Oscarsborg	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Oscarsborg	59,6833	10,6167		8816	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8816	
1694	OscarsborgTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	OscarsborgTG	59,6781	10,6049		8817	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8817	
1695	Oskarshamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Oskarshamn	57,2750	16,4781		443	1960 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=443	
1696	OskarshamnTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	OskarshamnTG	57,2700	16,5700		11634	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11634	
1697	Oslo	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Oslo	59,9000	10,7333		8819	2006 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8819	
1698	OsloTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	OsloTG	59,9086	10,7345		8820	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8820	
1699	OudeSchildTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	OudeSchildTG	53,0400	4,8500		8821	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8821	

1700	QuinneTG	France	Shom - France	QuinneTG	-	21,9829	166,6833	368630	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368630
1701	QuinneTG-1min	France	Shom - France	QuinneTG-1min	-	21,9829	166,6833	369450	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369450
1702	QuinneTG-60min	France	Shom - France	QuinneTG-60min	-	21,9829	166,6833	370088	2013 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370088
1703	OuistrehamTG	France	Shom - France	OuistrehamTG	49,2794	-	0,2490	368631	2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368631
1704	OuistrehamTG-10min	France	Shom - France	OuistrehamTG-10min	49,2794	-	0,2490	370089	2016 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370089
1705	OuistrehamTG-1min	France	Shom - France	OuistrehamTG-1min	49,2794	-	0,2490	369453	2016 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369453
1706	OuistrehamTG-60min	France	Shom - France	OuistrehamTG-60min	49,2794	-	0,2490	370090	2017 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370090
1707	Oulu	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Oulu	65,0403	25,4182	13388	13388	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13388
1708	OuveaTG	France	Shom - France	OuveaTG	-	20,5498	166,5619	368632	2017 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368632
1709	OuveaTG-1min	France	Shom - France	OuveaTG-1min	-	20,5498	166,5619	369455	2017 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369455
1710	OuveaTG-60min	France	Shom - France	OuveaTG-60min	-	20,5498	166,5619	370871	2017 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370871
1711	OxelosundVinterklasen	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	OxelosundVinterklasen	58,6617	17,1248	967432	967432	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967432
1712	PaimboeufTG	France	Shom - France	PaimboeufTG	47,2866	-	2,0004	368633	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368633
1713	PaimboeufTG-5min	France	Shom - France	PaimboeufTG-5min	47,2866	-	2,0004	369456	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369456
1714	PaimboeufTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PaimboeufTG-60min	47,2866	-	2,0004	370091	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370091
1715	Paldiski	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Paldiski	59,3349	24,0796	8822	8822	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8822
1716	PalmaMallorcaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	PalmaMallorcaTG	39,5603	2,6375	8824	8824	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8824
1717	PapeeteTG	France	Shom - France	PapeeteTG	-	17,5331	149,5727	368980	2007 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368980
1718	PapeeteTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PapeeteTG-1min	-	17,5331	149,5727	369650	2007 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369650
1719	papho	Cyprus	UNY CYPRUS - Cyprus Oceanography Center - Cyprus	papho	34,7551	32,4088	9176	9176	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9176
1720	Parnu	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Parnu	58,3889	24,4868	8827	8827	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8827
1721	PenicheTG	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	PenicheTG	39,3540	-	9,3670	8828	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8828
1722	PettenZuidTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	PettenZuidTG	52,7740	4,6500	8829	8829	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8829

1723	Pietarsaari	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Pietarsaari	63,7086	22,6896	8830	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8830
1724	Plymouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Plymouth	50,3684	4,1852	8831	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8831
1725	PlymouthTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	PlymouthTG	50,3700	4,1900	8832	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8832
1726	PointeAPitreTG	France	Shom - France	PointeAPitreTG	16,2300	61,5300	8833	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8833
1727	PointeAPitreTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PointeAPitreTG-10min	16,2300	61,5300	370092	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370092
1728	PointeAPitreTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PointeAPitreTG-1min	16,2300	61,5300	369489	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369489
1729	PointeAPitreTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PointeAPitreTG-60min	16,2300	61,5300	370093	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370093
1730	POLLENSA	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	POLLENSA	39,9046	3,0885	13872	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13872
1731	Pomorie	Bulgaria	Bulgaria	Pomorie	42,5510	27,6390	11258	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11258
1732	PontDuBraultTG	France	Shom - France	PontDuBraultTG	46,3168	1,0826	369078	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369078
1733	PontDuBraultTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PontDuBraultTG-10min	46,3168	1,0826	369458	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369458
1734	PontDuBraultTG-5min	France	Shom - France	PontDuBraultTG-5min	46,3168	1,0826	370094	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370094
1735	PontDuBraultTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PontDuBraultTG-60min	46,3168	1,0826	370095	2013 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370095
1736	Pori	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Pori	61,5944	21,4634	13389	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13389
1737	PortBlocTG	France	Shom - France	PortBlocTG	45,5684	1,0616	8835	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8835
1738	PortBlocTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PortBlocTG-10min	45,5684	1,0616	369945	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369945
1739	PortBlocTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PortBlocTG-1min	45,5684	1,0616	369459	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369459
1740	PortBlocTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PortBlocTG-60min	45,5684	1,0616	370096	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370096
1741	Portbury	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Portbury	51,5000	2,7284	25867	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25867
1742	PortCamargueTG	France	Shom - France	PortCamargueTG	43,5203	4,1264	368634	2011 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368634
1743	PortCamargueTG-5min	France	Shom - France	PortCamargueTG-5min	43,5203	4,1264	369461	2010 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369461
1744	PortEllen	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PortEllen	55,6274	6,1901	25868	1991 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25868
1745	PortErin	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PortErin	54,0854	4,7681	25869	1992 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25869

1746	PortFerreolTG	France	Shom - France	PortFerreolTG	43,3591	6,7176	368635	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368635	
1747	PortFerreolTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PortFerreolTG-10min	43,3591	6,7176	370097	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370097	
1748	PortFerreolTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PortFerreolTG-1min	43,3591	6,7176	369463	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369463	
1749	PortFerreolTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PortFerreolTG-60min	43,3591	6,7176	370098	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370098	
1750	PortLaNouvelleTG	France	Shom - France	PortLaNouvelleTG	43,0147	3,0641	368636	2013 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368636	
1751	PortLaNouvelleTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PortLaNouvelleTG-10min	43,0147	3,0641	370099	2009 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370099	
1752	PortLaNouvelleTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PortLaNouvelleTG-1min	43,0147	3,0641	369464	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369464	
1753	PortLaNouvelleTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PortLaNouvelleTG-60min	43,0147	3,0641	370100	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370100	
1754	PORTO-CRISTO	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System	PORTO-CRISTO	39,5392	3,3351	15102	2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=15102	
1755	Portpatrick	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Portpatrick	54,8424	-	5,1189	21	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=21
1756	PortpatrickTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	PortpatrickTG	54,8426	-	5,1200	8836	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8836
1757	Portrush	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Portrush	55,2000	-	6,6667	80	1995 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=80
1758	PortrushTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	PortrushTG	55,2068	-	6,6568	8837	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8837
1759	Portsmouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Portsmouth	50,8004	-	1,1102	43	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=43
1760	PortsmouthTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	PortsmouthTG	50,8026	-	1,1118	8838	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8838
1761	PortTudyTG	France	Shom - France	PortTudyTG	47,6443	-	3,4460	8839	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8839
1762	PortTudyTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PortTudyTG-10min	47,6443	-	3,4460	370101	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370101
1763	PortTudyTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PortTudyTG-1min	47,6443	-	3,4460	369465	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369465
1764	PortTudyTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PortTudyTG-60min	47,6443	-	3,4460	370102	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370102
1765	PortVendresTG	France	Shom - France	PortVendresTG	42,5201	3,1073	8840	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8840	
1766	PortVendresTG-10min	France	Shom - France	PortVendresTG-10min	42,5201	3,1073	370103	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370103	
1767	PortVendresTG-1min	France	Shom - France	PortVendresTG-1min	42,5201	3,1073	369468	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369468	
1768	PortVendresTG-60min	France	Shom - France	PortVendresTG-60min	42,5201	3,1073	370104	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370104	

1769	Porvoo	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Porvoo	60,2058	25,6251	13390													2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13390
1770	PSMSL_AARHUS_76	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	AARHUS_76	56,1472	10,2239	12052	76	0											1888 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12052
1771	PSMSL_ABASHIRI_1104	Other	Not Defined	ABASHIRI_1104	44,0194	144,2858	12765	1104	327											1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12765
1772	PSMSL_ABERDEEN I 361	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	ABERDEEN I 361	57,1441	- 2,0774	12231	361	0											1931 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12231
1773	PSMSL_ABERDEEN II_21	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	ABERDEEN II_21	57,1500	- 2,0833	12010	21	0											1862 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12010
1774	PSMSL_ABIDIAN_1313	Other	Not Defined	ABIDIAN_1313	5,2500	- 4,0000	12897	1313	257											1971 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12897
1775	PSMSL_ABURATSU 814	Other	Not Defined	ABURATSU 814	31,5769	131,4094	12578	814	82											1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12578
1776	PSMSL_ABURATSUBO_130	Other	Not Defined	ABURATSUBO_130	35,1603	139,6153	12094	130	0											1930 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12094
1777	PSMSL_ACAJUTLA_1011	Other	Not Defined	ACAJUTLA_1011	13,5667	- 89,8333	12706	1011	182											1962 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12706
1778	PSMSL_ACAPULCO_686	Other	Not Defined	ACAPULCO_686	16,8333	- 99,9167	12483	686	267											1967 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12483
1779	PSMSL_ADAK SWEEPER COVE 487	Other	Not Defined	ADAK SWEEPER COVE 487	51,8633	- 176,6317	12331	487	302											1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12331
1780	PSMSL_ADEN_44	Other	Not Defined	ADEN_44	12,7883	44,9742	12029	44	3											1879 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12029
1781	PSMSL_AGUADILLA_2121	Other	Not Defined	AGUADILLA_2121	18,4567	- 67,1633	13335	2121	0											2006 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13335
1782	PSMSL_AION 730	France	Shom - France	AION 730	69,9333	167,9833	12514	730	371	0										72 1954 - 2007	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12514
1783	PSMSL_AJACCIO_1929	France	Shom - France	AJACCIO_1929	41,9228	8,7629	13241	1929	0											1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13241
1784	PSMSL_AKKO_2218	Other	Not Defined	AKKO_2218	32,9193	35,0702	13378	2218	0											2012 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13378
1785	PSMSL_AKUNE_1265	Other	Not Defined	AKUNE_1265	32,0175	130,1908	12868	1265	0											1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12868
1786	PSMSL_AKYAB 421	Other	Not Defined	AKYAB 421	20,1333	92,9000	12278	421	37											1937 - 1942	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12278
1787	PSMSL_ALAMEDA (NAVAL AIR STATION)_437	Other	Not Defined	ALAMEDA (NAVAL AIR STATION)_437	37,7717	- 122,2983	12291	437	0											1939 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12291
1788	PSMSL_ALAMITOS BAY ENTRANCE_717	Other	Not Defined	ALAMITOS BAY ENTRANCE_717	33,7500	- 118,1167	12503	717	80	0										174 1953 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12503
1789	PSMSL_ALBANY 957	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALBANY 957	- 35,0337	117,8926	12671	957	0											1987 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12671
1790	PSMSL_ALCUDIA_2063	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALCUDIA_2063	39,8346	3,1390	13288	2063	0											2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13288
1791	PSMSL_ALERT BAY_554	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	ALERT BAY_554	50,5833	- 126,9500	12378	554	128	0										308 1948 - 1978	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12378

1792	PSMSL_ALERT_1110	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	ALERT_1110	82,4900	62,3200	12771	1110	333	1965 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12771
1793	PSMSL_ALESUND_509	Other	Not Defined	ALESUND_509	62,4694	6,1519	12347	509	0	1945 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12347
1794	PSMSL_ALEXANDRIA_503	Other	Not Defined	ALEXANDRIA_503	31,2167	29,9167	12344	503	349	1944 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12344
1795	PSMSL_ALEXANDROUPOLIS_1238	Other	Not Defined	ALEXANDROUPOLIS_1238	40,8441	25,8783	12844	1238	19	123 1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12844
1796	PSMSL_ALGECIRAS_2_2055	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALGECIRAS_2_2055	36,1770	5,3984	13280	2055	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13280
1797	PSMSL_ALGECIRAS_B_2117	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALGECIRAS_B_2117	36,1214	5,4371	13331	2117	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13331
1798	PSMSL_ALGECIRAS_490	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALGECIRAS_490	36,1167	5,4333	12334	490	0	1943 - 2002	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12334
1799	PSMSL_ALICANTE_L_208	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALICANTE_L_208	38,3333	0,4833	12152	208	0	1952 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12152
1800	PSMSL_ALMERIA_2_2056	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALMERIA_2_2056	36,8300	2,4784	13281	2056	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13281
1801	PSMSL_ALMERIA_1455	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ALMERIA_1455	36,8333	2,4833	12993	1455	245	206 1977 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12993
1802	PSMSL_ALMIRANTE BROWN_858	Other	Not Defined	ALMIRANTE BROWN_858	64,9000	62,8667	12613	858	0	1957 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12613
1803	PSMSL_ALOTAU_1607	Other	Not Defined	ALOTAU_1607	10,3167	150,4500	13063	1607	63	1984 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13063
1804	PSMSL_ALVARADO_768	Other	Not Defined	ALVARADO_768	18,7667	95,7667	12545	768	0	1955 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12545
1805	PSMSL_AMASRA_1919	Other	Not Defined	AMASRA_1919	41,4333	32,2333	13235	1919	0	2001 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13235
1806	PSMSL_AMBARCHIK_604	Other	Not Defined	AMBARCHIK_604	69,6167	162,3000	12415	604	0	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12415
1807	PSMSL_AMDERMA_599	Other	Not Defined	AMDERMA_599	69,7500	61,7000	12410	599	0	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12410
1808	PSMSL_AMERICAN RIVER_631	Other	Not Defined	AMERICAN RIVER_631	35,8000	137,7667	12436	631	0	1950 - 1952	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12436
1809	PSMSL_AMHERST_746	Other	Not Defined	AMHERST_746	16,0833	97,5667	12526	746	0	1954 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12526
1810	PSMSL_AMRUM (WITTDUEN)_1036	Other	Not Defined	AMRUM (WITTDUEN)_1036	54,6167	8,3833	12722	1036	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12722
1811	PSMSL_ANABAR_1780	Other	Not Defined	ANABAR_1780	73,2167	113,5000	13154	1780	0	1991 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13154
1812	PSMSL_ANCHORAGE_1067	Other	Not Defined	ANCHORAGE_1067	61,2383	149,8900	12737	1067	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12737
1813	PSMSL_ANCONA_II_2098	Italy	ISPRa - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ANCONA_II_2098	43,6248	13,5065	13315	2098	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13315
1814	PSMSL_ANCONA_101	Italy	ISPRa - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ANCONA_101	43,5833	13,4833	12075	101	0	1966 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12075

1815	PSMSL_ANDENES_425	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	ANDENES_425	69,3261	16,1348	12279	425	322	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12279
1816	PSMSL_ANDREIA (ANDREIA OSTROV)_646	Other	Not Defined	ANDREIA (ANDREIA OSTROV)_646	76,8000	110,7500	12449	646	0	1951 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12449
1817	PSMSL_ANGRA DO HEROISMO_380	Other	Not Defined	ANGRA DO HEROISMO_380	38,6500	27,2333	12247	380	0	1976 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12247
1818	PSMSL_ANHEUNG 1699	Other	Not Defined	ANHEUNG 1699	36,6736	126,1322	13108	1699	0	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13108
1819	PSMSL_ANNAPOLIS (NAVAL ACADEMY)_311	Other	Not Defined	ANNAPOLIS (NAVAL ACADEMY)_311	38,9833	76,4800	12207	311	0	1928 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12207
1820	PSMSL_ANTALYA II_1681	Other	Not Defined	ANTALYA II_1681	36,8333	30,6167	13102	1681	836	333 1985 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13102
1821	PSMSL_ANTIFER 1383	Other	Not Defined	ANTIFER 1383	49,6500	0,1500	12942	1383	0	1974 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12942
1822	PSMSL_ANTIPAIUTA_1128	Other	Not Defined	ANTIPAIUTA_1128	69,0833	76,8500	12781	1128	0	1965 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12781
1823	PSMSL_ANTOFAGASTA 2_510	Other	Not Defined	ANTOFAGASTA 2_510	23,6531	70,4044	12348	510	174	1945 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12348
1824	PSMSL_ANTOFAGASTA_51 1	Other	Not Defined	ANTOFAGASTA_511	23,6500	70,4167	12349	511	174	1945 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12349
1825	PSMSL_APALACHICOLA_11 93	Other	Not Defined	APALACHICOLA 1193	29,7267	84,9817	12814	1193	331	58 1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12814
1826	PSMSL_APIA B_1840	Other	Not Defined	APIA B_1840	13,8268	171,7613	13195	1840	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13195
1827	PSMSL_APRRA HARBOUR, GUAM_540	Other	Not Defined	APRA HARBOUR, GUAM_540	13,4383	144,6533	12368	540	149	1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12368
1828	PSMSL_ARCACHON-EYRAC 1918	France	Shom - France	ARCACHON-EYRAC 1918	44,6650	1,1636	13234	1918	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13234
1829	PSMSL_ARENA COVE, CALIFORNIA_2125	Other	Not Defined	ARENA COVE, CALIFORNIA_2125	38,9133	123,7067	13338	2125	0	1978 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13338
1830	PSMSL_ARGENTIA_1321	Canada	DFD - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	ARGENTIA_1321	47,3000	53,9833	12900	1321	0	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12900
1831	PSMSL_ARGENTINE ISLANDS_913	Other	Not Defined	ARGENTINE ISLANDS_913	65,2462	64,2574	12641	913	188	1958 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12641
1832	PSMSL_ARICA 618	Other	Not Defined	ARICA 618	18,4667	70,3333	12429	618	0	1950 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12429
1833	PSMSL_ARINAGA_2049	Other	Not Defined	ARINAGA_2049	27,8469	15,4015	13275	2049	0	2003 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13275
1834	PSMSL_ARRECIFE 2_2066	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ARRECIFE 2_2066	28,9719	13,5301	13291	2066	0	2008 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13291
1835	PSMSL_ARRECIFE 593	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ARRECIFE 593	28,9719	13,5300	12405	593	0	1949 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12405
1836	PSMSL_ARRECIFE-D_1710	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	ARRECIFE-D_1710	28,9500	13,5667	13118	1710	0	1992 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13118
1837	PSMSL_ASAMUSHI_721	Other	Not Defined	ASAMUSHI_721	40,8975	140,8592	12505	721	55	111 1954 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12505

1838	PSMSL_ASHDOD II_2219	Other	Not Defined	ASHDOD II_2219	31,8313	34,6405	13379	2219	0	2012 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13379
1839	PSMSL_ASHKLOM_2220	Other	Not Defined	ASHKLOM_2220	31,6818	34,5567	13380	2220	0	2012 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13380
1840	PSMSL_ASTORIA (TONGUE POINT)_265	Other	Not Defined	ASTORIA (TONGUE POINT)_265	46,2067	123,7683	12190	265	0	1925 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12190
1841	PSMSL ATLANTIC CITY 180	Other	Not Defined	ATLANTIC CITY 180	39,3550	74,4183	12132	180	220	1911 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12132
1842	PSMSL_AUCKLAND II_150	Other	Not Defined	AUCKLAND II_150	36,8431	174,7695	12110	150	127	1903 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12110
1843	PSMSL_AVEIRO_1402	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	AVEIRO_1402	40,6500	8,7500	12955	1402	0	1975 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12955
1844	PSMSL_AVONMOUTH 257	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	AVONMOUTH 257	51,5077	2,7128	12187	257	0	1986 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12187
1845	PSMSL_AWA SIMA_1093	Other	Not Defined	AWA SIMA_1093	38,4678	139,2550	12754	1093	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12754
1846	PSMSL_AYUKAWA_131	Other	Not Defined	AYUKAWA_131	38,2967	141,5053	12095	131	0	1958 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12095
1847	PSMSL_BACKEVIK_97	Other	Not Defined	BACKEVIK_97	58,3667	11,2500	12071	97	0	1895 - 1928	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12071
1848	PSMSL_BAHIA DE LOS ANGELES 1357	Other	Not Defined	BAHIA DE LOS ANGELES 1357	28,9667	113,5500	12927	1357	168	62 1973 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12927
1849	PSMSL_BAHIA ESPERANZA_988	Other	Not Defined	BAHIA ESPERANZA_988	63,3000	56,9167	12689	988	185	1961 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12689
1850	PSMSL_BAHIA SAN QUINTIN_1457	Other	Not Defined	BAHIA SAN QUINTIN_1457	30,4833	115,9833	12995	1457	0	1977 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12995
1851	PSMSL_BAIE COMEAU 1218	Other	Not Defined	BAIE COMEAU 1218	49,2333	68,1333	12832	1218	0	1968 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12832
1852	PSMSL_BAKAR_353	Other	Not Defined	BAKAR_353	45,3000	14,5333	12228	353	0	1930 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12228
1853	PSMSL_BALANACAN, MARINDUQUE_2157	Other	Not Defined	BALANACAN, MARINDUQUE_2157	13,5333	121,8667	13359	2157	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13359
1854	PSMSL_BALBOA_163	Other	Not Defined	BALBOA_163	8,9667	79,5667	12118	163	168	1908 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12118
1855	PSMSL_BALINTANG, QUEZON, PALAWAN 2155	Other	Not Defined	BALINTANG, QUEZON, PALAWAN 2155	9,3500	118,1333	13358	2155	0	2011 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13358
1856	PSMSL_BALLINA_319	Other	Not Defined	BALLINA_319	28,8667	153,5833	12215	319	0	1959 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12215
1857	PSMSL_BALTIMORE_148	Other	Not Defined	BALTIMORE_148	39,2667	76,5783	12109	148	0	1902 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12109
1858	PSMSL_BALTRA-B 1645	Other	Not Defined	BALTRA-B 1645	0,4333	90,2833	13086	1645	169	1985 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13086
1859	PSMSL_BAMFIELD_1242	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	BAMFIELD_1242	48,8500	125,1333	12848	1242	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12848
1860	PSMSL_BANGOR_1856	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	BANGOR_1856	54,6648	5,6695	13204	1856	0	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13204

PSMSL_BAR HARBOR, 1861 FRENCHMAN BAY, ME_525	Other	Not Defined	BAR HARBOR, FRENCHMAN BAY, ME_525	44,3917	-	68,2050	12360	525	259	0	221	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12360
1862 PSMSL_BAR_1075	Other	Not Defined	BAR_1075	42,0833	-	19,0833	12744	1075		0		1964 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12744
1863 PSMSL_BARAHONA_745	Other	Not Defined	BARAHONA_745	18,2000	-	71,0833	12525	745		0		1954 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12525
1864 PSMSL_BARCELONA 1811	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BARCELONA 1811	41,3418	-	2,1657	13178	1811		0		1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13178
PSMSL_BARENTSBURG_54 1865 1	Other	Not Defined	BARENTSBURG_541	78,0667	-	14,2500	12369	541		231		1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12369
1866 PSMSL_BARI_2075	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	BARI_2075	41,1402	-	16,8660	13297	2075		0		2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13297
1867 PSMSL_BARMOUTH 1771	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	BARMOUTH 1771	52,7193	-	4,0450	13149	1771		0		1991 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13149
1868 PSMSL_BARSEBACK_2109	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	BARSEBACK_2109	55,7564	-	12,9033	13326	2109		0		1937 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13326
1869 PSMSL_BATISCAN_144	Other	Not Defined	BATISCAN_144	46,5000	-	72,2500	12106	144		0		1901 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12106
1870 PSMSL_BATUMI_51	Other	Not Defined	BATUMI_51	41,6333	-	41,7000	12034	51		0		1882 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12034
PSMSL_BAY WAVELAND 1871 YACHT CLUB II 2215	Other	Not Defined	BAY WAVELAND YACHT CLUB II 2215	30,3267	-	89,3250	13375	2215		0		2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13375
PSMSL_BAY WAVELAND 1872 YACHT CLUB_1715	Other	Not Defined	BAY WAVELAND YACHT CLUB_1715	30,3250	-	89,3250	13121	1715		0		1987 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13121
1873 PSMSL_BEACHPORT_304	Other	Not Defined	BEACHPORT_304	-	37,5000	140,0000	12205	304	72	0	129	1927 - 1931	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12205
1874 PSMSL_BEAUFORT 1537	Other	Not Defined	BEAUFORT 1537	32,4333	-	80,6667	13026	1537		0		1981 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13026
1875 PSMSL_BECANCOUR_1798	Other	Not Defined	BECANCOUR_1798	46,4000	-	72,3833	13166	1798		0		1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13166
1876 PSMSL_BEIHAI_1408	Other	Not Defined	BEIHAI_1408	21,4833	-	109,0833	12961	1408		0		1975 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12961
1877 PSMSL_BELEM_580	Other	Not Defined	BELEM_580	-	1,4500	-	48,5000	12399	580	0		1949 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12399
1878 PSMSL_BELFAST 2 219	Other	Not Defined	BELFAST 2 219	54,6000	-	5,9167	12160	219		0		1917 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12160
1879 PSMSL_BELLA BELLA_984	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	BELLA BELLA_984	52,1667	-	128,1333	12685	984		0		1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12685
PSMSL_BELLA 1880 COOLA_1084	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	BELLA COOLA_1084	52,3667	-	126,7833	12749	1084	41	0	102	1964 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12749
1881 PSMSL_BELLEDUNE 2069	Other	Not Defined	BELLEDUNE 2069	47,9000	-	65,8500	13293	2069		0		1999 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13293
1882 PSMSL_BELIYI NOS_859	Other	Not Defined	BELIYI NOS_859	69,6000	-	60,2167	12614	859		0		1957 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12614
1883 PSMSL_BENOA B_2200	Other	Not Defined	BENOA B_2200	-	8,7467	115,2117	13372	2200		49		2006 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13372

PSMSL_BERGEN POINT, 1884 STATEN IS_1637	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	BERGEN POINT, STATEN IS_1637	40,6367	-	74,1417	13078	1637	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13078
1885 PSMSL_BERGEN_58	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	BERGEN_58	60,3980	5,3205	12037	58	0	0	1915 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12037
1886 PSMSL_BERLEVAG_442	Other	Not Defined	BERLEVAG_442	70,8500	29,1000	12295	442	0	0	1939 - 1944	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12295
1887 PSMSL BETIO 1804	Other	Not Defined	BETIO 1804	1,3651	172,9330	13171	1804	113	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13171
1888 PSMSL_BHAUNAGAR I_420	Other	Not Defined	BHAUNAGAR I_420	21,8000	72,3000	12277	420	0	0	1937 - 1955	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12277
PSMSL_BHAUNAGAR 1889 II_804	Other	Not Defined	BHAUNAGAR II_804	21,7500	72,2333	12571	804	0	0	1956 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12571
1890 PSMSL BILBAO 1806	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BILBAO 1806	43,3515	-	3,0451	13173	1806	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13173
1891 PSMSL BILLINGA_708	Other	Not Defined	BILLINGA_708	69,8833	175,7667	12496	708	0	0	1953 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12496
1892 PSMSL_BINTULU_1833	Other	Not Defined	BINTULU_1833	3,2622	113,0639	13189	1833	0	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13189
PSMSL_BIRKENHEAD 1893 (ALFRED DOCK)_765	Other	Not Defined	BIRKENHEAD (ALFRED DOCK)_765	53,4000	-	3,0167	12542	765	0	1955 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12542
1894 PSMSL BJORN 90	Other	Not Defined	BJORN 90	60,6333	17,9667	12066	90	0	0	1892 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12066
PSMSL_BLUFF (SOUTHLAND 1895 HARBOUR)_213	Other	Not Defined	BLUFF (SOUTHLAND HARBOUR)_213	46,5977	168,3454	12156	213	129	0	1917 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12156
1896 PSMSL_BODO_562	Other	Not Defined	BODO_562	67,2883	14,3908	12384	562	0	0	1949 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12384
1897 PSMSL BODRUM II 1680	Other	Not Defined	BODRUM II 1680	37,0333	27,4167	13101	1680	0	0	1985 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13101
PSMSL_BOLVANSKII NOS 1898 (FEDOROVA)_651	Other	Not Defined	BOLVANSKII NOS (FEDOROVA)_651	70,4500	59,0833	12454	651	0	0	1951 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12454
PSMSL_BOMBAY (PRINCES 1899 DOCK)_212	Other	Not Defined	BOMBAY (PRINCES DOCK)_212	18,9500	72,8333	12155	212	302	0	168 1916 - 1920	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12155
1900 PSMSL_BONANZA_1809	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	BONANZA_1809	36,8022	-	6,3381	13176	1809	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13176
1901 PSMSL BONAVISTA 2135	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	BONAVISTA 2135	49,0833	-	53,2000	13347	2135	34	161 2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13347
PSMSL_BOOBY 1902 ISLAND_1268	Other	Not Defined	BOOBY ISLAND_1268	10,6026	141,9101	12871	1268	61	0	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12871
PSMSL_BORKUM 1903 (FISCHERBAUJE)_1037	Other	Not Defined	BORKUM (FISCHERBAUJE)_1037	53,5833	6,6667	12723	1037	0	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12723
1904 PSMSL BORYEONG 1675	Other	Not Defined	BORYEONG 1675	36,4064	126,4861	13096	1675	347	0	327 1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13096
1905 PSMSL_BOSTON_235	Other	Not Defined	BOSTON_235	42,3533	-	71,0533	12173	235	0	1921 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12173
1906 PSMSL_BOUCAU_1801	Other	Not Defined	BOUCAU_1801	43,5273	-	1,5148	13169	1801	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13169

1907	PSMSL_BOULOGNE_471	France	Shom - France	BOULOGNE_471	50,7275	1,5775	12320	471	0	1941 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12320
1908	PSMSL_BOURGAS_317	Other	Not Defined	BOURGAS_317	42,4833	27,4833	12213	317	71	101 1929 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12213
1909	PSMSL_BOURNEMOUTH_1 878	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	BOURNEMOUTH_1878	50,7143	- 1,8749	13214	1878	0	1996 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13214
1910	PSMSL_BOUTILIER POINT_1259	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	BOUTILIER POINT_1259	44,6667	- 63,9667	12864	1259	0	1969 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12864
1911	PSMSL_BOWEN_II_2074	Other	Not Defined	BOWEN_II_2074	- 20,0167	148,2500	13296	2074	0	1986 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13296
1912	PSMSL_BREST_1	France	Shom - France	BREST_1	48,3829	- 4,4948	11993	1	822	242 1807 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11993
1913	PSMSL_BRIDGEPORT_1068	Other	Not Defined	BRIDGEPORT_1068	41,1733	- 73,1817	12738	1068	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12738
1914	PSMSL_BRIGHTON_677	Other	Not Defined	BRIGHTON_677	- 35,0333	138,5167	12475	677	0	1951 - 1952	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12475
1915	PSMSL_BRISBANE (WEST INNER BAR)_822	Other	Not Defined	BRISBANE (WEST INNER BAR)_822	- 27,3667	153,1667	12586	822	58	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12586
1916	PSMSL_BRONNOYSUND_8 03	Other	Not Defined	BRONNOYSUND_803	65,4833	12,2167	12570	803	708	334 1956 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12570
1917	PSMSL_BROOME_1159	Other	Not Defined	BROOME_1159	- 18,0008	122,2186	12802	1159	40	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12802
1918	PSMSL_BUCKIE_1281	Other	Not Defined	BUCKIE_1281	57,6667	- 2,9667	12881	1281	0	1971 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12881
1919	PSMSL_BUCKSPORT, WACCAMAW_R_1720	Other	Not Defined	BUCKSPORT, WACCAMAW_R_1720	33,6467	- 79,0950	13126	1720	0	1987 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13126
1920	PSMSL_BUENAVENTURA_4 56	Other	Not Defined	BUENAVENTURA_456	3,9000	- 77,1000	12306	456	295	170 238 1941 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12306
1921	PSMSL_BUENOS AIRES_157	Other	Not Defined	BUENOS AIRES_157	- 34,6000	- 58,3667	12113	157	0	1905 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12113
1922	PSMSL_BUGRINO_2025	Other	Not Defined	BUGRINO_2025	68,8000	49,3333	13263	2025	0	1952 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13263
1923	PSMSL_BUKOM_2032	Other	Not Defined	BUKOM_2032	1,2256	103,7785	13269	2032	0	2008 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13269
1924	PSMSL_BUNBURY_834	Other	Not Defined	BUNBURY_834	- 33,3234	115,6600	12598	834	0	1957 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12598
1925	PSMSL_BUNDBERG, BURNETT HEADS_1154	Other	Not Defined	BUNDBERG, BURNETT HEADS_1154	- 24,7667	152,3833	12797	1154	59	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12797
1926	PSMSL_BUORHAAIA (BUORHAAIA MYS)_735	Other	Not Defined	BUORHAAIA (BUORHAAIA MYS)_735	71,9500	132,7667	12518	735	0	1954 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12518
1927	PSMSL_BURNIE_683	Other	Not Defined	BURNIE_683	- 41,0501	145,9150	12480	683	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12480
1928	PSMSL_BUSAN_955	Other	Not Defined	BUSAN_955	35,0961	129,0356	12669	955	84	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12669
1929	PSMSL_BUZZARDS BAY_776	Other	Not Defined	BUZZARDS BAY_776	41,7417	- 70,6167	12550	776	0	1955 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12550

PSMSL_BYKOV MYS 1930 (BYKOV MYS)_1399	Other	Not Defined	BYKOV MYS (BYKOV MYS)_1399	72,0000	129,1167	12954	1399	0	1975 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12954
1931 PSMSL_CABO CRUZ_1910	Other	Not Defined	CABO CRUZ_1910	19,8333	77,7333	13231	1910	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13231
PSMSL_CABO SAN 1932 ANTONIO_1297	Other	Not Defined	CABO SAN ANTONIO_1297	21,9000	84,9000	12888	1297	214	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12888
PSMSL_CABO SAN 1933 LUCAS_1355	Other	Not Defined	CABO SAN LUCAS_1355	22,8833	109,9000	12925	1355	161	1973 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12925
1934 PSMSL_CADIZ II_209	Other	Not Defined	CADIZ II_209	36,5333	6,3167	12153	209	775	217 1880 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12153
1935 PSMSL_CADIZ III_985	Other	Not Defined	CADIZ III_985	36,5401	6,2862	12686	985	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12686
1936 PSMSL_CAGLIARI II_2089	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CAGLIARI II_2089	39,2102	9,1143	13307	2089	0	2001 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13307
1937 PSMSL_CAGLIARI_104	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CAGLIARI_104	39,2000	9,1667	12078	104	0	1896 - 1934	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12078
1938 PSMSL_CAIRNS_953	Other	Not Defined	CAIRNS_953	-	16,9167	145,7833	953	0	1960 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12667
1939 PSMSL_CALAIS_455	France	Shom - France	CALAIS_455	50,9694	1,8677	12305	455	0	1941 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12305
PSMSL_CALCUTTA 1940 (GARDEN REACH)_369	Other	Not Defined	CALCUTTA (GARDEN REACH)_369	22,5500	88,3000	12239	369	0	1932 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12239
1941 PSMSL_CALDERA_619	Other	Not Defined	CALDERA_619	-	27,0667	70,8333	619	174	32 1950 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12430
1942 PSMSL_CALETA PERCY_994	Other	Not Defined	CALETA PERCY_994	-	52,9000	70,2667	994	0	1961 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12692
PSMSL_CAMBRIDGE 1943 BAY_1132	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	CAMBRIDGE BAY_1132	69,1167	105,0667	12782	1132	0	1965 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12782
PSMSL_CAMBRIDGE 1944 II_1295	Other	Not Defined	CAMBRIDGE II_1295	38,5733	76,0683	12887	1295	0	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12887
1945 PSMSL_CAMBRIDGE_481	Other	Not Defined	CAMBRIDGE_481	38,5750	76,0717	12326	481	0	1942 - 1951	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12326
1946 PSMSL_CAMP COVE_549	Other	Not Defined	CAMP COVE_549	-	33,8333	151,2833	549	0	1948 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12376
PSMSL_CAMPBELL 1947 RIVER_1323	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	CAMPBELL RIVER_1323	50,0167	125,2333	12902	1323	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12902
1948 PSMSL_CANANEA_726	Other	Not Defined	CANANEA_726	-	25,0167	47,9333	726	350	89 1954 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12510
1949 PSMSL_CANAVIEIRAS_699	Other	Not Defined	CANAVIEIRAS_699	-	15,6667	38,9667	699	81	175 1952 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12491
PSMSL_CAP AUX 1950 MEULES_2031	Other	Not Defined	CAP AUX MEULES_2031	47,3789	61,8573	13268	2031	0	2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13268
PSMSL_CAPE 1951 FERGUSON_1492	Other	Not Defined	CAPE FERGUSON_1492	-	19,2773	147,0584	1492	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13010
PSMSL_CAPE 1952 LAMBERT_1328	Other	Not Defined	CAPE LAMBERT_1328	-	20,5880	117,1860	1328	220	314 1983 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12906

1953	PSMSL_CAPE MAY_1153	Other	Not Defined	CAPE MAY_1153	38,9683	-	74,9600	12796	1153	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12796
1954	PSMSL_CAPE PARRY_1282	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	CAPE PARRY_1282	70,1500	-	124,6667	12882	1282	0	1975 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12882
1955	PSMSL_CAPE ROBERTS ANTARCTICA_1763	Other	Not Defined	CAPE ROBERTS ANTARCTICA_1763	-	77,0339	163,1912	13146	1763	332	59 1990 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13146
1956	PSMSL_CAPE TOWN (GRANGER BAY)_1195	Other	Not Defined	CAPE TOWN (GRANGER BAY)_1195	-	33,9053	18,4347	12816	1195	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12816
1957	PSMSL_CAPO PASSERO_873	Other	Not Defined	CAPO PASSERO_873	36,6667	-	15,3000	12626	873	0	1957 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12626
1958	PSMSL_CARLOFORTE_2076	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CARLOFORTE_2076	39,1480	-	8,3095	13298	2076	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13298
1959	PSMSL_CARNARVON_1115	Other	Not Defined	CARNARVON_1115	-	24,8987	113,6510	12776	1115	52	1965 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12776
1960	PSMSL_CARTAGENA_1460	Other	Not Defined	CARTAGENA_1460	37,6000	-	0,9667	12996	1460	0	1977 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12996
1961	PSMSL_CARTAGENA_572	Other	Not Defined	CARTAGENA_572	10,4000	-	75,5500	12393	572	207	1949 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12393
1962	PSMSL_CASCAIS_52	Other	Not Defined	CASCAIS_52	38,6833	-	9,4167	12035	52	246	1882 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12035
1963	PSMSL_CASILDA II_2021	Other	Not Defined	CASILDA II_2021	21,7533	-	79,9917	13261	2021	0	1979 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13261
1964	PSMSL_CATANIA II_2094	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CATANIA II_2094	37,4981	-	15,0938	13311	2094	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13311
1965	PSMSL_CATANIA_102	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CATANIA_102	37,5000	-	15,1333	12076	102	0	1960 - 1971	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12076
1966	PSMSL_CATICLAN MALAY AKLAN_2172	Other	Not Defined	CATICLAN MALAY AKLAN_2172	11,9500	-	121,9333	13362	2172	1	115 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13362
1967	PSMSL_CEBU_394	Other	Not Defined	CEBU_394	10,3000	-	123,9167	12257	394	0	1935 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12257
1968	PSMSL_CEDAR KEY I_199	Other	Not Defined	CEDAR KEY I_199	29,1333	-	83,0333	12144	199	0	1914 - 1925	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12144
1969	PSMSL_CEDAR KEY II_428	Other	Not Defined	CEDAR KEY II_428	29,1350	-	83,0317	12282	428	0	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12282
1970	PSMSL_CENDERING_1592	Other	Not Defined	CENDERING_1592	5,2650	-	103,1867	13052	1592	293	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13052
1971	PSMSL_CEUTA_498	Other	Not Defined	CEUTA_498	35,8924	-	5,3159	12341	498	249	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12341
1972	PSMSL_CHABAHAR II_2228	Other	Not Defined	CHABAHAR II_2228	25,2958	-	60,6033	13382	2228	337	2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13382
1973	PSMSL_CHAMPERICO_120 1	Other	Not Defined	CHAMPERICO_1201	14,2833	-	91,9167	12821	1201	0	1967 - 1975	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12821
1974	PSMSL_CHAMPLAIN_1005	Other	Not Defined	CHAMPLAIN_1005	46,4333	-	72,4000	12702	1005	0	1962 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12702
1975	PSMSL_CHARCHANGA_149 6	Other	Not Defined	CHARCHANGA_1496	22,2167	-	91,0500	13014	1496	36	1979 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13014

1976	PSMSL_CHARLESTON I_234	Other	Not Defined	CHARLESTON I_234	32,7817	-	79,9250	12172	234	264	0	220	1921 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12172
1977	PSMSL_CHARLESTON IL_1269	Other	Not Defined	CHARLESTON IL_1269	43,3450	-	124,3217	12872	1269		0		1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12872
1978	PSMSL_CHARLOTTE AMALIE_1393	Other	Not Defined	CHARLOTTE AMALIE_1393	18,3350	-	64,9200	12950	1393		0		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12950
1979	PSMSL_CHARLOTTETOWN 427	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	CHARLOTTETOWN 427	46,2333	-	63,1167	12281	427		0		1911 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12281
1980	PSMSL_CHATHAM ISLAND_1920	Other	Not Defined	CHATHAM ISLAND_1920	43,9463	-	176,5612	13236	1920		128		2001 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13236
1981	PSMSL_CHENNAI / MADRAS_205	Other	Not Defined	CHENNAI / MADRAS_205	13,1000	-	80,3000	12149	205		34		1916 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12149
1982	PSMSL_CHERBOURG 467	France	Shom - France	CHERBOURG 467	49,6513	-	1,6356	12316	467		0		1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12316
1983	PSMSL_CHERRY POINT_1633	Other	Not Defined	CHERRY POINT_1633	48,8633	-	122,7567	13074	1633	290	0	305	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13074
1984	PSMSL_CHESAPEAKE BAY BR. TUN_1635	Other	Not Defined	CHESAPEAKE BAY BR. TUN_1635	36,9667	-	76,1133	13076	1635		0		1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13076
1985	PSMSL_CHETYREHSTOLBO VOI_650	Other	Not Defined	CHETYREHSTOLBO VOI_650	70,6333	-	162,4833	12453	650		0		1951 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12453
1986	PSMSL_CHI MA WAN, LANTAU ISLAND 987	Other	Not Defined	CHI MA WAN, LANTAU ISLAND 987	22,2333	-	114,0000	12688	987		0		1961 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12688
1987	PSMSL_CHICHUJIMA_1391	Other	Not Defined	CHICHUJIMA_1391	27,0833	-	142,1833	12948	1391		103		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12948
1988	PSMSL_CHIMBOTE_771	Other	Not Defined	CHIMBOTE_771	9,0833	-	78,6333	12547	771		0		1955 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12547
1989	PSMSL_CHINHAE 970	Other	Not Defined	CHINHAE 970	35,1500	-	128,6500	12675	970		0		1960 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12675
1990	PSMSL_CHITTAGONG A_2196	Other	Not Defined	CHITTAGONG A_2196	22,2467	-	91,8250	13370	2196		36		2007 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13370
1991	PSMSL_CHOSHI I_879	Other	Not Defined	CHOSHI I_879	35,7333	-	140,8667	12631	879		0		1957 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12631
1992	PSMSL_CHOSHI-GYOKO_1544	Other	Not Defined	CHOSHI-GYOKO_1544	35,7444	-	140,8583	13029	1544		0		1982 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13029
1993	PSMSL_CHRISTIANSTED HARBOUR 2118	Other	Not Defined	CHRISTIANSTED HARBOUR 2118	17,7500	-	64,7050	13332	2118		0		2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13332
1994	PSMSL_CHRISTMAS ISLAND IL_1371	Other	Not Defined	CHRISTMAS ISLAND IL_1371	1,9833	-	157,4833	12937	1371		146		1974 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12937
1995	PSMSL_CHRISTMAS ISLAND_801	Other	Not Defined	CHRISTMAS ISLAND_801	1,9833	-	157,4667	12568	801		146		1956 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12568
1996	PSMSL_CHUJADO 1588	Other	Not Defined	CHUJADO 1588	33,9617	-	126,3003	13048	1588		0		1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13048
1997	PSMSL_CHURCHILL_447	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	CHURCHILL_447	58,7667	-	94,1833	12300	447		0		1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12300
1998	PSMSL_CHUUK, MOEN ISLAND_528	Other	Not Defined	CHUUK, MOEN ISLAND_528	7,4467	-	151,8467	12363	528		116		1947 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12363

1999	PSMSL_CILACAP_B_2199	Other	Not Defined	CILACAP_B_2199	-	7,7517	109,0167	13371	2199	291	2007 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13371
2000	PSMSL_CIUADAD DEL CARMEN_796	Other	Not Defined	CIUDAD DEL CARMEN_796	-	18,6333	91,8500	12565	796	0	1956 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12565
2001	PSMSL_CIUADAD MADERO_1020	Other	Not Defined	CIUDAD MADERO_1020	-	22,2500	97,8000	12711	1020	0	1962 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12711
2002	PSMSL_CIVITAVECCHIA_106	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CIVITAVECCHIA_106	-	42,0500	11,8167	12080	106	0	1896 - 1922	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12080
2003	PSMSL_CLEARWATER BEACH_1638	Other	Not Defined	CLEARWATER BEACH_1638	-	27,9783	82,8317	13079	1638	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13079
2004	PSMSL_COATZACOALCOS_692	Other	Not Defined	COATZACOALCOS_692	-	18,1500	94,4167	12487	692	0	1952 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12487
2005	PSMSL_COCHIN (WILLINGDON IS.)_438	Other	Not Defined	COCHIN (WILLINGDON IS.)_438	-	9,9667	76,2667	12292	438	60	287 1939 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12292
2006	PSMSL_COCO SOLO_1530	Other	Not Defined	COCO SOLO_1530	-	9,3667	79,8833	13024	1530	280	195 1991 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13024
2007	PSMSL_COCOS ISLAND (HOME IS.)_983	Other	Not Defined	COCOS ISLAND (HOME IS.)_983	-	12,1167	96,8944	12684	983	46	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12684
2008	PSMSL_COFF'S HARBOUR L_799	Other	Not Defined	COFF'S HARBOUR L_799	-	30,3167	153,0833	12567	799	13	145 1956 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12567
2009	PSMSL_COLONIA_433	Other	Not Defined	COLONIA_433	-	34,4833	57,8500	12287	433	0	1954 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12287
2010	PSMSL_COMODORO RIVADAVIA_181	Other	Not Defined	COMODORO RIVADAVIA_181	-	45,8667	67,4833	12133	181	0	1959 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12133
2011	PSMSL_COMOX_630	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	COMOX_630	-	49,6667	124,9167	12435	630	0	1950 - 1953	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12435
2012	PSMSL_CONCARNEAU_1301	France	Shom - France	CONCARNEAU_1301	-	47,8737	3,9074	12891	1301	0	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12891
2013	PSMSL_CONSTANTZA_379	Romania	NIMRD - National Institute for Marine Research and Development - Romania	CONSTANTZA_379	-	44,1667	28,6667	12246	379	0	1933 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12246
2014	PSMSL_CORDOVA_566	Other	Not Defined	CORDOVA_566	-	60,5583	145,7517	12388	566	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12388
2015	PSMSL_CORFU (KERKYRA)_1933	Greece	HCMR - Hellenic Center Marine Research	CORFU (KERKYRA)_1933	-	39,6282	19,9053	13245	1933	16	138 2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13245
2016	PSMSL_CORPUS CHRISTI, GULF MEXICO, TX_1903	Other	Not Defined	CORPUS CHRISTI, GULF MEXICO, TX_1903	-	27,5833	97,2167	13228	1903	819	233 1998 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13228
2017	PSMSL_CORRAL_1057	Other	Not Defined	CORRAL_1057	-	39,8667	73,4333	12730	1057	0	1963 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12730
2018	PSMSL_COX'S BAZAAR_1476	Other	Not Defined	COX'S BAZAAR_1476	-	21,4500	91,8333	13004	1476	0	1978 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13004
2019	PSMSL_CRESCENT CITY_378	Other	Not Defined	CRESCENT CITY_378	-	41,7450	124,1817	12245	378	0	1933 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12245
2020	PSMSL_CRISTOBAL_169	Other	Not Defined	CRISTOBAL_169	-	9,3500	79,9167	12124	169	208	1909 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12124
2021	PSMSL_CROMER_1632	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	CROMER_1632	-	52,9344	1,3016	13073	1632	0	1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13073

2022	PSMSL_CULEBRA_2120	Other	Not Defined	CULEBRA_2120	18,3017	-	65,3033	13334	2120	0	2005 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13334	
2023	PSMSL_CURRIMAO ILOCOS NORTE_2173	Other	Not Defined	CURRIMAO ILOCOS NORTE_2173	17,9833	-	120,4833	13363	2173	11	146 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13363	
2024	PSMSL_CUTLER II_1524	Other	Not Defined	CUTLER II_1524	44,6417	-	67,2967	13021	1524	833	224 1981 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13021	
2025	PSMSL_CUTLER 1081	Other	Not Defined	CUTLER 1081	44,6500	-	67,2167	12747	1081	0	1964 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12747	
2026	PSMSL_CUXHAVEN 2_7	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	CUXHAVEN 2_7	53,8667	-	8,7167	11997	7	284	1843 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11997	
2027	PSMSL_DAEHEUKSANDO_1 489	Other	Not Defined	DAEHEUKSANDO_1489	34,6839	-	125,4364	13007	1489	0	1979 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13007	
2028	PSMSL_DAKAR 2 1816	Other	Not Defined	DAKAR 2 1816	14,6833	-	17,4167	13181	1816	253	1992 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13181	
2029	PSMSL_DAKAR_476	Other	Not Defined	DAKAR_476	14,6333	-	17,4500	12324	476	253	1942 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12324	
2030	PSMSL_DALHOUSIE_1358	Other	Not Defined	DALHOUSIE_1358	48,0667	-	66,3833	12928	1358	0	1973 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12928	
2031	PSMSL_DALIAN_723	Other	Not Defined	DALIAN_723	38,8667	-	121,6833	12507	723	79	1954 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12507	
2032	PSMSL_DANANG 1475	Other	Not Defined	DANANG 1475	16,1000	-	108,2167	13003	1475	82	182 1978 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13003	
2033	PSMSL_DARWIN_935	Other	Not Defined	DARWIN_935	-	-	12,4718	130,8459	12657	935	62	1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12657
2034	PSMSL_DAUGAVGRIVA_37	Other	Not Defined	DAUGAVGRIVA_37	57,0500	-	24,0333	12024	37	0	1872 - 1938	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12024	
2035	PSMSL_DAUPHIN ISLAND 1156	Other	Not Defined	DAUPHIN ISLAND 1156	30,2500	-	88,0750	12799	1156	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12799	
2036	PSMSL_DAVAO, DAVAO GULF_537	Other	Not Defined	DAVAO, DAVAO GULF_537	7,0833	-	125,6333	12365	537	71	1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12365	
2037	PSMSL_DAYTONA BEACH SHORES_1182	Other	Not Defined	DAYTONA BEACH SHORES_1182	29,1467	-	80,9633	12807	1182	0	1966 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12807	
2038	PSMSL_DAYTONA BEACH_270	Other	Not Defined	DAYTONA BEACH_270	29,2333	-	81,0000	12194	270	294	241 1925 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12194	
2039	PSMSL_DELFZIJL 24	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DELFZIJL 24	53,3264	-	6,9331	12013	24	0	1865 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12013	
2040	PSMSL_DEN HELDER_23	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	DEN HELDER_23	52,9644	-	4,7450	12012	23	0	1865 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12012	
2041	PSMSL_DEPOE BAY_1541	Other	Not Defined	DEPOE BAY_1541	44,8100	-	124,0567	13027	1541	0	1981 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13027	
2042	PSMSL_DESCHAILLONS_20 1	Other	Not Defined	DESCHAILLONS 201	46,5667	-	72,1000	12145	201	0	1915 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12145	
2043	PSMSL_DEVONPORT_1118	Other	Not Defined	DEVONPORT_1118	-	-	41,1847	146,3624	12778	1118	0	1989 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12778
2044	PSMSL_DEVONPORT_982	Other	Not Defined	DEVONPORT_982	50,3684	-	4,1853	12683	982	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12683	

PSMSL_DIAMOND 2045 HARBOUR_543	Other	Not Defined	DIAMOND HARBOUR_543	22,2000	88,1667	12371	543	0	1948 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12371
PSMSL_DIEGO GARCIA 2046 D_2190	Other	Not Defined	DIEGO GARCIA D_2190	7,2900	72,3933	13368	2190	26	2003 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13368
PSMSL_DIEGO GARCIA- 2047 C_1740	Other	Not Defined	DIEGO GARCIA-C_1740	7,2833	72,4000	13133	1740	26	1988 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13133
PSMSL_DIEGO 2048 RAMIREZ 1785	Other	Not Defined	DIEGO RAMIREZ 1785	56,5000	68,7167	13157	1785	0	1991 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13157
PSMSL_DIEPPE_474	France	Shom - France	DIEPPE_474	49,9291	1,0838	12322	474	0	1954 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12322
PSMSL_DIGBY_1230	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	DIGBY_1230	44,6333	65,7500	12838	1230	0	1968 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12838
PSMSL_DIKSON 611	Other	Not Defined	DIKSON 611	73,5000	80,4000	12422	611	312	1950 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12422
PSMSL_DONGFANG_1407	Other	Not Defined	DONGFANG_1407	19,1000	108,6167	12960	1407	0	1983 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12960
PSMSL_DOUGLAS_435	Other	Not Defined	DOUGLAS_435	54,1500	4,4667	12289	435	0	1938 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12289
PSMSL_DOVER_255	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	DOVER_255	51,1144	1,3227	12185	255	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12185
PSMSL_DRAGHALLAN 122	Other	Not Defined	DRAGHALLAN 122	62,3667	17,5333	12091	122	0	1898 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12091
PSMSL_DUBLAT (SAUGOR IS.)_49	Other	Not Defined	DUBLAT (SAUGOR IS.)_49	21,6333	88,1333	12033	49	0	1881 - 1886	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12033
PSMSL_DUBLIN_432	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	DUBLIN_432	53,3500	6,2167	12286	432	0	1938 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12286
PSMSL_DUBROVNIK 760	Other	Not Defined	DUBROVNIK 760	42,6583	18,0633	12537	760	0	1956 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12537
PSMSL_DUCK PIER OUTSIDE_1636	Other	Not Defined	DUCK PIER OUTSIDE_1636	36,1833	75,7467	13077	1636	219	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13077
PSMSL_DUNAI (DUNAI OSTROV)_640	Other	Not Defined	DUNAI (DUNAI OSTROV)_640	73,9333	124,5000	12443	640	0	1951 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12443
PSMSL_DUNBAR_190	Other	Not Defined	DUNBAR_190	56,0000	2,5167	12138	190	0	1913 - 1950	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12138
PSMSL_DUNEDIN II 136	Other	Not Defined	DUNEDIN II 136	45,8787	170,5134	12100	136	0	1900 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12100
PSMSL_DUNKERQUE_468	France	Shom - France	DUNKERQUE_468	51,0481	2,3667	12317	468	0	1942 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12317
PSMSL_DURBAN_284	Other	Not Defined	DURBAN_284	29,8742	31,0508	12196	284	147	30 1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12196
PSMSL_DUTCH HARBOR 390	Other	Not Defined	DUTCH HARBOR 390	53,9000	166,5333	12254	390	102	1934 - 1955	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12254
PSMSL_DZAOUZI_1642	Other	Not Defined	DZAOUZI_1642	12,7821	45,2582	13083	1642	96	2008 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13083
PSMSL_EAST LONDON_1192	Other	Not Defined	EAST LONDON_1192	33,0272	27,9317	12813	1192	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12813

PSMSL_EASTER ISLAND-2068_D_1462	Other	Not Defined	EASTER ISLAND-D_1462	-	27,1500	-	109,4500	12997	1462	137	1977 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12997
PSMSL_EASTER ISLAND-2069_E_1272	Other	Not Defined	EASTER ISLAND-E_1272	-	27,1547	-	109,4728	12874	1272	137	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12874
2070 PSMSL_EASTPORT_332	Other	Not Defined	EASTPORT_332	-	44,9033	-	66,9817	12221	332	0	1929 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12221
2071 PSMSL_EDEN 833	Germany	WISOE - Waterways and Shipping Board Emden - Germany	EDEN 833	-	37,0737	-	149,9077	12597	833	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12597
2072 PSMSL_EDITHBURG_516	Other	Not Defined	EDITHBURG_516	-	35,0833	-	137,7500	12352	516	0	1946 - 1952	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12352
2073 PSMSL_EILAT NORTH_2148	Other	Not Defined	EILAT NORTH_2148	-	29,5447	-	34,9522	13351	2148	0	2010 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13351
2074 PSMSL_EILAT SOUTH 2149	Other	Not Defined	EILAT SOUTH 2149	-	29,5019	-	34,9178	13352	2149	0	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13352
2075 PSMSL_ENEWETOK_665	Other	Not Defined	ENEWETOK_665	-	11,3667	-	162,3500	12466	665	0	1951 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12466
PSMSL_ENGLISH BAY 2076 (ASCENSION ISLAND)_1831	Other	Not Defined	ENGLISH BAY (ASCENSION ISLAND)_1831	-	7,8928	-	14,3857	13187	1831	263	1993 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13187
2077 PSMSL_ENSENADA_795	Other	Not Defined	ENSENADA_795	-	31,8500	-	116,6333	12564	795	0	1956 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12564
2078 PSMSL_ERDEK 1598	Other	Not Defined	ERDEK 1598	-	40,3833	-	27,8500	13058	1598	0	1984 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13058
2079 PSMSL_ERDEMLI_2009	Other	Not Defined	ERDEMLI_2009	-	36,5667	-	34,2500	13256	2009	0	2003 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13256
2080 PSMSL_ESASHI_1605	Other	Not Defined	ESASHI_1605	-	41,8667	-	140,1333	13062	1605	0	1984 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13062
2081 PSMSL_ESBJERG 80	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	ESBJERG 80	-	55,4608	-	8,4411	12056	80	0	1889 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12056
2082 PSMSL_ESPERANCE_1114	Other	Not Defined	ESPERANCE_1114	-	33,8709	-	121,8954	12775	1114	54	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12775
PSMSL_ESPERANZA, 2083 VIEQUES_2209	Other	Not Defined	ESPERANZA, VIEQUES_2209	-	18,0933	-	65,4717	13373	2209	2	113 2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13373
PSMSL_EUGENE 2084 ISLAND_440	Other	Not Defined	EUGENE ISLAND_440	-	29,3717	-	91,3850	12294	440	804	321 1939 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12294
2085 PSMSL_EVANS HEAD 1229	Other	Not Defined	EVANS HEAD 1229	-	29,1167	-	153,4333	12837	1229	0	1968 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12837
2086 PSMSL_EVENSKJAER_531	Other	Not Defined	EVENSKJAER_531	-	68,5833	-	16,5500	12364	531	0	1947 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12364
2087 PSMSL_EXMOUTH_1762	Other	Not Defined	EXMOUTH_1762	-	21,9549	-	114,1409	13145	1762	0	1998 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13145
2088 PSMSL_FAMAGUSTA 436	Other	Not Defined	FAMAGUSTA 436	-	35,1167	-	33,9500	12290	436	0	1938 - 1940	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12290
2089 PSMSL_FANNING-B_1361	Other	Not Defined	FANNING-B_1361	-	3,9000	-	159,3833	12929	1361	0	1973 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12929
PSMSL_FEDOROVA 2090 (CHELUSKIN MYS)_601	Other	Not Defined	FEDOROVA (CHELUSKIN MYS)_601	-	77,7167	-	104,3000	12412	601	0	1950 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12412

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

2091	PSMSL_FELIXSTOWE_214	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	FELIXSTOWE_214	51,9577	1,3466	12157	214	542	0	156	1980 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12157	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/214.php	
2092	PSMSL_FERNANDINA BEACH_112	Other	Not Defined	FERNANDINA BEACH_112	30,6717	- 81,4650	12085	112		0		1897 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12085	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/112.php	
2093	PSMSL_FERROL_2_2053	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	FERROL_2_2053	43,4762	- 8,2485	13278	2053		0		2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13278	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2053.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2094	PSMSL_FISHGUARD_939	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	FISHGUARD_939	52,0132	- 4,9838	12661	939		0		1974 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12661	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/939.php	
2095	PSMSL_FOGLO / DEGERBY_249	Other	Not Defined	FOGLO / DEGERBY_249	60,0319	20,3848	12183	249		0		1923 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12183	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/249.php	
2096	PSMSL_FORCADOS_389	Other	Not Defined	FORCADOS_389	5,3500	5,3500	12253	389		0		1934 - 1975	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12253	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/389.php	
2097	PSMSL_FORMENTERA_2060	Other	Not Defined	FORMENTERA_2060	38,7347	1,4190	13285	2060		0		2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13285	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2060.php	
2098	PSMSL_FORSMARK_2103	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	FORSMARK_2103	60,4086	18,2108	13320	2103		0		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13320	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2103.php	
2099	PSMSL_FORT MYERS_1106	Other	Not Defined	FORT MYERS_1106	26,6467	- 81,8700	12767	1106		0		1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12767	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1106.php	
2100	PSMSL_FORT PHRACHULA CHOMKLAO (POM PHRACHUN)_444	Other	Not Defined	FORT PHRACHULA CHOMKLAO (POM PHRACHUN)_444	13,5500	100,5833	12297	444		0		1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12297	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/444.php	
2101	PSMSL_FORT PULASKI_395	Other	Not Defined	FORT PULASKI_395	32,0333	- 80,9017	12258	395	560	289	150	1935 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12258	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/395.php	
2102	PSMSL_FORTALEZA_559	Other	Not Defined	FORTALEZA_559	- 3,7167	- 38,4833	12382	559	41	336	102	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12382	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/559.php	
2103	PSMSL_FORT-DE-FRANCE II_1942	France	Shom - France	FORT-DE-FRANCE II_1942	14,6015	- 61,0632	13251	1942		338		1976 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13251	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1942.php	
2104	PSMSL_FRANKLIN HARBOR_402	Other	Not Defined	FRANKLIN HARBOR_402	- 33,6833	136,9333	12264	402		0		1935 - 1939	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12264	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/402.php	
2105	PSMSL_FREDERICIA_81	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	FREDERICIA_81	55,5608	9,7544	12057	81	333	0	57	1889 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12057	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/81.php	
2106	PSMSL_FREDERIKSHAVN_91	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	FREDERIKSHAVN_91	57,4364	10,5489	12067	91		0		1894 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12067	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/91.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2107	PSMSL_FREEPORT_725	Other	Not Defined	FREEPORT_725	28,9483	- 95,3083	12509	725		0		1954 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12509	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/725.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2108	PSMSL_FREMANTLE_111	Other	Not Defined	FREMANTLE_111	- 32,0656	115,7481	12084	111		53		1897 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12084	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/111.php	
2109	PSMSL_FRENCH FRIGATE SHOALS B_2192	Other	Not Defined	FRENCH FRIGATE SHOALS B_2192	23,8683	- 166,2883	13369	2192		107		2007 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13369	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2192.php	
2110	PSMSL_FRENCH FRIGATE SHOALS_1372	Other	Not Defined	FRENCH FRIGATE SHOALS_1372	23,8667	- 166,2833	12938	1372		107		1974 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12938	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1372.php	
2111	PSMSL_FRIDAY HARBOR (OCEAN. LABS.)_384	Other	Not Defined	FRIDAY HARBOR (OCEAN. LABS.)_384	48,5467	- 123,0100	12249	384		0		1934 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12249	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/384.php	
2112	PSMSL_FUERTEVENTURA_2048	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	FUERTEVENTURA_2048	28,4925	- 13,8582	13274	2048		0		2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13274	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2048.php	
2113	PSMSL_FUKUE_1101	Other	Not Defined	FUKUE_1101	32,6961	128,8494	12762	1101		0		1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12762	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1101.php	

PSMSL_FULFORD 2114 HARBOUR_688	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	FULFORD HARBOUR_688	48,7667	-	123,4500	12484	688	0	1952 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12484	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/688.php	
2115 PSMSL_FUNAFUTI_1839	Other	Not Defined	FUNAFUTI_1839	8,5025	-	179,1952	13194	1839	121	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13194	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1839.php	
2116 PSMSL_FUNAFUTI_1452	Other	Not Defined	FUNAFUTI_1452	8,5333	-	179,2167	12990	1452	121	1977 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12990	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1452.php	
2117 PSMSL_FUNCHAL II 2024	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	FUNCHAL II 2024	32,6511	-	17,1178	13262	2024	250	2003 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13262	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2024.php	
2118 PSMSL_FUNCHAL_1030	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	FUNCHAL_1030	32,6440	-	16,9131	12717	1030	250	1963 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12717	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1030.php	
PSMSL_FURUOGRUND_20 2119 3	Sweden	Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	FURUOGRUND_203	64,9158	-	21,2306	12147	203	57	108 1916 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12147	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/203.php	
2120 PSMSL_FYNHAV 1197	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	FYNHAV 1197	54,9950	-	9,9869	12818	1197	221	0 268 1967 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12818	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1197.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou d221.nc
2121 PSMSL_GADEOKDO_1445	Other	Not Defined	GADEOKDO_1445	35,0247	-	128,8108	12983	1445	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12983	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1445.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou d.nc
PSMSL_GALVESTON I, 2122 PLEASURE PIER, TX_828	Other	Not Defined	GALVESTON I, PLEASURE PIER, TX_828	29,2850	-	94,7883	12592	828	217	1957 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12592	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/828.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
PSMSL_GALVESTON II, PIER 2123 21, TX_161	Other	Not Defined	GALVESTON II, PIER 21, TX_161	29,3100	-	94,7933	12116	161	217	1908 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12116	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/161.php	
2124 PSMSL_GAN II 1707	Other	Not Defined	GAN II 1707	0,6833	-	73,1500	13116	1707	27	1987 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13116	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1707.php	
2125 PSMSL_GANDIA_2058	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	GANDIA_2058	38,9952	-	0,1514	13283	2058	0	2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13283	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2058.php	
2126 PSMSL_GANGRA_1369	Other	Not Defined	GANGRA_1369	21,9500	-	88,0167	12935	1369	0	1974 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12935	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1369.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou d.nc
2127 PSMSL_GARIBALDI II 2214	Other	Not Defined	GARIBALDI II 2214	45,5550	-	123,9183	13374	2214	0	2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13374	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2214.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou rly/d.nc
2128 PSMSL_GARIBALDI_1285	Other	Not Defined	GARIBALDI_1285	45,5533	-	123,9183	12884	1285	0	1970 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12884	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1285.php	
2129 PSMSL_GAZENICA_1577	Other	Not Defined	GAZENICA_1577	44,0833	-	15,2667	13042	1577	0	1983 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13042	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1577.php	
PSMSL_GDANSK/NOWY 2130 PORT_64	Poland	IMWMMB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland	GDANSK/NOWY PORT_64	54,4000	-	18,6833	12042	64	0	1951 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12042	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/64.php	
2131 PSMSL_GDYNIA 364	Poland	IMWMMB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland	GDYNIA 364	54,5333	-	18,5500	12234	364	0	1931 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12234	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/364.php	
2132 PSMSL_GEDSER_120	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	GEDSER_120	54,5728	-	11,9256	12089	120	0	1892 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12089	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/120.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hou d.nc
PSMSL_GEIBERGA 2133 (GEIBERGA OSTROV)_648	Other	Not Defined	GEIBERGA (GEIBERGA OSTROV)_648	77,6000	-	101,5167	12451	648	0	1951 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12451	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/648.php	
PSMSL_GENERAL 2134 DYNAMICS PIER 1721	Other	Not Defined	GENERAL DYNAMICS PIER 1721	33,0167	-	79,9167	13127	1721	0	1987 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13127	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1721.php	
2135 PSMSL_GENOVA II_2090	Italy	ISPRa - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	GENOVA II_2090	44,4101	-	8,9255	13308	2090	0	2001 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13308	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2090.php	
2136 PSMSL_GENOVA_59	Italy	ISPRa - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	GENOVA_59	44,4000	-	8,9000	12038	59	0	1884 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12038	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/59.php	

2137	PSMSL_GEOMUNDO_1546	Other	Not Defined	GEOMUNDO_1546	34,0283	127,3092	13031	1546	0	1982 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13031	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1546.php	
2138	PSMSL_GERALDTON_1031	Other	Not Defined	GERALDTON_1031	28,7760	114,6019	12718	1031	281	194 1993 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12718	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1031.php	
2139	PSMSL_GETING_1703	Other	Not Defined	GETING_1703	6,2264	102,1067	13112	1703	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13112	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1703.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2140	PSMSL_GIBARA_563	Other	Not Defined	GIBARA_563	21,1083	76,1250	12385	563	276	223 1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12385	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/563.php	
2141	PSMSL_GIBALTAR_981	United Kingdom	POL - Proudman Oceanographic Laboratory - United Kingdom	GIBALTAR_981	36,1483	5,3649	12682	981	248	1961 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12682	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/981.php	
2142	PSMSL_GIJON II_1871	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	GIJON II_1871	43,5580	5,6984	13211	1871	0	1996 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13211	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1871.php	
2143	PSMSL_GINGERVILLE CREEK 1203	Other	Not Defined	GINGERVILLE CREEK 1203	38,9583	76,5550	12822	1203	293	236 1967 - 1973	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12822	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1203.php	
2144	PSMSL_GIRNE_1911	Other	Not Defined	GIRNE_1911	35,3500	33,3333	13232	1911	0	2000 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13232	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1911.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2145	PSMSL_GISBORNE_1613	Other	Not Defined	GISBORNE_1613	38,6755	178,0224	13066	1613	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13066	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1613.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2146	PSMSL_GLADSTONE_825	Other	Not Defined	GLADSTONE_825	23,8538	151,3137	12589	825	0	1978 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12589	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/825.php	
2147	PSMSL_GLOUCESTER POINT 597	Other	Not Defined	GLOUCESTER POINT 597	37,2467	76,5000	12408	597	0	1950 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12408	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/597.php	
2148	PSMSL_GOLD COAST SEAWAY 2_1704	Other	Not Defined	GOLD COAST SEAWAY 2_1704	27,9500	153,4167	13113	1704	0	1987 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13113	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1704.php	
2149	PSMSL_GOLOMIANYI (GOLOMIANYI OSTROV)_729	Other	Not Defined	GOLOMIANYI (GOLOMIANYI OSTROV)_729	79,5500	90,6167	12513	729	0	1954 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12513	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/729.php	
2150	PSMSL_GOODS ISLAND 1368	Other	Not Defined	GOODS ISLAND 1368	10,5617	142,1517	12934	1368	0	1989 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12934	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1368.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2151	PSMSL_GOTEBORG - KLIPPAN_74	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GOTEBORG - KLIPPAN_74	57,6833	11,9000	12051	74	0	1959 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12051	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/74.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2152	PSMSL_GOTEBORG - TORSHAMNEN_1236	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GOTEBORG - TORSHAMNEN_1236	57,6847	11,7906	12842	1236	233	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12842	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1236.php	
2153	PSMSL_GOTEBORG-RINGON_2133	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	GOTEBORG-RINGON_2133	57,7167	11,9667	13345	2133	0	1887 - 1958	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13345	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2133.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2154	PSMSL_GRANADILLA 2050	Other	Not Defined	GRANADILLA 2050	28,0853	16,4896	13276	2050	0	2003 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13276	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2050.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2155	PSMSL_GRAND ISLE_526	Other	Not Defined	GRAND ISLE_526	29,2633	89,9567	12361	526	0	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12361	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/526.php	
2156	PSMSL_GRAND PORT_930	Other	Not Defined	GRAND PORT_930	20,3667	57,7500	12654	930	0	1958 - 1960	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12654	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/930.php	
2157	PSMSL_GREYMOUTH 993	Other	Not Defined	GREYMOUTH 993	42,4500	171,2000	12691	993	0	1961 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12691	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/993.php	
2158	PSMSL_GRINDAVIK_877	Other	Not Defined	GRINDAVIK_877	63,8333	22,4333	12630	877	288	229 1957 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12630	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/877.php	
2159	PSMSL_GRINDSTONE_1143	Other	Not Defined	GRINDSTONE_1143	47,3833	61,8667	12788	1143	0	1965 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12788	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1143.php	

2160	PSMSL_GRONDINES_387	Other	Not Defined	GRONDINES_387	46,5833	-	72,0333	12252	387	0	1934 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12252	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/387.php	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2161	PSMSL_GRONSKAR_77	Other	Not Defined	GRONSKAR_77	59,2833	-	19,0333	12053	77	824	205 1888 - 1932	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12053	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/77.php	
2162	PSMSL_GUADALUPE ISLAND II_1413	Other	Not Defined	GUADALUPE ISLAND II_1413	28,8833	-	118,3000	12964	1413	160	1977 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12964	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1413.php	
2163	PSMSL_GUANTANAMO BAY 418	Other	Not Defined	GUANTANAMO BAY 418	19,9067	-	75,1467	12276	418	181	13 1937 - 1971	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12276	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/418.php	
2164	PSMSL_GUAYMAS_693	Other	Not Defined	GUAYMAS_693	27,9167	-	110,9000	12488	693	0	1952 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12488	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/693.php	
2165	PSMSL_GUIRIA_1053	Other	Not Defined	GUIRIA_1053	10,5667	-	62,2833	12728	1053	0	1963 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12728	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1053.php	
2166	PSMSL_GUNSAN (OUTER PORT) 1527	Other	Not Defined	GUNSAN (OUTER PORT) 1527	35,9756	-	126,5633	13023	1527	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13023	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1527.php	
2167	PSMSL_HACHINOHE I_460	Other	Not Defined	HACHINOHE I_460	40,5333	-	141,5333	12310	460	0	1941 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12310	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/460.php	
2168	PSMSL_HACHINOHE II_1266	Other	Not Defined	HACHINOHE II_1266	40,5317	-	141,5278	12869	1266	0	1970 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12869	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1266.php	
2169	PSMSL_HADERA_1797	Other	Not Defined	HADERA_1797	32,4704	-	34,8632	13165	1797	80	1992 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13165	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1797.php	http://uhsic.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
2170	PSMSL_HAGI 1306	Other	Not Defined	HAGI 1306	34,4333	-	131,4167	12894	1306	0	1971 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12894	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1306.php	
2171	PSMSL_HAIFA II_2221	Other	Not Defined	HAIFA II_2221	32,8289	-	34,9907	13381	2221	349	325 2013 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13381	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2221.php	
2172	PSMSL_HAIKOU_1428	Other	Not Defined	HAIKOU_1428	20,0167	-	110,2833	12973	1428	289	248 1976 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12973	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1428.php	
2173	PSMSL_HAKATA 1094	Other	Not Defined	HAKATA 1094	33,6189	-	130,4078	12755	1094	830	243 1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12755	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1094.php	
2174	PSMSL_HAKODATE I_813	Other	Not Defined	HAKODATE I_813	41,7817	-	140,7247	12577	813	88	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12577	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/813.php	
2175	PSMSL_HAKODATE II_671	Other	Not Defined	HAKODATE II_671	41,7667	-	140,7167	12471	671	88	1955 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12471	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/671.php	
2176	PSMSL_HALDIA_1270	Other	Not Defined	HALDIA_1270	22,0333	-	88,1000	12873	1270	0	1970 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12873	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1270.php	
2177	PSMSL_HALIFAX 96	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	HALIFAX 96	44,6667	-	63,5833	12070	96	826	341 1895 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12070	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/96.php	
2178	PSMSL_HAMADA II_1585	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	HAMADA II_1585	34,8972	-	132,0661	13045	1585	326	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13045	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1585.php	
2179	PSMSL_HAMINA_315	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	HAMINA_315	60,5628	-	27,1792	12211	315	0	1928 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12211	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/315.php	
2180	PSMSL_HAMMERFEST 758	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HAMMERFEST 758	70,6646	-	23,6832	12535	758	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12535	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/758.php	
2181	PSMSL_HANASAKI II_1442	Other	Not Defined	HANASAKI II_1442	43,2781	-	145,5678	12980	1442	601	185 1983 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12980	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1442.php	
2182	PSMSL_HANASAKI_139	Other	Not Defined	HANASAKI_139	43,2833	-	145,5833	12103	139	175	53 1957 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12103	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/139.php	

PSMSL_HANKO / 2183 HANGO_71	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	HANKO / HANGO_71	59,8229	22,9766	12048	71	0	1887 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12048	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/71.php
2184 PSMSL_HANSTHOLM_703	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	HANSTHOLM_703	57,1189	8,5956	12493	703	731	191 1953 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12493	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/703.php
2185 PSMSL_HARLINGEN_25	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands	HARLINGEN_25	53,1756	5,4094	12014	25	0	1865 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12014	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/25.php
PSMSL_HARRINGTON 2186 HBR 176	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	HARRINGTON HBR 176	50,5000	59,4833	12130	176	0	1910 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12130	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/176.php
2187 PSMSL_HARSTAD_681	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HARSTAD_681	68,8013	16,5482	12478	681	0	1952 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12478	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/681.php
2188 PSMSL_HARWICH_742	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	HARWICH_742	51,9480	1,2921	12523	742	0	1960 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12523	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/742.php
PSMSL_HAULOVER 2189 PIER 1717	Other	Not Defined	HAULOVER PIER 1717	25,9033	80,1200	13123	1717	0	1987 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13123	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1717.php
2190 PSMSL_HAY POINT_1246	Other	Not Defined	HAY POINT_1246	21,2833	149,3000	12852	1246	0	1969 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12852	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1246.php
2191 PSMSL_HEIMSJO_313	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HEIMSJO_313	63,4252	9,1015	12209	313	0	1928 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12209	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/313.php
2192 PSMSL_HEL_146	Other	Not Defined	HEL_146	54,6000	18,8000	12108	146	0	1901 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12108	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/146.php
2193 PSMSL_HELGEROA 1113	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HELGEROA 1113	58,9952	9,8564	12774	1113	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12774	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1113.php
2194 PSMSL_HEUGMAN_231	Other	Not Defined	HEUGMAN_231	60,2000	19,3000	12170	231	0	1920 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12170	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/231.php
2195 PSMSL_HELSINKI_14	Other	Not Defined	HELSINKI_14	60,1536	24,9562	12004	14	0	1879 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12004	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/14.php
2196 PSMSL_HERMANUS 928	Other	Not Defined	HERMANUS 928	34,4333	19,2333	12653	928	0	1958 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12653	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/928.php
2197 PSMSL_HEYSHAM_936	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	HEYSHAM_936	54,0318	2,9203	12658	936	0	1960 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12658	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/936.php
2198 PSMSL_HIERRO_2051	Other	Not Defined	HIERRO_2051	27,7844	17,9016	13277	2051	0	2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13277	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/2051.php
2199 PSMSL_HILLARYS_1761	Other	Not Defined	HILLARYS_1761	31,8256	115,7386	13144	1761	0	1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13144	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1761.php
PSMSL_HILO, HAWAII 2200 ISLAND 300	Other	Not Defined	HILO, HAWAII ISLAND 300	19,7300	155,0550	12202	300	287	1927 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12202	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/300.php
PSMSL_HINKLEY 2201 POINT_1758	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	HINKLEY POINT_1758	51,2106	3,1313	13141	1758	0	1990 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13141	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1758.php
PSMSL_HIRON 2202 POINT_1451	Other	Not Defined	HIRON POINT_1451	21,7833	89,4667	12989	1451	0	1983 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12989	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1451.php
2203 PSMSL_HIROSIMA 1028	Other	Not Defined	HIROSIMA 1028	34,3531	132,4647	12715	1028	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12715	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1028.php
2204 PSMSL_HIRTSHALS_89	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	HIRTSHALS_89	57,5956	9,9639	12065	89	0	1892 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12065	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/89.php
PSMSL_HOEK VAN 2205 HOLLAND_22	Other	Not Defined	HOEK VAN HOLLAND_22	51,9775	4,1200	12011	22	0	1864 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12011	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/22.php

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<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

2206	PSMSL_HOLYHEAD_5	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	HOLYHEAD_5	53,3139	-	4,6204	11996	5	0	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11996	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/5.php
2207	PSMSL_HONDAU_841	Other	Not Defined	HONDAU_841	20,6667	-	106,8000	12604	841	0	1957 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12604	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/841.php
2208	PSMSL_HONIARA_II_1373	Other	Not Defined	HONIARA_II_1373	-	9,4333	159,9500	12939	1373	66	1974 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12939	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1373.php
2209	PSMSL_HONIARA-B_1861	Other	Not Defined	HONIARA-B_1861	-	9,4289	159,9554	13209	1861	5	112 1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13209	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1861.php
2210	PSMSL_HONNGU_1003	Other	Not Defined	HONNGU_1003	18,8000	-	105,7667	12700	1003	0	1962 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12700	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1003.php
2211	PSMSL_HONNINGSVAG_1267	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	HONNINGSVAG_1267	70,9803	-	25,9727	12870	1267	0	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12870	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1267.php
2212	PSMSL_HONOLULU_155	Other	Not Defined	HONOLULU_155	21,3067	-	157,8667	12112	155	108	1905 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12112	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/155.php
2213	PSMSL_HORNBAEK_119	Other	Not Defined	HORNBAEK_119	56,0911	-	12,4583	12088	119	275	222 1891 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12088	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/119.php
2214	PSMSL_HOSOJIMA_133	Other	Not Defined	HOSOJIMA_133	32,4286	-	131,6694	12097	133	0	1930 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12097	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/133.php
2215	PSMSL_HUELVA_1883	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	HUELVA_1883	37,1320	-	6,8337	13217	1883	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13217	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1883.php
2216	PSMSL_IBIZA_1932	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	IBIZA_1932	38,9112	-	1,4498	13244	1932	7	120 2003 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13244	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1932.php
2217	PSMSL_IGNEDA_1926	Other	Not Defined	IGNEDA_1926	41,8833	-	28,0167	13239	1926	0	2002 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13239	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1926.php
2218	PSMSL_UMUIDEN_32	Other	Not Defined	UMUIDEN_32	52,4622	-	4,5547	12021	32	0	1871 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12021	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/32.php
2219	PSMSL_ILES DU SALUT_2012	France	Shom - France	ILES DU SALUT_2012	5,2843	-	52,5865	13259	2012	202	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13259	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/2012.php
2220	PSMSL_ILFRACOMBE_1214	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	ILFRACOMBE_1214	51,2111	-	4,1124	12828	1214	0	1983 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12828	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1214.php
2221	PSMSL_ILHA FISCAL_1032	Other	Not Defined	ILHA FISCAL_1032	-	22,8967	-	12719	1032	195	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12719	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1032.php
2222	PSMSL_IMBITUBA_542	Other	Not Defined	IMBITUBA_542	-	28,2333	-	12370	542	351	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12370	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/542.php
2223	PSMSL_IMMINGHAM_286	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	IMMINGHAM_286	53,6302	-	0,1874	12198	286	908	38 1959 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12198	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/286.php
2224	PSMSL_IMPERIA_2078	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	IMPERIA_2078	43,8783	-	8,0189	13299	2078	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13299	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/2078.php
2225	PSMSL_INCE POINT_1300	Other	Not Defined	INCE POINT_1300	-	10,5083	142,3100	12890	1300	0	1998 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12890	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1300.php
2226	PSMSL_INCHEON_956	Other	Not Defined	INCHEON_956	37,4519	-	126,5922	12670	956	0	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12670	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/956.php
2227	PSMSL_INDIAN RIVER INLET_1337	Other	Not Defined	INDIAN RIVER INLET_1337	38,6100	-	75,0700	12911	1337	0	1972 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12911	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/1337.php
2228	PSMSL_INVERGORDON_944	Other	Not Defined	INVERGORDON_944	57,6833	-	4,1667	12662	944	0	1959 - 1971	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12662	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/944.php

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/>
<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

2252	PSMSL_JUNEAU_405	Other	Not Defined	JUNEAU_405	58,2983	-	134,4117	12265	405	0	1936 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12265	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/405.php		
2253	PSMSL_JUNGRUSUND_18	Other	Not Defined	JUNGRUSUND_18	59,9500		22,3667	12008	18	0	1858 - 1934	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12008	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/18.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc	
2254	PSMSL_JURONG_1275	Other	Not Defined	JURONG_1275	1,3000		103,7167	12876	1275	0	1970 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12876	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtainings/stations/1275.php		
2255	PSMSL_KABELVAG_45	Other	Not Defined	KABELVAG_45	68,2126		14,4821	12030	45	0	1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12030			
2256	PSMSL_KAGOSHIMA_I_868	Other	Not Defined	KAGOSHIMA_I_868	31,6000		130,5667	12621	868	0	1957 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12621			
2257	PSMSL_KAHULUI HARBOR, MAUI ISLAND_521	Other	Not Defined	KAHULUI HARBOR, MAUI ISLAND_521	20,8950	-	156,4767	12356	521	0	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12356			
2258	PSMSL_KAINAN_701	Other	Not Defined	KAINAN_701	34,1442		135,1914	12492	701	0	1953 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12492			
2259	PSMSL_KALAMAJ_411	Other	Not Defined	KALAMAJ_411	37,0237		22,1158	12270	411	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12270			
2260	PSMSL_KALININGRAD_289	Other	Not Defined	KALININGRAD_289	54,9500		20,2167	12200	289	97	1926 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12200			
2261	PSMSL_KALIX_2101	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KALIX_2101	65,6969		23,0961	13318	2101	0	1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13318			
2262	PSMSL_KAMAISI II_1346	Other	Not Defined	KAMAISI II_1346	39,2733		141,8892	12917	1346	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12917			
2263	PSMSL_KAMINATO II (HATIZYO SIMA)_1440	Other	Not Defined	KAMINATO II (HATIZYO SIMA)_1440	33,1303		139,8047	12978	1440	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12978			
2264	PSMSL_KANDLA_596	Other	Not Defined	KANDLA_596	23,0167		70,2167	12407	596	0	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12407			
2265	PSMSL_KANMEN_934	Other	Not Defined	KANMEN_934	28,0833		121,2833	12656	934	94	1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12656			
2266	PSMSL_KANTON ISLAND_575	Other	Not Defined	KANTON ISLAND_575	-	2,8000	-	171,7167	12395	575	145	1949 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12395		
2267	PSMSL_KANTON ISLAND-B_1329	Other	Not Defined	KANTON ISLAND-B_1329	-	2,8167	-	171,7167	12907	1329	145	1972 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12907		
2268	PSMSL_KAOHSIUNG II_1356	Other	Not Defined	KAOHSIUNG II_1356	22,5333		120,3167	12926	1356	0	1973 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12926			
2269	PSMSL_KAPINGAMARANGI_1473	Other	Not Defined	KAPINGAMARANGI_1473	1,1000		154,7833	13001	1473	117	1978 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13001			
2270	PSMSL_KARACHI_204	Other	Not Defined	KARACHI_204	24,8117		66,9750	12148	204	30	1916 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12148			
2271	PSMSL_KARIYA_1318	Other	Not Defined	KARIYA_1318	33,4731		129,8492	12898	1318	0	1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12898			
2272	PSMSL_KARUMBA_835	Other	Not Defined	KARUMBA_835	-	17,5000	140,8333	12599	835	0	1985 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12599			
2273	PSMSL_KARIWAR_1273	Other	Not Defined	KARIWAR_1273	14,8000		74,1167	12875	1273	0	1970 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12875			
2274	PSMSL_KASHIWAZAKI_753	Other	Not Defined	KASHIWAZAKI_753	37,3567		138,5083	12530	753	0	1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12530			

PSMSL_KASKINEN / 2275 KASKO_285	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	KASKINEN / KASKO_285	62,3440	21,2148	12197	285	0	1926 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12197
2276 PSMSL_KATAKOLON_1240	Other	Not Defined	KATAKOLON_1240	37,6448	21,3197	12846	1240	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12846
2277 PSMSL_KATSUURA_1191	Other	Not Defined	KATSUURA_1191	35,1294	140,2494	12812	1191	184	76 1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12812
2278 PSMSL_KAVALLA_375	Other	Not Defined	KAVALLA_375	40,9346	24,4121	12242	375	0	1969 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12242
2279 PSMSL_KAVIENG_1608	Other	Not Defined	KAVIENG_1608	2,5833	150,8000	13064	1608	0	1984 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13064
PSMSL_KAWAIHAE, 2280 HAWAII ISLAND_2128	Other	Not Defined	KAWAIHAE, HAWAII ISLAND_2128	20,0367	155,8300	13341	2128	0	1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13341
2281 PSMSL_KEELUNG II 545	Other	Not Defined	KEELUNG II 545	25,1333	121,7333	12373	545	0	1956 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12373
2282 PSMSL_KEMI_229	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	KEMI_229	65,6734	24,5153	12168	229	0	1920 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12168
PSMSL_KEPPEL 2283 HARBOUR_1534	Other	Not Defined	KEPPEL HARBOUR_1534	1,2667	103,8167	13025	1534	44	1981 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13025
2284 PSMSL_KETCHIKAN_225	Other	Not Defined	KETCHIKAN_225	55,3317	131,6250	12164	225	0	1919 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12164
PSMSL_KEY COLONY 2285 BEACH 1424	Other	Not Defined	KEY COLONY BEACH 1424	24,7183	81,0167	12969	1424	0	1976 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12969
2286 PSMSL_KEY WEST_188	Other	Not Defined	KEY WEST_188	24,5550	81,8067	12136	188	216	1913 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12136
PSMSL_KHALKIS 2287 NORTH_1237	Other	Not Defined	KHALKIS NORTH_1237	38,4723	23,5926	12843	1237	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12843
PSMSL_KHALKIS 2288 SOUTH 1441	Other	Not Defined	KHALKIS SOUTH 1441	38,4609	23,5895	12979	1441	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12979
2289 PSMSL_KHEPUPARA_1454	Other	Not Defined	KHEPUPARA_1454	21,8333	89,8333	12992	1454	0	1977 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12992
2290 PSMSL_KHIOS_408	Other	Not Defined	KHIOS_408	38,3715	26,1412	12267	408	0	1969 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12267
2291 PSMSL_KIDDERPORE_48	Other	Not Defined	KIDDERPORE_48	22,5333	88,3333	12032	48	0	1881 - 1931	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12032
PSMSL_KIEL- 2292 HOLTENAU 789	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	KIEL-HOLTENAU 789	54,3722	10,1569	12559	789	0	1956 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12559
2293 PSMSL_KIGILIAH_642	Other	Not Defined	KIGILIAH_642	73,3333	139,8667	12445	642	0	1951 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12445
2294 PSMSL_KING BAY_1549	Other	Not Defined	KING BAY_1549	20,6236	116,7491	13034	1549	0	1982 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13034
2295 PSMSL KINGSTON 515	Other	Not Defined	KINGSTON 515	36,8333	139,8500	12351	515	352	86 1946 - 1952	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12351
PSMSL_KINLOCHBERVIE_1 2296 775	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	KINLOCHBERVIE_1775	58,4566	5,0504	13153	1775	0	1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13153
PSMSL_KIPTOPEKE 2297 BEACH_636	Other	Not Defined	KIPTOPEKE BEACH_636	37,1650	75,9883	12439	636	0	1951 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12439

2298	PSMSL_KJOLSDAL_398	Other	Not Defined SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KJOLSDAL_398	61,9167	5,6333	12261	398	0	1935 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12261
2299	PSMSL_KLAGSHAMN_330	Sweden		KLAGSHAMN_330	55,5222	12,8936	12219	330	0	1929 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12219
2300	PSMSL_KLAIPEDA_118	Norway	CMR - Christian Michelsen Research - Norway	KLAIPEDA_118	55,7000	21,1333	12087	118	0	1898 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12087
2301	PSMSL_KNYSNA_950	Other	Not Defined	KNYSNA_950	34,0494	23,0456	12664	950	0	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12664
2302	PSMSL_KO_LAK_174	Other	Not Defined	KO_LAK_174	11,8000	99,8167	12128	174	39	1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12128
2303	PSMSL_KO_MATTAPHON_1792	Other	Not Defined	KO_MATTAPHON_1792	10,4500	99,2500	13160	1792	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13160
2304	PSMSL_KO_SICHANG_449	Other	Not Defined	KO_SICHANG_449	13,1500	100,8167	12302	449	0	1940 - 2002	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12302
2305	PSMSL_KO_TAPHAO NOI_446	Other	Not Defined	KO_TAPHAO_NOI_446	7,8333	98,4333	12299	446	42	1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12299
2306	PSMSL_KOBBAKLINTAR_63	Other	Not Defined	KOBBAKLINTAR_63	60,0333	19,8833	12041	63	0	1885 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12041
2307	PSMSL_KOBE_II_1790	Other	Not Defined	KOBE_II_1790	34,6822	135,1903	13159	1790	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13159
2308	PSMSL_KOBE_846	Other	Not Defined	KOBE_846	34,6833	135,1833	12607	846	0	1957 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12607
2309	PSMSL_KOBENHAVN_82	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	KOBENHAVN_82	55,7050	12,6000	12058	82	0	1889 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12058
2310	PSMSL_KOCHI_II_1184	Other	Not Defined	KOCHI_II_1184	33,5000	133,5833	12809	1184	0	1966 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12809
2311	PSMSL_KOCHI_III_1567	Other	Not Defined	KOCHI_III_1567	33,4992	133,5692	13038	1567	0	1983 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13038
2312	PSMSL_KODIAK_ISLAND, WOMENS_BAY_567	Other	Not Defined	KODIAK_ISLAND, WOMENS_BAY_567	57,7317	152,5117	12389	567	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12389
2313	PSMSL_KOLOBRZEG_643	Other	Not Defined	KOLOBRZEG_643	54,1833	15,5500	12446	643	0	1951 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12446
2314	PSMSL_KOLUCHIN_621	Other	Not Defined	KOLUCHIN_621	67,4833	174,6500	12432	621	0	1950 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12432
2315	PSMSL_KOMATSUSHIMA_8 09	Other	Not Defined	KOMATSUSHIMA_809	34,0092	134,5878	12573	809	0	1958 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12573
2316	PSMSL_KOPER_1009	Slovenia	ARSO - Slovenian Environment Agency - Slovenia	KOPER_1009	45,5667	13,7500	12705	1009	0	1962 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12705
2317	PSMSL_KORSOR_113	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	KORSOR_113	55,3322	11,1422	12086	113	348	326 1897 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12086
2318	PSMSL_KOSEROW_1448	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	KOSEROW_1448	54,0603	14,0008	12986	1448	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12986
2319	PSMSL_KOSYSTYI (KOSYSTYI_MYS)_736	Other	Not Defined	KOSYSTYI (KOSYSTYI MYS)_736	73,6500	109,7333	12519	736	0	1954 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12519
2320	PSMSL_KOTA KINABALU_1733	Other	Not Defined	KOTA_KINABALU_1733	5,9833	116,0667	13130	1733	0	1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13130

PSMSL_KOTELNYI 2321 (KOTELNYI OSTROV)_641	Other	Not Defined	KOTELNYI (KOTELNYI OSTROV)_641	76,0000	137,8667	12444	641	0	1951 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12444
2322 PSMSL_KOTKA_164	Other	Not Defined	KOTKA_164	60,4500	26,9500	12119	164	0	1908 - 1927	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12119
2323 PSMSL_KOZU SIMA_1061	Other	Not Defined	KOZU SIMA_1061	34,2092	139,1317	12732	1061	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12732
PSMSL_KRASNOFLOTSKIE (KRASNOFLOTSKIE OSTROVA) 738	Other	Not Defined	KRASNOFLOTSKIE (KRASNOFLOTSKIE OSTROVA) 738	78,6000	98,8333	12521	738	0	1954 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12521
2324										
PSMSL_KRENKELIA (HEISA OSTROV)_1012	Other	Not Defined	KRENKELIA (HEISA OSTROV)_1012	80,6167	58,0500	12707	1012	0	1962 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12707
2325										
PSMSL_KRISTANSUNDN_6 2326 82	Norway	Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	KRISTANSUNDN_682	63,1139	7,7344	12479	682	40	302 1952 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12479
PSMSL_KUCHINOTSU_138 2327 6	Other	Not Defined	KUCHINOTSU 1386	32,6053	130,1953	12943	1386	0	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12943
2328 PSMSL_KUDAT_1876	Other	Not Defined	KUDAT_1876	6,8794	116,8436	13212	1876	0	1996 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13212
2329 PSMSL_KUKUP_1677	Other	Not Defined	KUKUP_1677	1,3253	103,4428	13098	1677	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13098
PSMSL_KUNGS HOLMSFOR 2330 T_70	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KUNGS HOLMSFORT_70	56,1053	15,5894	12047	70	0	1887 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12047
2331 PSMSL_KUNGSVIK 2113	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	KUNGSVIK 2113	58,9967	11,1272	13330	2113	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13330
2332 PSMSL_KUNSAN_959	Other	Not Defined	KUNSAN_959	35,9833	126,7167	12673	959	0	1960 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12673
2333 PSMSL_KURE I_1320	Other	Not Defined	KURE I_1320	33,3336	133,2433	12899	1320	0	1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12899
2334 PSMSL_KURE II 749	Other	Not Defined	KURE II 749	34,2333	132,5333	12528	749	0	1954 - 1961	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12528
2335 PSMSL_KURE III_1023	Other	Not Defined	KURE III_1023	34,2333	132,5500	12712	1023	0	1962 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12712
2336 PSMSL_KURE IV_1209	Other	Not Defined	KURE IV_1209	34,2406	132,5503	12823	1209	0	1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12823
2337 PSMSL_KUSHIMOTO_134	Other	Not Defined	KUSHIMOTO_134	33,4758	135,7733	12098	134	85	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12098
2338 PSMSL_KUSHIRO 518	Other	Not Defined	KUSHIRO 518	42,9756	144,3714	12353	518	89	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12353
2339 PSMSL_KWAJALEIN_513	Other	Not Defined	KWAJALEIN_513	8,7317	167,7350	12350	513	111	1946 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12350
2340 PSMSL_LA CORUNA I_484	Other	Not Defined	LA CORUNA I_484	43,3686	- 8,3978	12328	484	243	1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12328
2341 PSMSL LA CORUNA II 763	Other	Not Defined	LA CORUNA II 763	43,3667	- 8,4000	12540	763	243	1955 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12540
PSMSL_LA CORUNA 2342 III_1808	Other	Not Defined	LA CORUNA III_1808	43,3573	- 8,3893	13175	1808	699	44 1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13175
2343 PSMSL_LA GOMERA_2065	Other	Not Defined	LA GOMERA_2065	28,0878	- 17,1083	13290	2065	0	2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13290

PSMSL_LA JOLLA (SCRIPPS PIER)_256	Other	Not Defined	LA JOLLA (SCRIPPS PIER)_256	32,8667	-	117,2567	12186	256	159	1924 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12186
2345 PSMSL_LA LIBERTAD II_544	Other	Not Defined	LA LIBERTAD II_544	-	2,2000	-	80,9167	12372	544	1948 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12372
PSMSL_LA MADDALENA_109	Other	Not Defined	LA MADDALENA_109	41,2333	9,3667		12083	109	0	1896 - 1913	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12083
2347 PSMSL LA PALMA 2064	Other	Not Defined	LA PALMA 2064	28,6778	-	17,7680	13289	2064	0	2007 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13289
2348 PSMSL_LA PALOMA_764	Other	Not Defined	LA PALOMA_764	-	34,6500	-	54,1500	12541	764	1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12541
2349 PSMSL_LA PAZ_695	Other	Not Defined	LA PAZ_695	24,1667	-	110,3500	12489	695	0	1952 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12489
PSMSL_LA ROCHELLE-LA PALLICE 466	Other	Not Defined	LA ROCHELLE-LA PALLICE 466	46,1585	-	1,2207	12315	466	0	1941 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12315
2351 PSMSL_LA UNION_558	Other	Not Defined	LA UNION_558	13,3333	-	87,8167	12381	558	0	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12381
2352 PSMSL_LABUAN 2_1879	Other	Not Defined	LABUAN 2_1879	5,2728	115,2500		13215	1879	0	1996 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13215
2353 PSMSL_LAE_1303	Other	Not Defined	LAE_1303	-	6,7500	147,0000	12892	1303	0	1984 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12892
2354 PSMSL LAGOS 162	Other	Not Defined	LAGOS 162	37,1000	-	8,6667	12117	162	0	1908 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12117
2355 PSMSL_LAHAT DATU_1877	Other	Not Defined	LAHAT DATU_1877	5,0189	118,3461		13213	1877	0	1996 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13213
PSMSL_LAJES DAS FLORES_2171	Other	Not Defined	LAJES DAS FLORES_2171	39,3785	-	31,1686	13361	2171	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13361
PSMSL_LAKE WORTH PIER 1696	Other	Not Defined	LAKE WORTH PIER 1696	26,6117	-	80,0333	13106	1696	176	54 1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13106
PSMSL_LAMESHUR BAY_2119	Other	Not Defined	LAMESHUR BAY_2119	18,3167	-	64,7233	13333	2119	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13333
2359 PSMSL_LAMPEDUSA_2079	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LAMPEDUSA_2079	35,4998	12,6044		13300	2079	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13300
PSMSL_LANDSORT NORRA_2132	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LANDSORT NORRA_2132	58,7689	17,8589		13344	2132	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13344
2361 PSMSL LANDSORT 68	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	LANDSORT 68	58,7422	17,8653		12045	68	0	1887 - 2005	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12045
PSMSL_LANGARA POINT_840	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	LANGARA POINT_840	54,2500	-	133,0333	12603	840	0	1975 - 2003	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12603
PSMSL_LARK HARBOUR_1044	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	LARK HARBOUR_1044	49,1000	-	58,3667	12725	1044	0	1963 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12725
PSMSL_LAS PALMAS C (PUERTO DE LA LUZ) 565	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LAS PALMAS C (PUERTO DE LA LUZ) 565	28,1466	-	15,4075	12387	565	752	289 1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12387
PSMSL_LAS PALMAS D_1802	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LAS PALMAS D_1802	28,1406	-	15,4118	13170	1802	251	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13170
PSMSL_LAS PALMAS, PUERTO DE LA LUZ_590	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	LAS PALMAS, PUERTO DE LA LUZ_590	28,1667	-	15,4167	12404	590	251	1949 - 1951	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12404

2367	PSMSL_LAUTOKA_1805	Other	Not Defined	LAUTOKA_1805	17,6049	177,4383	13172	1805	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13172
2368	PSMSL_LE_CONQUET_1294	Other	Not Defined	LE_CONQUET_1294	48,3594	4,7808	12886	1294	0	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12886
2369	PSMSL_LE_CROUESTY_1921	Other	Not Defined	LE_CROUESTY_1921	47,5427	2,8952	13237	1921	0	1996 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13237
2370	PSMSL_LE_HAVRE_453	Other	Not Defined	LE_HAVRE_453	49,4819	0,1060	12303	453	0	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12303
2371	PSMSL_LE_VERDON_459	Other	Not Defined	LE_VERDON_459	45,5500	1,0667	12309	459	0	1941 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12309
2372	PSMSL_LEGASPI, ALBAY_522	Other	Not Defined	LEGASPI, ALBAY_522	13,1500	123,7500	12357	522	72	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12357
2373	PSMSL_LEITH_II_1526	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LEITH_II_1526	55,9898	3,1817	13022	1526	0	250 1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13022
2374	PSMSL_LEITH_802	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LEITH_802	55,9833	3,1667	12569	802	0	1956 - 1971	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12569
2375	PSMSL_LEIXOES_791	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	LEIXOES_791	41,1833	8,7000	12561	791	0	1956 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12561
2376	PSMSL_LEMSTROM_84	Other	Not Defined	LEMSTROM_84	60,1000	20,0167	12060	84	0	1889 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12060
2377	PSMSL_LEROS_1233	Other	Not Defined	LEROS_1233	37,1297	26,8480	12840	1233	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12840
2378	PSMSL_LERWICK_830	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LERWICK_830	60,1540	1,1403	12594	830	236	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12594
2379	PSMSL_LES_SABLES D OLLONNE_1747	Other	Not Defined	LES_SABLES D OLLONNE_1747	46,4975	1,7937	13135	1747	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13135
2380	PSMSL_LESKINA (LESKINA MYS) 654	Other	Not Defined	LESKINA (LESKINA MYS) 654	72,3167	79,5667	12457	654	0	1951 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12457
2381	PSMSL_L'ESTARTIT_1764	Other	Not Defined	L'ESTARTIT_1764	42,0500	3,2000	13147	1764	0	1990 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13147
2382	PSMSL_LEVKAS_1239	Other	Not Defined	LEVKAS_1239	38,8345	20,7121	12845	1239	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12845
2383	PSMSL_LEWES (BREAKWATER HARBOR)_224	Other	Not Defined	LEWES (BREAKWATER HARBOR)_224	38,7817	75,1200	12163	224	0	1919 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12163
2384	PSMSL_LIANYUNGANG_14 05	Other	Not Defined	LIANYUNGANG_1405	34,7500	119,4500	12958	1405	0	1975 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12958
2385	PSMSL_LIEPAJA_26	Other	Not Defined	LIEPAJA_26	56,5333	20,9833	12015	26	0	1865 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12015
2386	PSMSL_LIME TREE BAY, ST CROIX_1447	Other	Not Defined	LIME TREE BAY, ST CROIX_1447	17,6933	64,7533	12985	1447	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12985
2387	PSMSL_LIMHAMN_323	Other	Not Defined	LIMHAMN_323	55,5833	12,9333	12218	323	0	1928 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12218
2388	PSMSL_LINAKHAMARI_365	Other	Not Defined	LINAKHAMARI_365	69,6500	31,3667	12235	365	0	1931 - 1939	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12235
2389	PSMSL_LISBON_1336	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	LISBON_1336	38,7000	9,1333	12910	1336	0	1972 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12910

PSMSL_LITTLE 2390 CORNWALLIS ISLAND_1822	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	LITTLE CORNWALLIS ISLAND_1822	75,3833	-	96,9500	13184	1822	0	1992 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13184
PSMSL_LIVERPOOL 2391 (GLADSTONE DOCK)_1774	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LIVERPOOL (GLADSTONE DOCK)_1774	53,4497	-	3,0180	13152	1774	0	1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13152
PSMSL_LIVERPOOL 2392 GEORGES AND PRINCES PIERS_15	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LIVERPOOL GEORGES AND PRINCES PIERS_15	53,4000	-	3,0000	12005	15	0	1858 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12005
2393 PSMSL LIVORNO II 2080	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	LIVORNO II 2080	43,5463	-	10,2993	13301	2080	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13301
2394 PSMSL_LLANDUDNO_1854	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LLANDUDNO_1854	53,3317	-	3,8252	13202	1854	0	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13202
2395 PSMSL_LOHM_233	Other	Not Defined	LOHM_233	60,1000	-	21,6667	12171	233	0	1920 - 1927	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12171
2396 PSMSL LOK ON PAI 1685	Other	Not Defined	LOK ON PAI 1685	22,3667	-	114,0000	13103	1685	0	1986 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13103
2397 PSMSL_LOMBRUM_1860	Other	Not Defined	LOMBRUM_1860	-	2,0421	147,3738	13208	1860	335	56 1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13208
PSMSL_LORD HOWE 2398 ISLAND_818	Other	Not Defined	LORD HOWE ISLAND_818	-	31,5167	159,0667	12582	818	217	148 251 1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12582
2399 PSMSL LORETO_1410	Other	Not Defined	LORETO_1410	26,0167	-	111,3667	12962	1410	0	1975 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12962
2400 PSMSL LORNE 1836	Other	Not Defined	LORNE 1836	-	38,5472	143,9888	13192	1836	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13192
2401 PSMSL_LOS ANGELES_245	Other	Not Defined	LOS ANGELES_245	33,7200	-	118,2717	12179	245	0	1923 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12179
PSMSL_LOWER 2402 ESCUMINAC_1349	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LOWER ESCUMINAC_1349	47,0833	-	64,8833	12919	1349	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12919
2403 PSMSL LOWESTOFT 754	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	LOWESTOFT 754	52,4731	-	1,7501	12531	754	56	144 1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12531
2404 PSMSL_LUCINDA_1630	Other	Not Defined	LUCINDA_1630	-	18,5167	146,3833	13071	1630	0	1985 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13071
2405 PSMSL_LUDERITZ_911	Other	Not Defined	LUDERITZ_911	-	26,6433	15,1550	12639	911	0	1958 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12639
2406 PSMSL_LUMUT_1594	Other	Not Defined	LUMUT_1594	4,2400	-	100,6133	13054	1594	43	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13054
2407 PSMSL LUSI 979	Other	Not Defined	LUSI 979	32,1333	-	121,6167	12680	979	283	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12680
2408 PSMSL_LYOKKI_16	Other	Not Defined	LYOKKI_16	60,8500	-	21,1833	12006	16	0	1858 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12006
2409 PSMSL_LYPYRTTI_17	Other	Not Defined	LYPYRTTI_17	60,6000	-	21,2333	12007	17	0	1858 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12007
2410 PSMSL MAASSLUIS 9	Other	Not Defined	MAASSLUIS 9	51,9175	-	4,2497	11999	9	825	284 1848 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11999
PSMSL_MACABALAN PORT, 2411 CAGAYAN DE ORO_2154	Other	Not Defined	MACABALAN PORT, CAGAYAN DE ORO_2154	8,5000	-	124,6667	13357	2154	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13357
2412 PSMSL_MACAU_269	Other	Not Defined	MACAU_269	22,2000	-	113,5500	12193	269	0	1925 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12193

2413	PSMSL_MACKAY_564	Other	Not Defined	MACKAY_564	-	21,1000	149,2333	12386	564	0	1960 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12386
2414	PSMSL_MADANG_1254	Other	Not Defined	MADANG_1254	-	5,2167	145,8000	12860	1254	0	1984 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12860
2415	PSMSL_MAGUEYES ISLAND_759	Other	Not Defined	MAGUEYES ISLAND_759	-	17,9700	67,0450	12536	759	91	172 1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12536
2416	PSMSL MAHON 2062	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MAHON 2062	-	39,8930	4,2706	13287	2062	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13287
2417	PSMSL_MAISAKA_1089	Other	Not Defined	MAISAKA_1089	-	34,6819	137,6089	12751	1089	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12751
2418	PSMSL_MAIZURU I_663	Other	Not Defined	MAIZURU I_663	-	35,4833	135,4000	12464	663	0	1951 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12464
2419	PSMSL_MAIZURU II 1387	Other	Not Defined	MAIZURU II 1387	-	35,4767	135,3869	12944	1387	0	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12944
2420	PSMSL_MAIZURU III_1523	Other	Not Defined	MAIZURU III_1523	-	35,4500	135,3167	13020	1523	0	1981 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13020
2421	PSMSL_MAJURO-B_1217	Other	Not Defined	MAJUORO-B_1217	-	7,1000	171,3667	12831	1217	112	1968 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12831
2422	PSMSL_MAJURO-C_1838	Other	Not Defined	MAJUORO-C_1838	-	7,1060	171,3728	13193	1838	112	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13193
2423	PSMSL_MAKAR, GENERAL SANTOS CITY 2153	Other	Not Defined	MAKAR, GENERAL SANTOS CITY 2153	-	6,1000	125,1500	13356	2153	351	87 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13356
2424	PSMSL_MAKURAZAKI I_1142	Other	Not Defined	MAKURAZAKI I_1142	-	31,2667	130,3000	12787	1142	0	1965 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12787
2425	PSMSL_MALAGA II_1810	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MALAGA II_1810	-	36,7118	4,4171	13177	1810	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13177
2426	PSMSL_MALAGA 496	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MALAGA 496	-	36,7127	4,4155	12339	496	0	1944 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12339
2427	PSMSL_MALAKAL-B_1252	Other	Not Defined	MALAKAL-B_1252	-	7,3333	134,4667	12858	1252	120	1969 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12858
2428	PSMSL_MALE-B, HULULE_1753	Other	Not Defined	MALE-B, HULULE_1753	-	4,1833	73,5333	13140	1753	28	1989 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13140
2429	PSMSL_MALIN HEAD_916	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	MALIN HEAD_916	-	55,3667	7,3333	12643	916	239	1958 - 2002	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12643
2430	PSMSL_MALOY 486	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	MALOY 486	-	61,9338	5,1133	12330	486	0	1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12330
2431	PSMSL_MALYE KARMAKULY_609	Other	Not Defined	MALYE KARMAKULY_609	-	72,3667	52,7000	12420	609	0	1950 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12420
2432	PSMSL_MALYI TAIMYR (MALYI TAIMYR OSTROV)_620	Other	Not Defined	MALYI TAIMYR (MALYI TAIMYR OSTROV)_620	-	78,0833	106,8167	12431	620	0	1950 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12431
2433	PSMSL_MALYSHEVA (MALYSHEVA OSTROV) 741	Other	Not Defined	MALYSHEVA (MALYSHEVA OSTROV) 741	-	72,0667	129,8333	12522	741	0	1954 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12522
2434	PSMSL_MAMBAJAO CAMGUIN_2174	Other	Not Defined	MAMBAJAO CAMGUIN_2174	-	9,2500	124,7333	13364	2174	14	107 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13364
2435	PSMSL_MANFREDONIA_1262	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	MANFREDONIA_1262	-	41,6167	15,9167	12865	1262	0	1969 - 1971	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12865

PSMSL_MANGALORE 2436 (PANAMBURU)_1423	Other	Not Defined	MANGALORE (PANAMBURU)_1423	12,9167	74,8000	12968	1423	0	1976 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12968
2437 PSMSL_MANGALORE_696	Other	Not Defined	MANGALORE_696	12,8500	74,8333	12490	696	207	249 1953 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12490
PSMSL_MANILA, S. 2438 HARBOR_145	Other	Not Defined	MANILA, S. HARBOR_145	14,5833	120,9667	12107	145	73	1901 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12107
2439 PSMSL_MANTYLIUOTO 172	Other	Not Defined	MANTYLIUOTO 172	61,5944	21,4634	12126	172	353	85 1910 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12126
PSMSL_MANUS 2440 ISLAND_1609	Other	Not Defined	MANUS ISLAND_1609	2,0167	147,2667	13065	1609	0	1984 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13065
PSMSL_MANZANILLO 2441 2_1818	Other	Not Defined	MANZANILLO 2_1818	19,0667	104,3000	13182	1818	163	1992 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13182
PSMSL_MANZANILLO_193 2442 4	Other	Not Defined	MANZANILLO 1934	20,3333	77,1500	13246	1934	0	2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13246
2443 PSMSL_MANZANILLO_737	Other	Not Defined	MANZANILLO_737	19,0500	104,3333	12520	737	163	1954 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12520
2444 PSMSL_MAPUTO_986	Other	Not Defined	MAPUTO_986	25,9667	32,5667	12687	986	0	1961 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12687
2445 PSMSL_MAR DE AJO_1542	Other	Not Defined	MAR DE AJO_1542	36,7000	56,6667	13028	1542	0	1981 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13028
PSMSL_MAR DEL PLATA 2446 (NAVAL BASE) 819	Other	Not Defined	MAR DEL PLATA (NAVAL BASE) 819	38,0333	57,5167	12583	819	192	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12583
PSMSL_MAR DEL PLATA 2447 (PUERTO)_857	Other	Not Defined	MAR DEL PLATA (PUERTO)_857	38,0333	57,5333	12612	857	192	1957 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12612
PSMSL_MARATHON 2448 SHORES_1187	Other	Not Defined	MARATHON SHORES_1187	24,7333	81,0333	12810	1187	399	148 1966 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12810
PSMSL_MARII PRONCHISHEVOI 2449 (BUKHTA) 667	Other	Not Defined	MARII PRONCHISHEVOI (BUKHTA) 667	75,5333	113,4333	12467	667	0	1951 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12467
2450 PSMSL_MARMAGAO_1249	Other	Not Defined	MARMAGAO_1249	15,4167	73,8000	12855	1249	281	1969 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12855
PSMSL_MARMARA 2451 EREGLISI_2010	Other	Not Defined	MARMARA EREGLISI_2010	40,9667	27,9667	13257	2010	0	2004 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13257
PSMSL_MARSAXLOKK (FORMALLY 2452 VALLETTA)_1735	Malta	UOM - CALYPSO - Dept. of Geosciences, University of Malta - Malta	MARSAXLOKK (FORMALLY VALLETTA)_1735	35,8201	14,5330	13132	1735	351	87 1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13132
2453 PSMSL_MARSEILLE 61	France	Shom - France SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	MARSEILLE 61	43,2788	5,3539	12039	61	205	1885 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12039
2454 PSMSL_MARVIKEN_2104	Sweden		MARVIKEN_2104	58,5536	16,8372	13321	2104	13	145 1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13321
PSMSL_MASSACRE 2455 BAY_491	Other	Not Defined	MASSACRE BAY_491	52,8333	173,2000	12335	491	0	1943 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12335
2456 PSMSL_MATAPEAKE 1338	Other	Not Defined	MATAPEAKE 1338	38,9567	76,3550	12912	1338	0	1972 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12912
2457 PSMSL_MATARANI_458	Other	Not Defined	MATARANI_458	17,0000	72,1167	12308	458	0	1941 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12308
2458 PSMSL_MATSUYAMA L_880	Other	Not Defined	MATSUYAMA L_880	33,8667	132,7000	12632	880	0	1957 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12632

PSMSL_MATSUYAMA 2459 IL_1062	Other	Not Defined	MATSUYAMA IL_1062	33,8589	132,7122	12733	1062	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12733
2460 PSMSL_MAYPORT_316	Other	Not Defined	MAYPORT_316	30,3933	81,4317	12212	316	0	1928 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12212
2461 PSMSL_MAZATLAN_712	Other	Not Defined	MAZATLAN_712	23,2000	106,4167	12500	712	0	1953 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12500
2462 PSMSL_MELILLA_2057	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MELILLA_2057	35,2906	2,9285	13282	2057	0	2008 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13282
PSMSL_MENTES/IZMIR_16 2463 79	Other	Not Defined	MENTES/IZMIR_1679	38,4333	26,7167	13100	1679	0	1985 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13100
2464 PSMSL_MERA_359	Other	Not Defined	MERA_359	34,9189	139,8250	12229	359	86	1931 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12229
2465 PSMSL_MIAMI BEACH_363	Other	Not Defined	MIAMI BEACH_363	25,7683	80,1317	12233	363	0	1931 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12233
PSMSL_MIDWAY 2466 ISLAND_523	Other	Not Defined	MIDWAY ISLAND_523	28,2117	177,3600	12358	523	106	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12358
2467 PSMSL_MIKUNI_1190	Other	Not Defined	MIKUNI_1190	36,2547	136,1489	12811	1190	729	192 1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12811
PSMSL_MILFORD HAVEN (HAKIN)_1700	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	MILFORD HAVEN (HAKIN)_1700	51,7074	5,0515	13109	1700	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13109
PSMSL_MILFORD HAVEN (NEWTON NOYES)_66	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	MILFORD HAVEN (NEWTON NOYES)_66	51,7000	5,0167	12044	66	209	246 1963 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12044
2470 PSMSL_MILLPORT_755	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	MILLPORT_755	55,7498	4,9063	12532	755	53	149 1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12532
PSMSL_MILNER BAY 2471 (GROOTE EYLANDT)_1160	Other	Not Defined	MILNER BAY (GROOTE EYLANDT)_1160	13,8601	136,4156	12803	1160	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12803
PSMSL_MINA 2472 SULMAN_1494	Other	Not Defined	MINA SULMAN_1494	26,2333	50,6000	13012	1494	0	1979 - 2007	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13012
2473 PSMSL_MINAMI IZU_1064	Other	Not Defined	MINAMI IZU_1064	34,6167	138,8833	12734	1064	0	1964 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12734
2474 PSMSL_MIRI_1819	Other	Not Defined	MIRI_1819	4,4011	113,9744	13183	1819	0	1992 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13183
2475 PSMSL_MISUMI_810	Other	Not Defined	MISUMI_810	32,6231	130,4514	12574	810	0	1957 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12574
PSMSL_MIYAKE 2476 SIMA_1060	Other	Not Defined	MIYAKE SIMA_1060	34,0672	139,4808	12731	1060	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12731
2477 PSMSL_MIYAKO I_463	Other	Not Defined	MIYAKO I_463	39,6333	141,9667	12313	463	0	1941 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12313
2478 PSMSL_MIYAKO II_1149	Other	Not Defined	MIYAKO II_1149	39,6431	141,9753	12792	1149	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12792
2479 PSMSL_MIYAZU_872	Other	Not Defined	MIYAZU_872	35,5333	135,1833	12625	872	0	1957 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12625
2480 PSMSL_MOKPO_954	Other	Not Defined	MOKPO_954	34,7797	126,3756	12668	954	0	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12668
PSMSL_MOKUOLOE 2481 ISLAND_823	Other	Not Defined	MOKUOLOE ISLAND_823	21,4317	157,7900	12587	823	51	105 1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12587

2482	PSMSL_MOMBASA II_2183	Other	Not Defined	MOMBASA II_2183	-	4,0667	39,6500	13367	2183	8	1986 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13367
2483	PSMSL_MOMMARK_271	Other	Not Defined	MOMMARK_271	-	54,9333	10,0667	12195	271	0	1925 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12195
2484	PSMSL_MONA ISLAND_2122	Other	Not Defined	MONA ISLAND_2122	-	18,0900	67,9383	13336	2122	0	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13336
2485	PSMSL_MONACO (FONTVIEILLE) 788	France	Shom - France	MONACO (FONTVIEILLE) 788	-	43,7288	7,4215	12558	788	0	1956 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12558
2486	PSMSL_MONBETU L_772	Other	Not Defined	MONBETU L_772	-	44,3500	143,3667	12548	772	0	1955 - 1978	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12548
2487	PSMSL_MONTAIUK_519	Other	Not Defined	MONTAIUK_519	-	41,0483	71,9600	12354	519	0	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12354
2488	PSMSL_MONTEREY 1352	Other	Not Defined	MONTEREY 1352	-	36,6050	121,8867	12922	1352	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12922
2489	PSMSL_MONTEVIDEO (PUNTA LOBOS)_431	Other	Not Defined	MONTEVIDEO (PUNTA LOBOS)_431	-	34,9000	56,2500	12285	431	300	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12285
2490	PSMSL_MOOLOOLABA 2_1493	Other	Not Defined	MOOLOOLABA 2_1493	-	26,6833	153,1333	13011	1493	0	1979 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13011
2491	PSMSL_MOREHEAD CITY_719	Other	Not Defined	MOREHEAD CITY_719	-	34,7167	76,7333	12504	719	0	1953 - 1962	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12504
2492	PSMSL_MORZHOVAIA (HARASAVEI MYS) 732	Other	Not Defined	MORZHOVAIA (HARASAVEI MYS) 732	-	71,4167	67,5833	12516	732	805	323 1954 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12516
2493	PSMSL_MOSJOEN_781	Other	Not Defined	MOSJOEN_781	-	65,8500	13,2000	12553	781	0	1955 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12553
2494	PSMSL_MOSSEL BAY_910	Other	Not Defined	MOSSEL BAY_910	-	34,1786	22,1353	12638	910	0	1958 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12638
2495	PSMSL_MOTRIL 2 1940	Spain	PIE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	MOTRIL 2 1940	-	36,7202	3,5236	13249	1940	0	2005 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13249
2496	PSMSL_MOTURIKI ISLAND_978	Other	Not Defined	MOTURIKI ISLAND_978	-	37,6317	176,1850	12679	978	0	2002 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12679
2497	PSMSL_MOULMEIN_747	Other	Not Defined	MOULMEIN_747	-	16,4833	97,6167	12527	747	141	1954 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12527
2498	PSMSL_MOURILYAN HARBOUR_1629	Other	Not Defined	MOURILYAN HARBOUR_1629	-	17,5833	146,0833	13070	1629	0	1985 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13070
2499	PSMSL_MOZAMBIQUE ISLAND 1054	Other	Not Defined	MOZAMBIQUE ISLAND 1054	-	15,0333	40,7333	12729	1054	395	163 1963 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12729
2500	PSMSL_MOZI_912	Other	Not Defined	MOZI_912	-	33,9500	130,9667	12640	912	0	1958 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12640
2501	PSMSL_MUKHO_1108	Other	Not Defined	MUKHO_1108	-	37,5503	129,1164	12769	1108	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12769
2502	PSMSL_MUMBAI / BOMBAY (APOLLO BANDAR) 43	Other	Not Defined	MUMBAI / BOMBAY (APOLLO BANDAR) 43	-	18,9167	72,8333	12028	43	0	1878 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12028
2503	PSMSL_MUMBLES_1732	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	MUMBLES_1732	-	51,5700	3,9754	13129	1732	0	1988 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13129
2504	PSMSL_MUOSTAH (MUOSTAH OSTROV)_649	Other	Not Defined	MUOSTAH (MUOSTAH OSTROV)_649	-	71,5500	130,0333	12452	649	0	1951 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12452

2505	PSMSL_MURMANSK_684	Other	Not Defined	MURMANSK_684	68,9667	33,0500	12481	684	274	1952 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12481
2506	PSMSL_MURORAN_1194	Other	Not Defined	MURORAN_1194	42,3500	140,9500	12815	1194	0	1967 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12815
2507	PSMSL_MUROTOMISAKI_1390	Other	Not Defined	MUROTOMISAKI_1390	33,2664	134,1644	12947	1390	0	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12947
2508	PSMSL_MUSCAT_1716	Other	Not Defined	MUSCAT_1716	23,6333	58,5667	13122	1716	0	1987 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13122
2509	PSMSL_MYRTLE BEACH_862	Other	Not Defined	MYRTLE BEACH_862	33,6833	78,8850	12616	862	0	1957 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12616
2510	PSMSL_MYS PIKSHUEVA_2026	Other	Not Defined	MYS PIKSHUEVA_2026	69,5500	32,4333	13264	2026	22	137 1955 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13264
2511	PSMSL_MYS SHMIDTA_616	Other	Not Defined	MYS SHMIDTA_616	68,9000	179,3667	12427	616	0	1950 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12427
2512	PSMSL_N SPIT, HUMBOLDT BAY_1639	Other	Not Defined	N SPIT, HUMBOLDT BAY_1639	40,7667	124,2167	13080	1639	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13080
2513	PSMSL_NAGAEVO_827	Other	Not Defined	NAGAEVO_827	59,5500	150,7167	12591	827	92	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12591
2514	PSMSL_NAGAPPATTINAM_1308	Other	Not Defined	NAGAPPATTINAM_1308	10,7667	79,8500	12895	1308	0	1971 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12895
2515	PSMSL_NAGASAKI_1100	Other	Not Defined	NAGASAKI_1100	32,7350	129,8661	12761	1100	83	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12761
2516	PSMSL_NAGOYA II_1488	Other	Not Defined	NAGOYA II_1488	35,0914	136,8808	13006	1488	0	1979 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13006
2517	PSMSL_NAGOYA_860	Other	Not Defined	NAGOYA_860	35,0833	136,8833	12615	860	0	1957 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12615
2518	PSMSL_NAHA_1151	Other	Not Defined	NAHA_1151	26,2133	127,6653	12794	1151	81	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12794
2519	PSMSL_NAIBA_1497	Other	Not Defined	NAIBA_1497	70,8500	130,7500	13015	1497	0	1979 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13015
2520	PSMSL_NAIN_1029	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	NAIN_1029	56,5500	61,7000	12716	1029	224	2001 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12716
2521	PSMSL_NAKANO SIMA_1105	Other	Not Defined	NAKANO SIMA_1105	29,8419	129,8478	12766	1105	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12766
2522	PSMSL_NAN SHA_1730	Other	Not Defined	NAN SHA_1730	9,5500	112,8800	13128	1730	0	1998 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13128
2523	PSMSL_NANOOSE BAY_1825	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	NANOOSE BAY_1825	49,2667	124,1333	13185	1825	0	1992 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13185
2524	PSMSL_NANTUCKET ISLAND_1111	Other	Not Defined	NANTUCKET ISLAND_1111	41,2850	70,0967	12772	1111	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12772
2525	PSMSL_NAOS ISLAND 2 1783	Other	Not Defined	NAOS ISLAND 2 1783	8,9183	79,5333	13155	1783	0	1991 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13155
2526	PSMSL_NAOS ISLAND_581	Other	Not Defined	NAOS ISLAND_581	8,9183	79,5500	12400	581	0	1949 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12400
2527	PSMSL_NAPIER_1750	Other	Not Defined	NAPIER_1750	39,4755	176,9200	13138	1750	0	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13138

2528	PSMSL_NAPLES_1107	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	NAPLES_1107	26,1317	-	81,8067	12768	1107	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12768
2529	PSMSL_NAPOLI (MANDRACCIO)_105	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	NAPOLI (MANDRACCIO)_105	40,8667	-	14,2667	12079	105	0	1896 - 1922	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12079
2530	PSMSL_NAPOLI_II_2092	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	NAPOLI_II_2092	40,8414	-	14,2692	13309	2092	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13309
2531	PSMSL_NARVIK_312	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	NARVIK_312	68,4283	-	17,4258	12208	312	0	1928 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12208
2532	PSMSL_NASE_I_887	Other	Not Defined	NASE_I_887	28,3833	-	129,5000	12636	887	0	1957 - 1961	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12636
2533	PSMSL_NASE_III_1522	Other	Not Defined	NASE_III_1522	28,5000	-	129,5000	13019	1522	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13019
2534	PSMSL_NAURU_1374	Other	Not Defined	NAURU_1374	-	0,5333	166,9000	12940	1374	114	1974 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12940
2535	PSMSL_NAURU-B_1844	Other	Not Defined	NAURU-B_1844	-	0,5294	166,9101	13199	1844	114	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13199
2536	PSMSL_NAWILIWILI BAY, KAUAI ISLAND_756	Other	Not Defined	NAWILIWILI BAY, KAUAI ISLAND_756	21,9533	-	159,3550	12533	756	0	1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12533
2537	PSMSL_NEAH_BAY_385	Other	Not Defined	NEAH_BAY_385	48,3667	-	124,6117	12250	385	211	245 1934 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12250
2538	PSMSL_NEDRE_GAVLE_99	Other	Not Defined	NEDRE_GAVLE_99	60,6833	-	17,1667	12073	99	0	1896 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12073
2539	PSMSL_NEDRE NYKOPING_170	Other	Not Defined	NEDRE_NYKOPING_170	58,7500	-	17,0167	12125	170	0	1909 - 1920	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12125
2540	PSMSL_NEDRE SODERTALJE_31	Other	Not Defined	NEDRE_SODERTALJE_31	59,2000	-	17,6167	12020	31	0	1869 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12020
2541	PSMSL_NELSON_787	Other	Not Defined	NELSON_787	-	41,2613	173,2728	12557	787	217	251 1956 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12557
2542	PSMSL_NEMKOVA (NEMKOVA OSTROV)_797	Other	Not Defined	NEMKOVA (NEMKOVA OSTROV)_797	71,4167	-	150,7500	12566	797	0	1956 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12566
2543	PSMSL_NETTEN_613	Other	Not Defined	NETTEN_613	66,9667	-	171,9333	12424	613	0	1950 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12424
2544	PSMSL_NEUVILLE_192	Other	Not Defined	NEUVILLE_192	46,7000	-	71,5667	12139	192	0	1914 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12139
2545	PSMSL_NEVLUNGHAVN_40 1	Other	Not Defined	NEVLUNGHAVN_401	58,9667	-	9,8833	12263	401	0	1935 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12263
2546	PSMSL_NEW WESTMINSTER_1245	Other	Not Defined	NEW WESTMINSTER_1245	49,2000	-	122,9167	12851	1245	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12851
2547	PSMSL_NEW_LONDON_429	Other	Not Defined	NEW_LONDON_429	41,3600	-	72,0900	12283	429	0	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12283
2548	PSMSL_NEW ROCHELLE_856	Other	Not Defined	NEW_ROCHELLE_856	40,8933	-	73,7817	12611	856	0	1957 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12611
2549	PSMSL_NEW_YORK (THE BATTERY)_12	Other	Not Defined	NEW_YORK (THE BATTERY)_12	40,7000	-	74,0133	12002	12	551	158 1856 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12002
2550	PSMSL_NEWCASTLE_III_267	Other	Not Defined	NEWCASTLE_III_267	-	32,9167	151,8000	12192	267	0	1925 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12192

2551	PSMSL_NEWCASTLE_V_837	Other	Not Defined	NEWCASTLE_V_837	-	32,9240	151,7886	12601	837	0	1957 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12601
2552	PSMSL_NEWHAVEN_1548	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NEWHAVEN_1548		50,7818	0,0570	13033	1548	0	1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13033
2553	PSMSL_NEWLYN_202	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NEWLYN_202		50,1030	5,5428	12146	202	829	340 1915 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12146
2554	PSMSL_NEWPORT BAY_766	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NEWPORT BAY_766		33,6033	117,8817	12543	766	0	1955 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12543
2555	PSMSL_NEWPORT_1832	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NEWPORT_1832		51,5500	2,9874	13188	1832	592	157 1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13188
2556	PSMSL_NEWPORT_351	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	NEWPORT_351		41,5050	71,3267	12226	351	290	1930 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12226
2557	PSMSL_NEZUGASEKI_752	Other	Not Defined	NEZUGASEKI_752		38,5633	139,5458	12529	752	372	71 1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12529
2558	PSMSL_NICE_1468	France	Shom - France	NICE_1468		43,6956	7,2855	12998	1468	0	1978 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12998
2559	PSMSL_NIEUWPOORT_489	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	NIEUWPOORT_489		51,1500	2,7333	12333	489	0	1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12333
2560	PSMSL_NIKISKI ALASKA_1350	Other	Not Defined	NIKISKI_ALASKA_1350		60,6833	151,3967	12920	1350	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12920
2561	PSMSL_NISINOOMOTE_1096	Other	Not Defined	NISINOOMOTE_1096		30,7350	130,9922	12757	1096	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12757
2562	PSMSL_NOME ALASKA_1800	Other	Not Defined	NOME_ALASKA_1800		64,5000	165,4300	13168	1800	74	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13168
2563	PSMSL_NORFOLK ISLAND_821	Other	Not Defined	NORFOLK ISLAND_821		29,0583	167,9536	12585	821	124	1994 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12585
2564	PSMSL_NORTH POINT_333	Other	Not Defined	NORTH POINT_333		22,3000	114,2000	12222	333	77	1929 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12222
2565	PSMSL_NORTH SALAMINOS II_1938	Other	Not Defined	NORTH SALAMINOS II_1938		37,9796	23,5342	13248	1938	0	2004 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13248
2566	PSMSL_NORTH SALAMINOS_1604	Other	Not Defined	NORTH SALAMINOS_1604		37,9796	23,5417	13061	1604	0	1984 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13061
2567	PSMSL_NORTH SHIELDS_95	Other	Not Defined	NORTH SHIELDS_95		55,0074	1,4398	12069	95	0	1895 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12069
2568	PSMSL_NORTH SOUND_1422	Other	Not Defined	NORTH SOUND_1422		19,3000	81,3167	12967	1422	0	1976 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12967
2569	PSMSL_NORTH SYDNEY_1299	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	NORTH SYDNEY_1299		46,2167	60,2500	12889	1299	0	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12889
2570	PSMSL_NOSY-BE_926	Other	Not Defined	NOSY-BE_926		13,4000	48,2833	12651	926	15	1958 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12651
2571	PSMSL_NOUMEA-CHALEIX_852	Other	Not Defined	NOUMEA-CHALEIX_852		22,3000	166,4333	12610	852	123	1970 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12610
2572	PSMSL_NOUMEA-NUMBO_2134	France	Shom - France	NOUMEA-NUMBO_2134		22,2420	166,4162	13346	2134	123	2001 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13346
2573	PSMSL_NUKU HIVA_1555	France	Shom - France	NUKU HIVA_1555		8,9333	140,0833	13037	1555	142	1982 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13037

PSMSL_NUKU'ALOFA 2574 B_1842	Other	Not Defined	NUKU'ALOFA B_1842	-	21,1368	-	175,1807	13197	1842	125	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13197
2575 PSMSL_NY-ALESUND_1421	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	NY-ALESUND_1421		78,9285		11,9380	12966	1421	345	1976 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12966
2576 PSMSL_ODOMARI_1097	Other	Not Defined	ODOMARI_1097		31,0236		130,6892	12758	1097	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12758
2577 PSMSL_OFUNATO I 1140	Other	Not Defined	OFUNATO I 1140		39,0667		141,7167	12786	1140	87	1965 - 1973	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12786
2578 PSMSL_OFUNATO II_1364	Other	Not Defined	OFUNATO II_1364		39,0197		141,7533	12930	1364	87	261 1974 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12930
2579 PSMSL_OGA_1264	Other	Not Defined	OGA_1264		39,9422		139,7058	12867	1264	0	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12867
2580 PSMSL_OGI 1344	Other	Not Defined	OGI 1344		37,8147		138,2811	12915	1344	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12915
2581 PSMSL_OITA II_1293	Other	Not Defined	OITA II_1293		33,2661		131,6867	12885	1293	0	1971 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12885
2582 PSMSL_OKADA_1091	Other	Not Defined	OKADA_1091		34,7894		139,3914	12753	1091	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12753
2583 PSMSL_OKHA_1395	Other	Not Defined	OKHA_1395		22,4667		69,0833	12952	1395	0	1975 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12952
2584 PSMSL_OKINAWA 1388	Other	Not Defined	OKINAWA 1388		26,1794		127,8244	12945	1388	0	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12945
PSMSL_OLANDS NORRA 2585 UDDE_69	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	OLANDS NORRA UDDE_69		57,3661		17,0972	12046	69	0	1887 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12046
2586 PSMSL_OMAEZAKI II_1263	Other	Not Defined	OMAEZAKI II_1263		34,6083		138,2222	12866	1263	600	181 1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12866
2587 PSMSL_OMINATO 679	Other	Not Defined	OMINATO 679		41,2500		141,1500	12476	679	830	243 1952 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12476
2588 PSMSL_ONAGAWA_674	Other	Not Defined	ONAGAWA_674		38,4333		141,4667	12474	674	0	1951 - 1960	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12474
2589 PSMSL_ONAHAMA_635	Other	Not Defined	ONAHAMA_635		36,9375		140,8919	12438	635	148	42 1951 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12438
2590 PSMSL_ONISAKI_1026	Other	Not Defined	ONISAKI_1026		34,9039		136,8236	12713	1026	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12713
2591 PSMSL_ONSLOW 1631	Other	Not Defined	ONSLOW 1631	-	21,6497		115,1315	13072	1631	0	1985 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13072
2592 PSMSL_OOSTENDE_413	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	OOSTENDE_413		51,2333		2,9167	12272	413	0	1937 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12272
2593 PSMSL_ORTONA II_2097	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ORTONA II_2097		42,3559		14,4149	13314	2097	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13314
2594 PSMSL_ORTONA 972	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ORTONA 972		42,3500		14,4000	12677	972	0	1960 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12677
2595 PSMSL_OSAKA_1099	Other	Not Defined	OSAKA_1099		34,6581		135,4328	12760	1099	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12760
2596 PSMSL_OSCARSBORG_33	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	OSCARSBORG_33		59,6781		10,6049	12022	33	0	1872 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12022

2597	PSMSL_OSHORO I_159	Other	Not Defined	OSHORO I_159	43,2167	140,8667	12115	159	0	1930 - 1962	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12115
2598	PSMSL_OSHORO II_1027	Other	Not Defined	OSHORO II_1027	43,2094	140,8581	12714	1027	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12714
2599	PSMSL_OSKARSHAMN_210 6	Sweden	Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	OSKARSHAMN_2106	57,2750	16,4781	13323	2106	0	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13323
2600	PSMSL_OSLO 62	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	OSLO 62	59,9086	10,7345	12040	62	0	1885 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12040
2601	PSMSL_OTRANTO II_2096	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	OTRANTO II_2096	40,1472	18,4971	13313	2096	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13313
2602	PSMSL_OTRANTO_990	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	OTRANTO_990	40,1333	18,5000	12690	990	0	1961 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12690
2603	PSMSL_OULU / ULEABORG 79	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	OULU / ULEABORG 79	65,0403	25,4182	12055	79	0	1889 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12055
2604	PSMSL_OURA_1102	Other	Not Defined	OURA_1102	32,9767	130,2206	12763	1102	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12763
2605	PSMSL_OWASE_1146	Other	Not Defined	OWASE_1146	34,0764	136,2072	12789	1146	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12789
2606	PSMSL_PADRE ISLAND_919	Other	Not Defined	PADRE ISLAND_919	26,0683	- 97,1517	12646	919	0	1958 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12646
2607	PSMSL_PAGADIAN CITY 2152	Other	Not Defined	PAGADIAN CITY 2152	7,8167	123,4333	13355	2152	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13355
2608	PSMSL_PAGET ISLAND_886	Other	Not Defined	PAGET ISLAND_886	32,3667	- 64,6667	12635	886	0	1957 - 1961	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12635
2609	PSMSL_PAGO BAY, GUAM_2130	Other	Not Defined	PAGO BAY, GUAM_2130	13,4283	144,7967	13343	2130	0	2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13343
2610	PSMSL_PAGO PAGO 539	Other	Not Defined	PAGO PAGO 539	- 14,2800	- 170,6900	12367	539	144	1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12367
2611	PSMSL_PALERMO II_2093	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALERMO II_2093	38,1214	13,3713	13310	2093	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13310
2612	PSMSL_PALERMO_107	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALERMO_107	38,1333	13,3333	12081	107	0	1896 - 1922	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12081
2613	PSMSL_PALERMO_832	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALERMO_832	- 34,5667	- 58,4000	12596	832	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12596
2614	PSMSL_PALINURO 2082	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALINURO 2082	40,0299	15,2753	13302	2082	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13302
2615	PSMSL_PALM BEACH_1669	Other	Not Defined	PALM BEACH_1669	26,7000	- 80,0500	13091	1669	0	1985 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13091
2616	PSMSL_PALMA DE MALLORCA 2_2061	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	PALMA DE MALLORCA 2_2061	39,5602	2,6375	13286	2061	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13286
2617	PSMSL_PALMA DE MALLORCA 1892	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	PALMA DE MALLORCA 1892	39,5509	2,6390	13220	1892	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13220
2618	PSMSL_PALMA_1087	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	PALMA_1087	39,5500	2,6200	12750	1087	0	1964 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12750
2619	PSMSL_PANAMA CITY, ST.ANDREWS BAY, FL_1641	Other	Not Defined	PANAMA CITY, ST.ANDREWS BAY, FL_1641	30,1517	- 85,6667	13082	1641	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13082

PSMSL_PANWA 2620 CAPE_2230	Other	Not Defined	PANWA CAPE_2230	7,8014	98,4064	13383	2230	47	0	103	2013 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13383
PSMSL_PAPEETE-B, FARE 2621 UTE POINT, SOCSIS_1397	France	Shom - France	PAPEETE-B, FARE LITE POINT, SOCSIS_1397	- 17,5331	- 149,5727	12953	1397		140		1969 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12953
2622 PSMSL_PARADIP_1161	Other	Not Defined	PARADIP_1161	20,2667	86,7000	12804	1161		0		1966 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12804
2623 PSMSL_PASAIES 561	Other	Not Defined	PASAIES 561	43,3167	- 1,9167	12383	561		0		1948 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12383
2624 PSMSL_PATRAI_1250	Other	Not Defined	PATRAI_1250	38,4167	21,7287	12856	1250		0		1969 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12856
PSMSL_PATRICIA 2625 BAY_1152	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PATRICIA BAY_1152	48,6500	- 123,4500	12795	1152		0		1976 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12795
PSMSL_PELABUHAN 2626 KELANG 1591	Other	Not Defined	PELABUHAN KELANG 1591	3,0500	101,3583	13051	1591		0		1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13051
2627 PSMSL_PENRHYN_1450	Other	Not Defined	PENRHYN_1450	- 9,0167	- 158,0667	12988	1450		143		1977 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12988
2628 PSMSL_PENSACOLA_246	Other	Not Defined	PENSACOLA_246	30,4033	- 87,2100	12180	246	242	288	216	1923 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12180
PSMSL_PESCHANYI 2629 (PESCHANYI MYS)_1006	Other	Not Defined	PESCHANYI (PESCHANYI MYS)_1006	79,4333	102,4833	12703	1006		0		1962 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12703
PSMSL_PETROPAVLOVSK- 2630 KAMCHATSKY 824	Other	Not Defined	PETROPAVLOVSK- KAMCHATSKY 824	52,9833	158,6500	12588	824		93		1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12588
2631 PSMSL_PVEK_606	Other	Not Defined	PVEK_606	69,7000	170,2500	12417	606	800	0	322	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12417
PSMSL_PHILADELPHIA 2632 (PIER 9N)_135	Other	Not Defined	PHILADELPHIA (PIER 9N)_135	39,9333	- 75,1417	12099	135		0		1900 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12099
2633 PSMSL_PICTOU 1121	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PICTOU 1121	45,6833	- 62,7000	12779	1121		0		1965 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12779
PSMSL_PIETARSAARI / 2634 JAKOBSTAD_194	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	PIETARSAARI / JAKOBSTAD_194	63,7086	22,6896	12141	194		0		1914 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12141
2635 PSMSL_PINEY POINT_971	Other	Not Defined	PINEY POINT_971	38,1333	- 76,5333	12676	971		0		1960 - 1973	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12676
2636 PSMSL_PIONERSKY_1719	Other	Not Defined	PIONERSKY_1719	54,7000	20,4833	13125	1719		0		1987 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13125
2637 PSMSL_PIRAEVS 374	Other	Not Defined	PIRAEVS 374	37,9373	23,6267	12241	374		0		1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12241
2638 PSMSL_PIRAMIDE_867	Other	Not Defined	PIRAMIDE_867	- 42,5833	- 64,2833	12620	867		0		1957 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12620
2639 PSMSL_PLOCE_1945	Other	Not Defined	PLOCE_1945	43,0500	17,4167	13253	1945		0		2006 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13253
2640 PSMSL_PLUM ISLAND 875	Other	Not Defined	PLUM ISLAND 875	41,1667	- 72,2000	12628	875		0		1957 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12628
2641 PSMSL_POHANG_1324	Other	Not Defined	POHANG_1324	36,0472	129,3839	12903	1324		0		1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12903
2642 PSMSL_POHNPEI C_1925	Other	Not Defined	POHNPEI C_1925	6,9805	158,2002	13238	1925		115		2002 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13238

2643	PSMSL_POHNPEI-B_1370	Other	Not Defined	POHNPEI-B_1370	6,9833	158,2333	12936	1370		115		1974 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12936
2644	PSMSL_POINT ATKINSON_193	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	POINT ATKINSON_193	49,3333	- 123,2500	12140	193		0		1914 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12140
2645	PSMSL_POINT REYES_1394	Other	Not Defined	POINT REYES_1394	37,9950	- 122,9767	12951	1394		0		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12951
2646	PSMSL_POINT SAPIN	1138	Other	Not Defined	POINT SAPIN	1138	46,9667	- 64,8333	12785	1138		1965 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12785
2647	PSMSL_POINT TUPPER_1332	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	POINT TUPPER_1332	45,6000	- 61,3667	12909	1332		0		1972 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12909
2648	PSMSL_POINTE DES GALETS_1501	Other	Not Defined	POINTE DES GALETS_1501	-	20,9349	55,2850	13016	1501	17		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13016
2649	PSMSL_POINTE NOIRE	938	Other	Not Defined	POINTE NOIRE	938	- 4,7833	11,8333	12660	938	261	1977 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12660
2650	PSMSL_POINTE ST. GILDAS_1078	Other	Not Defined	POINTE ST. GILDAS_1078	47,1333	- 2,2500	12745	1078		0		1964 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12745
2651	PSMSL_POINTE-A-PITRE_1784	France	Shom - France	POINTE-A-PITRE_1784	16,2244	- 61,5314	13156	1784		0		1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13156
2652	PSMSL_POINTE-AU-PERE_138	Other	Not Defined	POINTE-AU-PERE_138	48,5167	- 68,4667	12102	138		0		1900 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12102
2653	PSMSL_POINTE-DU-CHENE	1309	Other	Not Defined	POINTE-DU-CHENE	1309	46,2500	- 64,5333	12896	1309	0	1971 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12896
2654	PSMSL_POLYARNIY_2027	Other	Not Defined	POLYARNIY_2027	69,2000	33,4833	13265	2027		0		1906 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13265
2655	PSMSL_PONTA DELGADA_258	Other	Not Defined	PONTA DELGADA_258	37,7356	- 25,6714	12188	258	333	245	57	1978 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12188
2656	PSMSL_POPOVA (BELYI OSTROV) 653	Other	Not Defined	POPOVA (BELYI OSTROV) 653	73,3333	70,0500	12456	653		0		1951 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12456
2657	PSMSL_PORT ADELAIDE (OUTER HARBOR)_448	Other	Not Defined	PORT ADELAIDE (OUTER HARBOR)_448	-	34,7798	138,4807	12301	448	0		1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12301
2658	PSMSL_PORT ALBERNI_527	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PORT ALBERNI_527	49,2333	- 124,8167	12362	527		0		1947 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12362
2659	PSMSL_PORT ALLEN, HANAPEPE BAY, KAUAI ISLAND_2129	Other	Not Defined	PORT ALLEN, HANAPEPE BAY, KAUAI ISLAND_2129	21,9033	- 159,5917	13342	2129		0		1989 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13342
2660	PSMSL_PORT ALMA	2072	Other	Not Defined	PORT ALMA	2072	- 23,5833	150,8667	13294	2072	0	1986 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13294
2661	PSMSL_PORT ANGELES, WASHINGTON_2127	Other	Not Defined	PORT ANGELES, WASHINGTON_2127	48,1250	- 123,4400	13340	2127		0		1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13340
2662	PSMSL_PORT ARANSAS, H. CALDWELL PIER_922	Other	Not Defined	PORT ARANSAS, H. CALDWELL PIER_922	27,8267	- 97,0500	12649	922		0		1958 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12649
2663	PSMSL_PORT AU PRINCE	583	Other	Not Defined	PORT AU PRINCE	583	18,5667	- 72,3500	12401	583	209	1949 - 1961	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12401
2664	PSMSL_PORT AUGUSTA_574	Other	Not Defined	PORT AUGUSTA_574	-	32,5500	137,7833	12394	574	0		1949 - 1953	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12394
2665	PSMSL_PORT AUX BASQUES_392	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PORT AUX BASQUES_392	47,5667	- 59,1333	12255	392		0		1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12255

2666	PSMSL_PORT BLAIR_206	Other	Not Defined	PORT BLAIR_206	11,6833	92,7667	12150	206	38	1916 - 1964	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12150
2667	PSMSL_PORT BLOC_1915	Other	Not Defined	PORT BLOC_1915	45,5685	1,0616	13233	1915	803	234 1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13233
2668	PSMSL_PORT CHALMERS_1643	Other	Not Defined	PORT CHALMERS_1643	45,8147	170,6241	13084	1643	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13084
2669	PSMSL_PORT DOUGLAS 2 1471	Other	Not Defined	PORT DOUGLAS 2 1471	16,4833	145,4667	12999	1471	0	1978 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12999
2670	PSMSL_PORT ELIZABETH_820	Other	Not Defined	PORT ELIZABETH_820	33,9511	25,6297	12584	820	76	1978 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12584
2671	PSMSL_PORT ERIN_1793	Other	Not Defined	PORT ERIN_1793	54,0854	4,7681	13161	1793	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13161
2672	PSMSL_PORT GILES 1550	Other	Not Defined	PORT GILES 1550	35,0218	137,7683	13035	1550	0	1995 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13035
2673	PSMSL_PORT HARDY_1071	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PORT HARDY_1071	50,7167	127,4833	12741	1071	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12741
2674	PSMSL_PORT HEDLAND_189	Other	Not Defined	PORT HEDLAND_189	20,3176	118,5744	12137	189	370	73 1966 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12137
2675	PSMSL_PORT IRENE_1705	Other	Not Defined	PORT IRENE_1705	18,3833	122,1000	13114	1705	0	1987 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13114
2676	PSMSL_PORT ISABEL 497	Other	Not Defined	PORT ISABEL 497	26,0600	97,2150	12340	497	0	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12340
2677	PSMSL_PORT JEFFERSON_848	Other	Not Defined	PORT JEFFERSON_848	40,9500	73,0767	12609	848	0	1957 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12609
2678	PSMSL_PORT KEMBLA_831	Other	Not Defined	PORT KEMBLA_831	34,4738	150,9119	12595	831	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12595
2679	PSMSL_PORT LINCOLN 230	Other	Not Defined	PORT LINCOLN 230	34,7159	135,8700	12169	230	0	1965 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12169
2680	PSMSL_PORT LOUIS_477	Other	Not Defined	PORT LOUIS_477	20,1500	57,5000	12325	477	329	77 1942 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12325
2681	PSMSL_PORT LYTTTELTON_247	Other	Not Defined	PORT LYTTTELTON_247	43,6056	172,7219	12181	247	169	51 1923 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12181
2682	PSMSL_PORT MACDONNELL L_871	Other	Not Defined	PORT MACDONNELL L_871	38,0000	140,6667	12624	871	0	1957 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12624
2683	PSMSL_PORT MANSFIELD 1038	Other	Not Defined	PORT MANSFIELD 1038	26,5533	97,4217	12724	1038	0	1963 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12724
2684	PSMSL_PORT MORESBY_439	Other	Not Defined	PORT MORESBY_439	9,4833	147,1333	12293	439	0	1957 - 1959	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12293
2685	PSMSL_PORT NOLLOTH_836	Other	Not Defined	PORT NOLLOTH_836	29,2567	16,8678	12600	836	0	1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12600
2686	PSMSL_PORT OF SPAIN 415	Other	Not Defined	PORT OF SPAIN 415	10,6500	61,5167	12274	415	203	1983 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12274
2687	PSMSL_PORT ORFORD_1640	Other	Not Defined	PORT ORFORD_1640	42,7383	124,4983	13081	1640	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13081
2688	PSMSL_PORT PIRIE_216	Other	Not Defined	PORT PIRIE_216	33,1776	138,0117	12159	216	540	155 1941 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12159

PSMSL_PORT 2689 RENFREW_842	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PORT RENFREW_842	48,5500	-	124,4167	12605	842	0	1957 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12605
2690 PSMSL_PORT ROYAL_744	Other	Not Defined	PORT ROYAL_744	17,9333	-	76,8500	12524	744	210	1954 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12524
2691 PSMSL_PORT SAID_253	Other	Not Defined	PORT SAID_253	31,2500		32,3000	12184	253	0	1923 - 1946	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12184
PSMSL_PORT SAN 2692 LUIS_508	Other	Not Defined	PORT SAN LUIS_508	35,1767	-	120,7600	12346	508	0	1945 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12346
PSMSL_PORT 2693 STANVAC_1506	Other	Not Defined	PORT STANVAC_1506	-	35,1086	138,4670	13018	1506	0	1993 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13018
2694 PSMSL_PORT SUDAN_1690	Other	Not Defined	PORT SUDAN_1690	19,6333		37,1167	13104	1690	0	1986 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13104
PSMSL_PORT 2695 TARANAKI_996	Other	Not Defined	PORT TARANAKI_996	-	39,0562	174,0344	12693	996	0	1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12693
PSMSL_PORT 2696 TOWNSEND_1325	Other	Not Defined	PORT TOWNSEND_1325	48,1117	-	122,7567	12904	1325	0	1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12904
2697 PSMSL_PORT TUDY_1247	Other	Not Defined	PORT TUDY_1247	47,6443	-	3,4459	12853	1247	0	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12853
2698 PSMSL_PORT VILA B_1841	Other	Not Defined	PORT VILA B_1841	-	17,7553	168,3077	13196	1841	348	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13196
PSMSL_PORT 2699 WALLAROO_383	Other	Not Defined	PORT WALLAROO_383	-	33,9333	137,6333	12248	383	554	159 1933 - 1937	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12248
PSMSL_PORT- 2700 ALFRED_1392	Other	Not Defined	PORT-ALFRED_1392	48,3333	-	70,8667	12949	1392	0	1975 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12949
2701 PSMSL_PORTBURY_2011	Other	Not Defined	PORTBURY_2011	51,5000	-	2,7285	13258	2011	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13258
PSMSL_PORTLAND 2702 (MAINE) 183	Other	Not Defined	PORTLAND (MAINE) 183	43,6567	-	70,2467	12134	183	0	1912 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12134
2703 PSMSL_PORTLAND_1547	Other	Not Defined	PORTLAND_1547	-	38,3434	141,6132	13032	1547	55	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13032
2704 PSMSL_PORTNEUF_951	Other	Not Defined	PORTNEUF_951	46,6833	-	71,8833	12655	951	0	1960 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12655
PSMSL_PORTO 2705 CORSINI_100	Other	Not Defined	PORTO CORSINI_100	44,5000		12,2833	12074	100	0	1969 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12074
PSMSL_PORTO 2706 EMPEDOCLE SICILY 2083	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTO EMPEDOCLE, SICILY 2083	37,2858		13,5268	13303	2083	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13303
PSMSL_PORTO 2707 GARIBALDI_2144	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTO GARIBALDI_2144	44,6779		12,2494	13349	2144	0	2009 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13349
PSMSL_PORTO GRANDE 2708 (ST. VINCENT) 2_1769	Other	Not Defined	PORTO GRANDE (ST. VINCENT) 2_1769	16,8833	-	25,0000	13148	1769	0	1990 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13148
PSMSL_PORTO 2709 MAURIZIO 108	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTO MAURIZIO 108	43,8667		8,0167	12082	108	0	1896 - 1922	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12082
PSMSL_PORTO 2710 TORRES_2084	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTO TORRES_2084	40,8422		8,4039	13304	2084	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13304
PSMSL_PORTPATRICK_1211 5	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PORTPATRICK_1215	54,8426	-	5,1200	12829	1215	0	1968 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12829

2712	PSMSL_PORTRUSH_1867	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PORTRUSH_1867	55,2068	-	6,6568	13210	1867	0	1995 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13210	
2713	PSMSL_PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS_137	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PORT-SAINT-FRANCOIS_137	46,2667	-	72,6167	12101	137	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12101	
2714	PSMSL_PORTSOUTH (NORFOLK NAVY YARD)_399	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PORTSMOUTH (NORFOLK NAVY YARD)_399	36,8217	-	76,2933	12262	399	0	1935 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12262	
2715	PSMSL_PORTSOUTH_350	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	PORTSMOUTH_350	50,8023	-	1,1113	12225	350	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12225	
2716	PSMSL_POSIDHONIA_409	Other	Not Defined	POSIDHONIA_409	37,9512	-	22,9601	12268	409	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12268	
2717	PSMSL_POTI_41	Other	Not Defined	POTI_41	42,1667	-	41,6833	12026	41	0	1874 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12026	
2718	PSMSL_PRAVDY (PRAVDY OSTROV)_615	Other	Not Defined	PRAVDY (PRAVDY OSTROV)_615	76,2667	-	94,7667	12426	615	0	1950 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12426	
2719	PSMSL_PREOBRAZHENIA (PREOBRAZHENIA OSTROV)_652	Other	Not Defined	PREOBRAZHENIA (PREOBRAZHENIA OSTROV)_652	74,6667	-	112,9333	12455	652	0	1951 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12455	
2720	PSMSL_PREVEZA_410	Other	Not Defined	PREVEZA_410	38,9591	-	20,7566	12269	410	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12269	
2721	PSMSL_PRIMORSK_237	Other	Not Defined	PRIMORSK_237	60,3500	-	28,6167	12175	237	0	1921 - 1939	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12175	
2722	PSMSL_PRINCE RUPERT_167	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	PRINCE RUPERT_167	54,3167	-	130,3333	12122	167	155	1909 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12122	
2723	PSMSL_PROGRESO_690	Other	Not Defined	PROGRESO_690	21,3000	-	89,6667	12486	690	213	1952 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12486	
2724	PSMSL_PROVIDENCE (STATE PIER)_430	Other	Not Defined	PROVIDENCE (STATE PIER)_430	41,8067	-	71,4000	12284	430	0	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12284	
2725	PSMSL_PROVIDENIA_662	Other	Not Defined	PROVIDENIA_662	64,4167	-	173,2333	12463	662	309	1951 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12463	
2726	PSMSL_PRUDHOE BAY, ALASKA_1857	Other	Not Defined	PRUDHOE BAY, ALASKA_1857	70,4000	-	148,5267	13205	1857	151	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13205	
2727	PSMSL_PT. LA RUE_1846	Other	Not Defined	PT. LA RUE_1846	-	-	4,6667	55,5333	13201	1846	339	1993 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13201
2728	PSMSL_PUERTO ANGEL_1015	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO ANGEL_1015	15,5000	-	96,5000	12709	1015	164	1967 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12709	
2729	PSMSL_PUERTO ARMUELLES_668	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO ARMUELLES_668	8,2667	-	82,8667	12468	668	223	253 1951 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12468	
2730	PSMSL_PUERTO BOLIVAR_1277	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO BOLIVAR_1277	-	-	3,2667	80,0000	12877	1277	0	1970 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12877
2731	PSMSL_PUERTO CASTILLA_779	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO CASTILLA_779	16,0167	-	86,0333	12552	779	0	1955 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12552	
2732	PSMSL_PUERTO CORTES_557	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO CORTES_557	15,8333	-	87,9500	12380	557	0	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12380	
2733	PSMSL_PUERTO DE HIERRO_782	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO DE HIERRO_782	10,6167	-	62,0833	12554	782	0	1955 - 1963	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12554	
2734	PSMSL_PUERTO DESEADO_185	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO DESEADO_185	-	-	47,7500	65,9167	12135	185	190	1970 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12135

PSMSL_PUERTO 2735 LIMON_552	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO LIMON_552	10,0000	-	83,0333	12377	552	0	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12377
PSMSL_PUERTO 2736 MADRYN_501	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO MADRYN_501	42,7667	-	65,0333	12343	501	253	191 290 1944 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12343
PSMSL_PUERTO 2737 PLATA_577	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO PLATA_577	19,8167	-	70,7000	12396	577	0	1949 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12396
PSMSL_PUERTO PRINCESA, 2738 PALAWAN 207	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO PRINCESA, PALAWAN 207	9,7500	-	118,7333	12151	207	0	1990 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12151
PSMSL_PUERTO 2739 SOBERANIA_1603	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO SOBERANIA_1603	62,4833	-	59,6333	13060	1603	189	1984 - 2002	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13060
PSMSL_PUERTO 2740 WILLIAMS_1122	Other	Not Defined	PUERTO WILLIAMS_1122	54,9167	-	67,6167	12780	1122	0	1965 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12780
PSMSL_PULAU 2741 LANGKAWI 1676	Other	Not Defined	PULAU LANGKAWI 1676	6,4308	-	99,7642	13097	1676	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13097
PSMSL_PULAU 2742 PINANG_1595	Other	Not Defined	PULAU PINANG_1595	5,4217	-	100,3467	13055	1595	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13055
PSMSL_PULAU 2743 TIOMAN_1678	Other	Not Defined	PULAU TIOMAN_1678	2,8072	-	104,1400	13099	1678	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13099
PSMSL_PULUPANDAN, NEGROS 2744 OCCIDENTAL_2151	Other	Not Defined	PULUPANDAN, NEGROS OCCIDENTAL_2151	10,5167	-	122,8000	13354	2151	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13354
PSMSL_PUNTA 2745 ARENAS 473	Other	Not Defined	PUNTA ARENAS 473	53,1667	-	70,9000	12321	473	0	1964 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12321
PSMSL_PUNTA DEL 2746 ESTE_434	Other	Not Defined	PUNTA DEL ESTE_434	34,9667	-	54,9500	12288	434	0	1964 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12288
2747 PSMSL_PUNTARENAS_464	Other	Not Defined	PUNTARENAS_464	9,9667	-	84,8333	12314	464	0	1941 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12314
PSMSL_QIKIQTARJUAQ_19 2748 35	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	QIKIQTARJUAQ 1935	67,8667	-	64,1167	13247	1935	0	2004 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13247
PSMSL_QINHUANGDAO_6 2749 14	Other	Not Defined	QINHUANGDAO_614	39,9000	-	119,6000	12425	614	0	1950 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12425
2750 PSMSL_QUARRY BAY_1674	Other	Not Defined	QUARRY BAY_1674	22,2911	-	114,2133	13095	1674	360	77 324 1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13095
PSMSL_QUEBEC 2751 (LAUZON)_173	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	QUEBEC (LAUZON)_173	46,8333	-	71,1667	12127	173	0	1910 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12127
PSMSL_QUEEN CHARLOTTE 2752 CITY 829	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	QUEEN CHARLOTTE CITY 829	53,2500	-	132,0667	12593	829	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12593
2753 PSMSL_QUEPOS_844	Other	Not Defined	QUEPOS_844	9,4000	-	84,1667	12606	844	167	1957 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12606
2754 PSMSL_QUEQUEN_223	Other	Not Defined	QUEQUEN_223	38,5833	-	58,7000	12162	223	0	1918 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12162
2755 PSMSL_QUINHON 1449	Other	Not Defined	QUINHON 1449	13,7667	-	109,2500	12987	1449	75	1977 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12987
PSMSL_RAAHE / 2756 BRAHESTAD_240	Other	Not Defined	RAAHE / BRAHESTAD_240	64,6663	-	24,4071	12178	240	0	1922 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12178
2757 PSMSL_RABAUL_1164	Other	Not Defined	RABAUL_1164	4,2000	-	152,1833	12805	1164	364	65 88 1966 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12805

PSMSL_RAFFLES LIGHT 2758 HOUSE_1351	Other	Not Defined	RAFFLES LIGHT HOUSE_1351	1,1667	103,7500	12921	1351	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12921
2759 PSMSL_RAFINA_1695	Other	Not Defined	RAFINA_1695	38,0333	24,0000	13105	1695	0	1986 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13105
2760 PSMSL_RANGIROA_2216	France	Shom - France	RANGIROA_2216	-	14,9458 - 147,7060	13376	2216	355	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13376
2761 PSMSL_RANGOON 210	Other	Not Defined	RANGOON 210	16,7667	96,1667	12154	210	0	1916 - 1962	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12154
PSMSL_RAROTONGA 2762 B_1843	Other	Not Defined	RAROTONGA B_1843	-	21,2048 - 159,7848	13198	1843	139	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13198
2763 PSMSL_RAROTONGA_1453	Other	Not Defined	RAROTONGA_1453	-	21,2000 - 159,7667	12991	1453		1807 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12991
2764 PSMSL_RATAN 88	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	RATAN 88	63,9861	20,8950	12064	88	0	1892 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12064
2765 PSMSL_RATMANOVA_617	Other	Not Defined	RATMANOVA_617	66,8500	- 169,1333	12428	617	0	1950 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12428
2766 PSMSL_RAU-CHUA_605	Other	Not Defined	RAU-CHUA_605	69,5000	166,5833	12416	605	0	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12416
PSMSL_RAUMA / 2767 RAUMO_376	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	RAUMA / RAUMO_376	61,1335	21,4258	12243	376	0	1933 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12243
PSMSL_REAL 2768 QUEZON 2035	Other	Not Defined	REAL QUEZON 2035	14,6667	121,6000	13272	2035	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13272
2769 PSMSL_RECIFE_556	Other	Not Defined	RECIFE_556	-	8,0500 - 34,8667	12379	556	0	1948 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12379
2770 PSMSL_REEDY POINT_786	Other	Not Defined	REEDY POINT_786	39,5583	- 75,5733	12556	786	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12556
PSMSL_REGGIO CALABRIA 2771 II 2142	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	REGGIO CALABRIA II 2142	38,1217	15,6489	13348	2142	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13348
PSMSL_REGGIO 2772 CALABRIA_670	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	REGGIO CALABRIA_670	38,1000	15,6500	12470	670	0	1951 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12470
2773 PSMSL_REPOSAARI_85	Other	Not Defined	REPOSAARI_85	61,6167	21,4500	12061	85	0	1913 - 1926	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12061
2774 PSMSL_RESOLUTE_863	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	RESOLUTE_863	74,6833	- 94,8833	12617	863	0	1957 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12617
2775 PSMSL_REYKJAVIK 638	Other	Not Defined	REYKJAVIK 638	64,1506	- 21,9399	12441	638		1956 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12441
2776 PSMSL_RHODOS_1243	Other	Not Defined	RHODOS_1243	36,4417	28,2364	12849	1243	729	192 1969 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12849
PSMSL_RICHARDS 2777 BAY_1443	France	Shom - France	RICHARDS BAY_1443	-	28,8119 32,0786	12981	1443	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12981
2778 PSMSL_RICHMOND 462	Other	Not Defined	RICHMOND 462	37,5667	- 77,4500	12312	462	0	1941 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12312
2779 PSMSL_RIKITEA_1253	France	Shom - France	RIKITEA_1253	-	23,1223 - 134,9667	12859	1253	138	1969 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12859
2780 PSMSL_RIMOUSKI_1597	Other	Not Defined	RIMOUSKI_1597	48,4833	- 68,5167	13057	1597	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13057

PSMSL_RINCON 2781 ISLAND_1013	Other	Not Defined	RINCON ISLAND_1013	34,3483	-	119,4417	12708	1013	0	1962 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12708	
2782 PSMSL_RINGHALS_2111	Sweden	Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	RINGHALS_2111	57,2497	-	12,1125	13328	2111	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13328	
PSMSL_RIO DE 2783 JANEIRO_579	Other	Not Defined	RIO DE JANEIRO_579	-	22,9333	-	43,1333	12398	579	1949 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12398	
2784 PSMSL RIO SANTIAGO	897 Other	Not Defined	RIO SANTIAGO_897	-	34,8500	-	57,9000	12637	897	1957 - 1959	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12637	
2785 PSMSL RIOHACHA_714	Other	Not Defined	RIOHACHA_714	11,5500	-	72,9167	12501	714	0	1953 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12501	
PSMSL_RIVIERE-AU- 2786 RENARD_1213	Other	Not Defined	RIVIERE-AU-RENARD_1213	49,0000	-	64,3833	12827	1213	0	1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12827	
PSMSL_RIVIERE-DU- 2787 LOUP_1284	Other	Not Defined	RIVIERE-DU-LOUP_1284	47,8500	-	69,5667	12883	1284	0	1970 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12883	
2788 PSMSL ROCKLAND_1279	Other	Not Defined	ROCKLAND_1279	44,1050	-	69,1017	12879	1279	0	1970 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12879	
2789 PSMSL ROCKPORT_538	Other	Not Defined	ROCKPORT_538	28,0217	-	97,0467	12366	538	0	1948 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12366	
2790 PSMSL ROBBYHAVN_762	Other	Not Defined	ROBBYHAVN_762	54,6558	-	11,3486	12539	762	0	1955 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12539	
PSMSL_RODRIGUES 2791 IS_1672	Other	Not Defined	RODRIGUES IS_1672	-	19,6667	63,4167	13094	1672	19	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13094	
2792 PSMSL RONNSKAR_30	Other	Not Defined	RONNSKAR_30	63,0667	-	20,8000	12019	30	0	1867 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12019	
PSMSL_ROOMPOT 2793 BUITEN_1551	Other	Not Defined	ROOMPOT BUITEN_1551	51,6197	-	3,6819	13036	1551	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13036	
2794 PSMSL RORVIK_1241	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	RORVIK_1241	64,8595	-	11,2301	12847	1241	234	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12847	
2795 PSMSL ROSALES_870	Other	Not Defined	ROSALES_870	-	38,9333	-	62,0667	12623	870	1957 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12623	
2796 PSMSL ROSCOFF_1347	France	Shom - France	ROSCOFF_1347	48,7184	-	3,9659	12918	1347	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12918	
PSMSL_ROSSLYN 2797 BAY_1760	Other	Not Defined	ROSSLYN BAY_1760	-	23,1610	150,7902	13143	1760	355	81 1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13143	
2798 PSMSL ROSYTH_1074	Other	Not Defined	ROSYTH_1074	56,0167	-	3,4500	12743	1074	0	1964 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12743	
2799 PSMSL ROTHERA_1931	Other	Not Defined	ROTHERA_1931	-	67,5713	-	68,1298	13243	1931	8	342 119 2003 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13243
2800 PSMSL ROVINI_761	Other	Not Defined	ROVINI_761	45,0833	-	13,6283	12538	761	0	1955 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12538	
2801 PSMSL RUSSARO_28	Other	Not Defined	RUSSARO_28	59,7667	-	22,9500	12017	28	0	1866 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12017	
PSMSL_RUSSKAIA GAVAN 2802 IL_710	Other	Not Defined	RUSSKAIA GAVAN IL_710	76,1833	-	62,5833	12498	710	99	1953 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12498	
PSMSL_RUSSKAYA 2803 GAVAN_711	Other	Not Defined	RUSSKAYA GAVAN_711	76,2000	-	62,5833	12499	711	99	1953 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12499	

PSMSL_RUSSKII (RUSSKII OSTROV)_655	Other	Not Defined	RUSSKII (RUSSKII OSTROV)_655	77,1667	96,4333	12458	655	0	1951 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12458
PSMSL_RUSTICO_1330	Other	Not Defined	RUSTICO_1330	46,4667	63,2833	12908	1330	834	239 1973 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12908
PSMSL_SABINE PASS NORTH_1835	Other	Not Defined	SABINE PASS NORTH_1835	29,7283	93,8700	13191	1835	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13191
PSMSL_SABINE PASS 920	Other	Not Defined	SABINE PASS 920	29,7050	93,8533	12647	920	0	1958 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12647
PSMSL_SAGUNTO_2059	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SAGUNTO_2059	39,6339	0,2062	13284	2059	0	2007 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13284
PSMSL_SAGYLLAH-ARY_1019	Other	Not Defined	SAGYLLAH-ARY_1019	73,1500	128,8833	12710	1019	0	1962 - 1980	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12710
PSMSL_SAIGO 1095	Other	Not Defined	SAIGO 1095	36,2014	133,3311	12756	1095	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12756
PSMSL_SAINT JOHN, N.B._195	Other	Not Defined	SAINT JOHN, N.B._195	45,2667	66,0667	12142	195	0	1896 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12142
PSMSL_SAIPAN_1474	Other	Not Defined	SAIPAN_1474	15,2333	145,7500	13002	1474	118	1978 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13002
PSMSL_SAKAI_811	Other	Not Defined	SAKAI_811	35,5478	133,2431	12575	811	799	209 1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12575
PSMSL_SALAMANDER_1427	Other	Not Defined	SALAMANDER 1427	33,0667	18,0000	12972	1427	0	1976 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12972
PSMSL_SALERNO_2086	Other	Not Defined	SALERNO_2086	40,6766	14,7508	13305	2086	0	2001 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13305
PSMSL_SALGRUND_228	Other	Not Defined	SALGRUND_228	62,3333	21,2000	12167	228	0	1919 - 1928	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12167
PSMSL_SALINA CRUZ 689	Other	Not Defined	SALINA CRUZ 689	16,1667	95,2000	12485	689	0	1952 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12485
PSMSL_SALINOPOLIS_589	Other	Not Defined	SALINOPOLIS_589	0,6500	47,3833	12403	589	0	1949 - 1956	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12403
PSMSL_SALVADOR_578	Other	Not Defined	SALVADOR_578	12,9667	38,5167	12397	578	334	1949 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12397
PSMSL_SAMOS ISLAND - VATHI_1941	Other	Not Defined	SAMOS ISLAND - VATHI_1941	37,7552	26,9765	13250	1941	0	2005 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13250
PSMSL_SAN CLEMENTE ISLAND 883	Other	Not Defined	SAN CLEMENTE ISLAND 883	33,0000	118,5500	12634	883	0	1957 - 1962	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12634
PSMSL_SAN CRISTOBAL_927	Other	Not Defined	SAN CRISTOBAL_927	0,9000	89,6167	12652	927	0	1960 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12652
PSMSL_SAN DIEGO (QUARANTINE STATION)_158	Other	Not Defined	SAN DIEGO (QUARANTINE STATION)_158	32,7133	117,1733	12114	158	0	1906 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12114
PSMSL_SAN FELIX 1751	Other	Not Defined	SAN FELIX 1751	26,2922	80,1086	13139	1751	177	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13139
PSMSL_SAN FERNANDO, LA UNION_548	Other	Not Defined	SAN FERNANDO, LA UNION_548	16,6167	120,3000	12375	548	0	1948 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12375
PSMSL_SAN FRANCISCO_10	Other	Not Defined	SAN FRANCISCO_10	37,8067	122,4650	12000	10	158	1854 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12000

2827	PSMSL_SAN JOSE II_777	Other	Not Defined	SAN JOSE II_777	13,9167	-	90,8167	12551	777	283	0	336	1963 - 1975	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12551
2828	PSMSL_SAN JOSE_1711	Other	Not Defined	SAN JOSE_1711	12,3333	121,0833	13119	1711			0		1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13119
2829	PSMSL_SAN JOSE_973	Other	Not Defined	SAN JOSE_973	13,9167	-	90,8333	12678	973	316	0	267	1960 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12678
2830	PSMSL_SAN JUAN 1001	Other	Not Defined	SAN JUAN 1001	18,4583	-	66,1150	12698	1001		206		1962 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12698
2831	PSMSL_SAN JUAN_923	Other	Not Defined	SAN JUAN_923	-	15,3667	-	75,2000	12650	923	0		1958 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12650
2832	PSMSL_SAN MATEO_1663	Other	Not Defined	SAN MATEO_1663	37,5833	-	122,2500	13090	1663		0		1985 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13090
2833	PSMSL_SAND POINT, POPOF IS., AK 1634	Other	Not Defined	SAND POINT, POPOF IS., AK 1634	55,3367	-	160,5017	13075	1634		100		1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13075
2834	PSMSL_SANDAKAN_1834	Other	Not Defined	SANDAKAN_1834	5,8100	118,0672	13190	1834			0		1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13190
2835	PSMSL_SANDNESSJOEN_1137	Other	Not Defined	SANDNESSJOEN_1137	66,0167	12,6333	12784	1137			0		1965 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12784
2836	PSMSL_SANDWICH MARINA, CAPE COD CANAL ENTRANCE_775	Other	Not Defined	SANDWICH MARINA, CAPE COD CANAL ENTRANCE_775	41,7667	-	70,5000	12549	775		0		1955 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12549
2837	PSMSL_SANDY HOOK 366	Other	Not Defined	SANDY HOOK 366	40,4667	-	74,0083	12236	366		0		1932 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12236
2838	PSMSL_SANNIKOVA (SANNIKOVA PROLIV)_602	Other	Not Defined	SANNIKOVA (SANNIKOVA PROLIV)_602	74,6667	138,9000	12413	602	907		0	37	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12413
2839	PSMSL_SANTA BARBARA, CALIFORNIA_2126	Other	Not Defined	SANTA BARBARA, CALIFORNIA_2126	34,4083	-	119,6850	13339	2126		0		1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13339
2840	PSMSL_SANTA CRUZ DE LA PALMA B 568	Other	Not Defined	SANTA CRUZ DE LA PALMA B 568	28,6720	-	17,7687	12390	568		0		1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12390
2841	PSMSL_SANTA CRUZ DE LA PALMA_585	Other	Not Defined	SANTA CRUZ DE LA PALMA_585	28,6833	-	17,7500	12402	585		0		1949 - 1960	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12402
2842	PSMSL_SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE I_303	Other	Not Defined	SANTA CRUZ DE TENERIFE I_303	28,4833	-	16,2333	12204	303		0		1927 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12204
2843	PSMSL_SANTA CRUZ_1472	Other	Not Defined	SANTA CRUZ_1472	-	0,7500	-	90,3167	13000	1472			1807 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13000
2844	PSMSL_SANTA MONICA (MUNICIPAL PIER) 377	Other	Not Defined	SANTA MONICA (MUNICIPAL PIER) 377	34,0083	-	118,5000	12244	377		0		1933 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12244
2845	PSMSL_SANTANA_1975	Other	Not Defined	SANTANA_1975	-	0,0500	-	51,1667	13255	1975	0		1984 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13255
2846	PSMSL_SANTANDER I_485	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SANTANDER I_485	43,4613	-	3,7908	12329	485		0		1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12329
2847	PSMSL_SANTANDER II 1051	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SANTANDER II 1051	43,4667	-	3,7667	12727	1051		0		1963 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12727
2848	PSMSL_SANTANDER III_1807	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SANTANDER III_1807	43,4613	-	3,7908	13174	1807		0		1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13174
2849	PSMSL_SANTO TOMAS DE CASTILLA_1080	Other	Not Defined	SANTO TOMAS DE CASTILLA_1080	15,7000	-	88,6167	12746	1080		0		1964 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12746

2850	PSMSL_SAPPI_226	Other	Not Defined	SAPPI_226	61,4833	21,3333	12165	226	0	1919 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12165
2851	PSMSL_SASEBO I_672	Other	Not Defined	SASEBO I_672	33,1667	129,7167	12472	672	0	1951 - 1966	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12472
2852	PSMSL_SASEBO II_1147	Other	Not Defined	SASEBO II_1147	33,1581	129,7239	12790	1147	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12790
2853	PSMSL_SASSNITZ_397	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	SASSNITZ_397	54,5108	13,6431	12260	397	0	1935 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12260
2854	PSMSL_SAUGOR/SAGAR_417	Other	Not Defined	SAUGOR/SAGAR_417	21,6500	88,0500	12275	417	0	1937 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12275
2855	PSMSL_SAVAGE COVE_1280	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	SAVAGE COVE_1280	51,3333	56,7000	12880	1280	0	1970 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12880
2856	PSMSL_SCOTT BASE_2029	Other	Not Defined	SCOTT BASE_2029	77,8501	166,7690	13267	2029	134	2001 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13267
2857	PSMSL_SEATTLE_127	Other	Not Defined	SEATTLE_127	47,6017	122,3383	12093	127	0	1899 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12093
2858	PSMSL_SEAVEY ISLAND_288	Other	Not Defined	SEAVEY ISLAND_288	43,0800	70,7417	12199	288	0	1926 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12199
2859	PSMSL_SECOND VALLEY_443	Other	Not Defined	SECOND VALLEY_443	35,5167	138,1667	12296	443	0	1939 - 1942	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12296
2860	PSMSL_SEJINGKAT_1893	Other	Not Defined	SEJINGKAT_1893	1,5828	110,4222	13221	1893	0	1997 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13221
2861	PSMSL_SE-LAHA_1200	Other	Not Defined	SE-LAHA_1200	70,1500	72,5667	12820	1200	775	217 1967 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12820
2862	PSMSL_SELDOVIA_1070	Other	Not Defined	SELDOVIA_1070	59,4400	151,7200	12740	1070	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12740
2863	PSMSL_SEMBAWANG_724	Other	Not Defined	SEMBAWANG_724	1,4667	103,8333	12508	724	0	1954 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12508
2864	PSMSL_SEOGWIPO_1627	Other	Not Defined	SEOGWIPO_1627	33,2400	126,5617	13068	1627	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13068
2865	PSMSL_SEPT-ILES_1322	Other	Not Defined	SEPT-ILES_1322	50,2000	66,4000	12901	1322	0	1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12901
2866	PSMSL_SETE_958	France	Shom - France	SETE_958	43,3976	3,6991	12672	958	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12672
2867	PSMSL_SETROIA_1425	Other	Not Defined	SETROIA_1425	38,5000	8,9000	12970	1425	0	1976 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12970
2868	PSMSL_SETTLEMENT POINT_1646	Other	Not Defined	SETTLEMENT POINT_1646	26,7100	78,9967	13087	1646	211	1985 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13087
2869	PSMSL_SEVASTOPOL_42	Other	Not Defined	SEVASTOPOL_42	44,6167	33,5333	12027	42	0	1910 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12027
2870	PSMSL_SEVILLA-ESCLUSA_2047	Other	Not Defined	SEVILLA-ESCLUSA_2047	37,3317	5,9950	13273	2047	0	1992 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13273
2871	PSMSL_SEWARD_266	Other	Not Defined	SEWARD_266	60,1200	149,4267	12191	266	150	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12191
2872	PSMSL_SEWELLS POINT, HAMPTON ROADS_299	Other	Not Defined	SEWELLS POINT, HAMPTON ROADS_299	36,9467	76,3300	12201	299	0	1927 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12201

PSMSL_SHALAUROVA 2873 (SHALAUROVA MYS)_603	Other	Not Defined	SHALAUROVA (SHALAUROVA MYS)_603	73,1833	143,2333	12414	603	0	1950 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12414
2874 PSMSL_SHANWEI_1406	Other	Not Defined	SHANWEI_1406	22,7500	115,3500	12959	1406	0	1975 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12959
2875 PSMSL_SHEERNESS_3	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	SHEERNESS_3	51,4456	0,7434	11995	3	0	1832 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=11995
2876 PSMSL_SHEK PIK 1902	Other	Not Defined	SHEK PIK 1902	22,2203	113,8944	13227	1902	0	1998 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13227
PSMSL_SHELL POINT, 2877 WALKER CREEK_1670	Other	Not Defined	SHELL POINT, WALKER CREEK_1670	30,0600	84,2900	13092	1670	362	83 1985 - 1986	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13092
2878 PSMSL_SHIUISUO_1404	Other	Not Defined	SHIUISUO_1404	35,3833	119,5500	12957	1404	0	1975 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12957
PSMSL_SHIMIZU- 2879 MINATO 808	Other	Not Defined	SHIMIZU-MINATO 808	35,0117	138,5175	12572	808	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12572
PSMSL_SHIMONOSEKI 2880 II_783	Other	Not Defined	SHIMONOSEKI II_783	33,9667	130,9500	12555	783	0	1955 - 1960	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12555
PSMSL_SHIMONOSEKI 2881 III_1830	Other	Not Defined	SHIMONOSEKI III_1830	33,9250	130,9278	13186	1830	0	1993 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13186
2882 PSMSL_SHIRAHAMA_1150	Other	Not Defined	SHIRAHAMA_1150	33,6836	135,3753	12793	1150	11	146 1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12793
PSMSL_SHUTE HARBOUR 2883 2 1569	Other	Not Defined	SHUTE HARBOUR 2 1569	20,2833	148,7833	13040	1569	0	1983 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13040
2884 PSMSL_SIBAURA_952	Other	Not Defined	SIBAURA_952	35,6333	139,7500	12666	952	0	1960 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12666
2885 PSMSL_SIMONS BAY_826	Other	Not Defined	SIMONS BAY_826	34,1878	18,4401	12590	826	52	109 1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12590
PSMSL_SIMRISHAMN_210 2886 7	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SIMRISHAMN 2107	55,5575	14,3578	13324	2107	0	1982 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13324
2887 PSMSL_SINES_1456	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	SINES_1456	37,9500	8,8833	12994	1456	0	1977 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12994
2888 PSMSL_SIRO5_1234	Other	Not Defined	SIRO5_1234	37,4400	24,9458	12841	1234	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12841
2889 PSMSL_SITKA_426	Other	Not Defined	SITKA_426	57,0517	135,3417	12280	426	154	1938 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12280
2890 PSMSL_SKAGSUUDE 2102	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SKAGSUUDE 2102	63,1906	19,0125	13319	2102	18	122 1982 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13319
2891 PSMSL_SKAGWAY_495	Other	Not Defined	SKAGWAY_495	59,4500	135,3267	12338	495	0	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12338
2892 PSMSL_SKANOR_2108	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SKANOR_2108	55,4167	12,8294	13325	2108	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13325
2893 PSMSL_SKOPELOS 1907	Other	Not Defined	SKOPELOS 1907	39,1236	23,7295	13229	1907	0	1999 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13229
2894 PSMSL_SKURU_142	Other	Not Defined	SKURU_142	60,1000	23,5500	12105	142	0	1900 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12105
2895 PSMSL_SLIPSHAVN_98	Other	Not Defined	SLIPSHAVN_98	55,2883	10,8278	12072	98	0	1896 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12072

2896	PSMSL_SMOGEN_179	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SMOGEN_179	58,3536	11,2178	12131	179	0	1911 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12131
2897	PSMSL_SODERSKAR_29	Other	Not Defined	SODERSKAR_29	60,1167	25,4167	12018	29	0	1866 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12018
2898	PSMSL_SOKCHO_1365	Other	Not Defined	SOKCHO_1365	38,2072	128,5942	12931	1365	0	1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12931
2899	PSMSL_SOLNECHNAIA (SOLNECHNAIA BLUKHTA) 656	Other	Not Defined	SOLNECHNAIA (SOLNECHNAIA BLUKHTA) 656	78,2000	103,2667	12459	656	0	1951 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12459
2900	PSMSL_SOLOMON'S ISLAND (BIOL. LAB.)_412	Other	Not Defined	SOLOMON'S ISLAND (BIOL. LAB.)_412	38,3167	76,4517	12271	412	0	1937 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12271
2901	PSMSL_SOMA_1345	Other	Not Defined	SOMA_1345	37,8308	140,9622	12916	1345	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12916
2902	PSMSL_SOOKE 921	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	SOOKE 921	48,3667	123,7333	12648	921	0	1958 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12648
2903	PSMSL_SOPOCHNAIA KARGA_917	Other	Not Defined	SOPOCHNAIA KARGA_917	71,8667	82,7000	12644	917	0	1958 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12644
2904	PSMSL_SOUHDAS_1232	Other	Not Defined	SOUHDAS_1232	35,4875	24,0825	12839	1232	0	1969 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12839
2905	PSMSL_SOUTH BEACH_1196	Other	Not Defined	SOUTH BEACH_1196	44,6250	124,0417	12817	1196	157	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12817
2906	PSMSL_SOUTH ISLAND PLANTATION, WINYAH BAY 1651	Other	Not Defined	SOUTH ISLAND PLANTATION, WINYAH BAY 1651	33,2350	79,2033	13088	1651	0	1985 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13088
2907	PSMSL_SOUTH SOUND_1426	Other	Not Defined	SOUTH SOUND_1426	19,2667	81,3833	12971	1426	0	1976 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12971
2908	PSMSL_SOUTHEND_334	Other	Not Defined	SOUTHEND_334	51,5167	0,7333	12223	334	0	1933 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12223
2909	PSMSL_SOUTHPORT 1431	Other	Not Defined	SOUTHPORT 1431	33,9150	78,0183	12975	1431	171	46 1976 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12975
2910	PSMSL_SPIKARNA_1211	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SPIKARNA_1211	62,3633	17,5311	12825	1211	0	1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12825
2911	PSMSL_SPLIT - GRADSKA LUKA_352	Other	Not Defined	SPLIT - GRADSKA LUKA_352	43,5067	16,4417	12227	352	0	1954 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12227
2912	PSMSL_SPLIT RT MARIJANA_685	Other	Not Defined	SPLIT RT MARIJANA_685	43,5083	16,3917	12482	685	0	1952 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12482
2913	PSMSL_SPRING BAY 1216	Other	Not Defined	SPRING BAY 1216	42,5459	147,9327	12830	1216	56	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12830
2914	PSMSL_SPRINGMAID PIER_1444	Other	Not Defined	SPRINGMAID PIER_1444	33,6550	78,9183	12982	1444	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12982
2915	PSMSL_ST HELIER (JERSEY) 2_1795	Other	Not Defined	ST HELIER (JERSEY) 2_1795	49,1833	2,1167	13163	1795	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13163
2916	PSMSL_ST JEAN DE LUZ (SOCOA) 469	Other	Not Defined	ST JEAN DE LUZ (SOCOA) 469	43,3952	1,6816	12318	469	0	1942 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12318
2917	PSMSL_ST. GEORGES / ESSO PIER (BERMUDA)_368	Other	Not Defined	ST. GEORGES / ESSO PIER (BERMUDA)_368	32,3733	64,7033	12238	368	762	221 288 1932 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12238
2918	PSMSL_ST. JOHN'S, NFLD_393	Other	Not Defined	ST. JOHN'S, NFLD_393	47,5667	52,7167	12256	393	223	1935 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12256

2919	PSMSL_ST.MALO_454	Other	Not Defined	ST. MALO_454	48,6411	-	2,0282	12304	454	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12304	
2920	PSMSL_ST.MARKS_1136	Other	Not Defined	ST. MARKS_1136	30,0667	-	84,1833	12783	1136	0	1965 - 1975	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12783	
2921	PSMSL_ST.MARYS_1855	Other	Not Defined	ST. MARYS_1855	49,9179	-	6,3172	13203	1855	0	1994 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13203	
2922	PSMSL_ST.NAZAIRE_457	Other	Not Defined	ST. NAZAIRE_457	47,2700	-	2,2000	12307	457	0	1941 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12307	
2923	PSMSL_ST.PAUL'S HARBOR, KODIAK_1179	Other	Not Defined	ST. PAUL'S HARBOR, KODIAK_1179	57,7450	-	152,4817	12806	1179	0	82 1966 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12806	
2924	PSMSL_ST.PETERSBURG_520	Other	Not Defined	ST. PETERSBURG_520	27,7600	-	82,6267	12355	520	0	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12355	
2925	PSMSL_STANLEY II 1796	Other	Not Defined	STANLEY II 1796	-	51,6924	-	57,8205	13164	1796	305	1992 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13164
2926	PSMSL_STANLEY_1082	Other	Not Defined	STANLEY_1082	-	51,6903	-	57,8649	12748	1082	305	1964 - 1974	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12748
2927	PSMSL_STAVANGER_47	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	STAVANGER_47	58,9743		5,7301	12031	47	0	1919 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12031	
2928	PSMSL_STE-ANNE-DES-MONTS_1199	Other	Not Defined	STE-ANNE-DES-MONTS_1199	49,1333	-	66,4833	12819	1199	0	1967 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12819	
2929	PSMSL_STENHOUSE BAY 492	Other	Not Defined	STENHOUSE BAY 492	-	35,2500	137,7667	12336	492	0	1944 - 1946	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12336	
2930	PSMSL_STENUNGSUND_2112	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	STENUNGSUND_2112	58,0933		11,8325	13329	2112	0	1962 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13329	
2931	PSMSL_STERLEGOVA (STERLEGOVA MYS)_612	Other	Not Defined	STERLEGOVA (STERLEGOVA MYS)_612	75,4167		88,9000	12423	612	0	1950 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12423	
2932	PSMSL_STEVESTON 1255	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	STEVESTON 1255	49,1167	-	123,1833	12861	1255	0	1969 - 1997	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12861	
2933	PSMSL_ST-FRANCOIS_999	Other	Not Defined	ST-FRANCOIS_999	47,0000	-	70,8167	12696	999	0	1962 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12696	
2934	PSMSL_ST-JEAN-PORT-JOLI_1223	Other	Not Defined	ST-JEAN-PORT-JOLI_1223	47,2167	-	70,2833	12835	1223	0	1968 - 1979	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12835	
2935	PSMSL_ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE_1244	Other	Not Defined	ST-JOSEPH-DE-LA-RIVE_1244	47,4500	-	70,3667	12850	1244	0	1967 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12850	
2936	PSMSL_STOCKHOLM 78	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	STOCKHOLM 78	59,3242		18,0817	12054	78	341	1889 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12054	
2937	PSMSL_STOMPNEUS BAY_882	Other	Not Defined	STOMPNEUS BAY_882	-	32,7167	17,9833	12633	882	0	1957 - 1962	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12633	
2938	PSMSL_STONY POINT_1033	Other	Not Defined	STONY POINT_1033	-	38,3721	145,2247	12720	1033	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12720	
2939	PSMSL_STORNOWAY 314	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	STORNOWAY 314	58,2078	-	6,3890	12210	314	238	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12210	
2940	PSMSL_STROMSTAD_140	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	STROMSTAD_140	58,9500		11,1833	12104	140	0	1900 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=12104	
2941	PSMSL_SUBIC ZAMBALES_2176	Other	Not Defined	SUBIC ZAMBALES_2176	14,7667		120,2500	13366	2176	4	114 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=13366	

2942	PSMSL_SUCURAJ_1706	Other	Not Defined	SUCURAJ_1706	43,1333	17,2000	13115	1706	0	1987 - 2005	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13115		
2943	PSMSL_SULTAN SHOAL_1248	Other	Not Defined	SULTAN SHOAL_1248	1,2333	103,6500	12854	1248	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12854		
2944	PSMSL_SUMOTO_1098	Other	Not Defined	SUMOTO_1098	34,3406	134,9067	12759	1098	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12759		
2945	PSMSL_SUR SARI 227	Other	Not Defined	SUR SARI 227	60,0833	26,9833	12166	227	328	39 1919 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12166		
2946	PSMSL_SURIGAO_1708	Other	Not Defined	SURIGAO_1708	9,7833	125,5000	13117	1708	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13117		
2947	PSMSL_SUVA-A_1327	Other	Not Defined	SUVA-A_1327	-	18,1357	178,4228	12905	1327	700	188 1972 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12905	
2948	PSMSL_SVIATOI NOS (SVIATOI NOS MYS) 657	Other	Not Defined	SVIATOI NOS (SVIATOI NOS MYS) 657	72,8333	140,7333	12460	657	0	1951 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12460		
2949	PSMSL_SWANSEA_967	Other	Not Defined	SWANSEA_967	51,6167	-	3,9167	12674	967	0	1960 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12674	
2950	PSMSL_SWINOUJSCIE_2	Other	Not Defined	SWINOUJSCIE_2	53,9167	14,2333	11994	2	0	1811 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11994		
2951	PSMSL_SYDNEY, FORT DENISON 2_196	Other	Not Defined	SYDNEY, FORT DENISON 2_196	-	33,8547	151,2258	12143	196	57	1914 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12143	
2952	PSMSL_SYDNEY, FORT DENISON 65	Other	Not Defined	SYDNEY, FORT DENISON 65	-	33,8500	151,2333	12043	65	57	1886 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12043	
2953	PSMSL_TABLE BAY HARBOUR_866	Other	Not Defined	TABLE BAY HARBOUR_866	-	33,9167	18,4333	12619	866	0	1957 - 1972	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12619	
2954	PSMSL_TACLOBAN, LEYTE_664	Other	Not Defined	TACLOBAN, LEYTE_664	11,2500	125,0000	12465	664	0	1951 - 1976	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12465		
2955	PSMSL_TADIBE-IAHA 767	Other	Not Defined	TADIBE-IAHA 767	70,3667	72,5667	12544	767	0	1955 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12544		
2956	PSMSL_TADOUSSAC_1219	Other	Not Defined	TADOUSSAC_1219	48,1333	-	69,7167	12833	1219	0	1968 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12833	
2957	PSMSL_TAGO_1437	Other	Not Defined	TAGO_1437	34,8069	138,7642	12976	1437	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12976		
2958	PSMSL_TAI MIU WAN_1891	Other	Not Defined	TAI MIU WAN_1891	22,2697	114,2886	13219	1891	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13219		
2959	PSMSL_TAI PO KAU, TOLO HARBOUR 1034	Other	Not Defined	TAI PO KAU, TOLO HARBOUR 1034	22,4425	114,1839	12721	1034	0	1963 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12721		
2960	PSMSL_TAJIRI_1148	Other	Not Defined	TAJIRI_1148	35,5936	134,3158	12791	1148	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12791		
2961	PSMSL_TAKAMATSU II_1789	Other	Not Defined	TAKAMATSU II_1789	34,3514	134,0569	13158	1789	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13158		
2962	PSMSL_TAKAMATSU 847	Other	Not Defined	TAKAMATSU 847	34,3500	134,0500	12608	847	0	1957 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12608		
2963	PSMSL_TAKORADI_331	Other	Not Defined	TAKORADI_331	4,8846	-	1,7450	12220	331	335	1929 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12220	
2964	PSMSL_TALARA_475	Other	Not Defined	TALARA_475	-	4,6167	-	81,2833	12323	475	231	335 1942 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12323

2965	PSMSL_TALCAHUANO_571	Other	Not Defined	TALCAHUANO_571	36,6833	73,1000	12392	571	0	1949 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12392
2966	PSMSL_TALLINN_321	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	TALLINN_321	59,4500	24,8000	12216	321	0	1928 - 1938	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12216
2967	PSMSL_TANAH_MERAH_2034	Other	Not Defined	TANAH_MERAH_2034	1,3123	103,9884	13271	2034	0	2008 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13271
2968	PSMSL_TANDAG_SURIGAO_DEL_SUR_2158	Other	Not Defined	TANDAG_SURIGAO_DEL_SUR_2158	9,0833	126,2000	13360	2158	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13360
2969	PSMSL_TANGACHCHIMAD_AM_1258	Other	Not Defined	TANGACHCHIMAD_1258	9,2833	79,2500	12863	1258	0	1969 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12863
2970	PSMSL_TANGGU_1403	Other	Not Defined	TANGGU_1403	39,0000	117,7167	12956	1403	0	1975 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12956
2971	PSMSL_TANJONG_CHANGI_2033	Other	Not Defined	TANJONG_CHANGI_2033	1,3903	103,9989	13270	2033	0	2008 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13270
2972	PSMSL_TANIUNG_GELANG_1589	Other	Not Defined	TANIUNG_GELANG_1589	3,9750	103,4300	13049	1589	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13049
2973	PSMSL_TANIUNG_KELING_1593	Other	Not Defined	TANIUNG_KELING_1593	2,2150	102,1533	13053	1593	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13053
2974	PSMSL_TANIUNG_SEDILI_1702	Other	Not Defined	TANIUNG_SEDILI_1702	1,9317	104,1150	13111	1702	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13111
2975	PSMSL_TAN-NOWA_817	Other	Not Defined	TAN-NOWA_817	34,3389	135,1781	12581	817	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12581
2976	PSMSL_TAPPI_1587	Other	Not Defined	TAPPI_1587	41,2425	140,3814	13047	1587	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13047
2977	PSMSL_TARANTO_II_2095	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TARANTO_II_2095	40,4756	17,2238	13312	2095	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13312
2978	PSMSL_TARANTO_103	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TARANTO_103	40,4333	17,2667	12077	103	0	1906 - 1911	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12077
2979	PSMSL_TARAWA-A_BETIO_1381	Other	Not Defined	TARAWA-A_BETIO_1381	1,3667	172,9333	12941	1381	113	1974 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12941
2980	PSMSL_TARAWA-B_BAIRIKI_1579	Other	Not Defined	TARAWA-B_BAIRIKI_1579	1,3333	173,0167	13044	1579	113	1983 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13044
2981	PSMSL_TARIFA_2_2054	Other	Not Defined	TARIFA_2_2054	36,0065	5,6035	13279	2054	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13279
2982	PSMSL_TARIFA_488	Other	Not Defined	TARIFA_488	36,0086	5,6026	12332	488	0	1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=12332
2983	PSMSL_TAURANGA_SALISBURY_WHARF_1590	Other	Not Defined	TAURANGA_SALISBURY_WHARF_1590	37,6410	176,1811	13050	1590	0	1984 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13050
2984	PSMSL_TAWAU_1734	Other	Not Defined	TAWAU_1734	4,2333	117,8833	13131	1734	0	1988 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13131
2985	PSMSL_TEJIN_1812	Other	Not Defined	TEJIN_1812	55,2497	14,8378	13179	1812	0	1992 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13179
2986	PSMSL_TEL_AVIV_YAFO_2147	Other	Not Defined	TEL_AVIV_YAFO_2147	32,0528	34,7497	13350	2147	0	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13350
2987	PSMSL_TEL_AVIV_1880	Other	Not Defined	TEL_AVIV_1880	32,0833	34,7667	13216	1880	0	1996 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spl.aspx?id=13216

2988	PSMSL_TEMA_1049	Other	Not Defined	TEMA_1049	5,6167	-	12726	1049	0	1963 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12726
2989	PSMSL_TERIBERKA_2028	Other	Not Defined	TERIBERKA_2028	69,2000	35,1167	13266	2028	0	1941 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13266
2990	PSMSL_TERPIAI-TUMSA_790	Other	Not Defined	TERPIAI-TUMSA_790	73,5500	118,6667	12560	790	0	1956 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12560
2991	PSMSL_THESSALONIKI_373	Other	Not Defined	THESSALONIKI_373	40,6325	22,9349	12240	373	0	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12240
2992	PSMSL_THEVENARD_386	Other	Not Defined	THEVENARD_386	-	32,1489	133,6413	12251	308	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12251
2993	PSMSL_TIKSI (TIKSI) BUKHTA_569	Other	Not Defined	TIKSI (TIKSI) BUKHTA_569	71,5833	128,9167	12391	569	313	1949 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12391
2994	PSMSL_TILBURY_335	Other	Not Defined	TILBURY_335	51,4667	0,3667	12224	335	0	1961 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12224
2995	PSMSL_TIMARU HARBOUR_998	Other	Not Defined	TIMARU HARBOUR_998	-	44,3041	171,2561	12695	998	1962 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12695
2996	PSMSL_TOBA_627	Other	Not Defined	TOBA_627	34,4667	136,8500	12434	627	0	1950 - 1977	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12434
2997	PSMSL_TOBERMORY_1491	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	TOBERMORY_1491	56,6231	-	6,0642	13009	1491	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13009
2998	PSMSL_TOFINO_165	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	TOFINO_165	49,1500	-	125,9167	12120	165	1909 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12120
2999	PSMSL_TOKE POINT, WILLIPA BAY, WA_1354	Other	Not Defined	TOKE POINT, WILLIPA BAY, WA_1354	46,7067	-	123,9667	12924	1354	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12924
3000	PSMSL_TOKUYAMA I_669	Other	Not Defined	TOKUYAMA I_669	34,0333	131,8000	12469	669	103	18 1951 - 1967	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12469
3001	PSMSL_TOKUYAMA II_1210	Other	Not Defined	TOKUYAMA II_1210	34,0408	131,8028	12824	1210	0	1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12824
3002	PSMSL_TOKYO II_1222	Other	Not Defined	TOKYO II_1222	35,6500	139,7667	12834	1222	0	1968 - 1982	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12834
3003	PSMSL_TOKYO III_1545	Other	Not Defined	TOKYO III_1545	35,6486	139,7700	13030	1545	0	1982 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13030
3004	PSMSL_TONGYEONG_1446	Other	Not Defined	TONGYEONG_1446	34,8275	128,4347	12984	1446	0	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12984
3005	PSMSL_TONOURA_94	Other	Not Defined	TONOURA_94	34,9000	132,0667	12068	94	326	1894 - 1984	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12068
3006	PSMSL_TOPOLOBAMPO_793	Other	Not Defined	TOPOLOBAMPO_793	25,6000	-	109,0500	12563	793	1956 - 1965	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12563
3007	PSMSL_TORSHAVN_839	Other	Not Defined	TORSHAVN_839	62,0167	-	6,7667	12602	839	1957 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12602
3008	PSMSL_TOSA SHIMIZU_815	Other	Not Defined	TOSA SHIMIZU_815	32,7792	132,9589	12579	815	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12579
3009	PSMSL_TOULON_980	France	Shom - France	TOULON_980	43,1129	5,9147	12681	980	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12681
3010	PSMSL_TOWNSVILLE I_637	Other	Not Defined	TOWNSVILLE I_637	-	19,2500	146,8333	12440	60	1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12440

3011	PSMSL_TOYAMA_1389	Other	Not Defined	TOYAMA_1389	36,7622	137,2247	12946	1389	325	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12946
3012	PSMSL_TRABZON II_1927	Turkey	GCM - The Ministry of National Defense, General Command of Mapping - Turkey	TRABZON II_1927	41,0000	39,7333	13240	1927	0	2002 - 2009	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13240
3013	PSMSL_TRAVEMUNDE_13	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	TRAVEMUNDE_13	53,9581	10,8722	12003	13	0	1856 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12003
3014	PSMSL_TREGDE 302	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TREGDE 302	58,0064	7,5548	12203	302	321	1927 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12203
3015	PSMSL_TRENTON_1654	Other	Not Defined	TRENTON_1654	40,1883	74,7550	13089	1654	0	1985 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13089
3016	PSMSL_TRIBENI_1002	Other	Not Defined	TRIBENI_1002	22,9833	88,4000	12699	1002	0	1962 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12699
3017	PSMSL_TRIDENT PIER, PORT CANAVERAL 2123	Other	Not Defined	TRIDENT PIER, PORT CANAVERAL 2123	28,4150	80,5917	13337	2123	0	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13337
3018	PSMSL_TRIESTE II_2099	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TRIESTE II_2099	45,6494	13,7579	13316	2099	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13316
3019	PSMSL_TRIESTE_154	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TRIESTE_154	45,6474	13,7585	12111	154	340	1875 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12111
3020	PSMSL_TROIS-RIVIERES_126	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	TROIS-RIVIERES_126	46,3333	72,5500	12092	126	0	1899 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12092
3021	PSMSL_TROMSO 680	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TROMSO 680	69,6474	18,9613	12477	680	0	1952 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12477
3022	PSMSL_TRONDHEIM 2_1748	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TRONDHEIM 2_1748	63,4365	10,3917	13136	1748	0	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13136
3023	PSMSL_TRONDHEIM_34	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TRONDHEIM_34	63,4333	10,4333	12023	34	0	1945 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12023
3024	PSMSL_TSAWWASSEN_134	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	TSAWWASSEN 1341	49,0000	123,1333	12913	1341	0	1972 - 1978	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12913
3025	PSMSL_TSIM BEI TSUI_1366	Other	Not Defined	TSIM BEI TSUI_1366	22,4872	114,0142	12932	1366	0	1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12932
3026	PSMSL_TUAPSE_215	Other	Not Defined	TUAPSE_215	44,1000	39,0667	12158	215	98	1917 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12158
3027	PSMSL_TUAS (WEST JURONG)_1894	Other	Not Defined	TUAS (WEST JURONG)_1894	1,2833	103,6667	13222	1894	0	1997 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13222
3028	PSMSL_TUBUAI 2217	France	Shom - France	TUBUAI 2217	23,3418	149,4755	13377	2217	356	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13377
3029	PSMSL_TUKIZI_673	Other	Not Defined	TUKIZI_673	35,6667	139,7667	12473	673	0	1951 - 1960	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12473
3030	PSMSL_TUKTOYAKTUK_1000	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	TUKTOYAKTUK_1000	69,4167	132,9667	12697	1000	0	1961 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12697
3031	PSMSL_TUMACO 639	Other	Not Defined	TUMACO 639	1,8333	78,7333	12442	639	171	1953 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12442
3032	PSMSL_TURKEY POINT_1714	Other	Not Defined	TURKEY POINT_1714	29,9150	84,5117	13120	1714	0	1987 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13120
3033	PSMSL_TURKU / ABO_239	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	TURKU / ABO_239	60,4283	22,1005	12177	239	286	190 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12177

PSMSL_TURTLE 3034 HEAD_1749	Other	Not Defined	TURTLE HEAD_1749	10,5217	142,2117	13137	1749	0	1998 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13137
3035 PSMSL_TUTICORIN_1072	Other	Not Defined	TUTICORIN_1072	8,7500	78,2000	12742	1072	0	1964 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12742
3036 PSMSL_TUXPAN_918	Other	Not Defined	TUXPAN_918	21,0000	97,3333	12645	918	0	1958 - 1990	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12645
3037 PSMSL_TVARMINNE_238	Other	Not Defined	TVARMINNE_238	59,8500	23,2500	12176	238	0	1921 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12176
3038 PSMSL_UADEI_709	Other	Not Defined	UADEI_709	71,5167	136,4167	12497	709	0	1953 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12497
3039 PSMSL_UBIN_2068	Other	Not Defined	UBIN_2068	1,4194	103,9278	13292	2068	0	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13292
3040 PSMSL_UBLI_1718	Other	Not Defined	UBLI_1718	42,7500	16,8333	13124	1718	0	1987 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13124
3041 PSMSL_UCHIURA_407	Other	Not Defined	UCHIURA_407	35,0172	138,8903	12266	407	0	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12266
PSMSL_UEDINENIA 3042 (UEDINENIA OSTROV)_707	Other	Not Defined	UEDINENIA (UEDINENIA OSTROV)_707	77,5000	82,2000	12495	707	807	349 1953 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12495
PSMSL_UGORSKII SHAR (UGORSKII SHAR PROLIV)_622	Other	Not Defined	UGORSKII SHAR (UGORSKII SHAR PROLIV)_622	69,8167	60,7500	12433	622	0	1950 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12433
3044 PSMSL_ULLAPOOL_1112	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	ULLAPOOL_1112	57,8953	5,1579	12773	1112	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12773
3045 PSMSL_ULLEUNG_1490	Other	Not Defined	ULLEUNG_1490	37,4914	130,9136	13008	1490	0	1979 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13008
3046 PSMSL_ULSAN_997	Other	Not Defined	ULSAN_997	35,5019	129,3872	12694	997	0	1962 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12694
PSMSL_ULUKHAKTOK (FORMALLY HOLMAN) 1930	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	ULUKHAKTOK (FORMALLY HOLMAN) 1930	71,2333	118,2667	13242	1930	0	2003 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13242
3048 PSMSL_UNALASKA_757	Other	Not Defined	UNALASKA_757	53,8800	166,5367	12534	757	102	1955 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12534
3049 PSMSL_UNO_812	Other	Not Defined	UNO_812	34,4886	133,9494	12576	812	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12576
3050 PSMSL_URAGAMI_1090	Other	Not Defined	URAGAMI_1090	33,5583	135,8964	12752	1090	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12752
3051 PSMSL_URAKAWA_I_869	Other	Not Defined	URAKAWA_I_869	42,1667	142,7667	12622	869	0	1957 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12622
3052 PSMSL_URANGAN_2073	Other	Not Defined	URANGAN_2073	25,3000	152,9167	13295	2073	0	1986 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13295
3053 PSMSL_USHUJIA_I_874	Other	Not Defined	USHUJIA_I_874	54,8167	68,2167	12627	874	181	1957 - 1969	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12627
3054 PSMSL_UST_KARA_600	Other	Not Defined	UST_KARA_600	69,2500	64,5167	12411	600	0	1950 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12411
3055 PSMSL_UST_OLENEK_610	Other	Not Defined	UST_OLENEK_610	73,0000	119,8667	12421	610	0	1950 - 1998	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12421
3056 PSMSL_USTKA_644	Poland	IMW/MB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland	USTKA_644	54,5833	16,8667	12447	644	0	1951 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12447

3057	PSMSL_UTO_27	Other	Not Defined	UTO_27	59,7833	21,3667	12016	27	0	1866 - 1936	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12016
3058	PSMSL_UWAJIMA_I_461	Other	Not Defined	UWAJIMA_I_461	33,2333	132,5500	12311	461	0	1957 - 1968	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12311
3059	PSMSL_UWAJIMA_II_1212	Other	Not Defined	UWAJIMA_II_1212	33,2272	132,5511	12826	1212	0	1968 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12826
3060	PSMSL_VAASA / VASA_57	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	VAASA / VASA_57	63,0815	21,5712	12036	57	172	3 1883 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12036
3061	PSMSL_VACA_KEY_1701	Other	Not Defined	VACA_KEY_1701	24,7117	- 81,1050	13110	1701	0	1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13110
3062	PSMSL_VADINAR_1943	Other	Not Defined	VADINAR_1943	22,4500	69,6833	13252	1943	0	2005 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13252
3063	PSMSL_VADSO_1257	Other	Not Defined	VADSO_1257	70,0667	29,7500	12862	1257	0	1969 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12862
3064	PSMSL_VALDEZ_1353	Other	Not Defined	VALDEZ_1353	61,1250	- 146,3617	12923	1353	0	1973 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12923
3065	PSMSL_VALENCIA_1813	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	VALENCIA_1813	39,4420	- 0,3113	13180	1813	0	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13180
3066	PSMSL_VALKARKAI_792	Other	Not Defined	VALKARKAI_792	70,0833	170,9333	12562	792	0	1956 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12562
3067	PSMSL_VALPARAISO_499	Other	Not Defined	VALPARAISO_499	- 33,0272	- 71,6258	12342	499	175	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12342
3068	PSMSL_VANCOUVER_175	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	VANCOUVER_175	49,2833	- 123,1167	12129	175	0	1909 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12129
3069	PSMSL_VANKAREM_607	Other	Not Defined	VANKAREM_607	67,8333	- 175,8333	12418	607	559	154 1950 - 2007	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12418
3070	PSMSL_VARBERG_73	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	VARBERG_73	57,1000	12,2167	12050	73	0	1887 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12050
3071	PSMSL_VARDO_524	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	VARDO_524	70,3750	31,1040	12359	524	323	1947 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12359
3072	PSMSL_VARNA_318	Bulgaria	IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	VARNA_318	43,1833	27,9167	12214	318	0	1929 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12214
3073	PSMSL_VENEZIA (ARSENALE)_87	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VENEZIA (ARSENALE)_87	45,4167	12,3500	12063	87	0	1889 - 1913	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12063
3074	PSMSL_VENEZIA (PUNTA DELLA SALUTE)_168	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VENEZIA (PUNTA DELLA SALUTE)_168	45,4333	12,3333	12123	168	0	1909 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12123
3075	PSMSL_VENEZIA (S.STEFANO)_39	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VENEZIA (S.STEFANO)_39	45,4167	12,3333	12025	39	0	1872 - 1920	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12025
3076	PSMSL_VENEZIA_II_2100	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VENEZIA_II_2100	45,4182	12,4265	13317	2100	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13317
3077	PSMSL_VERAVAL_770	Other	Not Defined	VERAVAL_770	20,9000	70,3667	12546	770	31	1955 - 1983	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12546
3078	PSMSL_VIANA_1482	Other	Not Defined	VIANA_1482	41,6833	- 8,8333	13005	1482	0	1978 - 1985	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13005
3079	PSMSL_VICTOR HARBOUR_1069	Other	Not Defined	VICTOR HARBOUR_1069	- 35,5625	138,6354	12739	1069	906	141 1965 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12739

PSMSL_VICTORIA 3080 DOCK_1183	Other	Not Defined	VICTORIA DOCK_1183	1,2667	103,8500	12808	1183	44	1966 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12808
3081 PSMSL_VICTORIA_166	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	VICTORIA_166	48,4167	123,3667	12121	166	0	1909 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12121
3082 PSMSL_VIESTE_2087	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VIESTE_2087	41,8881	16,1770	13306	2087	0	2001 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13306
3083 PSMSL_VIGO II 1898	Other	Not Defined	VIGO II 1898	42,2431	8,7260	13226	1898	0	1993 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13226
3084 PSMSL_VIGO_483	Other	Not Defined	VIGO_483	42,2380	8,7310	12327	483	0	1943 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12327
3085 PSMSL_VIKEN_2110	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	VIKEN_2110	56,1422	12,5792	13327	2110	0	1976 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13327
3086 PSMSL_VIKER 1759	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	VIKER 1759	59,0360	10,9498	13142	1759	0	1990 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13142
PSMSL_VILLA 3087 SANIURJO_506	Other	Not Defined	VILLA SANIURJO_506	35,2500	3,9167	12345	506	0	1944 - 1949	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12345
3088 PSMSL_VILLAGARCIA_1897	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	VILLAGARCIA_1897	42,6000	8,7667	13225	1897	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13225
3089 PSMSL_VILSANDI_322	Other	Not Defined	VILSANDI_322	58,3833	21,8167	12217	322	0	1928 - 1938	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12217
PSMSL_VIRAC, 3090 CATANDUANES 2150	Other	Not Defined	VIRAC, CATANDUANES 2150	13,5833	124,2333	13353	2150	0	2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13353
PSMSL_VIRGINIA 3091 BEACH_945	Other	Not Defined	VIRGINIA BEACH_945	36,8500	75,9667	12663	945	364	88 1959 - 1970	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12663
PSMSL_VIRGINIA KEY, 3092 FL_1858	Other	Not Defined	VIRGINIA KEY, FL_1858	25,7300	80,1617	13206	1858	332	1994 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13206
3093 PSMSL_VISBY 2105	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	VISBY 2105	57,6392	18,2844	13322	2105	0	1916 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13322
PSMSL_VIS-CESKA 3094 VILA_1574	Other	Not Defined	VIS-CESKA VILA_1574	43,0667	16,2000	13041	1574	0	1983 - 1991	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13041
PSMSL_VISE (VISE 3095 OSTROV)_704	Other	Not Defined	VISE (VISE OSTROV)_704	79,5000	76,9833	12494	704	0	1953 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12494
PSMSL_VISHAKHAPATNAM 3096 _414	Other	Not Defined	VISHAKHAPATNAM_414	17,6833	83,2833	12273	414	35	1937 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12273
3097 PSMSL_VLISSINGEN 20	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands	VLISSINGEN 20	51,4422	3,5961	12009	20	0	1862 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12009
PSMSL_VRANGELIA 3098 (VRANGELIA OSTROV)_608	Other	Not Defined	VRANGELIA (VRANGELIA OSTROV)_608	70,9833	178,4833	12419	608	0	1950 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12419
3099 PSMSL_VUNGTAU_1495	Other	Not Defined	VUNGTAU_1495	10,3333	107,0667	13013	1495	0	1979 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13013
3100 PSMSL_VYBORG 83	Other	Not Defined	VYBORG 83	60,7000	28,7333	12059	83	0	1889 - 1944	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12059
PSMSL_WAGLAN 3101 ISLAND_1698	Other	Not Defined	WAGLAN ISLAND_1698	22,1831	114,3028	13107	1698	167	52 1987 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13107
3102 PSMSL_WAJIMA_132	Other	Not Defined	WAJIMA_132	37,4058	136,9003	12096	132	0	1930 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=12096

3103	PSMSL_WAKAYAMA_816	Other	Not Defined	WAKAYAMA_816	34,2217	135,1456	12580	816	0	1957 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12580	
3104	PSMSL_WAKE ISLAND_595	Other	Not Defined	WAKE ISLAND_595	19,2900	166,6167	12406	595	157	105	35 1950 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12406
3105	PSMSL_WAKKANAI_1103	Other	Not Defined	WAKKANAI_1103	45,4078	141,6853	12764	1103	324	1975 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12764	
3106	PSMSL_WALLAROO II 1420	Other	Not Defined	WALLAROO II 1420	-	33,9260	137,6152	12965	1420	0	1976 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12965
3107	PSMSL_WALTON ON THE NAZE_1224	Other	Not Defined	WALTON ON THE NAZE_1224	51,8500	1,2667	12836	1224	87	0	167 1968 - 1978	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12836
3108	PSMSL_WALVIS BAY_914	Other	Not Defined	WALVIS BAY_914	-	22,9493	14,4985	12642	914	314	1958 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12642
3109	PSMSL_WANDO 1568	Other	Not Defined	WANDO 1568	34,3153	126,7597	13039	1568	0	1983 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13039	
3110	PSMSL_WANGANUI_1621	Other	Not Defined	WANGANUI_1621	-	39,9446	174,9932	13067	1621	0	1984 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13067
3111	PSMSL_WARNEMUNDE 2_11	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	WARNEMUNDE 2_11	54,1697	12,1033	12001	11	0	1855 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12001	
3112	PSMSL_WASHINGTON DC_360	Other	Not Defined	WASHINGTON DC_360	38,8733	-	77,0217	12230	360	0	1931 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12230
3113	PSMSL_WAVELAND, GULF OF MEX., MS 1884	Other	Not Defined	WAVELAND, GULF OF MEX., MS 1884	30,2817	-	89,3667	13218	1884	0	1996 - 2005	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13218
3114	PSMSL_WEIPA_1157	Other	Not Defined	WEIPA_1157	-	12,6667	141,8667	12800	1157	0	1966 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12800
3115	PSMSL_WELLINGTON HARBOUR_221	Other	Not Defined	WELLINGTON HARBOUR_221	-	41,2843	174,7798	12161	221	101	1944 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12161
3116	PSMSL_WEST COAST 1895	Other	Not Defined	WEST COAST 1895	1,3000	103,7667	13223	1895	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13223	
3117	PSMSL_WEST ST. MODESTE_1278	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	WEST ST. MODESTE_1278	51,6000	-	56,7000	12878	1278	0	1970 - 1989	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12878
3118	PSMSL_WEST TUAS_1896	Other	Not Defined	WEST TUAS_1896	1,3444	103,6340	13224	1896	0	1997 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13224	
3119	PSMSL_WESTPORT HARBOUR_1004	Other	Not Defined	WESTPORT HARBOUR_1004	-	41,7456	171,5947	12701	1004	0	1984 - 1995	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12701
3120	PSMSL_WEST-TERSCHELLING 236	Other	Not Defined	WEST-TERSCHELLING 236	53,3631	5,2200	12174	236	0	1921 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12174	
3121	PSMSL_WEWAK_1304	Other	Not Defined	WEWAK_1304	-	3,5500	143,6333	12893	1304	0	1984 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12893
3122	PSMSL_WEYMOUTH_1773	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	WEYMOUTH_1773	50,6085	-	2,4479	13151	1773	166	40 1991 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13151
3123	PSMSL_WHANGAREI HARBOUR (MARSDEN POINT) 1065	Other	Not Defined	WHANGAREI HARBOUR (MARSDEN POINT) 1065	-	35,7574	174,3500	12735	1065	0	1964 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12735
3124	PSMSL_WHITBY_1505	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	WHITBY_1505	54,4900	-	0,6147	13017	1505	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13017
3125	PSMSL_WHYALLA III_1367	Other	Not Defined	WHYALLA III_1367	-	33,0128	137,5904	12933	1367	0	1974 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12933

3126	PSMSL_WHYALLA_493	Other	Not Defined	WHYALLA_493	-	33,0167	137,5667	12337	493	0	1943 - 1946	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12337
3127	PSMSL_WICK_1109	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	WICK_1109		58,4410	- 3,0863	12770	1109	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12770
3128	PSMSL_WIDO_1628	Other	Not Defined	WIDO_1628		35,6181	126,3019	13069	1628	0	1985 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13069
3129	PSMSL_WILLETS POINT 362	Other	Not Defined	WILLETS POINT 362		40,7933	- 73,7817	12232	362	0	1931 - 2000	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12232
3130	PSMSL_WILMINGTON_396	Other	Not Defined	WILMINGTON_396		34,2267	- 77,9533	12259	396	0	1935 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12259
3131	PSMSL_WINTER HARBOUR_1799	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	WINTER HARBOUR_1799		50,5167	- 128,0333	13167	1799	0	1989 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13167
3132	PSMSL_WISMAR 2 8	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	WISMAR 2 8		53,8989	11,4581	11998	8	0	1848 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=11998
3133	PSMSL_WLADYSLAWOWO_645	Other	Not Defined	WLADYSLAWOWO_645		54,8000	18,4167	12448	645	0	1951 - 1999	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12448
3134	PSMSL_WONSAN_1007	Other	Not Defined	WONSAN_1007		39,1667	127,4500	12704	1007	307	1962 - 1992	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12704
3135	PSMSL_WOODS HOLE (OCEAN. INST.)_367	Other	Not Defined	WOODS HOLE (OCEAN. INST.)_367		41,5233	- 70,6717	12237	367	0	1932 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12237
3136	PSMSL_WORKINGTON_179 4	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	WORKINGTON 1794		54,6507	- 3,5672	13162	1794	0	1992 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13162
3137	PSMSL_WYNDHAM_1116	Other	Not Defined	WYNDHAM_1116	-	15,4533	128,1010	12777	1116	0	1984 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12777
3138	PSMSL_XI SHA_1745	Other	Not Defined	XI SHA_1745		16,8333	112,3333	13134	1745	0	1990 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13134
3139	PSMSL_XIAMEN 727	Other	Not Defined	XIAMEN 727		24,4500	118,0667	12511	727	247	1954 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12511
3140	PSMSL_YAIZU_1438	Other	Not Defined	YAIZU_1438		34,8706	138,3272	12977	1438	0	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12977
3141	PSMSL_YAKUTAT_445	Other	Not Defined	YAKUTAT_445		59,5483	- 139,7333	12298	445	0	1940 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12298
3142	PSMSL_YAMBA_310	Other	Not Defined	YAMBA_310	-	29,4297	153,3619	12206	310	0	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12206
3143	PSMSL_YANTAI 731	Other	Not Defined	YANTAI 731		37,5333	121,3833	12515	731	50	106 1954 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12515
3144	PSMSL_YAP B_1251	Other	Not Defined	YAP B_1251		9,5167	138,1333	12857	1251	0	1807 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12857
3145	PSMSL_YARMOUTH_1158	Canada	DFO - Fisheries and Oceans - Canada	YARMOUTH_1158		43,8333	- 66,1333	12801	1158	0	1965 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12801
3146	PSMSL_YEOSU 1155	Other	Not Defined	YEOSU 1155		34,7472	127,7656	12798	1155	0	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12798
3147	PSMSL_YKSPIHLAJA_86	Other	Not Defined	YKSPIHLAJA_86		63,8333	23,0333	12062	86	0	1889 - 1924	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12062
3148	PSMSL_YOKOSUKA_722	Other	Not Defined	YOKOSUKA_722		35,2881	139,6514	12506	722	0	1954 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12506

3149	PSMSL_YOSIOKA_1596	Other	Not Defined SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	YOSIOKA_1596	41,4500	140,2500	13056	1596	0	1984 - 2008	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13056	
3150	PSMSL_YSTAD_72	Sweden		YSTAD_72	55,4167	13,8167	12049	72	0	1887 - 1981	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12049	
3151	PSMSL_YUZHNO KURILSK_546	Other	Not Defined	YUZHNO KURILSK_546	44,0167	145,8667	12374	546	90	1948 - 1994	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12374	
3152	PSMSL_ZADAR_1859	Other	Not Defined	ZADAR_1859	44,1233	15,2350	13207	1859	0	1994 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13207	
3153	PSMSL_ZAMBOANGA CITY_2175	Other	Not Defined	ZAMBOANGA CITY_2175	6,9167	122,0667	13365	2175	9	66 2011 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13365	
3154	PSMSL_ZANZIBAR_1600	Other	Not Defined	ZANZIBAR_1600	-	6,1500	39,1833	13059	1600	297	1984 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13059
3155	PSMSL_ZEEBRUGGE_470	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	ZEEBRUGGE_470	51,3500	3,2000	12319	470	0	1942 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12319	
3156	PSMSL_ZEMLIA BUNGE_658	Other	Not Defined	ZEMLIA BUNGE_658	74,8833	142,1167	12461	658	0	1951 - 1987	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12461	
3157	PSMSL_ZHAPO_933	Other	Not Defined	ZHAPO_933	21,5833	111,8167	12655	933	78	1959 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12655	
3158	PSMSL_ZHELANIA II (ZHELANIA MYS)_647	Other	Not Defined	ZHELANIA II (ZHELANIA MYS)_647	76,9500	68,5500	12450	647	0	1951 - 1996	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12450	
3159	PSMSL_ZHOHOVA (ZHOHOVA OSTROV)_937	Other	Not Defined	ZHOHOVA (ZHOHOVA OSTROV)_937	76,1500	152,8333	12659	937	0	1959 - 1993	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=12659	
3160	PSMSL_ZLARIN_1578	Other	Not Defined	ZLARIN_1578	43,7000	15,6667	13043	1578	0	1983 - 1988	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13043	
3161	Q11TG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	Q11TG	52,9250	4,1490	11635			2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=11635	
3162	Raah	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Raah	64,6659	24,4071	13391			1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13391	
3163	RampolbrugTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RampolbrugTG	52,6140	5,8400	8843			2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8843	
3164	Randers	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Randers	56,4500	10,0500	8844			2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8844	
3165	RangiroaTG	France	Shom - France	RangiroaTG	-	14,9458 -	147,7060	368981		2011 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=368981	
3166	RangiroaTG-10min	France	Shom - France	RangiroaTG-10min	-	14,9458 -	147,7060	370358		2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370358	
3167	RangiroaTG-2min	France	Shom - France	RangiroaTG-2min	-	14,9458 -	147,7060	369651		2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369651	
3168	RangiroaTG-60min	France	Shom - France SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	RangiroaTG-60min	-	14,9458 -	147,7060	370105		2010 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=370105	
3169	Ratan	Sweden		Ratan	63,9861	20,8950	444			1891 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=444	
3170	Rauma	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Rauma	61,1335	21,4634	13392			1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13392	
3171	Ribe	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Ribe	55,3333	8,6833	8845			2005 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8845	

3172	RibeTG	Denmark	DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	RibeTG	55,3333	8,6833	9281	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9281	
3173	RichardTG	France	Shom - France	RichardTG	45,4537	0,9231	638731	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=638731	
3174	RikiteaTG	France	Shom - France	RikiteaTG	-	23,1223	134,9668	369946	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369946
3175	RikiteaTG-1min	France	Shom - France	RikiteaTG-1min	-	23,1223	134,9668	369675	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369675
3176	RikiteaTG-60min	France	Shom - France	RikiteaTG-60min	-	23,1223	134,9668	371431	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371431
3177	RikiteaWharfTG	France	Shom - France	RikiteaWharfTG	-	23,1178	134,9690	368982	2007 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368982
3178	RikiteaWharfTG-1min	France	Shom - France	RikiteaWharfTG-1min	-	23,1178	134,9690	369652	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369652
3179	RikiteaWharfTG-2min	France	Shom - France	RikiteaWharfTG-2min	-	23,1178	134,9690	370872	2013 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370872
3180	RikiteaWharfTG-60min	France	Shom - France	RikiteaWharfTG-60min	-	23,1178	134,9690	370106	2013 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370106
3181	Ringhals	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Ringhals	57,2497	12,1125	445	1967 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=445	
3182	RinghalsTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	RinghalsTG	57,2498	12,1126	8846	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8846	
3183	RMN_Ancona	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ancona	43,6248	13,5065	26216	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26216	
3184	RMN_Anzio	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Anzio	41,4469	12,6348	26198	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26198	
3185	RMN Bari	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Bari	41,1402	16,8660	26195	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26195	
3186	RMN_Cagliari	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Cagliari	39,2101	9,1142	26197	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26197	
3187	RMN_Carloforte	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Carloforte	39,1436	8,3081	26189	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26189	
3188	RMN_Catania	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Catania	37,4980	15,0938	26213	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26213	
3189	RMN_Civitavecchia	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Civitavecchia	42,0940	11,7896	26192	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26192	
3190	RMN_Crotone	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Crotone	39,0836	17,1371	26215	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26215	
3191	RMN_Gaeta	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Gaeta	41,2100	13,5897	26208	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26208	
3192	RMN_Genova	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Genova	44,4101	8,9255	26203	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26203	
3193	RMN_Ginostra (Isola di Stromboli)	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ginostra (Isola di Stromboli)	38,7840	15,1933	26202	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26202	
3194	RMN_Imperia	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Imperia	43,8769	8,0188	26212	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26212	

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

3195	RMN_Imperia 2	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Imperia 2	43,8783	8,0188	26220	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26220	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/daily/
3196	RMN_Isole Tremiti	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Isole Tremiti	42,1189	15,5016	26204	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26204	https://www.psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
3197	RMN_Lampedusa	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Lampedusa	35,4998	12,6044	26217	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26217		
3198	RMN_Le Castella	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Le Castella	38,9084	17,0287	26194	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26194		
3199	RMN_Livorno	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Livorno	43,5463	10,2993	26223	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26223		
3200	RMN_Marina Di Campo	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Marina Di Campo	42,7426	10,2383	26209	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26209		
3201	RMN_Messina	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Messina	38,1963	15,5635	26218	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26218		
3202	RMN_Napoli	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Napoli	40,8397	14,2692	26200	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26200		
3203	RMN_Ortona	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ortona	42,3559	14,4149	26191	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26191		
3204	RMN_Otranto	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Otranto	40,1464	18,4969	26206	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26206		
3205	RMN_Palermo	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Palermo	38,1214	13,3713	26201	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26201		
3206	RMN_Palinuro	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Palinuro	40,0299	15,2753	26211	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26211		
3207	RMN_Pantelleria	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Pantelleria	36,8348	11,9366	26221	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26221		
3208	RMN_Ponza	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ponza	40,8952	12,9656	26199	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26199		
3209	RMN_Porto empedocle	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Porto empedocle	37,2858	13,5268	26207	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26207		
3210	RMN_Porto Torres	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Porto Torres	40,8422	8,4039	26219	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26219		
3211	RMN_Portopalo di Capo Passero	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Portopalo di Capo Passero	36,6691	15,1228	26222	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26222		
3212	RMN_Ravenna	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ravenna	44,4921	12,2829	26224	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26224		
3213	RMN_Reggio Calabria	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Reggio Calabria	38,1217	15,6489	26225	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26225		
3214	RMN_S.Benedetto Del Tronto	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	S.Benedetto Del Tronto	42,9551	13,8898	26214	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26214		
3215	RMN_Sciacca	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Sciacca	37,5045	13,0765	26210	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26210		
3216	RMN_Taranto	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Taranto	40,4756	17,2238	26196	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26196		
3217	RMN_Trieste	Italy	ISPRA - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Trieste	45,6544	13,7561	26190	2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26190		

3218	RMN_Venice	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Venice	45,4182	12,4265	26205			2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26205	
3219	RMN_Vieste	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Vieste	41,8881	16,1770	26193			2016 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=26193	
3220	RMN-ANCONA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ANCONA	43,6248	13,5065	11906			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11906	
3221	RMN-Anzio	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Anzio	41,4469	12,6348	607890			2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=607890	
3222	RMN-BARI	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	BARI	41,1402	16,8660	11915			1979 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11915	
3223	RMN-CAGLIARI	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CAGLIARI	39,2101	9,1142	11902			1986 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11902	
3224	RMN-CARLOFORTE	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CARLOFORTE	39,1436	8,3081	11907			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11907	
3225	RMN-CATANIA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CATANIA	37,4980	15,0938	11874			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11874	
3226	RMN-CIVITAVECCHIA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CIVITAVECCHIA	42,0940	11,7896	11888			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11888	
3227	RMN-CROTONE	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	CROTONE	39,0836	17,1371	11903			1991 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11903	
3228	RMN-Gaeta	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Gaeta	41,2100	13,5897	416537			2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=416537	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3229	RMN-GENOVA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	GENOVA	44,4101	8,9255	11896			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11896	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3230	RMN-Ginostra	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ginostra	38,7840	15,1933	33624			2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=33624	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3231	RMN-IMPERIA	Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy	IMPERIA	43,8769	8,0188	11897			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11897	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3232	RMN-Imperia2	Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy	Imperia2	43,8783	8,0188	31763			2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31763	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3233	RMN-IsoleTremiti	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	IsoleTremiti	42,1189	15,5016	639609			2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=639609	https://www.psms.org/data/obtainings/stations/_php
3234	RMN-LAMPEDUSA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	LAMPEDUSA	35,4998	12,6044	11048			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11048	
3235	RMN-LeCastella	Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy	LeCastella	38,9084	17,0287	31764			2017 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31764	
3236	RMN-LIVORNO	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	LIVORNO	43,5463	10,2993	11904			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11904	
3237	RMN-MarinaDiCampo	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	MarinaDiCampo	42,7426	10,2383	31765			2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31765	
3238	RMN-MESSINA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	MESSINA	38,1963	15,5635	11878			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11878	
3239	RMN-NAPOLI	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	NAPOLI	40,8397	14,2692	11880			1986 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11880	
3240	RMN-ORTONA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	ORTONA	42,3559	14,4149	11885			2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11885	

<http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc>

3241	RMN-OTRANTO	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	OTRANTO	40,1464	18,4969	11916	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11916
3242	RMN-PALERMO	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALERMO	38,1214	13,3713	11918	1992 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11918
3243	RMN-PALINURO	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PALINURO	40,0299	15,2753	11905	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11905
3244	RMN-Pantelleria	Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy	Pantelleria	36,8348	11,9366	31766	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31766
3245	RMN-Ponza	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Ponza	40,8952	12,9656	581972	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=581972
3246	RMN-PORTOEMPEDOCLE	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTOEMPEDOCLE	37,2858	13,5268	11889	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11889
3247	RMN-PortopaloDiCapoPassero	Italy	JRC - Institute for Environment and Sustainability (IES) - Italy	PortopaloDiCapoPassero	36,6691	15,1228	31767	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31767
3248	RMN-PORTOTORRES	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	PORTOTORRES	40,8422	8,4039	11914	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11914
3249	RMN-RAVENNA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	RAVENNA	44,4921	12,2829	11895	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11895
3250	RMN-REGGIOCALABRIA	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	REGGIOCALABRIA	38,1217	15,6489	11898	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11898
3251	RMN-SBenedettoDelTronto	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	SBenedettoDelTronto	42,9551	13,8898	31768	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31768
3252	RMN-Sciacca	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Sciacca	37,5045	13,0765	31769	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31769
3253	RMN-TARANTO	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TARANTO	40,4756	17,2238	11909	1991 - 2004	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11909
3254	RMN-TRIESTE	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	TRIESTE	45,6544	13,7561	11881	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11881
3255	RMN-Venice	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	Venice	45,4182	12,4265	31770	2017 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=31770
3256	RMN-VIESTE	Italy	ISPR - Istituto Superiore per la Protezione e la Ricerca Ambientale - Italy	VIESTE	41,8881	16,1770	11913	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11913
3257	RocheFortTG	France	Shom - France	RocheFortTG	45,9463	0,9535	369079	1993 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369079
3258	RocheFortTG-10min	France	Shom - France	RocheFortTG-10min	45,9463	0,9535	369469	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369469
3259	RocheFortTG-5min	France	Shom - France	RocheFortTG-5min	45,9463	0,9535	370107	1993 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370107
3260	Rodby	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Rodby	54,6500	11,3500	8850	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8850
3261	Rodvig	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Rodvig	55,2542	12,3728	8851	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8851
3262	RoggebotsluisNoordTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RoggebotsluisNoordTG	52,5455	5,8565	8852	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8852
3263	RoggebotsluisZuidTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RoggebotsluisZuidTG	52,5427	5,8557	8853	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8853

3264	Rohukula	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Rohukula	58,9049	23,4248	8854	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8854	
3265	Ronne	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Ronne	55,1000	14,6833	8855	1994 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8855	
3266	RoopotBuiten	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RoopotBuiten	51,6210	3,6820	8858	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8858	
3267	RoopotbuitenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RoopotbuitenTG	51,6200	3,6800	514	2014 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=514	
3268	Rorvik	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Rorvik	64,8667	11,2500	8859	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8859	
3269	RorvikTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	RorvikTG	64,8595	11,2301	8860	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8860	
3270	RoscoffTG	France	Shom - France	RoscoffTG	48,7184	-	3,9659	8861	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8861
3271	RoscoffTG-10min	France	Shom - France	RoscoffTG-10min	48,7184	-	3,9659	370108	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370108
3272	RoscoffTG-1min	France	Shom - France	RoscoffTG-1min	48,7184	-	3,9659	369471	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369471
3273	RoscoffTG-60min	France	Shom - France	RoscoffTG-60min	48,7184	-	3,9659	370109	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370109
3274	Roskilde	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Roskilde	55,6500	12,0833	8862	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8862	
3275	Rosslare	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Rosslare	52,2546	-	6,6648	791343	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=791343
3276	Rostock	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Rostock	54,0831	12,1550	8863	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8863	
3277	RostockTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	RostockTG	54,0830	12,1550	8864	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8864	
3278	RotterdamTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	RotterdamTG	51,9200	4,5000	11636	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11636	
3279	RoyanTG	France	Shom - France	RoyanTG	45,6206	-	1,0278	368638	2006 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368638
3280	RoyanTG-5min	France	Shom - France	RoyanTG-5min	45,6206	-	1,0278	369474	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369474
3281	SaguntoTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SaguntoTG	39,6340	-	0,2060	8866	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8866
3282	SainteMarieTG	France	Shom - France	SainteMarieTG	-	20,8928	55,5369	25870	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25870
3283	SainteMarieTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SainteMarieTG-10min	-	20,8928	55,5369	370873	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370873
3284	SainteMarieTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SainteMarieTG-1min	-	20,8928	55,5369	369475	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369475
3285	SainteMarieTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SainteMarieTG-60min	-	20,8928	55,5369	370110	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370110
3286	SaintGildasTG	France	Shom - France	SaintGildasTG	47,1404	-	2,2464	371432	1986 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371432

3287	SaintGildasTG-5min	France	Shom - France	SaintGildasTG-5min	47,1404	-	2,2464	370111	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370111
3288	SaintGildasTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SaintGildasTG-60min	47,1404	-	2,2464	370112	2013 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370112
3289	SaintMaloTG	France	Shom - France	SaintMaloTG	48,6411	-	2,0276	8867	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8867
3290	SaintMaloTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SaintMaloTG-10min	48,6411	-	2,0276	370113	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370113
3291	SaintMaloTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SaintMaloTG-1min	48,6411	-	2,0276	369477	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369477
3292	SaintMaloTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SaintMaloTG-60min	48,6411	-	2,0276	370114	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370114
3293	SaintMartinTG	France	Shom - France	SaintMartinTG	18,0833	-	63,0854	368983	2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368983
3294	SaintMartinTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SaintMartinTG-1min	18,0833	-	63,0854	369659	2016 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369659
3295	SaintMartinTG-5min	France	Shom - France	SaintMartinTG-5min	18,0833	-	63,0854	370115	2002 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370115
3296	SaintMartinTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SaintMartinTG-60min	18,0833	-	63,0854	370116	2002 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370116
3297	SaintNazaireTG	France	Shom - France	SaintNazaireTG	47,2700	-	2,2000	8868	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8868
3298	SaintNazaireTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SaintNazaireTG-10min	47,2700	-	2,2000	370117	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370117
3299	SaintNazaireTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SaintNazaireTG-1min	47,2700	-	2,2000	369478	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369478
3300	SaintNazaireTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SaintNazaireTG-60min	47,2700	-	2,2000	370118	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370118
3301	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG	France	Shom - France	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG	46,7788	-	56,1683	368639	2012 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368639
3302	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-10min	46,7788	-	56,1683	370119	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370119
3303	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-1min	46,7788	-	56,1683	369480	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369480
3304	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-5min	France	Shom - France	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-5min	46,7788	-	56,1683	370120	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370120
3305	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SaintPierreEtMiquelonTG-60min	46,7788	-	56,1683	370121	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370121
3306	SaintQuayPortrieuxTG	France	Shom - France	SaintQuayPortrieuxTG	48,6475	-	2,8181	372074	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=372074
3307	SantanderTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	SantanderTG	43,4610	-	3,7910	8870	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8870
3308	SANT-ANTONI	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System	SANT-ANTONI	38,9771	-	1,2988	13878	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13878
3309	SA-RAPITA	Spain	SOCIB - Balearic Islands Coastal Observing and Forecasting System	SA-RAPITA	39,3603	-	2,9533	13873	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13873

3310	Sassnitz	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Sassnitz	54,5108	13,6431	8872	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8872
3311	SassnitzTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	SassnitzTG	54,5112	13,6433	8873	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8873
3312	SchellingwoudeTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	SchellingwoudeTG	52,3800	4,9680	8875	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8875
3313	ScheveningenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	ScheveningenTG	52,1000	4,2640	8878	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8878
3314	SchiermonnikoogWaddenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	SchiermonnikoogWaddenTG	53,4700	6,2030	8880	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8880
3315	Schleimuede	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Schleimuede	54,6733	10,0367	8883	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8883
3316	SchleimuedeTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	SchleimuedeTG	54,6730	10,0340	8884	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8884
3317	Schleswig	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Schleswig	54,5114	9,5692	8885	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8885
3318	SchoonhovenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	SchoonhovenTG	51,9440	4,8520	11637	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11637
3319	SD1013418031	Other	Not Defined	SD1013418031	43,2262	28,0136	832898	2019 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=832898
3320	SeteTG	France	Shom - France	SeteTG	43,4000	3,7017	8886	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8886
3321	SeteTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SeteTG-10min	43,4000	3,7017	370122	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370122
3322	SeteTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SeteTG-1min	43,4000	3,7017	369484	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369484
3323	SeteTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SeteTG-60min	43,4000	3,7017	370123	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370123
3324	Sevilla2TG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	Sevilla2TG	37,3185	6,0077	28148	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=28148
3325	Sheerness	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Sheerness	51,4500	0,7500	22	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=22
3326	SheernessTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	SheernessTG	51,4456	0,7434	8887	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8887
3327	Shkorpilovtsi	Bulgaria		Shkorpilovtsi	42,9580	27,8990	8888	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8888
3328	Sillamae	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Sillamae	59,4227	27,7401	8890	2006 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8890
3329	Simpevarp	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Simpevarp	57,4092	16,6759	967448	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967448
3330	Simrishamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Simrishamn	55,5575	14,3578	446	1982 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=446
3331	SimrishamnTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SimrishamnTG	55,5576	14,3577	8891	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8891
3332	SinesTG	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	SinesTG	37,9490	8,8880	8892	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8892

3333	Sinop	Turkey	GCM - The Ministry of National Defense, General Command of Mapping - Turkey	Sinop	42,0170	35,1500	27912		2016 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=27912
3334	SjaellandsOdde	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	SjaellandsOdde	55,9750	11,3722	8894		1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8894
3335	Skagen	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Skagen	57,7194	10,5858	8895		1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8895
3336	Skagsudde	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Skagsudde	63,1905	19,0124	447		1982 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=447
3337	Skagsudde2	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Skagsudde2	63,1881	19,0161	967449		2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967449
3338	Skonor	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Skonor	55,4167	12,8294	448		1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=448
3339	SkonorTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SkonorTG	55,4168	12,8296	8896		2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8896
3340	SkerriesHarbour	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	SkerriesHarbour	53,5850	6,1081	25873		2013 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25873
3341	Sligo	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Sligo	54,3046	8,5689	10350		2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10350
3342	Slipshavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Slipshavn	55,2833	10,8333	8898		2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8898
3343	Smogen	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Smogen	58,3536	11,2178	449		1910 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=449
3344	SmogenTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SmogenTG	58,3537	11,2178	8899		2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8899
3345	Sobra	Croatia	IZOR - Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries - Croatia	Sobra	42,7396	17,6198	371732		2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371732
3346	SocooTG	France	Shom - France	SocooTG	43,3984	1,6731	8900		2011 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8900
3347	SocooTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SocooTG-10min	43,3984	1,6731	370124		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370124
3348	SocooTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SocooTG-1min	43,3984	1,6731	369482		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369482
3349	SocooTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SocooTG-60min	43,3984	1,6731	370125		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370125
3350	SolenzaraTG	France	Shom - France	SolenzaraTG	41,8569	9,4038	8901		2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8901
3351	SolenzaraTG-10min	France	Shom - France	SolenzaraTG-10min	41,8569	9,4038	370126		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370126
3352	SolenzaraTG-1min	France	Shom - France	SolenzaraTG-1min	41,8569	9,4038	369483		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369483
3353	SolenzaraTG-60min	France	Shom - France	SolenzaraTG-60min	41,8569	9,4038	370127		2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370127
3354	Sonderborg	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Sonderborg	54,9167	9,7833	8902		2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8902
3355	SONEL_AIGUI	Other	Not Defined	AIGUI	46,3350	1,3164	364971		2013 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364971

3356	SONEL_AJACC	France	Shom - France	AJACC	41,9227	8,7629	364940	1981 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364940
3357	SONEL_BOUCA	Other	Not Defined	BOUCA	43,5273	1,5148	364942	1967 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364942
3358	SONEL_BOULO	Other	Not Defined	BOULO	50,7275	1,5775	364944	1941 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364944
3359	SONEL_BOURC	France	Shom - France	BOURC	45,8534	1,1778	364945	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364945
3360	SONEL_BREST	France	Shom - France	BREST	48,3829	4,4948	364946	1846 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364946
3361	SONEL_CALAI	France	Shom - France	CALAI	50,9694	1,8677	364947	1941 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364947
3362	SONEL_CENTU	France	Shom - France	CENTU	42,9658	9,3498	364948	2010 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364948
3363	SONEL_CHERB	France	Shom - France	CHERB	49,6513	1,6356	364949	1943 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364949
3364	SONEL_CIBOU	France	Shom - France	CIBOU	43,3892	1,6627	364950	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364950
3365	SONEL_CONCA	Other	Not Defined	CONCA	47,8737	3,9074	364951	1999 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364951
3366	SONEL_CONVE	Other	Not Defined	CONVE	43,5270	1,5136	364943	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364943
3367	SONEL_COTIN	Other	Not Defined	COTIN	45,9136	1,3278	364974	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364974
3368	SONEL_CROZE	Other	Not Defined	CROZE	46,4200	51,8700	364952	1995 - 2001	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364952
3369	SONEL_DEGRA	France	Shom - France	DEGRA	4,8528	52,2781	364953	1989 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364953
3370	SONEL_DESIR	Other	Not Defined	DESIR	16,3029	61,0725	364975	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364975
3371	SONEL_DIELE	France	Shom - France	DIELE	49,5525	1,8608	364954	1996 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364954
3372	SONEL_DIEPP	France	Shom - France	DIEPP	49,9292	1,0844	364955	1954 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364955
3373	SONEL_DUMON	France	Shom - France	DUMON	66,6651	140,0020	364956	1997 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364956
3374	SONEL_DUNKE	France	Shom - France	DUNKE	51,0481	2,3666	364957	1956 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364957
3375	SONEL_DZAOU	Other	Not Defined	DZAOU	12,7821	45,2582	364958	1963 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364958
3376	SONEL_EYRAC	Other	Not Defined	EYRAC	44,6650	1,1636	364941	1967 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364941
3377	SONEL_FIGUE	Other	Not Defined	FIGUE	43,4835	6,9349	364976	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364976
3378	SONEL_FOR2F	Other	Not Defined	FOR2F	14,6015	61,0632	364959	1976 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364959

<https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/.php>

<https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/.php>

<https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtainng/stations/.php>

3379	SONEL_FREOL	Other	Not Defined	FREOL	43,3591	6,7176	365002	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365002	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3380	SONEL_FSMER	Other	Not Defined	FSMER	43,4049	4,8929	364960	2006 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364960	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3381	SONEL_GALET	France	Shom - France	GALET	20,9349	55,2850	364998	1967 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364998	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	http://uhslc.soest.hawaii.edu/data/netcdf/fast/hourly/d.nc
3382	SONEL_GILDA	Other	Not Defined	GILDA	47,1404	2,2464	365013	1962 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365013	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3383	SONEL_HAVRE	Other	Not Defined	HAVRE	49,4819	0,1060	364982	1938 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364982	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3384	SONEL_HERBA	France	Shom - France	HERBA	47,0249	2,2989	364972	1985 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364972	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3385	SONEL_HIENG	France	Shom - France	HIENG	20,6920	164,9431	364962	1983 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364962	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3386	SONEL_HIVOA	France	Shom - France	HIVOA	9,8048	139,0341	364963	1977 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364963	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3387	SONEL_HUAHI	Other	Not Defined	HUAHI	16,7216	151,0324	364965	1989 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364965	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3388	SONEL_HVHTG	Other	Not Defined	HVHTG	51,9775	4,1200	364964	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364964	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3389	SONEL_ILAIX	France	Shom - France	ILAIX	46,0074	1,1743	364966	1973 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364966	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3390	SONEL_IMERE	Other	Not Defined	IMERE	4,8938	52,1905	364969	1978 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364969	https://www.psms-l.org/data/obtaining/stations/.php	
3391	SONEL_IROUS	Other	Not Defined	IROUS	42,6396	8,9352	364973	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364973		
3392	SONEL_KERGU	Other	Not Defined	KERGU	49,3522	70,2190	364970	1993 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364970		
3393	SONEL_LCONQ	Other	Not Defined	LCONQ	48,3594	4,7808	364980	1970 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364980		
3394	SONEL_LCROU	Other	Not Defined	LCROU	47,5427	2,8951	364981	1996 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364981		
3395	SONEL_LEAVA	France	Shom - France	LEAVA	14,2960	178,1602	364961	1986 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364961		
3396	SONEL_LEGOF	Other	Not Defined	LEGOF	5,2847	52,5867	364968	1989 - 2007	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364968		
3397	SONEL_LIFOU	France	Shom - France	LIFOU	20,9185	167,2787	364983	1969 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364983		
3398	SONEL_LROCH	Other	Not Defined	LROCH	46,1585	1,2207	364977	1941 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364977		
3399	SONEL_MAKEM	Other	Not Defined	MAKEM	16,6270	143,5692	364984	2013 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364984		
3400	SONEL_MARSE	Other	Not Defined	MARSE	43,2788	5,3539	364986	1849 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364986		
3401	SONEL_MATAU	France	Shom - France	MATAU	13,2847	176,1685	364987	1977 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364987		

3402	SONEL_MIMIZ	France	Shom - France	MIMIZ	44,2107	-	1,2951	364988	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364988	
3403	SONEL_MONAC	France	Shom - France	MONAC	43,7288		7,4215	364989	1960 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364989	
3404	SONEL_MRETG	Other	Not Defined	MRETG	-	21,5478	167,8771	364985	1982 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364985	
3405	SONEL_NHIVA	Other	Not Defined	NHIVA	-	8,9149	-	140,0960	364993	1982 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364993
3406	SONEL_NICE1	France	Shom - France	NICE1	43,6956		7,2855	364990	1981 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364990	
3407	SONEL_NOUME	Other	Not Defined	NOUME	-	22,2915	166,4367	364991	1967 - 2005	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364991	
3408	SONEL_NUMBO	Other	Not Defined	NUMBO	-	22,2420	166,4162	364992	2001 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364992	
3409	SONEL_OLONE	Other	Not Defined	OLONE	46,4975	-	1,7937	364979	1965 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364979	
3410	SONEL_OUINN	France	Shom - France	OUIIN	-	21,9829	166,6833	364994	1981 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364994	
3411	SONEL_OUIST	France	Shom - France	OUIST	49,2794	-	0,2490	364995	1980 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364995	
3412	SONEL_OUVEA	France	Shom - France	OUVEA	-	20,5498	166,5619	364996	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364996	
3413	SONEL_PAPEE	France	Shom - France	PAPEE	-	17,5331	-	149,5727	364997	1975 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364997
3414	SONEL_PBLOC	Other	Not Defined	PBLOC	45,5685	-	1,0616	365001	1959 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365001	
3415	SONEL_PBRAU	Other	Not Defined	PBRAU	46,3168	-	1,0826	365000	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365000	
3416	SONEL_PCAMA	Other	Not Defined	PCAMA	43,5203		4,1264	365005	2009 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365005	
3417	SONEL_PITRE	Other	Not Defined	PITRE	16,2244	-	61,5314	364999	1983 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364999	
3418	SONEL_PNOUV	Other	Not Defined	PNOUV	43,0147		3,0641	365006	2009 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365006	
3419	SONEL_PRECH	Other	Not Defined	PRECH	14,8076	-	61,2266	364978	2010 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=364978	
3420	SONEL_PTUDY	Other	Not Defined	PTUDY	47,6443	-	3,4459	365003	1966 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365003	
3421	SONEL_PVEND	Other	Not Defined	PVEND	42,5201		3,1073	365004	1981 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365004	
3422	SONEL_RANGI	France	Shom - France	RANGI	-	14,9458	-	147,7060	365007	1966 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365007
3423	SONEL_RFORT	Other	Not Defined	RFORT	45,9463	-	0,9535	365009	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365009	
3424	SONEL_RIKIW	Other	Not Defined	RIKIW	-	23,1178	-	134,9690	365008	1965 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=365008

3425	SONEL_ROYAL	Other	Not Defined	ROYAL	5,2847	-	52,5867	364967	1989 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=364967
3426	SONEL_ROYAN	Other	Not Defined	ROYAN	45,6206	-	1,0278	365011	1991 - 2011	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365011
3427	SONEL_RSCOF	Other	Not Defined	RSCOF	48,7184	-	3,9659	365010	1973 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365010
3428	SONEL_SAOTO	Other	Not Defined	SAOTO	0,3485	-	6,7376	365020	2004 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365020
3429	SONEL_SETE1	France	Shom - France	SETE1	43,3976	-	3,6991	365021	1956 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365021
3430	SONEL_SILUZ	Other	Not Defined	SILUZ	43,3952	-	1,6816	365012	1942 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365012
3431	SONEL_SMALO	Other	Not Defined	SMALO	48,6411	-	2,0274	365014	1986 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365014
3432	SONEL_SMARI	Other	Not Defined	SMARI	-	20,8928	55,5369	365019	2011 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365019
3433	SONEL_SNAZA	Other	Not Defined	SNAZA	47,2669	-	2,2016	365016	1957 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365016
3434	SONEL_SOLEN	France	Shom - France	SOLEN	41,8569	-	9,4038	365022	1977 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365022
3435	SONEL_SPAUL	Other	Not Defined	SPAUL	-	38,7147	77,5312	365017	1994 - 2006	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365017
3436	SONEL_SPMIQ	Other	Not Defined	SPMIQ	46,7788	-	56,1683	365018	1993 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365018
3437	SONEL_SSERV	Other	Not Defined	SSERV	48,6338	-	2,0305	365015	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365015
3438	SONEL_THITG	France	Shom - France	THITG	-	21,6138	166,2415	365023	1967 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365023
3439	SONEL_TOULO	France	Shom - France	TOULO	43,1174	-	5,9132	365024	1961 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365024
3440	SONEL_TUBUA	France	Shom - France	TUBUA	-	23,3418	149,4755	365025	2009 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365025
3441	SONEL_VAIRA	France	Shom - France	VAIRA	-	17,8059	149,2950	365026	1973 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=365026
3442	Soru	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Soru	58,6938	-	22,5229	9204	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9204
3443	SpijkenisseTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	SpijkenisseTG	51,8626	-	4,3342	8904	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8904
3444	Spikarna	Sweden	Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Spikarna	62,3633	-	17,5311	451	1968 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=451
3445	SpooldersluisTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	SpooldersluisTG	52,5109	-	6,0557	8905	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=8905
3446	StariGrad	Croatia	IZOR - Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries - Croatia	StariGrad	43,1811	-	16,5759	371734	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=371734
3447	StationInstitute	Croatia	IZOR - Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries - Croatia	StationInstitute	43,5081	-	16,3896	371697	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=371697

3448	Stavanger	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Stavanger	58,9667	5,7333	8906	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8906
3449	StavangerTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	StavangerTG	58,9743	5,7301	8907	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8907
3450	Stenungsund	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Stenungsund	58,0933	11,8325	452	1962 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=452
3451	StHelier	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	StHelier	49,1833	- 2,1167	8908	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8908
3452	STMARYS	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	STMARYS	49,9179	- 6,3156	81	1994 - 2013	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=81
3453	StMarysTG	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	StMarysTG	49,9185	- 6,3164	8909	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8909
3454	Stockholm	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Stockholm	59,3242	18,0817	453	1889 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=453
3455	Stornoway	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Stornoway	58,2167	- 6,3833	29	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=29
3456	StornowayTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	StornowayTG	58,2071	- 6,3889	8910	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8910
3457	StPauli	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	StPauli	53,5467	9,9717	8911	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8911
3458	StPauliTG	Germany	HPA - Hamburg Port Authority - Germany	StPauliTG	53,5470	9,9720	8912	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8912
3459	StPetersburg	Russian Federation	NWAHEM - North-West Regional Administration for Hydrometeorology and Environmental Monitoring - Russia	StPetersburg	59,9333	30,2667	8913	2004 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8913
3460	Stralsund	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Stralsund	54,3153	13,0986	8914	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8914
3461	StralsundTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	StralsundTG	54,3153	13,0990	8915	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8915
3462	Stromoren	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Stromoren	65,5497	22,2383	967456	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=967456
3463	Tallinn	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Tallinn	59,4444	24,7637	8973	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8973
3464	Tallinnamadal	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Tallinnamadal	59,7119	24,7314	8974	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8974
3465	TanguddenGBGHamn	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	TanguddenGBGHamn	57,6819	11,8721	967461	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=967461
3466	TarifaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	TarifaTG	36,0064	- 5,6036	8975	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8975
3467	TarragonaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	TarragonaTG	41,0789	1,2132	26122	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=26122
3468	Tejn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Tejn	55,2500	14,8333	8976	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8976
3469	TenerifeTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	TenerifeTG	28,4800	- 16,2400	8977	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8977
3470	TerschellingNoordzeeTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	TerschellingNoordzeeTG	53,4440	5,3330	8978	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as px?id=8978

3471	ThioTG	France	Shom - France	ThioTG	-	21,6138	166,2415	368642	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368642
3472	ThioTG-1min	France	Shom - France	ThioTG-1min	-	21,6138	166,2415	369488	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369488
3473	ThioTG-5min	France	Shom - France	ThioTG-5min	-	21,6138	166,2415	370874	2013 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370874
3474	ThioTG-60min	France	Shom - France	ThioTG-60min	-	21,6138	166,2415	370128	1982 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370128
3475	ThyboronHavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	ThyboronHavn		56,7054	8,2226	25875	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25875
3476	ThyboronKyst	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	ThyboronKyst		56,7075	8,2090	8979	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8979
3477	ThyboronKystTG	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	ThyboronKystTG		56,7075	8,2090	9282	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9282
3478	ThyboronYdermole	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark	ThyboronYdermole		56,7075	8,2090	25876	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25876
3479	TimmendorfPoel	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	TimmendorfPoel		53,9919	11,3756	8981	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8981
3480	TimmendorfPoelTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	TimmendorfPoelTG		53,9900	11,3800	8982	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8982
3481	Tobermory	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Tobermory		56,6231	6,0631	44	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=44
3482	TobermoryTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	TobermoryTG		56,6231	6,0642	8983	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8983
3483	TorsmindeHavn	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	TorsmindeHavn		56,3703	8,1201	25877	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25877
3484	TorsmindeKyst	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	TorsmindeKyst		56,3722	8,1137	8984	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8984
3485	TorsmindeKystTG	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark DCA - Danish Coastal Authority, Ministry of Transport and Energy - Denmark	TorsmindeKystTG		56,3700	8,1200	9283	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9283
3486	TorsmindeYdermole	Denmark	DaMSA - Danish Maritime Safety Administration - Denmark	TorsmindeYdermole		56,3722	8,1137	25878	2005 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25878
3487	ToulonTG	France	Shom - France	ToulonTG		43,1228	5,9146	8985	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8985
3488	ToulonTG-10min	France	Shom - France	ToulonTG-10min		43,1228	5,9146	370129	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370129
3489	ToulonTG-1min	France	Shom - France	ToulonTG-1min		43,1228	5,9146	369485	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369485
3490	ToulonTG-60min	France	Shom - France GCM - The Ministry of National Defense, General Command of Mapping - Turkey	ToulonTG-60min		43,1228	5,9146	370130	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370130
3491	Trabzon	Turkey	GCM - The Ministry of National Defense, General Command of Mapping - Turkey	Trabzon		41,0019	39,7445	639611	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=639611
3492	Travemuende	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Travemuende		53,9581	10,8722	8987	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8987
3493	TravemuendeTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	TravemuendeTG		53,9630	10,8730	8988	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8988

3494	Tregde	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Tregde	58,0000	7,5667	8989	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8989
3495	TregdeTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TregdeTG	58,0064	7,5548	8990	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8990
3496	Triigi	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Triigi	58,5914	22,7173	8992	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8992
3497	TromsøeTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TromsøeTG	69,6474	18,9613	8995	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8995
3498	Trondheim	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Trondheim	63,4333	10,4000	8996	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8996
3499	TrondheimTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	TrondheimTG	63,4365	10,3917	8997	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8997
3500	TubuaiTG	France	Shom - France	TubuaiTG	- 23,3418	- 149,4755	371433	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=371433
3501	TubuaiTG-1min	France	Shom - France	TubuaiTG-1min	- 23,3418	- 149,4755	370131	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370131
3502	TubuaiTG-2min	France	Shom - France	TubuaiTG-2min	- 23,3418	- 149,4755	370132	2009 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370132
3503	TubuaiTG-60min	France	Shom - France	TubuaiTG-60min	- 23,3418	- 149,4755	370133	2010 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370133
3504	Turku	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Turku	60,4283	22,1005	13393	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13393
3505	Udbyhoej	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Udbyhoej	56,6000	10,3000	8999	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=8999
3506	Uddevalla	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Uddevalla	58,3475	11,8948	15366	2010 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=15366
3507	Ueckermuende	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Ueckermuende	53,7503	14,0664	9000	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9000
3508	UeckermuendeTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	UeckermuendeTG	53,7500	14,0700	9001	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9001
3509	Ullapool	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Ullapool	57,8955	- 5,1568	16	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=16
3510	UllapoolTG	United Kingdom	Met Office - United Kingdom	UllapoolTG	57,8953	- 5,1579	9003	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9003
3511	UrtTG	France	Shom - France	UrtTG	43,5025	- 1,2995	368643	2018 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368643
3512	UrtTG-Smin	France	Shom - France	UrtTG-Smin	43,5025	- 1,2995	369487	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369487
3513	USNDBC_arpf1			USNDBC_arpf1	28,4330	- 82,6670	9751	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9751
3514	USNDBC_bdv1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_bdv1	25,4780	- 80,9890	9761	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9761
3515	USNDBC_bkyf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_bkyf1	25,1190	- 80,8340	9772	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9772
3516	USNDBC_bnkf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_bnkf1	25,0870	- 80,5190	9777	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9777

3517	USNDBC_bobf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_bobf1	25,0270	-	80,6810	9778	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9778
3518	USNDBC_bwsf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_bwsf1	25,1780	-	80,4380	9788	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9788
3519	USNDBC_canf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_canf1	25,4220	-	80,9420	9793	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9793
3520	USNDBC_cnb1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_cnb1	25,7020	-	81,1860	9819	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9819
3521	USNDBC_cwaf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_cwaf1	25,2970	-	81,0130	9829	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9829
3522	USNDBC_dkkf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_dkkf1	25,1800	-	80,4900	9837	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9837
3523	USNDBC_fhpf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_fhpf1	28,1530	-	82,8010	9858	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9858
3524	USNDBC_gbif1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_gbif1	25,3780	-	81,0290	9872	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9872
3525	USNDBC_gbtf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_gbtf1	25,1670	-	80,8010	9873	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9873
3526	USNDBC_gkyf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_gkyf1	24,6270	-	82,8720	13948	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13948
3527	USNDBC_hcef1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_hcef1	25,2540	-	80,4440	9886	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9886
3528	USNDBC_href1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_href1	25,4240	-	81,0600	9893	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9893
3529	USNDBC_jbyf1			USNDBC_jbyf1	25,2240	-	80,5410	991403	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=991403
3530	USNDBC_ikyf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_ikyf1	25,0530	-	80,9040	9903	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9903
3531	USNDBC_lbrf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_lbrf1	25,4840	-	81,1330	9956	2017 - 2017	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9956
3532	USNDBC_lbsf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_lbsf1	25,2140	-	80,4320	9957	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9957
3533	USNDBC_lmdf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_lmdf1	25,1760	-	80,6330	9965	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9965
3534	USNDBC_lmrf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_lmrf1	25,5560	-	81,1690	9967	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9967
3535	USNDBC_lrif1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_lrif1	25,2840	-	80,8940	9974	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9974
3536	USNDBC_lrkf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_lrkf1	24,9820	-	80,8260	9975	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9975
3537	USNDBC_lsnf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_lsnf1	25,2350	-	80,4570	9976	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9976
3538	USNDBC_md1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_md1	25,2890	-	80,3960	367567	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367567
3539	USNDBC_mnb1			USNDBC_mnb1	25,2390	-	80,4220	994596	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=994596

3540	USNDBC_nrrf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_nrrf1	25,3380	-	80,9110	10034	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10034
3541	USNDBC_pkyf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_pkyf1	24,9180	-	80,7470	10077	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10077
3542	USNDBC_shpf1			USNDBC_shpf1	30,0580	-	84,2910	10152	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10152
3543	USNDBC_sref1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_sref1	25,3520	-	81,1000	10168	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10168
3544	USNDBC_tbyf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_tbyf1	25,1550	-	80,7220	10181	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10181
3545	USNDBC_tcvf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_tcvf1	25,2130	-	80,5330	10185	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10185
3546	USNDBC_tcvf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_tcvf1	25,2130	-	80,5330	10185	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10185
3547	USNDBC_thr1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_thr1	25,2030	-	80,3720	367568	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=367568
3548	USNDBC_tpef1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_tpef1	25,4100	-	80,9640	10196	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10196
3549	USNDBC_trrf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_trrf1	25,2170	-	80,6500	10199	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10199
3550	USNDBC_wiwf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_wiwf1	25,5870	-	81,0440	10225	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10225
3551	USNDBC_wplf1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_wplf1	25,7100	-	81,2490	10229	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10229
3552	USNDBC_wrbf1	United States	NOAA - NDBC - US	USNDBC_wrbf1	25,0720	-	80,7350	10232	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10232
3553	USNDBC_wwef1	Other	Not Defined	USNDBC_wwef1	25,2320	-	80,9380	10233	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=10233
3554	Ustka	Poland	IMWMMB - Institute of Meteorology and Water Management - Poland	Ustka	54,5880	16,8538		967470	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967470
3555	Vaasa	Finland	FMI - Finnish Meteorological Institute - Finland	Vaasa	63,0815	21,5712		13394	1971 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=13394
3556	Vahemadal	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Vahemadal	59,5102	24,6662		9445	2015 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9445
3557	VairaoTG	France	Shom - France	VairaoTG	-	17,8059	149,2950	368984	2014 - 2019	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=368984
3558	VairaoTG-10min	France	Shom - France	VairaoTG-10min	-	17,8059	149,2950	370361	2018 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370361
3559	VairaoTG-2min	France	Shom - France	VairaoTG-2min	-	17,8059	149,2950	369661	2011 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=369661
3560	VairaoTG-60min	France	Shom - France	VairaoTG-60min	-	17,8059	149,2950	370134	2012 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=370134
3561	ValenciaTG	Spain	PIE - Puertos del Estado - Spain SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	ValenciaTG	39,4600	-	0,3300	9005	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9005
3562	Varberg2	Sweden		Varberg2	57,1096	12,2415		967471	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967471

3563	Vardoe	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Vardoe	70,3333	31,1000	9006	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9006
3564	VardoeTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	VardoeTG	70,3750	31,1040	9007	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9007
3565	Varna	Bulgaria	IOBAS - Institute of Oceanology - Bulgarian Academy of Science - Bulgaria	Varna	43,1920	27,9110	10392	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=10392
3566	Vastervik	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Vastervik	57,7482	16,6747	967472	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=967472
3567	Vedbaek	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Vedbaek	55,8500	12,5667	9008	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9008
3568	VelaLuka	Croatia	IZOR - Institute of Oceanography and Fisheries - Croatia	VelaLuka	42,9603	16,7033	371733	2020 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=371733
3569	VianaDoCasteloTG	Portugal	IH - Instituto Hidrografico - Portugal	VianaDoCasteloTG	41,6850	8,8396	9012	2012 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9012
3570	Vidaa	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Vidaa	54,9667	8,6667	9014	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9014
3571	Vidaa2	Denmark	DMI - Danmarks Meteorologiske Institut - Denmark	Vidaa2	54,9667	8,6667	13983	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13983
3572	VidaaTG	Denmark	DMIOS - Danish Meteorological Institute, Oceanographic Section - Denmark	VidaaTG	54,9667	8,6660	9015	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9015
3573	VigoTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	VigoTG	42,2430	8,7260	13843	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=13843
3574	VigoTG_H	Spain	IEO - Spanish Oceanographic Institute - Spain	VigoTG_H	42,2439	8,7269	9016	1943 - 2010	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9016
3575	Viken	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Viken	56,1422	12,5792	454	1976 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=454
3576	VikenTG	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	VikenTG	56,1421	12,5793	9017	2014 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9017
3577	Viker	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	Viker	59,0333	10,9500	9018	1990 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9018
3578	VikerTG	Norway	NHS - Norwegian Hydrographic Service - Norway	VikerTG	59,0361	10,9498	9019	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9019
3579	VilagarciaTG	Spain	PdE - Puertos del Estado - Spain	VilagarciaTG	42,6010	8,7700	9020	1997 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9020
3580	VillefrancheTG	France	Shom - France	VillefrancheTG	43,4380	1,4602	368641	2008 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=368641
3581	VillefrancheTG-5min	France	Shom - France	VillefrancheTG-5min	43,4380	1,4602	369486	2013 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=369486
3582	Vinga2	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Vinga2	57,6317	11,6076	967473	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=967473
3583	Virtsu	Estonia	MSI - Marine Systems Institute - Estonia	Virtsu	58,5761	23,5081	9021	2009 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9021
3584	Visby	Sweden	SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Visby	57,6392	18,2844	455	1960 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=455
3585	VlakteVdRaantG	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	VlakteVdRaantG	51,5046	3,2422	9024	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.as?px?id=9024

3586	VlielandHavenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	VlielandHavenTG	53,2972	5,0918	9025	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9025
3587	Vlissingen	Netherlands	Deltares - Netherlands	Vlissingen	51,4500	3,6000	11110	2011 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11110
3588	VlissingenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	VlissingenTG	51,4430	3,5960	9026	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9026
3589	VurenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	VurenTG	51,8230	5,0170	11638	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11638
3590	Wangerooge	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Wangerooge	53,8063	7,9292	9031	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9031
3591	WangeroogeTG	Germany	WSAW - Waterways and Shipping Authority Wilhelmshaven (WSA-WIL) - Germany	WangeroogeTG	53,8060	7,9290	9032	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9032
3592	Warnemuende	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Warnemuende	54,1697	12,1033	9033	2005 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9033
3593	WarnemuendeTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	WarnemuendeTG	54,1780	12,0900	9034	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9034
3594	WerkendamBuitenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	WerkendamBuitenTG	51,8070	4,8770	11639	2015 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=11639
3595	Westhinder	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	Westhinder	51,3890	2,4380	9035	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9035
3596	WestkapelleTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	WestkapelleTG	51,5223	3,4402	9036	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9036
3597	Wexford	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	Wexford	52,3385	6,4589	569	2007 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=569
3598	WexfordTG	Ireland	MI - Marine Institute - Ireland	WexfordTG	52,3385	6,4589	9037	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9037
3599	Weymouth	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Weymouth	50,6079	2,4465	45	1991 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=45
3600	WeymouthTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	WeymouthTG	50,6085	2,4479	9038	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9038
3601	Whitby	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Whitby	54,4833	0,6167	33	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=33
3602	WhitbyTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	WhitbyTG	54,4901	0,6142	9039	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9039
3603	Wick	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Wick	58,4333	3,0833	30	1990 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=30
3604	WickTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom	WickTG	58,4410	3,0863	9040	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9040
3605	WierumergrondenTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	WierumergrondenTG	53,5170	5,9590	9042	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9042
3606	Wilhelmshaven	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Wilhelmshaven	53,5144	8,1450	9043	2011 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9043
3607	WilhelmshavenTG	Germany	WSAW - Waterways and Shipping Authority Wilhelmshaven (WSA-WIL) - Germany	WilhelmshavenTG	53,5144	8,1450	9044	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9044
3608	Wismar	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Wismar	53,8989	11,4581	9045	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9045

3609	WismarTG	Germany	WSAL - Waterways and Shipping Authority Lübeck - Germany	WismarTG	53,8988	11,4581	9046	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9046
3610	Wittduen	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Wittduen	54,6317	8,3839	9047	2005 - 2015	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9047
3611	WittduenTG	Germany	WSOT - Waterways and Shipping Office Toenning - Germany	WittduenTG	54,6320	8,3840	9048	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9048
3612	WittowerFaehre	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	WittowerFaehre	54,5578	13,2472	9049	2014 - 2014	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9049
3613	WittowerFaehreTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	WittowerFaehreTG	54,5580	13,2470	9050	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9050
3614	WittowerFahre	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	WittowerFahre	54,5575	13,2450	25886	2011 - 2012	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=25886
3615	Wolgast	Germany	BSH - Bundesamt für Seeschifffahrt und Hydrographie - Germany	Wolgast	54,0417	13,7703	9051	2011 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9051
3616	WolgastTG	Germany	WSOS - Waterways and Shipping Office Stralsund	WolgastTG	54,0417	13,7703	9052	2014 - 2018	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9052
3617	Workington	United Kingdom	NOC - National Oceanography Centre Southampton - UK	Workington	54,6500	3,5667	46	1992 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=46
3618	WorkingtonTG	United Kingdom	Met Office- United Kingdom SMHI - Swedish Meteorological and Hydrological Institute - Sweden	WorkingtonTG	54,6508	3,5676	9053	2014 - 2016	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9053
3619	Ystad2	Sweden	Hydrological Institute - Sweden	Ystad2	55,4227	13,8255	967477	2019 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=967477
3620	ZeebruggeTG	Belgium	MDK - Maritieme Dienstverlening en Kust - Belgium	ZeebruggeTG	51,3460	3,2000	9055	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9055
3621	ZwartsluisTG	Netherlands	RWS - Rijkswaterstaat Waterdienst - Netherlands	ZwartsluisTG	52,6388	6,0784	9056	2014 - 2020	https://www.emodnet-physics.eu/map/spi.aspx?id=9056